

CODEBOOK

Level of Living Survey

2010

Introduction

This is the codebook for the main sample of the Level of Living Survey 2010 (LNU 2010). The structure of this codebook is essentially the same as in previous versions of the codebook, i.e. the codebooks of LNU 1968, 1974, 1981, 1991 and 2000. The variables in LNU 2010 have the prefix Z, while variables of LNU 2000 have the prefix X, variables of 1991 have the prefix Y, variables of 1981 have the prefix U, variables of 1974 have the prefix V, and variables of 1968 have the prefix W. The codebook contains directions to identical or comparable variables in the five previous versions of the survey. The codebook also contains, above and all, frequency tables for most of the included variables.

The sampling frame for LNU 2010 is, as with LNU 2000, constituted of individuals within the age interval 18-75 years (born 1935-1991). In previous level of living surveys, the age intervals have been 15-76 years (1968, 1974 and 1981) and 17-76 years (1991). For a more detailed description of population and sampling procedure, data collection procedure, response rates, missing data analysis, weights etc., see the technical report: *Teknisk rapport. En beskrivning av genomförande och metoder. Levnadsnivåundersökningen 2010.*

The main sampling frame of the Level of Living Survey 2010 edition initially reached 7,404 individuals. Among these, 151 were no longer considered to be a part of the sampling frame at the time of the interview. Interviews were conducted with 4,415 out of the remaining 7,253 individuals. The response rate is therefore about 60.9 percent ($4,415/7,253$). These individuals form the basis of all frequency tables in the codebook (number of respondents for specific questions is lower in some instances, due to internal missing values or that the question was not asked to everyone). Variables Z864-Z894 are based on the so-called personality questionnaire that was answered after the main interview. For these questions, the response rate was lower (3,864 i.e. 53.3 percent).

The tables are, with slight variations, designed the same way throughout the codebook. In order to facilitate interpretation, the different parts of the tables are described and explained below (see next page).

The main LNU has, in later years, been complemented with some additional surveys. Since LNU 2000, spouses and partners of the main respondent, who lives in the respondent's household, have been offered to complete the so-called Partner-LNU. This survey is less extensive and consists of a questionnaire sent out by mail. In LNU 2010, 3,347 spouses/partners of the main respondents were identified and 2,522 answered the questionnaire for Partner-LNU. This means that the response rate was 75.4 percent

1

2

3

Z570

SMOKING NUMBER OF YEARS

**X523 Y341
U279**

4

How many years have you been smoking altogether? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z569 NE 4.

6

7

5

<1		63	3,0
1-5		351	16,9
5-9		272	13,1
10-19		516	24,8
20-29		356	17,1
30-39		253	12,2
40-49		184	8,9
50-59		83	4,0
60>		1	0,0
	Total	2079	100
99	No answer	17	
	Not applicable	2319	8
		4415	
	Mean value	15,9	9
	Standard deviation	14,4	

- Variable number.** Every variable has a serial number, which can be used as identification when processing data.
- Variable name.**
- References** to corresponding variables in LNU68, LNU74, LNU81, LNU91 and LNU00. Jfr (compare) means that the variable (or question) doesn't have exactly the same construction in the other surveys. Note that the possible answers can be different even if the question that the variable is based on is identical for all years.
- The exact wording of the question** and/or an explanation of the construction of the variable and selection, if any (i.e. information on who the table is valid for).
- The code**, that in this example equals number of years. Some variables, like this one, are divided into categories. Note that the categories can be of different sizes. If the code equals a possible answer (e.g. 1=YES), this is stated.
- Number of respondents.**
- Percentage** is calculated based on the number of respondents. Percent is not calculated for decline and the like.
- The category that is **not selected** and how large this is.
- Mean value and Standard deviation.** The Mean value and the Standard deviations for variables divided in categories are calculated based on actual values and not interpolated medians.

(2,522/3,347). The data of Partner-LNU is presented in the variables PZ1-PZ110 below.

Since LNU 2000, the so-called Child-LNU has also been conducted. Children aged 10-18 years, who live in the household of the respondent, are offered to respond to an audio questionnaire about their living conditions. In LNU 2010, 1,283 children fitted the sampling

frame and 923 answered the audio questionnaire for Child-LNU. This means that the response rate was 71.9 percent (923/1,283).

Children who participated in Child-LNU 2000 were re-interviewed as young adults (20-28 years old) in 2010. This time they answered the main questionnaire. In this survey called Young-LNU, 1,485 young adults fitted the sampling frame and 929 were interviewed. This means that the response rate was 62.6 percent (929/1,485).

At the end of the data collection process for LNU 2010, persons who previously declined to participate were given the possibility to answer a much smaller short version of the main questionnaire, either through mail or by telephone. In total, counting both LNU and Young-LNU, 915 persons used this possibility. The total response rate of LNU 2010, including respondents of the short questionnaire, reaches 72.0 percent (6,259/8,889).

More information about the Level of Living Survey and its different complementing surveys is available at www.sofi.su.se/english/research/three-research-departments/lnu-level-of-living/documentation. Here you can also find questionnaires, the technical report and other documentation.

LNU-data is located and accessible for internal users (the LNU-group at SOFI) on the server of the Swedish Institute for Social Research at *X:\LNU-M\LNU 2010\LNU2010_DATA*. External users can apply for access to LNU-data at www.sofi.su.se/english/research/three-research-departments/lnu-level-of-living/apply-for-lnu-data.

Finally, I would like to thank everyone who made the Level of Living Survey 2010 possible. First and foremost, the respondents, of course, deserve huge credit for giving us their time in hourly long interviews, telling us about their lives. I would also like to thank our collaborators at Statistics Sweden and its interviewers, who have travelled around the whole country in order to conduct the interviews. The LNU-group also deserves credit for their work with the questionnaires, the data, the variables and, not least, this codebook. To conduct a study in the size of the Level of Living Survey cost a lot of money. Without generous grants from Forte, Riksbankens Jubileumsfond and Vetenskapsrådet it would not have been possible. Thank you!

Stockholm March 2015
Michael Gähler
Director for LNU 2010

VARIABLE LIST

VARIABLE NUMBER	VARIABLE NAME	NEW, IDENTICAL OR COMPARABLE (jfr) VARIABLES FOR LNU 2000, 1991, 1981, 1974, 1968
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INFORMATION ABOUT INTERVIEW

Z1	UB-NUMBER	X1, Y1, U1, V1, W1
Z2	PANEL CODE	X2
Z3	PART OF BARN-LNU 2000	NEW
Z4	INTERVIEWER NUMBER	X4, Y3, U3, V2
Z5	DATE OF INTERVIEW- MONTH, DAY	X5, Y4, U4, jfr V3, jfr W552
Z6	TIME AT START OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE	X6, Y5, U5, V5
Z7	TIME AT END OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE	X7, Y6, U6, V708
Z8	TYPE OF INTERVIEW	X10, Y7, U7
Z9	INDIRECT INTERVIEW	X11, Y8, U8, V719
Z10	INTERVIEW LANGUAGE	X12

SEX, AGE, OCCUPATION

Z11	SEX	X8, Y10, U10, V718, W2
Z12	YEAR OF BIRTH	X9, Y11, U11, V815, W533
Z13	SEI – OWN EMPLOYMENT STATUS	jfr X14, jfr Y14, jfr U14, jfr V715, jfr W996
Z14	OWN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GROUP	X15, Y13, jfr U13
Z15	NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION	X16
Z16	NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION	X17
Z17	OWN EGP	X18, Y669
Z18	OWN SSYK	NEW
Z19	OWN ISCO88	NEW
Z21	OWN SIOPS	NEW

MOVES

Z22	SAME PLACE OF RESIDENCE SINCE 2000	X19, jfr Y105, jfr U37, jfr V30
Z23	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT PLACE OF RESIDENCE	X20, jfr Y108, jfr U40, jfr V32, jfr W15
Z24	REASON FOR LATEST MOVE	X21, jfr Y107, jfr U39, jfr V33
Z25	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT DWELLING	X22, jfr Y111, jfr U42, jfr V35, jfr W96

LIVING CONDITIONS

Z26	NUMBER OF ROOMS, EXCLUDING THE KITCHEN	X24, Y113, U45, V38, W71
Z27	LIVING SPACE m ²	X25, Y114

Z28	NUMBER OF APARTMENTS IN THE HOUSE	X26, Y115, U44, V37, W70
Z29	BOOKS IN THE HOME	X28, Y117, U65, V55, W88
Z30	DAILY NEWSPAPER IN THE HOME	X30
Z31	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE	X33
Z32	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR MAINTENANCE	X34
Z33	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE, NEIGHBOURS	X35
Z34	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: VANDALISM OR CRIME	X36
Z35	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: SCARCITY OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT	X37
Z36	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: AFRAID AT NIGHT	X40
Z37	HOME OWNER/RENTER	X45, Y121, U71, V60, W94
Z38	COST OF DWELLING – NOT OWNER/RENTER	X46, Y122, U72, V61
Z39	TYPE OF POSSESSION	X47, Y123, jfr U73, jfr V62, jfr W95
Z40	DIRECT LEASE	NEW
Z41	COST OF DWELLING – RENT	X49, Y125, U75, jfr V63, jfr W98
Z42	DENSITY STANDARD	X50, Y130, U68, V745, W626

STAYS ABROAD (SINCE COMING TO SWEDEN)

Z43	NUMBER OF STAYS ABROAD	NEW
Z44	TIME STAYING ABROAD	NEW
Z45	YEAR/MONTH FIRST STAY ABROAD STARTED	NEW
Z46	COUNTRY OF FIRST STAY ABROAD	NEW
Z47	YEAR/MONTH END OF FIRST STAY ABROAD	NEW
Z45_a	YEAR/MONTH SECOND STAY ABROAD STARTED	NEW
Z46_a	COUNTRY OF SECOND STAY ABROAD	NEW
Z47_a	YEAR/MONTH END OF SECOND STAY ABROAD	NEW

CHILDHOOD CONDITIONS

NATIONALITY

Z48	BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN	X51
Z49	SWEDISH PARENTS	X52, jfr Y15, jfr U15, jfr V6, jfr W4
Z50	BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER	X53, jfr Y16, jfr U16, jfr V7, jfr W4
Z51	BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER	X54, jfr Y17, jfr U17, jfr V8, jfr W5
Z52	HOME LANGUAGE	X55, jfr Y18, jfr U18, jfr V9, jfr W6
Z53	AGE AT IMMIGRATION	X56, jfr Y19, jfr U19, jfr V10, jfr W7
Z54	COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	X57
Z55	ABILITY TO READ SWEDISH	NEW
Z56	ABILITY TO SPEAK SWEDISH	X58
Z57	RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – FATHER	jfr X59
Z58	RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – MOTHER	jfr X60

SIBLINGS, PARENTS AND CHILDHOOD FAMILY

Z59	NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL	X61, jfr Y34, jfr U28, jfr V22, jfr W30
Z60	NUMBER OF SIBLINGS ALIVE	X62
Z61	NUMBER OF BROTHERS, TOTAL	X63
Z62	NUMBER OF BROTHERS ALIVE	X64

Z63	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 1	jfr X65
Z64	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 2	jfr X66
Z65	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 3	jfr X67
Z66	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 4	jfr X68
Z67	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 5	jfr X69
Z68	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 6	jfr X70
Z69	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 7	jfr X71
Z70	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 8	jfr X72
Z71	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 9	jfr X73
Z72	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 10	jfr X74
Z73	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 11	jfr X75
Z74	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 12	jfr X76
Z75	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 13	jfr X77
Z76	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 14	jfr X78
Z77	SEX SIBLING 1	X79
Z78	SEX SIBLING 2	X80
Z79	SEX SIBLING 3	X81
Z80	SEX SIBLING 4	X82
Z81	SEX SIBLING 5	X83
Z82	SEX SIBLING 6	X84
Z83	SEX SIBLING 7	X85
Z84	SEX SIBLING 8	X86
Z85	SEX SIBLING 9	X87
Z86	SEX SIBLING 10	X88
Z87	SEX SIBLING 11	X89
Z88	SEX SIBLING 12	X90
Z89	SEX SIBLING 13	X91
Z90	SEX SIBLING 14	X92
Z91	AGE-POSITION AMONG SIBLINGS	X93
Z92	INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY	jfr X94, jfr Y20, jfr U20, jfr V11, jfr W20
Z93	RELATIONS WITH PARENT LIVING ELSEWHERE	X95
Z94	AGE WHEN PARENTS' COHABITATION ENDED	NEW
Z95	LIVED WITH STEPPARENTS	NEW
Z96	LIVED WITH STEPSIBLINGS	jfr X114
Z97	MOVED FROM PARENTAL HOME YEAR/MONTH	X115
Z98	CONFLICT IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY	X116, Y42, U26, V20, W29
Z99	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENTS	X117
Z100	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENT AND STEPPARENT	X118
Z101	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL MOTHER	X119
Z102	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL FATHER	X120
Z103	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND STEPMOTHER OR STEPFATHER	X121
Z104	CONFLICT BETWEEN OTHERS, WHO...	X122
Z105	FATHER'S EDUCATION	X123, jfr Y22, jfr U22, jfr V13, jfr W22
Z106	MOTHER'S EDUCATION	X124, jfr Y23, jfr U23, jfr V14, jfr W23
Z108	SEI FATHER	X126, jfr Y24, jfr U150
Z109	NYK80 FATHER	X127, Y25

Z110	NYK85 FATHER	X128
Z111	SSYK FATHER	NEW
Z112	ISCO88 FATHER	NEW
Z114	SIOPS FATHER	NEW
Z115	FATHER'S EGP	X848, Y670
Z116	FATHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	X129, jfr Y27, jfr U152, jfr V16, jfr W25
Z117	FATHER FARMER: AREA	X130, Y28, U153, jfr V16, jfr W25
Z118	FATHER'S PARENTAL LEAVE	NEW
Z120	SEI MOTHER	X132, jfr Y29, jfr U159
Z121	NYK80 MOTHER	X133, Y30
Z122	NYK85 MOTHER	X134
Z123	SSYK MOTHER	NEW
Z124	ISCO88 MOTHER	NEW
Z126	SIOPS MOTHER	NEW
Z127	MOTHER'S EGP	X849, Y671
Z128	MOTHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	jfr X135, jfr Y32, jfr U152
Z129	MOTHER FARMER: AREA	X136, Y33, jfr U153
Z130	RESPONDENT'S AGE WHEN MOTHER STARTED GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT	X137
Z131	CHILDHOOD FAMILY'S ECONOMY	X138, Y36, U25, V19, W28
Z132	PARENTS' HOME-OWNING	jfr X140, Y39
Z133	YEAR OF BIRTH – MOTHER	X237
Z134	MOTHER - ALIVE	X238, jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
Z135	YEAR OF DEATH – MOTHER	X239
Z136	CIVIL STATUS – MOTHER	X240
Z137	DISTANCE – MOTHER	X241
Z138	RELATIONS MOTHER	X242
Z139	TELEPHONE CONTACT MOTHER	X243
Z140	YEAR OF BIRTH – FATHER	X244
Z141	FATHER – ALIVE	X245, jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
Z142	YEAR OF DEATH – FATHER	X246
Z143	CIVIL STATUS – FATHER	X247
Z144	DISTANCE – FATHER	X248
Z145	RELATIONS FATHER	X249
Z146	TELEPHONE CONTACT FATHER	X250

HOME TOWN

Z147	NUMBER OF HOME TOWNS	X142, jfr Y44, jfr U30, jfr V24, jfr W9
Z148	TYPE OF HOME TOWN	X143, Y46, U32, V26, W11
Z149	HOME COUNTY – COUNTRY	X144, Y47, U33, V27, W12
Z150	HOME MUNICIPALITY	X145, Y48, U34, V28, W13

CHILD CARE AND SCHOOL

Z151	NUMBER OF MONTHS AT DAY-CARE CENTRE	X146, Y51
Z152	WENT TO CHILDMINDER	jfr X147, jfr Y52
Z153	WENT TO PREPARATORY SCHOOL	jfr X148, jfr Y53

FAMILY SITUATION

HOUSEHOLD STRUCTURE

Z154	CIVIL STATUS ACCORDING TO INTERVIEW	jfr X149, jfr Y57, jfr U90, jfr V68, jfr W36 X150
Z155	YEAR/MONTH START OF CURRENT COHABITATION	
Z156	YEAR/MONTH OF MARRIAGE	NEW
Z157	NUMBER OF PERSONS IN HOUSEHOLD	X151, Y58, U91, jfr V57, jfr W90
Z158	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S SEX	X152
Z159	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S YEAR OF BIRTH	X153
Z160	NUMBER OF CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	X154
Z161	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	X155, jfr Y59, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
Z162	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	X156, jfr Y60, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
Z163	NUMBER OF CHILDREN BORN 1992-2010 IN HOUSEHOLD	X157
Z164	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN BORN 2000-2009 IN HOUSEHOLD	X160, jfr Y81
Z165	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009	X161, jfr Y61, jfr U103
Z166	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009 BORN 1992-2009	X162
Z167	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009	X163, jfr Y62, jfr U103
Z168	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009 BORN 1992-2009	X164
Z169	FAMILY TYPE	X165
Z170	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1	X166, Y63
Z171	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2	X167, Y64
Z172	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3	X168, Y65
Z173	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4	X169, Y66
Z174	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5	X170, Y67
Z175	SEX CHILD 1	X171
Z176	SEX CHILD 2	X172
Z177	SEX CHILD 3	X173
Z178	SEX CHILD 4	X174
Z179	SEX CHILD 5	X175
Z180	LIVES WITH PARENT	X176, Y68
Z181	HOUSEHOLD WITH THREE GENERATIONS	X177, Y69
Z182	MARRIED/COHABITING 2009 AND 2010	X178, Y71, U110
Z183	OTHER CHILDREN 2009, NOT IN HOUSEHOLD 2010	X179, Y70

Z170 and Z175

Above variables are also given for child 6-8. The variable names correspond to above with suffixes: _a to _c, where _a indicates child number 6, _b child number 7 and _c child number 8. These are not tabulated but included in the dataset.

SPOUSE'S OCCUPATION

Z184	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE	X181, jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710
Z185	SEI SPOUSE	X182, jfr Y72, jfr U117, jfr V711
Z186	NYK80 SPOUSE	X183, Y73, U119
Z187	NYK85 SPOUSE	X184
Z188	SSYK SPOUSE	NEW

Z189	ISCO88 SPOUSE	NEW
Z191	SIOPS SPOUSE	NEW
Z192	SPOUSE'S EGP	X185, Y672
Z193	SPOUSE SELF-EMPLOYED: EMPLOYEES	X187, jfr Y75, jfr U120
Z194	SPOUSE'S CURRENT WORKING HOURS	X189, Y77, U111
Z195	SPOUSE'S/PARTNER'S HIGHEST EDUCATION	NEW

CHILDREN IN THE HOUSEHOLD

Z196	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN MUNICIPAL CHILDCARE	X200, jfr Y82
Z197	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN PRIVATE CHILDCARE	X201
Z198	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN MANAGING ALONE	X203, Y85
Z199	NUMBER OF COMMON (WITH SPOUSE/PARTNER) CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	jfr X220
Z200	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z201	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z202	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z203	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z204	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z205	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z206	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z207	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X221
Z208	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X222
Z209	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z210	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	jfr X231
Z211	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z212	SUPERVISION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z213	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
Z214	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
Z215	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR LATER)	NEW
Z216sei	SEI CHILD 1	NEW
Z216nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 1	NEW
Z216nyk85	NYK 85 CHILD 1	NEW
Z216ssyk	SSYK CHILD 1	NEW
Z216isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 1	NEW
Z216siops	SIOPS CHILD 1	NEW
Z216egp	EGP CHILD 1	NEW
Z217	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z218	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z219	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z220	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z221	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z222	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW

Z223	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z224	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X223
Z225	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X224
Z226	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z227	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X232
Z228	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z229	SUPERVISION – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z230	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z231	SUPERVISION – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z232	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR LATER)	NEW
Z233sei	SEI CHILD 2	NEW
Z233nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 2	NEW
Z233nyk85	NYK 85 CHILD 2	NEW
Z233ssyk	SSYK CHILD 2	NEW
Z233isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 2	NEW
Z233siops	SIOPS CHILD 2	NEW
Z233egp	EGP CHILD 2	NEW
Z234	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z235	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z236	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z237	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z238	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z239	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z240	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z241	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X225
Z242	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X226
Z243	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z244	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X233
Z245	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z246	SUPERVISION – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z247	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z248	SUPERVISION – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z249	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR LATER)	NEW
Z250sei	SEI CHILD 3	NEW
Z250nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 3	NEW
Z250nyk85	NYK 85 CHILD 3	NEW
Z250ssyk	SSYK CHILD 3	NEW
Z250isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 3	NEW
Z250siops	SIOPS CHILD 3	NEW
Z250egp	EGP CHILD 3	NEW
Z251	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z252	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW

Z253	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z254	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z255	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z256	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z257	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z258	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X227
Z259	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X228
Z260	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z261	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X234
Z262	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z263	SUPERVISION – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z264	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z265	SUPERVISION – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z266	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR LATER)	NEW
Z267sei	SEI CHILD 4	NEW
Z267nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 4	NEW
Z267nyk85	NYK 85 CHILD 4	NEW
Z267ssyk	SSYK CHILD 4	NEW
Z267isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 4	NEW
Z267siops	SIOPS CHILD 4	NEW
Z267egp	EGP CHILD 4	NEW
Z268	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z269	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Z270	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z271	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z272	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z273	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z274	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z275	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X229
Z276	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X230
Z277	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z278	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X235
Z279	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z280	SUPERVISION – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z281	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z282	SUPERVISION – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Z283	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR LATER)	NEW
Z284sei	SEI CHILD 5	NEW
Z284nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 5	NEW
Z284nyk85	NYK 85 CHILD 5	NEW
Z284ssyk	SSYK CHILD 5	NEW
Z284isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 5	NEW

Z284siops	SIOPS CHILD 5	NEW
Z284egp	EGP CHILD 5	NEW

Z201 to Z216egp

Above variables are also given for child 6-8. The variable names correspond to above with suffixes: _a to _c, where _a indicates child number 6, _b child number 7 and _c child number 8. These are not tabulated but included in the dataset.

Z285	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY	jfr X236
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CHILDREN OUTSIDE THE HOUSEHOLD

Z286	CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X204, Y89, U124, jfr V954, jfr W59
Z287	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X205, Y90, U125, jfr V954, jfr W59
Z288	NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X206, Y91, U126, jfr V958
Z289	NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X207, Y92, jfr U127, jfr V958
Z290	NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X208, Y93, jfr U129, jfr V956, jfr W61
Z291	NUMBER OF DECEASED CHILDREN	X209, jfr Y94, jfr U130, jfr V957, jfr W62
Z292	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD WHO LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT	X210
Z293	SEX – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z294	YEAR OF BIRTH – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z295	BIOLOGICAL CHILD - CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z296	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z297	LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT - CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z298	END OF LIVING TOGETHER WITH CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z299	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z300	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z301	SEES CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z302	CONTACT WTH CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z303	DISTANCE TO CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z304	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z305	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306sei	SEI – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306nyk80	NYK80 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306nyk85	NYK85 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306ssyk	SSYK – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306isco88	ISCO88 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306siops	SIOPS – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW
Z306egp	EGP – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1	NEW

Z293 to Z306egp

Above variables are also given for children staying with the other parent number 2-11. The variable names correspond to above with suffixes: _a to _j, where _a indicates the second child staying with the other parent, _b the third child and so forth. These are not tabulated but included in the dataset.

CIVIL STATUS

Z307	NOT LIVING WITH PARTNER	NEW
Z308	DURATION OF LIVE-APART-RELATIONSHIP	NEW
Z309	PREVIOUSLY COHABITING	X190, Y99

Z310	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS	X191, Y100
Z311	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS MARRIAGES	X192
Z312	YEAR/MONTH FOR FIRST COHABITATION	X193, jfr Y101
Z313	DURATION FIRST COHABITATION	X194, Y102
Z314	CIVIL STATUS FIRST COHABITATION	X195
Z315	YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED	jfr X196, jfr Y103
Z316	DURATION LAST COHABITATION	X197
Z317	REASON FOR SEPARATION LAST COHABITATION	X198, Y104
Z318	CIVIL STATUS LAST COHABITATION	X199
Z319	INITIATOR IN DECISION TO SEPARATE	NEW

FRIENDSHIP RELATIONS

Z320	NUMBER OF CLOSE FRIENDS	X251
Z321	CLOSE FRIENDS – MEN	X253
Z322	CLOSE FRIENDS – BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY	X254
Z323	CLOSE FRIENDS – UNEMPLOYED	X256
Z324	SEES CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	X259
Z325	TELEPHONE CONTACT WITH CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	X260
Z326	SEI CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z327	NYK80 CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z328	NYK85 CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z329	SSYK CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z330	ISCO88 CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z331	SIOPS CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW
Z332	EGP CLOSEST FRIEND	NEW

EDUCATION

Z342	YEARS OF EDUCATION, RESPONDENT	X261, Y131, U137, V229, W538
Z343	TOTAL VOCATIONAL EDUCATION, RESPONDENT	jfr Y133, U139, V231, jfr W833
Z344	HIGHEST COMPLETED EDUCATION IN SWEDEN	NEW
Z345	COUNTRY OF HIGHEST EDUCATION	NEW
Z346	YEARS OF EDUCATION ABROAD	Y157
Z347	COUNTRY OF FOREIGN EDUCATION	NEW
Z348	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL STUDIES ABROAD	Y158
Z349	MONTHS OF EDUCATION IN SWEDEN	jfr Y159
Z350	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL HIGHEST EDUCATION	NEW
Z352	HIGHEST EDUCATION – RESPONDENT	jfr X305, jfr Y164, jfr U138, jfr V230, jfr W537
Z354	YEAR/MONTH COMPLETED HIGHEST EDUCATION	jfr Y166
Z355	STUDIES NOW: TYPE OF STUDIES	jfr Y168, jfr U568, jfr V596, jfr W368

OCCUPATIONAL BIOGRAPHY

Z359	NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT	X311, Y183, U478, V517, W293
Z360	EVER WORKED 6 MONTHS	X312

Z361	COUNTRY OF FIRST JOB LASTING 6 MONTHS	NEW
Z362	YEAR/MONTH START OF FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z363	YEAR/MONTH END OF FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z364	YEAR/MONTH START OF LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z365	YEAR/MONTH END OF LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z366	COUNTRY OF LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z367	BEGAN WORKING (IN SWEDEN): YEAR	X313, Y184, jfr U144
Z368	STILL AT FIRST JOB (IF AT LEAST 6 MONTHS OF DURATION)	X314, jfr Y185
Z369	TIME IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	X315, Y186, jfr U478
Z370	WHEN LAST GAINFULLY EMPLOYED	X316, Y187
Z371	TIME IN UNEMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	Y188
Z372	LAST UNEMPLOYED AT LEAST 1 MONTH, YEAR	Y191
Z373	NUMBER OF TIMES UNEMPLOYED AT LEAST 1 MONTH	Y192
Z374	YEAR EMPLOYED IN CURRENT JOB	X322, jfr Y193, jfr U350, jfr V400, jfr W229
Z375	SENIORITY, CURRENT WORKPLACE, MONTHS	X323, Y195
Z376	SENIORITY, CURRENT JOB, MONTHS	X324, Y196
Z377	NUMBER OF GAINFUL EMPLOYMENTS, TOTAL	X325, Y197
Z378	NUMBERS OF JOBS AS EMPLOYEE	X326, Y198
Z379	NUMBER OF EMPLOYMENTS	Y201
Z380	TIME AWAY FROM GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	X329, Y202
Z381	TIME IN PARENTAL LEAVE, MONTHS	Y203
Z382	TIME IN HOUSEHOLD WORK, MONTHS	Y204
Z383	TIME IN SCHOOL, MONTHS	Y205
Z384	NUMBER OF TIMES IN SCHOOL, MONTHS	Y206
Z385	NUMBER OF TIMES AWAY FROM WORK, AT LEAST 1 MONTH	Y207
Z386	LAST TIME AWAY FROM WORK, YEAR	Y208
Z387	SEI AGE 25	X336, Y209
Z388	NYK80 AGE 25	Y210
Z389	NYK85 AGE 25	NEW
Z394	EGP AGE 25	Y211
Z395	SECTOR AGE 25	Y212
Z396	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 25	X341, Y213
Z397	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 25	X342, Y214
Z398	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 25	NEW
Z399	SEI AGE 30	X347, Y215
Z400	NYK80 AGE 30	Y216
Z401	NYK85 AGE 30	NEW
Z406	EGP AGE 30	Y217
Z407	SECTOR AGE 30	Y218
Z408	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 30	X352, Y219
Z409	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 30	X353, Y220
Z410	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 30	NEW
Z411	SEI AGE 35	X358, Y221
Z412	NYK80 AGE 35	Y222
Z413	NYK85 AGE 35	NEW
Z418	EGP AGE 35	Y223

Z419	SECTOR AGE 35	Y224
Z420	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 35	X363, Y225
Z421	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 35	X364, Y226
Z422	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 35	NEW
Z423	SEI AGE 40	X369, Y227
Z424	NYK80 AGE 40	Y228
Z425	NYK85 AGE 40	NEW
Z430	EGP AGE 40	Y229
Z431	SECTOR AGE 40	Y230
Z432	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 40	X374, Y231
Z433	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 40	X375, Y232
Z434	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 40	NEW
Z435	SEI AGE 45	X380, Y233
Z436	NYK80 AGE 45	Y234
Z437	NYK85 AGE 45	NEW
Z442	EGP AGE 45	Y235
Z443	SECTOR AGE 45	Y236
Z444	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 45	X385, Y237
Z445	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 45	X386, Y238
Z446	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 45	NEW
Z447	SEI AGE 50	X391, Y239
Z448	NYK80 AGE 50	Y240
Z449	NYK85 AGE 50	NEW
Z454	EGP AGE 50	Y241
Z455	SECTOR AGE 50	Y242
Z456	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 50	X396, Y243
Z457	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 50	X397, Y244
Z458	SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 50	NEW
Z459	SEI FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z460	NYK80 FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z461	NYK85 FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z462	EGP FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z463	FIRM SIZE (SELF-EMPLOYED) FIRST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z464	SEI LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z465	NYK80 LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z466	NYK85 LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z467	EGP LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z468	FIRM SIZE (SELF-EMPLOYED) LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW
Z469	SEI FIRST JOB	X402, Y245
Z470	NYK80 FIRST JOB	X403, Y246
Z471	NYK85 FIRST JOB	X404
Z476	EGP FIRST JOB	X405, Y247
Z479	SIZE OF WORKPLACE FIRST JOB	jfr Y249
Z480	SECTOR FIRST JOB	Y250
Z481	SEI CURRENT JOB	X412, Y251
Z482	NYK80 CURRENT JOB	X413, Y252

Z483	NYK85 CURRENT JOB	X414
Z484	SSYK CURRENT JOB	NEW
Z488	EGP CURRENT JOB	X415, Y253
Z489	SNI CURRENT JOB	NEW
Z491	WORKPLACE SIZE, CURRENT JOB	X417, jfr Y255
Z492	SECTOR, CURRENT JOB	X418, Y256
Z493	EMPLOYMENT STATUS WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z494	SEI WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z495	NYK80 WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z496	NYK85 WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z501	EGP WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z504	SIZE OF WORKPLACE WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
Z505	SECTOR WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW

HEALTH AND USE OF HEALTH CARE

Z506	GENERAL HEALTH	X435, Y257
Z507	WALK 100 M	X436, Y258, U160, V235, W101
Z508	RUN 100 M	X437, Y259, U161, V236, W102
Z509	WALK STAIRS	X438, Y260, U162, V237, W103
Z510	TURN TAP	X439, Y261
Z511	LENGTH IN CM	X440, Y262
Z512	WEIGHT IN KG	X441, Y263

ILLNESSES AND AILMENTS IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS

Z513	HEADACHE	X452, Y277, U190, V257, W120
Z514	COLD	X453, Y278, U191, V258, W121
Z515	POOR VISION	X454, Y279, U192, V259, W122
Z516	IMPAIRED HEARING	X455, Y280, U193, V260, W123
Z517	CHEST PAIN	X456, Y281, U194, V261, W124
Z518	BRONCHITIS	X457, Y282, U195, V262, W125
Z519	GOITRE	X458, Y283, U196, V263, W126
Z520	TUBERCULOSIS	X459, Y284, U197, V264, W127
Z521	ACHES IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES	X460, Y285, U198, V265, W128
Z522	HEART ATTACK	X461, Y286, U199, V266, W129
Z523	STROKE	X462
Z524	CARDIAC WEAKNESS	X463, Y287, U200, V267, W130
Z525	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE	X464, Y288, U201, V268, W131
Z526	STOMACH PAINS	X465, Y289, U202, V269, W132
Z527	GASTRIC ULCER	X466, Y290, U203, V270, W133
Z528	PAIN IN BACK/HIPS	X467, Y291, U204, V271, W134
Z529	BILIARY TROUBLE	X468, Y292, U205, V272, W135
Z530	KIDNEY TROUBLE	X469, Y293, U206, V273, W136
Z531	HAEMORRHOIDS	X470, Y294, U207, V274, W137
Z532	TROUBLE WITH URINATION	X471, Y295, U208, V275, W138
Z533	MENSTRUATION TROUBLE	X472, Y296, jfr U209, jfr V276, jfr W139

Z534	PREGNANCY COMPLICATIONS	X473, Y297, jfr U210, jfr V278, jfr W141
Z535	VAGINAL TROUBLE	X474, Y298, U211, V277, W140
Z536	INGUINAL HERNIA	X475, Y299, U212, V279, W142
Z537	VARICOSE VEINS	X476, Y300, U213, V280, W143
Z538	SWOLLEN LEGS	X477, Y301, U214, V281, W144
Z539	ACHES IN JOINTS	X478, Y302, U215, V282, W145
Z540	GENERAL TIREDNESS	X479, Y303, U216, V283, W146
Z541	INSOMNIA	X480, Y304, U217, V284, W147
Z542	NERVOUS TROUBLE	X481, Y305, U218, V285, W148
Z543	DEPRESSIONS	X482, Y306, U219, V286, W149
Z544	MENTAL ILLNESS	X483, Y307, U220, V287, W150
Z545	SWEATING	X484, Y308, U221, V288, W151
Z546	COUGH	X485, Y309, U222, V289, W152
Z547	DIFFICULTY BREATHING	X486, Y310, U223, V290, W153
Z548	DIZZINESS	X487, Y311, U224, V291, W154
Z549	NAUSEA	X488, Y312, U225, V292, W155
Z550	WEIGHT LOSS	X489, Y313, U226, V293, W156
Z551	VOMITING	X490, Y314, U227, V294, W157
Z552	DIARRHOEA	X491, Y315, U228, V295, W158
Z553	CONSTIPATION	X492, Y316, U229, V296, W159
Z554	OVEREXERTION	X493, Y317, U230, V297, W160
Z555	RASHES	X494, Y318, U231, V298, W161
Z556	CANCER	X495, Y319, U232, V299, W162
Z557	ANAEMIA	X496, Y320, U233, V300, W163
Z558	DIABETES	X497, Y321, U234, V301, W164
Z559	OVERWEIGHT	X498, Y322, U235, V302, W165
Z560	ORGANIC NERVE DISORDER	X499, Y323, U236, V303, W166
Z561	DISCOMFORT AFTER INJURY	X500, Y324, jfr U189
Z562	ALLERGY	X501, Y325
Z563	URINARY TRACT INFECTION	X502, Y326
Z564	OTHER ILLNESSES	jfr Y327, jfr Y328, jfr U237, jfr U238, jfr V304, jfr V305

USE OF HEALTH CARE

Z565	HOSPITALIZED	X509, Y329, U253, V310, jfr W172
Z566	BEEN TO A DOCTOR	jfr X511, jfr Y331, jfr U255, V321, jfr W176
Z567	VISITED A NURSE	X515, Y333, U257, V323, W177
Z568	CONDITION OF TEETH	X519, Y336, jfr U269, jfr V336, jfr W185

ALCOHOL OCH TOBACCO

Z569	SMOKING	X522, Y340, jfr U278, jfr V340, jfr W202, W203
Z570	SMOKING NUMBER OF YEARS	X523, Y341, U279
Z571	DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR ETC	X525, Y343, U280, jfr V341, jfr W204
Z572	NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC	X526
Z573	NUMBER OF GLASSES	X527

PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH

Z574	AGILITY	X528, Y346, U239, V734, W559
Z575	INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING	X529, Y347, U241, V736
Z576	PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING	X530, Y348, U242, V737, W573
Z577	OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX	X531, Y349
Z578	ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM	X532, Y350, U243, V739, W567
Z579	OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE	X533, Y351
Z580	CIRCULATORY SYSTEM	X534, Y352, U244, V740, W566
Z581	OLLE'S CIRCULATORY INDEX	X535, Y353
Z582	STOMACH TROUBLE	X536, Y354, U245, V741, W568
Z583	OLLE'S STOMACH INDEX	X537, Y355
Z584	DEFECATION TROUBLE	X538, Y356, U246, V742, W569
Z585	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE	X539, Y357, U247, V743, jfr W637
Z586	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE 2	X540, Y358
Z587	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM	X542, Y359, U248, V744, jfr W638
Z588	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM 2	X543

OCCUPATIONAL SITUATION

LAST YEAR

Z589	TOTAL NUMBER OF WEEKS WORKED 2009	NEW
Z590	TOTAL HOURS WORKED 2009	jfr X544, jfr Y360, jfr U283, jfr V789, jfr W940
Z591	EMPLOYED 2009	jfr X545 & X548, jfr Y361 & Y364, jfr U284 & U288, jfr V342 & V346, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
Z592	WEEKS FULL-TIME 2009	jfr X546 & X549, jfr Y362 & Y366, jfr U285 & U290, jfr V343 & V348, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
Z593	HOURS PER WEEK EMPLOYED 2009	jfr X547 & X550, jfr Y363 & Y365, jfr U286 & U289, jfr V344 & V347, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
Z594	WORK IN OWN FIRM 2009	jfr X557, jfr Y375, jfr U304, jfr V364, jfr W214, jfr W215
Z595	WEEKS IN OWN FIRM 2009	jfr X558 & X552, jfr Y376 & Y370, jfr U305 & U297, jfr V365 & V357, jfr W214 & W210, jfr W215 & W211
Z596	HOURS PER WEEK IN OWN FIRM 2009	jfr X559 & X553, jfr Y377 & Y371, jfr U306 & U298, jfr V366 & V358, jfr W214 & W210, jfr W215 & W211
Z597	UNEMPLOYED DURING 2009	jfr X566, jfr Y384, jfr U316, jfr V376, jfr W220
Z598	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED 2009	jfr X567, jfr Y385, jfr U317, jfr V377, jfr W220

LAST WEEK

Z599	LAST WEEK: FULL-TIME	X570, Y398, jfr U332, jfr V345
Z600	LAST WEEK: PART-TIME	X571, Y399, jfr U333, jfr V349
Z601	LAST WEEK: OWN FIRM OR FARM	jfr X574 & X572, jfr Y402 & Y400, jfr U338 & U336, jfr V367 & V359
Z602	LAST WEEK: FAMILY MEMBER'S FIRM OR FARM	jfr X575 & X573, jfr Y403 & Y401, jfr U339 & U337, jfr V371 & V363
Z603	LAST WEEK: FREELANCE OCCUPATION OR SIDE-LINE	X576, Y404, U340, V375
Z604	LAST WEEK: LOOKING FOR WORK	X577, Y405, U341, V378

Z605	LAST WEEK: PENSION	X578, Y406, U344, V387
Z606	LAST WEEK: STUDYING	X580, Y408, U346, V393
Z607	LAST WEEK: OTHER	X582, Y410, U347, V396

EMPLOYEES' WORKING CONDITIONS

Z608	SEI EMPLOYEES	X583, Y411, jfr U355, jfr V712
Z609	NYK80 EMPLOYEES	X584, Y412, jfr U356
Z610	NYK85 EMPLOYEES	X585
Z611	SSYK EMPLOYEES	NEW
Z612	ISCO88 EMPLOYEES	NEW
Z614	SIOPS EMPLOYEES	NEW
Z615	NUMBER OF YEARS IN SIMILAR KIND OF WORK	NEW
Z616	EMPLOYMENT CONTRACT	jfr X419
Z617	ABSENT FROM WORK LAST 3 MONTHS	NEW
Z618	REASON FOR ABSENCE LAST 3 MONTHS	NEW
Z619	ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, CURRENT JOB	jfr X587 & X588
Z620	ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, DIFFERENT EMPLOYERS	jfr X587 & X588
Z621	YEAR OF EMPLOYMENT CURRENT JOB	jfr Y193, jfr U350, jfr V400, jfr W229
Z622	NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES	X590, Y414, jfr U357, jfr V404, jfr W233
Z623	SUBORDINATES HAVE MANAGING POSITIONS	NEW
Z624	EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS	X591, Y415, U358, V405, jfr W234
Z625	SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	X592, Y416, U359, V406, jfr W234
Z626	LEARNING TIME	X593, Y417
Z627	USE OF PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE	X594, Y418
Z628	SPECIFIC COMPETENCE	X596, Y419

WORK TIMES LAST WEEK

Z629	WORKING HOURS OR SHIFT	jfr X601, Y422, jfr U360
Z630	UNCOMFORTABLE WORK TIME	NEW
Z631	REGULAR WEEKLY WORK HOURS	X602, Y460, U418, V459, W251
Z632	SUITABLE WORK TIME	X603, Y461, U420, V468
Z633	HOW OFTEN OVERTIME	X604
Z634	COMPENSATION FOR OVERTIME	X609
Z635	NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK/YEAR	X627
Z636	TRAVELLING TIME MINUTES PER DAY	X651, jfr Y441, jfr U387, jfr V765, jfr W244, W636

SALARY

Z637	FIXED MONTHLY SALARY BEFORE TAX	X611, Y464, U434, V720, jfr W272, W275
Z638	WEEKLY WAGE BEFORE TAX	X612, Y465, U435, V721, jfr W272, W275
Z639	FIXED HOURLY WAGE	X613, Y466, U436, V722, jfr W272, W275
Z640	INDIVIDUAL PIECE-RATE	X614, Y467, U437, jfr V723, V724, jfr W272, W275
Z641	GROUP PIECE-RATE	X615, Y468, U438, V725, jfr W272, W275
Z642	MONTHLY SALARY W BONUS/COMMISSION	X616, jfr Y469, jfr U439, jfr V726, jfr W272, W275

Z643	COMP. FOR INCONVENIENT WORKING HOURS	X617, Y470, U441, V729, jfr W272
Z644	OTHER WAGE FORM SEK/MONTH	X618, Y471, U442, V730, jfr W272
Z645	GROSS HOURLY WAGE	X619, jfr Y472, jfr U443, jfr V727, jfr W650
Z646	MONTHLY SALARY AFTER TAX	X620, Y473, U433, V490, jfr W276

AUTONOMY AND INFLUENCE

Z647	PUNCTUALITY DEMANDED	X628, Y482, U422, V470, W254
Z648	PUNCH CLOCK	X629, Y483, U423, V471, W255
Z649	FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS	X630, Y484, U424
Z650	LEVEL OF FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS	NEW
Z651	CAN GO ON AN ERRAND	X631, Y485, U427, V474, W258
Z652	CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK	X633, Y487, U429
Z653	INFLUENCE WHAT TASKS	X634, Y489
Z654	INFLUENCE WORKING METHODS	X635, Y490
Z655	LEARNS NEW THINGS	X636, Y491
Z656	GETS SUPPORT FROM WORKMATES	X638, Y494
Z657	BOSS' NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES	X645
Z658	SEX OF BOSS	X646
Z659	BOSS BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY	X647
Z660	BOSS IS TOP MANAGER AT WORKPLACE	NEW
Z661	RESPONDENT'S WORK DIFFICULT TO MONITOR	NEW
Z662	WORK EFFORTS, MOST IMPORTANT REASON	NEW
Z663	WORK EFFORTS, SECOND MOST IMPORTANT REASON	NEW
Z664	DIFFICULT TO REPLACE RESPONDENT	X648
Z665	DIFFICULT TO GET NEW JOB	X649
Z666	REMAINS WITH EMPLOYER, 1 YEAR FROM NOW	NEW

CONDITIONS FOR THE GAINFULLY EMPLOYED

WORKING ENVIROMENT

Z667	HEAVY LIFTING	X653, Y507, U447, V492, jfr W277
Z668	PHYSICALLY DEMANDING	X654, Y508, U448, V493, W278
Z669	DAILY SWEATING	X655, Y509, U449, V494, W279
Z670	MENTALLY TAXING	X656, Y510, U451, V496, W281
Z671	STRESSFUL WORK	X657, Y511, U452, V497, W282
Z672	MONOTONOUS WORK	X658, Y512, U453, V498, W283
Z673	MENTAL PRESSURE	X659, Y513
Z674	MENTAL ACTIVITY	X660, Y514
Z675	SEDENTARY WORK	NEW
Z676	MANAGING WORK	NEW
Z677	WORK WITH HUMANS, NO MANAGING	NEW
Z678	WORK WITH TEXT AND/OR NUMBERS	NEW
Z679	WORK WITH TOOLS	NEW
Z680	WORK WITH HIGH MENTAL EFFORT	NEW
Z681	WORK WITH LOW MENTAL EFFORT	NEW
Z682	WORK WITH EMOTIONALLY DEMANDING WORK TASKS	NEW

Z683	ABSENCE DUE TO ILLNESS	X669
Z684	NOISE	X663, Y515, U456, V501, W286
Z685	MONOTONOUS MOVEMENTS	X664, Y517, U465, V511
Z686	UNSUITABLE WORK POSITIONS	X665, Y518, U466, V512
Z687	GAS, DUST, SMOKE	X666, Y519, U468, V514, jfr W290
Z688	DIRTY WORK	X667, jfr U455, jfr V500, jfr W285
Z689	TOXIC SUBSTANCES, ACIDS, EXPLOSIVES	X668, Y521, U470, V516, jfr W291
Z690	SATISFACTION WITH WAGES	X671, Y523
Z691	JOB ATTITUDE	NEW

SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER

Z694	NYK80 SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER	Y536, jfr U498
Z695	NYK85 SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER	NEW
Z700	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES IN FIRM/FARM	jfr X684, jfr Y537, jfr U499, jfr V538, jfr W315
Z701	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS	jfr X685, jfr Y542, jfr U501, jfr V540, jfr W317
Z702	HOURS BUSY WEEKS	jfr X686
Z703	HOURS QUIET WEEKS	jfr X687
Z704	NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKS	jfr X688
Z705	VACATION 2009	jfr X689,
Z706	VACATION WEEKS 2009	jfr X690, jfr Y544, jfr U504, jfr V543, jfr W319
Z707	VALUE OF COMPANY/FARM	NEW
Z708	RESPONDENT'S SHARE OF OWNING IN COMPANY/FARM	NEW
Z709	PARTNER'S SHARE OF OWNING IN COMPANY/FARM	NEW

FREELANCE/SIDELINE OCCUPATION

Z710	SEI FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE	X691, Y545, jfr U508
Z711	NYK80 FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE	X692, Y546, jfr U509
Z712	NYK85 FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE	X693
Z717	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS	X694, Y548, U511, V547, jfr W323

UNEMPLOYED

Z718	SEI UNEMPLOYED	X695, Y549, jfr U516
Z719	NYK80 UNEMPLOYED	X696, Y550, jfr U517
Z720	NYK85 UNEMPLOYED	X697
Z725	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED	X698, Y551, U525, V559, jfr W345
Z726	PREFERED WORKING HOURS	NEW
Z727	WORK ATTITUDE	NEW

PENSIONERS

Z728	YEAR OF RETIREMENT	jfr Y552, jfr U552, jfr V584, jfr W362
Z736	FORMERLY SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER - EMPLOYEES	jfr X705, Y557, U558
Z737	WANTS TO WORK	X706, Y558, U559, V586, W363
Z738	WANTED WORKING HOURS PER WEEK	X707, Y559, jfr U560-U562
Z739	DOES NOT MANAGE TO WORK	X708, Y560, U563, V591
Z740	NOT PROFITABLE	X709, Y562, U565, V593

HOUSEWORK AND FAMILY

Z748	HOURS – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	X713, Y567, jfr U542, jfr V576
Z749	HOURS RESPONDENT – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	X714, Y568, jfr U543, jfr V577
Z750	HOURS – CARE OF CLOTHING	X715, Y569, jfr U536, U538, jfr V570, V572
Z751	HOURS RESPONDENT – CARE OF CLOTHING	X716, Y570, jfr U537, U539, jfr V571, V573
Z752	HOURS – CLEANING	X717, Y571, jfr U540, jfr V574
Z753	HOURS RESPONDENT - CLEANING	X718, Y572, jfr U541, jfr V575
Z754	HOURS – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X719
Z755	HOURS RESPONDENT – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X720
Z756	HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE	X721
Z757	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN	jfr X722
Z758	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS	jfr X723
Z759	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE	jfr X724
Z760	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE	jfr X725
Z761	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE	jfr X726
Z762	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER	jfr X727
Z763	DISTRIBUTION OF HOUSEHOLD'S MONEY	X728
Z764	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK	X729
Z765	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY	X730
Z766	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS	X733
Z767	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH RESPONDENT WORKS	X734
Z768	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT DROPS CHILDREN OFF	X735
Z769	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER DROPS CHILDREN OFF	X736
Z770	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE DROPS CHILDREN OFF	X737
Z771	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PICKS CHILDREN UP	X738
Z772	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PICKS CHILDREN UP	X739
Z773	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PICKS CHILDREN UP	X740
Z774	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT COOKS DINNER	X741
Z775	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER COOKS DINNER	X742
Z776	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE COOKS DINNER	X743
Z777	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PUTS CHILDREN TO BED	X744
Z778	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PUTS CHILDREN TO BED	X745
Z779	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PUTS CHILDREN TO BED	X746

ECONOMIC RESOURCES

Z780	CASH MARGIN	X748, Y574, U576, jfr V602, jfr W375
Z781	ACQUIRING CASH	X749, Y575, U577, jfr V602, jfr W375
Z782	ECONOMIC DIFFICULTIES	X754, Y584
Z783	RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH	X755
Z784	PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH	X756
Z785	INHERITANCE	NEW
Z786	TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT GIVEN	X760
Z787	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	X761

Z788	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	X762
Z789	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X763
Z790	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X764
Z791	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK	X765
Z792	TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT RECEIVED	X766
Z793	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	X767
Z794	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	X768
Z795	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X769
Z796	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X770
Z797	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK	X771
Z798	CLOSE FRIEND WHEN ILL	X775, Y614, U699
Z799	CLOSE FRIEND AS COMPANY	X776, Y615, U700
Z800	SOMEONE TO TALK TO	X777, Y616, U701
Z801	VALUE REAL ASSETS	NEW
Z802	DEBTS REAL ASSETS	NEW
Z803	REAL ASSETS, OWNING	NEW
Z804	FINANCIAL ASSETS	NEW
Z805	FINANCIAL ASSETS, OWNING	NEW

SAFETY OF LIFE AND PROSPERITY

Z806	SUFFERED FROM THEFT	X779, Y585, U593, jfr V618
Z807	SUFFERED FROM DAMAGE	X780, Y586, U596, V621
Z808	VIOLENCE LEADING TO BODILY HARM	X781, Y587, U601, V626
Z809	VIOLENCE WITHOUT BODILY HARM	X782, Y588, U602, V627
Z810	SERIOUS THREATS	X783, Y589, U603, V628

SPARETIME

Z811	VACATION TRIP 2009	X784, Y590, U611, V636, jfr W614
Z812	COTTAGE STAY2009	X785, Y594, U618, V643, W469
Z813	FISHING OR HUNTING IN SPARE TIME	X786, jfr Y596-597, jfr U621-622, jfr V646-647, jfr W472-473
Z814	GARDENING	X787, Y598, U623, V648, W474
Z815	GO TO THE CINEMA	X788, Y599, U624, V649, W475
Z816	GO TO THE THEATRE	X789, Y600, U625, V650, W476
Z817	GO TO A RESTAURANT	X790, Y601, U626, V651, W477
Z818	DANCING	X791, Y602, U627, V652, W478
Z819	VISIT RELATIVES	X792, Y604, U632, V657, W483
Z820	HAVE RELATIVES VISIT	X793, Y605, U633, V658, W485
Z821	VISIT FRIENDS AND ACQUAINTANCES	X794, Y606, U634, V659, W484
Z822	HAVE FRIENDS VISIT	X795, Y607, U635, V660, W486
Z823	READ BOOKS	X796, Y603, U628, V653, W479
Z824	STUDY CIRCLE	X797, Y608, U636, V661, W487
Z825	PLAY MUSIC OR SING IN A CHOIR	X798, jfr Y610-611, jfr U638, jfr V663, jfr W488
Z826	HOBBY ACTIVITY	X799, Y612, U640, V665, W490
Z827	INTERNET	NEW

Z828 SPORTS ACTIVITY X800, Y613

CIVIL SOCIETY PARTICIPATION

Z829 MEMBER OF TRADE UNION X801, Y617, U648,V666, jfr W491
Z830 UNION X802, Y618, U649, V667, jfr W491
Z831 VISITED TRADE UNION MEETING X803, jfr Y620, jfr U650, jfr V668,
jfr W492
Z832 UNION REPRESENTATIVE X804, Y621, U652, V670, W493
Z833 UNION ACTIVITY X805, Y622, U653, V749, W579
Z834 PARTY MEMBERSHIP X806, Y623, U654, V671, W494
Z835 VISITED POLITICAL MEETING X807, jfr Y624, jfr U656, jfr V672,
jfr W495
Z836 POLITICAL ACTIVITY X808, Y625, U658, V750, W578
Z837 PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 2006 X809, Y627, U659, V673, jfr W523
Z838 PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION – 2009 EU-P NEW
Z839 INTENTION TO VOTE IN ELECTION 2010 NEW
Z840 PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 2010 NEW
Z841 OTHER ASSOCIATIONS X810, Y629, jfr U670, jfr V683, jfr
W500
Z842 ASSOCIATION ACTIVITIES X811, Y630
Z843 RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION NEW
Z844 RELIGION IMPORTANT NEW
Z845 PUBLIC DEMONSTRATION LAST 10 YEARS NEW
Z846 PERSONAL CONTACT X815, Y634, U672, V685, W502
Z847 SPOKEN IN MEETING X816, Y635, U673, V686, W503
Z848 WRITTEN IN NEWSPAPER X817, Y636, U674, V687, W504
Z849 POLITICAL PARTICIPATION jfr X818, jfr Y637, jfr U675, jfr
V751, jfr W580,W599
Z850 CAN COMPLAIN X819, Y638, U678, V689, W506
Z851 HELP WHEN COMPLAINING X820, Y639
Z852 SPEAK ENGLISH NEW
Z853 READ ENGLISH NEW

EVALUATIONS

Z854 SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES X824, jfr Y643
Z855 SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES X825, Y645
Z856 SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY X826
Z857 SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY X827
Z858 TROUBLESHOOTER X828, Y649
Z859 LIFE SATISFACTION X829, Y650
Z860 HARD TO UNDERSTAND X830, Y651
Z861 CONTROL OF OWN LIFE X831, Y652
Z862 RESPONDENT'S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION X832, Y647, U702
Z863 HAS RESPONDENT'S CONDITIONS IMPROVED OR DETERIORATED X833, Y648, U703

PERSONALITY

Z864	I LIKE ORDERLINESS	NEW
Z865	I DO NOT SHOW FEELINGS TO OTHERS	NEW
Z866	SETBACKS DON'T DISCOURAGE ME	NEW
Z867	I TEND TO BE LAZY	NEW
Z868	I OFTEN THINK MORE ABOUT HOW OTHERS HAVE IT THAN OF MYSELF	NEW
Z869	TO SUCCEED IN LIFE YOU HAVE TO TAKE RISKS	NEW
Z870	I GET NERVOUS EASILY	NEW
Z871	I FIND IT EASY TO GET THINGS DONE	NEW
Z872	I LIKE TAKING RESPONSIBILITY	NEW
Z873	IT DOESN'T PAY TO PLAN FOR THE FUTURE	NEW
Z874	I HANDLE STRESS WELL	NEW
Z875	I FINISH WHATEVER I BEGIN	NEW
Z876	I'M A RISK TAKER	NEW
Z877	I DO NOT LIKE CHANGING OLD HABITS	NEW
Z878	I PUT EFFORT INTO THINGS THAT PAY OFF ONLY IN THE FUTURE	NEW
Z879	I FIND IT HARD TO RESIST TEMPTATIONS	NEW
Z880	SUCCESS IS A RESULT OF HARD WORK RATHER THAN LUCK	NEW
Z881	I HAVE AN ACTIVE IMAGINATION	NEW
Z882	I USUALLY PUT OF THINGS THAT FEEL BOTHERSOME	NEW
Z883	WHAT HAPPENS TO ME IS MY OWN DOING	NEW
Z884	I HAVE A GOOD SELF-CONFIDENCE	NEW
Z885	I HAVE FEW ARTISTIC INTERESTS	NEW
Z886	I AM OUTGOING AND SOCIABLE	NEW
Z887	I HAVE GOOD SELF-DISCIPLINE	NEW
Z888	I DEAL WITH TASKS THOROUGHLY	NEW
Z889	I PREFER TO STAY IN THE BACKGROUND	NEW
Z890	I TEND TO FIND FAULT WITH OTHERS	NEW
Z891	I AM A NATURAL LEADER	NEW
Z892	I AM GENERALLY TRUSTING	NEW
Z893	I AM RESERVED	NEW
Z894	IM AM ALMOST ALWAYS IN A GOOD MOOD	NEW

REGISTER INFORMATION AND WEIGHT SYSTEMS

Z913	NATIONALITY	X835, Y654, U705
Z914	COUNTY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION	X837, Y656, U707
Z915	MUNICIPALITY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION	X838, Y657, U708
Z916	H-REGION	X841, Y660, jfr U728
Z917	CIVIL STATUS	X842, Y661, U715, V814, W704
Z918	SPOUSE'S YEAR OF BIRTH	X843, Y663, U716
Z919	INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER ORDINARY DATA COLLECTION AND FOLLOW UP TO COLLECT MISSING DATA	NEW
Z920	INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER FOLLOW UP WITH A SHORT VERSION OF THE INTERVIEW	NEW
Z921	STRATUM 1-3: INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER ORDINARY DATA COLLECTION AND FOLLOW UP TO COLLECT MISSING DATA	jfr X845, jfr Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942
Z922	STRATUM 1-3: INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER FOLLOW UP WITH A SHORT VERSION OF THE INTERVIEW	NEW

PARTNER

INFORMATION ABOUT INTERVIEW

PZ1 P – TODAY’S DATE X1154

SEX, AGE, OCCUPATION

PZ2 P – SEX X1002

PZ3 P – YEAR OF BIRTH X1001

PZ4 P – SEI CURRENT OCCUPATION NEW

PZ5 P – SEI CURRENT EMPLOYMENT STATUS X1044

PZ6 P – NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION NEW

PZ7 P – NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION NEW

PZ11 P – EGP CURRENT OCCUPATION NEW

CHILDHOOD CONDITIONS

PZ12 P – BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN X1004

PZ13 P – BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER X1005

PZ14 P – BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER X1006

PZ15 P – COUNTRY OF ORIGIN X1008

PZ16 P – AGE AT IMMIGRATION X1009

SIBLINGS, PARENTS AND CHILDHOOD FAMILY

PZ17 P – INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY X1011

PZ18 P – SEI FATHER X1013

PZ19 P – NYK80 FATHER X1014

PZ20 P – NYK85 FATHER X1015

PZ25 P – SEI MOTHER X1017

PZ26 P – NYK80 MOTHER X1018

PZ27 P – NYK85 MOTHER X1019

PZ32 P – FATHER’S EDUCATION NEW

PZ33 P – MOTHER’S EDUCATION NEW

EDUCATION

PZ34 P – PARTNER’S EDUCATION IN YEARS X1023

PZ35 P – HIGHEST EDUCATION X1024

OCCUPATIONAL BIOGRAPHY

PZ36 P – NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT X1025

PZ37 P – BEGAN WORKING: YEAR NEW

PZ38 P – SEI FIRST JOB NEW

PZ39 P – NYK80 FIRST JOB NEW

PZ40 P – NYK85 FIRST JOB NEW

PZ45 P – EGP FIRST JOB X1031

PZ46	P – OCCUPATION AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1032
PZ47	P – SEI AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1033
PZ48	P – NYK80 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1034
PZ49	P – NYK85 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1035
PZ54	P – EGP AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1030
PZ61	P – IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT LAST WHEN	X1050

WORKING ENVIROMENT

PZ62	P – EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS	X1069
PZ63	P – SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	X1070
PZ64	P – SUPERVISORY TASKS	X1071
PZ65	P – NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES	X1072
PZ66	P – REGULAR WEEKLY WORK HOURS	X1053
PZ67	P – HOW OFTEN OVERTIME	X1055
PZ68	P – NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK: NUMBER OF NIGHTS/YEAR	X1068

SALARY

PZ69	P – GROSS MONTHLY SALARY	X1073
PZ70	P – NET MONTHLY SALARY	X1074

HOUSEHOLD WORK AND FAMILY

PZ71	P – HOURS P – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	X1097
PZ72	P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	X1098
PZ73	P - HOURS CHILDREN – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	X1099
PZ74	P – HOURS P – CARE OF CLOTHING	X1100
PZ75	P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CARE OF CLOTHING	X1101
PZ76	P – HOURS CHILDREN – CARE OF CLOTHING	X1102
PZ77	P – HOURS P – CLEANING	X1103
PZ78	P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CLEANING	X1104
PZ79	P – HOURS CHILDREN – CLEANING	X1105
PZ80	P – HOURS P – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X1106
PZ81	P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X1107
PZ82	P – HOURS CHILDREN – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X1108
PZ83	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK	X1116
PZ84	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY	X1117
PZ85	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS	X1120
PZ86	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS CHILD RAISING	X1119

OCCUPATIONAL SITUATION 2009

PZ87	P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 2009: NUMBER OF WEEKS	X1077
PZ88	P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 2009: HOURS/WEEK	X1078

FAMILY SITUATION

PZ89	P – PREVIOUSLY COHABITING	X1079
PZ90	P – NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS	X1080
PZ91	P – YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED	X1081

PZ92	P – CHILDREN NOT IN HOME	X1082
PZ93	P – NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1083
PZ94	P – NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1084
PZ95	P – NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1085
PZ96	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1086
PZ97	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1087
PZ98	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1088
PZ99	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1089
PZ100	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1090

ECONOMIC RESOURCES

PZ102	P – CASH MARGIN	X1122
PZ103	P – ACQUIRING CASH	X1123

HEALTH

PZ104	P – GENERAL HEALTH	X1124
PZ105	P – SMOKE	NEW
PZ106	P – DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR, ETC	X1143
PZ107	P – NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC	X1144
PZ108	P – NUMBER OF GLASSES	X1145
PZ109	P – P:S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION	X1153

OTHER REGISTER INFORMATION

PZ110	P – EDUCATIONAL LEVEL – ACCORDING TO REGISTER	
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VARIABLE PRESENTATION

VARIABLE TERMS, WORDINGS OF QUESTIONS, CONSTRUCTIONS OF VARIABLES, CODES AND SIMPLE FREQUENCIES

Z2	PANEL CODE			jfr X2
	Respondents' participation in previous editions of the Level of living survey.			
	1	Participated 2000	3038	68,8
	2	Participated 2000 (lived at home)	119	2,7
	3	Participated 1991 but not later	190	4,3
	4	Participated 1981 or earlier but not later	48	1,1
	5	Never participated	1020	23,1
		Total	4415	100
Z3	PART OF BARN-LNU 2000			NEW
	2	No	4415	100
		Total	4415	
Z4	INTERVIEWER NUMBER			X4, Y3, U3, V2
	Interviewer id. Not shown.			
Z5	DATE OF INTERVIEW- MONTH, DAY			X5, Y4, U4, jfr V3, jfr W552
	Date – month and day – when the interview was carried out. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	100426		1	
	110620		1	
		Total	4415	100
Z6	TIME AT START OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE			X6, Y5, U5, V5
	Interviewers note of time – hour and minute – when the interview started. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	0610		1	
	2319		1	
		Total	4415	100
Z7	TIME AT END OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE			X7, Y6, U6, V708
	Interviewers note of time – hour and minute – when the interview ended. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	1033		1	
	2245		1	
		Total	4406	100
	9999	No answer	9	
			4415	

Z8	TYPE OF INTERVIEW			X10, Y7, U7
	Note if the interview is carried out face-to-face or by phone.			
	1	In person	3278	74,3
	2	By phone	1137	25,7
		Total	4415	100
Z9	INDIRECT INTERVIEW			jfr X11, Y8, U8, V719
	Note if the interview is carried out with the respondent her-/himself.			
	1	Interview carried out with respondent	4383	99,3
	2	Interview with other than respondent	32	0,7
		Total	4415	100
Z10	INTERVIEW LANGUAGE			jfr X12
	Note if the interview is carried out in Swedish or carried out using interpreter.			
	1	Interview carried out in Swedish	4348	98,5
	2	Interview carried out using interpreter	67	1,5
		Total	4415	100
Z11	SEX			X8, Y10, U10, V718, W2
	The respondent's sex.			
	1	Male	2257	51,1
	2	Female	2158	48,9
		Total	4415	100
Z12	YEAR OF BIRTH			X9, Y11, U11, V815, W533
	The respondent's year of birth.			
	1935		40	0,9
	1936		44	1,0
	1937		64	1,4
	1938		70	1,6
	1939		58	1,3
	1940		47	1,1
	1941		63	1,4
	1942		90	2,0
	1943		81	1,8
	1944		79	1,8
	1945		100	2,3
	1946		107	2,4
	1947		85	1,9
	1948		83	1,9
	1949		86	1,9

1950	82	1,9
1951	80	1,8
1952	95	2,2
1953	74	1,7
1954	72	1,6
1955	74	1,7
1956	64	1,4
1957	73	1,7
1958	76	1,7
1959	72	1,6
1960	76	1,7
1961	88	2,0
1962	82	1,9
1963	90	2,0
1964	101	2,3
1965	77	1,7
1966	102	2,3
1967	72	1,6
1968	81	1,8
1969	89	2,0
1970	80	1,8
1971	91	2,1
1972	100	2,3
1973	80	1,8
1974	73	1,7
1975	94	2,1
1976	73	1,7
1977	79	1,8
1978	75	1,7
1979	76	1,7
1980	74	1,7
1981	63	1,4
1982	79	1,8
1983	59	1,3
1984	78	1,8
1985	65	1,5
1986	75	1,7
1987	70	1,6
1988	72	1,6
1989	75	1,7
1990	76	1,7
1991	91	2,1
Total	4415	100

Z13

SEI – OWN EMPLOYMENT STATUS

Occupation according to socio-economic classification (SEI) - occupational status.

**jfr X14, jfr
Y14, jfr U14,
jfr V715, jfr
W996**

1	Working	2935	66,9
2	Working in the home	31	0,7
3	Pensioner	637	14,5

	4	Studying	242	5,5
	5	Unemployed	204	4,7
	6	Sick, not working/early retirement pensioner	258	5,9
	9	Parental leave	80	1,8
		Total	4387	100
	99	No answer	28	
			4415	
Z14	OWN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GROUP			X15, Y13, jfr U13
	Own occupation according to socio-economic classification (SEI).*			
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	226	5,2
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	690	16,0
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	408	9,4
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	310	7,2
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	170	3,9
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	54	1,2
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	385	8,9
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	40	0,9
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	951	22,0
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	564	13,1
	57	Professional, upper-level executive**	129	3,0
	60	Self-employed professionals	31	0,7
	71	Self-employed without employees	169	3,9
	72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	99	2,3
	73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	10	0,2
	74	Self-employed 20+ employees	12	0,3
	79	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	26	0,6
	89	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	47	1,1
		Total	4321	100
	99	Unclassified	94	
			4415	
	* Unemployed, pensioners, students and others not gainfully employed have been coded according to their last occupation that lasted at least 6 months. Homemakers have been coded according to the husband's occupation. Unmarried students under the age of 24 have been coded according to their parent's occupation.			
Z15	NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION			X16
	Current profession or occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK").			
Z16	NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION			X17
	Current occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.			

Z17	OWN EGP		X18, Y669
	Own occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	31 0,7
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	705 16,3
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	962 22,3
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	696 16,1
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	417 9,7
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	135 3,1
	7	IVb Small proprietors without employees	169 3,9
	9	IVc Farmers	47 1,1
	10	Vs Supervisors	75 1,7
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	1 0,0
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	401 9,3
	13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary pr.	5 0,1
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	662 15,3
	15	15 VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary pr.	15 0,3
		Total	4321 100
	99	Unclassified	94
			4415
Z18	OWN SSYK		NEW
	Own occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.		
Z19	OWN ISCO88		NEW
	Own occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.		
Z20	OWN SIOPS		NEW
	Own occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.		
Z22	SAME PLACE OF RESIDENCE SINCE 2000		X19, jfr Y105, jfr U37, jfr V30
	Did you move to your current place of residence before or after 2001?		
	1	2000 or later	1591 36,1
	2	Before 2000	2817 63,9
		Total	4408 100
	9	No answer	7
Z23	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT PLACE OF RESIDENCE		X20, jfr Y108, jfr U40, jfr V32, jfr W15
	What year did you move to your current place of residence? Only year is shown.		
	1935		4 0,1
	1936		8 0,2
	1937		10 0,2

1938	6	0,1
1939	5	0,1
1940	8	0,2
1941	3	0,1
1942	12	0,3
1943	15	0,3
1944	17	0,4
1945	13	0,3
1946	20	0,5
1947	15	0,3
1948	15	0,3
1949	13	0,3
1950	21	0,5
1951	20	0,5
1952	21	0,5
1953	15	0,3
1954	18	0,4
1955	10	0,2
1956	17	0,4
1957	17	0,4
1958	26	0,6
1959	25	0,6
1960	24	0,5
1961	31	0,7
1962	34	0,8
1963	36	0,8
1964	47	1,1
1965	37	0,8
1966	32	0,7
1967	44	1,0
1968	45	1,0
1969	56	1,3
1970	63	1,4
1971	52	1,2
1972	53	1,2
1973	67	1,5
1974	66	1,5
1975	78	1,8
1976	59	1,3
1977	66	1,5
1978	41	0,9
1979	66	1,5
1980	70	1,6
1981	47	1,1
1982	62	1,4
1983	46	1,0
1984	76	1,7
1985	63	1,4
1986	72	1,6
1987	53	1,2
1988	85	1,9

1989		88	2,0
1990		100	2,3
1991		106	2,4
1992		64	1,5
1993		52	1,2
1994		73	1,7
1995		66	1,5
1996		81	1,8
1997		69	1,6
1998		95	2,2
1999		98	2,2
2000		107	2,4
2001		96	2,2
2002		87	2,0
2003		100	2,3
2004		132	3,0
2005		139	3,2
2006		148	3,4
2007		181	4,1
2008		203	4,6
2009		180	4,1
2010		207	4,7
2011		11	0,2
	Total	4408	100
9999	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z24

REASON FOR LATEST MOVE

**X21, jfr Y107,
jfr U39, jfr
V33**

What was the main reason for your moving to your current place of residence?

The table is valid for Z22 NE 2.

1	Better residence (built a house, gained more room, etc.)	348	21,8
2	Moved closer to family/friends	190	11,9
3	Better area to live in	196	12,3
4	Respondent got new job/better job opportunities	208	13,0
5	Own studies	146	9,1
6	Change of family situation	334	20,9
7	Spouse/partner changed jobs	55	3,4
8	Moved with parents	26	1,6
9	Other	94	5,9
	Total	1597	100
99	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	2817	
		4415	

Z25

YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT DWELLING

**X22, jfr Y111,
jfr U42, jfr
V35, jfr W96**

When did you move to your current dwelling? Only year is shown.

1935		1	0,0
1936		1	0,0

1937	1	0,0
1939	1	0,0
1942	1	0,0
1944	2	0,0
1945	1	0,0
1946	1	0,0
1947	1	0,0
1948	1	0,0
1950	1	0,0
1951	1	0,0
1952	3	0,1
1953	1	0,0
1955	1	0,0
1957	1	0,0
1958	3	0,1
1959	2	0,0
1960	1	0,0
1961	1	0,0
1962	2	0,0
1963	4	0,1
1964	7	0,2
1965	5	0,1
1966	9	0,2
1967	10	0,2
1968	7	0,2
1969	19	0,4
1970	23	0,5
1971	23	0,5
1972	28	0,6
1973	33	0,7
1974	43	1,0
1975	44	1,0
1976	38	0,9
1977	32	0,7
1978	35	0,8
1979	31	0,7
1980	56	1,3
1981	41	0,9
1982	56	1,3
1983	44	1,0
1984	50	1,1
1985	49	1,1
1986	47	1,1
1987	42	1,0
1988	52	1,2
1989	62	1,4
1990	85	1,9
1991	88	2,0
1992	60	1,4
1993	57	1,3
1994	62	1,4

1995		77	1,7
1996		94	2,1
1997		89	2,0
1998		104	2,4
1999		118	2,7
2000		123	2,8
2001		118	2,7
2002		114	2,6
2003		129	2,9
2004		170	3,9
2005		216	4,9
2006		226	5,1
2007		295	6,7
2008		402	9,1
2009		376	8,5
2010		457	10,4
2011		28	0,6
	Total	4406	100,0
979797	No accommodation	3	
999999	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z26

NUMBER OF ROOMS, EXCLUDING THE KITCHEN

**X24, Y113,
U45, V38, W71**

How many rooms do you have excluding the kitchen?

The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.

1		285	6,5
2		638	14,5
3		872	19,8
4		899	20,4
5		781	17,7
6		525	11,9
7		232	5,3
8		105	2,4
9		36	0,8
10		17	0,4
11		8	0,2
12		6	0,1
13		2	0,0
14		1	0,0
15		2	0,0
	Total	4409	100
999	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	3	
		4415	

Z27**LIVING SPACE m²****X25, Y114**How large is your residence in square meters (m²)? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.

20-29		69	1,6
30-39		101	2,4
40-49		139	3,3
50-59		226	5,3
60-69		355	8,4
70-79		359	8,5
80-89		371	8,8
90-99		276	6,5
100-109		278	6,6
110-119		275	6,5
120-129		342	8,1
130-139		228	5,4
140-149		228	5,4
150-159		203	4,8
160-169		183	4,3
170-179		126	3,0
180-189		111	2,6
190-199		40	0,9
200-299		284	6,7
300-399		38	0,9
400-499		3	0,1
500-599		1	0,0
600>		1	0,0
	Total	4237	100
9999	No answer	175	
	Not applicable	3	
	Mean value	109,1	
	Standard deviation	51,7	

Z28**NUMBER OF APARTMENTS IN THE HOUSE****X26, Y115,
U44, V37, W70**

How many apartments are there in the house where you live, all entrances counted?

The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.

1	1 apartment (detached house, row house)	2596	59,0
2	2 apartments	87	2,0
3	3-10 apartments	394	9,0
4	11 or more apartments	1324	30,1
	Total	4401	100
9	No answer	11	
	Not applicable	3	
		4415	

Z29	<p>BOOKS IN THE HOME</p> <p>Are there at least two running meters of books in your home, not counting works of reference? If yes: are there at least five running meters of books in your home, not counting works of reference?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>At least five running meters</td> <td>2455</td> <td>55,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>Two to five running meters</td> <td>1141</td> <td>25,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>Not two running meters</td> <td>813</td> <td>18,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4409</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	11	At least five running meters	2455	55,7	12	Two to five running meters	1141	25,9	20	Not two running meters	813	18,4		Total	4409	100	99	No answer	3			Not applicable	3				4415		X28, Y117, U65, V55, W88
11	At least five running meters	2455	55,7																											
12	Two to five running meters	1141	25,9																											
20	Not two running meters	813	18,4																											
	Total	4409	100																											
99	No answer	3																												
	Not applicable	3																												
		4415																												
Z30	<p>DAILY NEWSPAPER IN THE HOME</p> <p>Do you have access to a daily newspaper in your home?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>2958</td> <td>67,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>1453</td> <td>32,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4411</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>1</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2958	67,1	2	No	1453	32,9		Total	4411	100	9	No answer	1			Not applicable	3				4415		X30				
1	Yes	2958	67,1																											
2	No	1453	32,9																											
	Total	4411	100																											
9	No answer	1																												
	Not applicable	3																												
		4415																												
Z31	<p>PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE</p> <p>(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... traffic noise?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>530</td> <td>12,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>3882</td> <td>88,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4412</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	530	12,0	2	No	3882	88,0		Total	4412	100		Not applicable	3				4415		X33								
1	Yes	530	12,0																											
2	No	3882	88,0																											
	Total	4412	100																											
	Not applicable	3																												
		4415																												
Z32	<p>PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR MAINTENANCE</p> <p>(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... poor house/building maintenance?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>401</td> <td>9,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>4007</td> <td>90,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4408</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	401	9,1	2	No	4007	90,9		Total	4408	100	9	No answer	4			Not applicable	3				4415		X34				
1	Yes	401	9,1																											
2	No	4007	90,9																											
	Total	4408	100																											
9	No answer	4																												
	Not applicable	3																												
		4415																												

Z33	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE, NEIGHBOURS	X35
(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... noisy neighbours?		
The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.		
1	Yes	399 9,0
2	No	4012 91,0
	Total	4411 100
9	No answer	1
	Not applicable	3
		4415
Z34	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: VANDALISM OR CRIME	X36
(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... vandalism or crime?		
The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.		
1	Yes	379 8,6
2	No	4027 91,4
	Total	4406 100
9	No answer	6
	Not applicable	3
		4415
Z35	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: SCARCITY OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT	X37
(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... scarcity of public transport?		
The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.		
1	Yes	902 20,6
2	No	3471 79,4
	Total	4373 100
9	No answer	39
	Not applicable	3
		4415
Z36	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: AFRAID AT NIGHT	X40
(Do you have any of following problems where you live...) ... you are afraid of going out at night?		
The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.		
1	Yes	343 9,8
2	No	3975 90,2
	Total	4409 100
9	No answer	3
	Not applicable	3
		4415

Z37**HOME OWNER/RENTER****X45, Y121,
U71, V60, W94**

Who owns/rents the place you live in?

The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.

1	You yourself or your spouse	4039	91,5
2	Parents (own)	256	5,8
3	Own child/children	10	0,2
4	Parents-/ daughter-/ son-in-law	10	0,2
5	Sister/brother	9	0,2
6	Other close friend/relative	16	0,4
7	Other with whom respondent is lodging	24	0,5
8	Other	47	1,1
	Total	4411	100
9	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	3	
		4415	

Z38**COST OF DWELLING – NOT OWNER/RENTER****X46, Y122,
U72, V61**

Do you pay anything for where you live, and if so how much (cost per month (kronor))? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z37 NE 1.

0		182	50,0
500-999		6	1,6
1000-1999		20	5,5
1500-1999		23	6,3
2000-2499		31	8,5
2500-2999		24	6,6
3000-3499		22	6,0
3500-3999		18	4,9
4000-4499		13	3,6
4500-4599		6	1,6
>5000		19	5,2
	Total	364	100
888888	Doesn't know	3	
999999	No answer	5	
	Not applicable	4043	
		4415	

Z39**TYPE OF POSSESSION****X47, Y123, jfr
U73, jfr V62,
jfr W95**

Do you own the house/apartment or is it your own condominium apartment or are you renting?

The table is valid for Z37 EQ 1.

1	Own house	2164	53,6
2	Own condominium	703	17,4
3	Rent dwelling	1171	29,0
	Total	4038	100

	9	No answer		1	
		Not applicable		376	
				4415	
Z40	DIRECT LEASE			NEW	
	Do you rent directly or sublease?				
	The table is valid for Z39 EQ 3.				
	1	Direct lease		1135	97,0
	2	Sublease		35	3,0
		Total		1170	100
	9	No answer		1	
		Not applicable		3244	
				4415	
Z41	COST OF DWELLING – RENT			X49, Y125, U75, jfr V63, jfr W98	
	How much is your rent or charge per month? Add extra cost for fuel or heating if this applies, but do not deduct housing allowance (if any). This variable is divided into categories.				
	The table is valid for Z39 NE 1.				
	<2000			47	2,4
	2000-2999			202	10,9
	3000-3999			396	21,3
	4000-4999			391	21,0
	5000-5999			363	19,5
	6000-6999			249	13,4
	7000-7999			106	5,7
	8000-8999			48	2,6
	9000-9999			30	1,6
	10000-10999			16	0,9
	11000-11999			5	0,3
	12000>			8	0,5
		Total		1861	100
	999999	No answer		14	
		Not applicable		2540	
				4415	
		Mean value		4420,9	
		Standard deviation		1880,2	
Z42	DENSITY STANDARD			X50, Y130, U68, V745, W626	
	Index of dwelling space based on the questions about number of rooms in the home and number of persons in the household (Z26, Z151).				
	The table is valid for Z25 NE 9797.				
	1	Very high		509	11,5
	2	High		1460	33,1

3	Good	111	27,5
4	Acceptable	569	12,9
5	Bad	520	11,8
6	Overcrowded	130	2,9
7	Extremely overcrowded	10	0,2
	Total	4409	100
9	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	3	
		4415	

Z43 **NUMBER OF STAYS ABROAD** **NEW**

Number of times the respondent lived in other country than Sweden for at least 6 months (since respondent first came to Sweden if s/he was born in another country).

0		3440	77,9
1		701	15,9
2		186	4,2
3		58	1,3
4		17	0,4
5		5	0,1
6		2	0,0
7		2	0,0
8		1	0,0
9		1	0,0
10		1	0,0
15		1	0,0
	Total	4415	100
	Mean value (for values 1-15)	1,4	
	Standard deviation (for values 1-15)	1,0	

Z44 **TIME STAYING ABROAD** **NEW**

Total number of months the respondent has been staying abroad. Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z43 GT 0.

0		6	0,7
1-9		150	17,2
10-19		173	19,8
20-29		73	8,4
30-39		41	4,7
40-49		47	5,4
50-59		27	3,1
60-69		25	2,9
70-79		14	1,6
80-89		15	1,7
90-99		3	0,3
100-199		74	8,5
200-299		92	10,6
300-399		86	9,9

400-499		36	4,1
>500		10	1,1
	Total	872	100
997	Stays abroad now	1	
999	No answer	102	
	Not applicable	3440	
		4415	

Z45 YEAR/MONTH FIRST STAY ABROAD STARTED * NEW

Country the respondent lived in when s/he stayed abroad for the first time.

Only lowest and highest year and month are shown.

The table is valid for Z43 GT 0.

193503

201007

	Total	973
999999	No answer	2
	Not applicable	3440
		4415

*For information about additional stays abroad, see z45_a-z45_n (stays abroad 2-15)

Z46 COUNTRY OF FIRST STAY ABROAD NEW

Country the respondent lived in when s/he stayed abroad for the first time.

The table is valid for Z43 GT 0.

AFGHANISTAN	6	0,6
ARGENTINA	2	0,2
AUSTRALIA	22	2,3
BANGLADESH	3	0,3
BELGIUM	10	1,0
BOLIVIA	2	0,2
BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA	20	2,0
BRASILIA	7	0,7
BULGARIA	2	0,2
CHILE	14	1,4
COLOMBIA	2	0,2
COSTA RICA	2	0,2
CYPRUS	11	1,1
DENMARK	24	2,5
EGYPT	4	0,4
EL SALVADOR	1	0,1
IVORY COAST	1	0,1
ENGLAND	71	7,3
ERITREA	6	0,6
ESTONIA	3	0,3
ETHIOPIA	2	0,2

PHILIPPINES	2	0,2
FINLAND	90	9,2
FRANCE	38	3,9
UNITED ARAB EMIRATES	1	0,1
GAMBIA	2	0,2
GREECE	9	0,9
HOLLAND	6	0,6
INDIA	8	0,8
INDONESIA	1	0,1
IRAQ	16	1,6
IRAN	24	2,5
IRELAND	3	0,3
ICELAND	2	0,2
ISRAEL	6	0,6
ITALY	9	0,9
JAPAN	5	0,5
JORDAN	1	0,1
YUGOSLAVIA	2	0,2
CANADA	6	0,6
KENYA	3	0,3
CHINA	6	0,6
KONGO	3	0,3
KOREA, SOUTH-	5	0,5
KOSOVO	6	0,6
CROATIA	2	0,2
CUBA	3	0,3
KURDISTAN	1	0,1
KUWAIT	2	0,2
LATVIA	2	0,2
LEBANON	13	1,3
LIBERIA	3	0,3
LIBYA	2	0,2
LUXEMBOURG	1	0,1
MADAGASCAR	1	0,1
MACEDONIA	4	0,4
MALAYSIA	3	0,3
MOROCCO	1	0,1
MAURITIUS	1	0,1
MEXICO	1	0,1
MONACO	1	0,1
MONTENEGRO	2	0,2
NAMIBIA	1	0,1
NETHERLANDS	2	0,2
NEPAL	2	0,2
NIGERIA	2	0,2
NORWAY	61	6,3
NEW ZEALAND	2	0,2
PAKISTAN	5	0,5
PERU	3	0,3
POLAND	22	2,3
PORTUGAL	1	0,1

ROMANIA	1	0,1
RWANDA	1	0,1
RUSSIA	5	0,5
SAUDI ARABIA	8	0,8
SWITZERLAND	18	1,8
SERBIA	6	0,6
SINGAPORE	2	0,2
SOMALIA	2	0,2
SPAIN	28	2,9
SRI LANKA	2	0,2
GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND	20	2,0
SUDAN	5	0,5
SOUTH AFRICA	2	0,2
SYRIA	8	0,8
TANZANIA	4	0,4
TCHAD	1	0,1
THAILAND	7	0,7
CZECH REPUBLIC	3	0,3
TUNISIA	1	0,1
TURKEY	23	2,4
GERMANY	44	4,5
UGANDA	2	0,2
HUNGARY	4	0,4
URUGUAY	2	0,2
USA	141	14,5
VENEZUELA	1	0,1
VIETNAM	3	0,3
ZAMBIA	2	0,2
ZIMBABWE	4	0,4
AUSTRIA	10	1,0
Total	973	100
No answer	2	
Not applicable	3440	
	4415	

*For information about additional stays abroad, see z45_a-z45_n (stays abroad 2-15)

Z47

YEAR/MONTH END OF FIRST STAY ABROAD

NEW

Year and month when the respondent ended his/her first stay abroad. Only lowest and highest year and month are shown.

The table is valid for Z43 GT 0.

194202

201103

Total	970
999999 No answer	5
Not applicable	3440
	4415

*For information about additional stays abroad, see z45_a-z45_n (stays abroad 2-15)

Z48 BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN X51

Were both of your parents born in Sweden?

1	Yes	1150	64,9
2	No	621	35,1
	Total	1771	100
9	No answer	2	
	Question not asked	2642	
		4415	

Z49 SWEDISH PARENTS X52, jfr Y15, jfr U15, jfr V6, jfr W4

Were both of your parents Swedish citizens at the time of your birth? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Yes	2439	74,9
2	No	99	3,0
3	Both foreign	718	22,1
	Total	3256	100
9	No answer	9	
	Question not asked	1150	
		4415	

Z50 BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER X53, jfr Y16, jfr U16, jfr V7, jfr W4

What is the birth country of your father? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Swedish	3566	80,8
2	Danish, norwegian	73	1,7
3	Finnish	135	3,1
4	Former Yugoslavia	70	1,6
5	Rest of Eastern Europe	91	2,1
6	Germany, Austria, rest Western Europe	74	1,7
7	Spain, Italy, Greece	16	0,4
8	Other nationalities	387	8,8
	Total	4412	100
9	Unknown	3	
		4415	

Z51 BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER X54, jfr Y17, jfr U17, jfr V8, jfr W5

What is the birth country of your mother? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Swedish	3,572	81,0
2	Danish, norwegian	75	1,7
3	Finnish	169	3,8
4	Former Yugoslavia	68	1,5

5	Rest of Eastern Europe	90	2,0
6	Germany, Austria, rest of Western Europe	56	1,3
7	Spain, Italy, Greece	8	0,2
8	Other nationalities	374	8,5
	Total	4412	100
9	Unknown	3	
		4415	

Z52

HOME LANGUAGE

**X55, jfr Y18,
jfr U18, jfr V9,
jfr W6**

During your childhood and adolescence, i.e., up to your 16th birthday, what language was spoken most in your home? Two or more number indicate a multilingual home (e.g. code 13 stands for "1 Swedish" and "3 Finnish"). Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

The table is valid for Z48 NE 1

1	Swedish	263	27,9
2	Danish, norwegian	46	4,9
3	Finnish	81	8,6
4	Serbo-croatian, serbian, croatian, jugoslav	37	3,9
5	Rest of Eastern European languages, including hungarian	83	8,8
6	German	27	2,9
7	English	16	1,7
8	French, spanish, italian	39	4,1
9	Other languages	296	31,4
12		1	0,1
13		1	0,5
15		5	0,3
16		3	0,1
17		1	0,1
19		1	0,5
21		5	0,1
31		1	0,1
51		1	0,1
55		1	0,1
56		1	0,1
59		1	0,1
72		1	0,1
78		1	0,2
81		2	0,1
89		1	0,1
91		1	0,4
97		4	0,1
98		1	0,5
99		5	1,7
179		16	0,1
751		1	0,1
	Total	943	100,0
999	No answer	2	
	Question not asked	3470	

Z53	AGE AT IMMIGRATION		X56, jfr Y19, jfr U19, jfr V10, jfr W7
	Were you born in Sweden or in another country? If another country: How old were you when you came to Sweden? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
	10 In Sweden	165	20,0
	21 In another country < 7 years	80	9,7
	22 In another country, 7-16 years	93	11,3
	23 In another country, >16 years	486	59,0
	Total	824	100
	97 Less than 1 year	2	
	Question not asked	3,589	
		4,415	
Z54	COUNTRY OF ORIGIN		X57
	In which country were you born? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
	1 Sweden	1338	75,5
	2 Denmark, Norway	23	1,3
	3 Finland	20	1,1
	4 Yugoslavia	54	3,0
	5 Eastern Europe, incl. East Germany	49	2,8
	6 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	31	1,7
	7 Spain, Italy, Greece	4	0,2
	8 Other	253	14,3
	9 Unknown	1	0,1
	Total	1773	100
	Question not asked	2642	
		4415	
Z55	FÖRMÅGA ATT LÄSA SVENSKA		NEW
	Think of the content in a Swedish newspaper, do you understand ...		
	The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5 and Z53 EQ 22 OR 23.		
	1 Practically everything	90	34,5
	2 Most but not everying	122	46,7
	3 A few words and sentences, e.g. headlines	34	13,0
	4 Almost nothing	15	5,7
	Total	261	100,0
	Question not asked	4154	94,1
		4415	100

Z56 ABILITY TO SPEAK SWEDISH X58

How would you evaluate your ability to speak Swedish? Do you think your Swedish is quite good, fairly good, fairly bad or quite bad? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5 och Z53 EQ 22 OR 23.

1	Quite good	105	32,3
2	Fairly good	185	56,9
3	Fairly bad	26	8,0
4	Quite bad	9	2,8
	Total	325	100
9	No answer	2	
	Question not asked	4088	
		4415	

Z57 RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – FATHER jfr X59

What is/was the religious affiliation of your father? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Christianity	1225	71,2
2	Islam	205	11,9
3	Judaism	3	0,2
4	Hinduism	5	0,3
5	Buddhism	24	1,4
6	Other	9	0,5
7	No religious affiliation	249	14,5
	Total	1720	100
98	Doesn't know	51	
99	Doesn't want to report	2	
	Question not asked	2642	
		4415	

Z58 RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – MOTHER jfr X60

What is/was the religious affiliation of your mother? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Christianity	1290	74,4
2	Islam	198	11,4
3	Judaism	1	0,1
4	Hinduism	4	0,2
5	Buddhism	24	1,4
6	Other	10	0,6
7	No religious affiliation	206	11,9
	Total	1733	100
98	Doesn't know	20	
99	Doesn't want to report	1	
	Question not asked	2661	
		4415	

Z59**NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL****X61, jfr Y34,
jfr U28, jfr
V22, jfr W30**

Do you have or have you had siblings? If yes: How many?

0	290	6,6
1	1487	33,7
2	1156	26,2
3	662	15,0
4	362	8,2
5	178	4,0
6	110	2,5
7	69	1,6
8	36	0,8
9	28	0,6
10	15	0,3
11	7	0,2
12	6	0,1
13	2	0,0
14	2	0,0
16	1	0,0
23	1	0,0
27	1	0,0
Total	4413	100
88	Doesn't know	2
		4415

Z60**NUMBER OF SIBLINGS ALIVE****X62**

If you have siblings, how many of them are alive?

The table is valid for Z59 GT 0.

0	129	3,1
1	1515	36,7
2	1139	27,6
3	644	15,6
4	320	7,8
5	163	4,0
6	90	2,2
7	52	1,3
8	34	0,8
9	17	0,4
10	10	0,2
11	4	0,1
12	2	0,0
13	1	0,0
14	1	0,0
21	1	0,0
27	1	0,0
Total	4123	100
	Not applicable	292
		4415

Z61	NUMBER OF BROTHERS, TOTAL			X63
	If you have siblings, how many of them are your brothers?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 0.			
	0	1104	26,8	
	1	1720	41,7	
	2	780	18,9	
	3	305	7,4	
	4	141	3,4	
	5	33	0,8	
	6	25	0,6	
	7	9	0,2	
	8	3	0,1	
	9	1	0,0	
	12	1	0,0	
	13	1	0,0	
	Total	4123	100	
	Not applicable	292		
		4415		

Z62	NUMBER OF BROTHERS ALIVE			X64
	If you have brothers, how many of them are alive?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 0.			
	0	1299	31,5	
	1	1663	40,3	
	2	730	17,7	
	3	278	6,7	
	4	104	2,5	
	5	26	0,6	
	6	15	0,4	
	7	4	0,1	
	8	1	0,0	
	9	1	0,0	
	12	2	0,0	
	Total	4123	100	
	Not applicable	292		
		4415		

Z63	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 1			jfr X65
	What is the year of birth of sibling 1? Here this variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 0.			
	<1929	97	2,4	
	1930-1939	343	8,5	

9999	No answer	18
	Not applicable	2935
		4415

Z66 **YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 4** **jfr X68**

What is the year of birth of sibling 4? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z59 GT 3.

<1929		15	2,0
1930-1939		44	5,8
1940-1949		117	15,5
1950-1959		142	18,8
1960-1969		156	20,6
1970-1979		91	12,0
1980-1989		107	14,2
1990-1999		65	8,6
2000-2011		19	2,5
	Total	756	100,0
8888	Doesn't know	45	
9999	No answer	17	
	Not applicable	3597	
		4415	

Z67 **YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 5** **jfr X69**

What is the year of birth of sibling 5? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z59 GT 4.

<1929		5	1,2
1930-1939		34	8,3
1940-1949		63	15,3
1950-1959		79	19,2
1960-1969		85	20,6
1970-1979		53	12,9
1980-1989		43	10,4
1990-1999		41	10,0
2000-2011		9	2,2
	Total	412	100,0
8888	Doesn't know	28	0,6
9999	No answer	16	0,4
	Not applicable	3959	89,7
		4415	100,0

Z68**YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 6****jfr X70**

What is the year of birth of sibling 6? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z59 GT 5.

<1929		3	1,2
1930-1939		16	6,5
1940-1949		35	14,2
1950-1959		51	20,7
1960-1969		53	21,5
1970-1979		38	15,4
1980-1989		30	12,2
1990-1999		18	7,3
2000-2011		2	0,8
	Total	246	100,0
8888	Doesn't know	21	
9999	No answer	11	
	Not applicable	4137	
		4415	

Z69**YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 7****jfr X71**

What is the year of birth of sibling 7? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z59 GT 6.

<1929		2	1,4
1930-1939		12	8,2
1940-1949		21	14,4
1950-1959		22	15,1
1960-1969		32	21,9
1970-1979		28	19,2
1980-1989		20	13,7
1990-1999		7	4,8
2000-2011		2	1,4
	Total	146	100,0
8888	Doesn't know	15	
9999	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	4247	
		4415	

Z70**YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 8****jfr X72**

What is the year of birth of sibling 8? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z59 GT 7.

1930-1939		8	9,8
1940-1949		15	18,3
1950-1959		7	8,5
1960-1969		18	22,0

<p>Z76</p> <p>YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 14</p> <p>What is the year of birth of sibling 14? Here this variable is divided into categories.</p> <p>The table is valid for Z59 GT 13.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">jfr X78</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>8888</td> <td>Doesn't know</td> <td style="text-align: right;">4</td> <td style="text-align: right;">80,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9999</td> <td>No answer</td> <td style="text-align: right;">1</td> <td style="text-align: right;">20,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td style="text-align: right;">5</td> <td style="text-align: right;">100</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td style="text-align: right;">4410</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: right;">4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	8888	Doesn't know	4	80,0	9999	No answer	1	20,0		Total	5	100		Not applicable	4410				4415					
8888	Doesn't know	4	80,0																						
9999	No answer	1	20,0																						
	Total	5	100																						
	Not applicable	4410																							
		4415																							
<p>Z77</p> <p>SEX SIBLING 1</p> <p>Is sibling 1 a brother or a sister?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z59 GT 0.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">X79</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Brother</td> <td style="text-align: right;">2104</td> <td style="text-align: right;">51,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Sister</td> <td style="text-align: right;">2011</td> <td style="text-align: right;">48,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td style="text-align: right;">4115</td> <td style="text-align: right;">100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td style="text-align: right;">8</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td style="text-align: right;">292</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: right;">4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Brother	2104	51,1	2	Sister	2011	48,9		Total	4115	100	9	No answer	8			Not applicable	292				4415	
1	Brother	2104	51,1																						
2	Sister	2011	48,9																						
	Total	4115	100																						
9	No answer	8																							
	Not applicable	292																							
		4415																							
<p>Z78</p> <p>SEX SIBLING 2</p> <p>Is sibling 2 a brother or a sister?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z59 GT 1.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">X80</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Brother</td> <td style="text-align: right;">1339</td> <td style="text-align: right;">51,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Sister</td> <td style="text-align: right;">1288</td> <td style="text-align: right;">49,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td style="text-align: right;">2627</td> <td style="text-align: right;">100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td style="text-align: right;">9</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td style="text-align: right;">1779</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: right;">4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Brother	1339	51,0	2	Sister	1288	49,0		Total	2627	100	9	No answer	9			Not applicable	1779				4415	
1	Brother	1339	51,0																						
2	Sister	1288	49,0																						
	Total	2627	100																						
9	No answer	9																							
	Not applicable	1779																							
		4415																							
<p>Z79</p> <p>SEX SIBLING 3</p> <p>Is sibling 3 a brother or a sister?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z59 GT 2.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">X81</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Brother</td> <td style="text-align: right;">750</td> <td style="text-align: right;">50,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Sister</td> <td style="text-align: right;">724</td> <td style="text-align: right;">49,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td style="text-align: right;">1474</td> <td style="text-align: right;">100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td style="text-align: right;">6</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td style="text-align: right;">2935</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: right;">4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Brother	750	50,9	2	Sister	724	49,1		Total	1474	100	9	No answer	6			Not applicable	2935				4415	
1	Brother	750	50,9																						
2	Sister	724	49,1																						
	Total	1474	100																						
9	No answer	6																							
	Not applicable	2935																							
		4415																							

Z80	SEX SIBLING 4			X82
	Is sibling 4 a brother or a sister?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 3.			
	1	Brother	412	50,7
	2	Sister	400	49,3
		Total	812	100
	9	No answer	6	
		Not applicable	3597	
			4415	
Z81	SEX SIBLING 5			X83
	Is sibling 5 a brother or a sister?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 4.			
	1	Brother	219	48,3
	2	Sister	234	51,7
		Total	453	100
	9	No answer	3	
		Not applicable	3959	
			4415	
Z82	SEX SIBLING 6			X84
	Is sibling 6 a brother or a sister?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 5.			
	1	Brother	219	48,3
	2	Sister	234	51,7
		Total	453	100
	9	No answer	3	
		Not applicable	3959	
			4415	
Z83	SEX SIBLING 7			X85
	Is sibling 7 a brother or a sister?			
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 6.			
	1	Brother	132	48,0
	2	Sister	143	52,0
		Total	275	100
	9	No answer	3	
		Not applicable	4137	
			4415	

Z84	SEX SIBLING 8		X86
	Is sibling 8 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 7.		
	1 Brother	80	48,5
	2 Sister	85	51,5
	Total	165	100
	9 No answer	3	
	Not applicable	4247	
		4415	
Z85	SEX SIBLING 9		X87
	Is sibling 9 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 8.		
	1 Brother	52	53,1
	2 Sister	46	46,9
	Total	98	100
	9 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4316	
		4415	
Z86	SEX SIBLING 10		X88
	Is sibling 10 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 9.		
	1 Brother	28	45,2
	2 Sister	34	54,8
	Total	62	100
	9 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4352	
		4415	
Z87	SEX SIBLING 11		X89
	Is sibling 11 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 10.		
	1 Brother	19	55,9
	2 Sister	15	44,1
	Total	34	100
	9 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4380	
		4415	

Z88	SEX SIBLING 12		X90
	Is sibling 12 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 11.		
	1 Brother	9	50,0
	2 Sister	9	50,0
	Total	18	100
	9 No answer	2	
	Not applicable	4395	
		4415	
Z89	SEX SIBLING 13		X91
	Is sibling 13 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 12.		
	1 Brother	7	58,3
	2 Sister	5	41,7
	Total	12	100
	9 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4402	
		4415	
Z90	SEX SIBLING 14		X92
	Is sibling 14 a brother or a sister?		
	The table is valid for Z59 GT 13.		
	1 Brother	2	50,0
	2 Sister	2	50,0
	Total	4	100
	9 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4410	
		4415	
Z91	AGE-POSITION AMONG SIBLINGS		jfr X93
	Respondent's age-position among the siblings. Decimals regard siblings born the same year. Siblings with missing data for birthyear is not included in the calculation of age-position among the siblings.		
	The table is valid for Z59 NE 88.		
	1	1814	41,1
	1.5	33	0,7
	2	1404	31,8
	2.5	28	0,6
	3	610	13,8
	3.5	14	0,3

4	242	5,5
4.5	8	0,2
5	131	3,0
5.5	5	0,1
6	53	1,2
6.5	2	0,0
7	35	0,8
8	13	0,3
8.5	1	0,0
9	7	0,2
9.5	3	0,1
10	6	0,1
11	2	0,0
12	2	0,0
Total	4413	100
Not applicable	2	
	4415	

Z92

INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY

**jfr X94, jfr
Y20, jfr U20,
jfr V11, jfr
W20**

Did you live with both your biological parents during your whole childhood, i.e. up to age 16? If no: Why not?
Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

10	Yes	3548	80,5
21	Divorce, judicial separation, separation	573	13,0
22	Parents never lived together	39	0,9
23	Both parents deceased	6	0,1
24	Father deceased	82	1,9
25	Mother deceased	41	0,9
26	Lived with foster parents	11	0,2
27	Lived with adoptive parents	12	0,3
28	Did not grow up with both, no reason	53	1,2
29	Born outside marriage	40	0,9
30	Father away travelling	1	0,0
	Total	4406	100
99	No answer	9	
		4415	

Z93

RELATIONS WITH PARENT LIVING ELSEWHERE

X95

During the period when your parents did not live together, how often did you see the parent with whom you did not mainly live? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

The table is valid for Z92 EQ 21 OR 22.

1	Several times a week	99	14,5
2	About once a week	85	12,5
3	1-3 times a month	185	27,2
4	Less often	191	28,0
5	Never	121	17,8
	Total	681	100

9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	3725	
		4415	

Z94	AGE WHEN PARENTS' COHABITATION ENDED		NEW
	The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5 AND Z92 EQ 21.		
	0	9	3,9
	1	15	6,6
	2	15	6,6
	3	16	7,0
	4	8	3,5
	5	19	8,3
	6	22	9,6
	7	18	7,9
	8	15	6,6
	9	18	7,9
	10	12	5,2
	11	17	7,4
	12	13	5,7
	13	12	5,2
	14	7	3,1
	15	13	5,7
	Total	229	100
88	Doesn't know	5	
	Not applicable	4181	
		4415	

Z95	LIVED WITH STEPPARENTS		NEW
	Did you live together with a stepparent at any occasion during your childhood/adolescence?		
	The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5 AND Z92 NE 10.		
	1 Yes	195	58,7
	2 No	137	41,3
	Total	332	100
8	Doesn't know	1	
	Not applicable	4082	
		4415	

Z96	LIVED WITH STEPSIBLINGS		jfr X114
	Did you live together with step-siblings at any occasion during your childhood/adolescence? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
	The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5 AND Z92 NE 10.		
	1 Yes	327	17,8
	2 No	1511	82,2
	Total	1838	100
8	Doesn't know	18	

1989		89	2,0
1990		95	2,2
1991		81	1,8
1992		85	1,9
1993		68	1,5
1994		86	2,0
1995		70	1,6
1996		66	1,5
1997		68	1,5
1998		90	2,0
1999		76	1,7
2000		62	1,4
2001		49	1,1
2002		57	1,3
2003		65	1,5
2004		52	1,2
2005		67	1,5
2006		54	1,2
2007		70	1,6
2008		52	1,2
2009		53	1,2
2010		49	1,1
2011		2	0,0
	Total	4399	100
999999	No answer	16	
		4415	

Z98

CONFLICT IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY

**X116, Y42,
U26, V20, W29**

Was there any serious friction in your family while you were growing up? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Yes	488	11,1
2	Unsure	229	5,2
3	No	3669	83,7
	Total	4386	100
9	No answer	29	
		4415	

Z99

CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENTS

X117

Was there any serious friction between your biological parents? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.

1	Yes	264	72,1
2	No	102	27,9
	Total	366	100
9	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	4042	
		4415	

Z100	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENT AND STEPPARENT		X118	
	Was there any serious friction between a biological parent and a stepparent? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.			
	The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.			
	1	Yes	43	11,8
	2	No	320	88,2
		Total	363	100
	9	No answer	10	
		Not applicable	4042	
			4415	
Z101	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL MOTHER		X119	
	Was there any serious friction between you and your biological mother? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.			
	The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.			
	1	Yes	51	13,9
	2	No	315	86,1
		Total	366	100
	9	No answer	7	
		Not applicable	4042	
			4415	
Z102	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL FATHER		X120	
	Was there any serious friction between you and your biological father? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.			
	The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.			
	1	Yes	55	15,2
	2	No	307	84,8
		Total	362	100
	9	No answer	11	
		Not applicable	4042	
			4415	
Z103	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND STEPMOTHER OR STEPFATHER		X121	
	Was there any serious friction between you and your stepmother or stepfather? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.			
	The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.			
	1	Yes	30	8,3
	2	No	333	91,7
		Total	363	100

	9	No answer	10	
		Not applicable	4042	
			4415	
Z104		CONFLICT BETWEEN OTHERS		X122
		Was there any serious friction between others? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
		The table is valid for Z98 EQ 1.		
	1	Yes	81	22,3
	2	No	282	77,7
		Total	363	100
	9	No answer	10	
		Not applicable	4042	
			4415	
Z105		FATHER'S EDUCATION		X123, jfr Y22, jfr U22, jfr V13, jfr W22
		Did your father (foster father) receive any education apart from elementary or compulsory school? If yes: Which of the following best describes your father's level of education? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
	1	Elementary or compulsory school only	2106	49,4
	2	Vocational education above elementary/compulsory level	638	15,0
	3	Lower secondary school, 2-year social/econ./techn. program at upper secondary level	311	7,3
	4	Upper secondary school exam (cf. A-level, Abitur, Bac), 3- to 4-year academic program	436	10,2
	5	University or university college education	204	4,8
	6	University degree	500	11,7
	7	Father has not been at school	71	1,7
		Total	4266	100
	8	Doesn't know	123	
	9	No answer	26	
			4415	
Z106		MOTHER'S EDUCATION		X124, jfr Y23, jfr U23, jfr V14, jfr W23
		Did your mother (foster mother) receive any education apart from elementary or compulsory school? If yes: Which of the following best describes your mother's level of education? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.		
	1	Elementary or compulsory school only	2171	50,2
	2	Vocational education above elementary/compulsory level	513	11,9
	3	Lower secondary school, 2-year social/econ./techn. program at upper secondary level	460	10,6
	4	Upper secondary school exam (cf. A-level, Abitur, Bac), 3- to 4-year academic program	419	9,7
	5	University or university college education	314	7,3
	6	University degree	338	7,8
	7	Mother has not been at school	110	2,5
		Total	4325	100

Z111	SSYK FATHER	NEW																																																																								
	Father's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.																																																																									
Z112	ISCO88 FATHER	NEW																																																																								
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Z114	SIOPS FATHER	NEW																																																																								
	Father's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present. Not shown.																																																																									
Z115	FATHER'S EGP	X848, Y670																																																																								
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Z116	FATHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	X129, jfr Y27, jfr U152, jfr V16, jfr W25																																																																								
	If father self-employed: How many employees had the company besides your father? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.																																																																									
	<table> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes, no employees</td> <td>402</td> <td>9,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Yes, 1-9 employees</td> <td>380</td> <td>9,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Yes, 10-19 employees</td> <td>106</td> <td>2,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Yes, 20 or more employees</td> <td>79</td> <td>1,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>No</td> <td>3185</td> <td>76,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4152</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>263</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes, no employees	402	9,7	2	Yes, 1-9 employees	380	9,2	3	Yes, 10-19 employees	106	2,6	4	Yes, 20 or more employees	79	1,9	5	No	3185	76,7		Total	4152	100	9	No answer	263																																														
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Z117 FATHER FARMER: AREA X130, Y28,**U153, jfr V16,
jfr W25**

If father a farmer: How large was the farm? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Small farm	157	37,2
2	Average farm	237	56,2
3	Large farm	28	6,6
	Total	422	100
9	No answer	35	
	Question not asked (fadern ej jordbrukare)	3958	
		4415	

Z118 FATHER'S PARENTAL LEAVE NEW

Before you started school (i.e. up to age 7), was your father at some time on parental leave taking care of you in the home? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Yes, more than 3 months	54	8,1
2	Yes, 3 months or less	86	12,9
3	Yes, don't know for how long	49	7,4
4	No	477	71,6
	Total	666	100
8	Doesn't know	202	
	Question not asked	3547	
		4415	

Z120 SEI MOTHER X132, jfr Y29,**jfr U159**

Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother's (foster mother's) main occupation? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI". Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	305	7,1
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	853	19,9
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	50	1,2
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	209	4,9
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	262	6,1
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	24	0,6
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	194	4,5
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	25	0,6
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	524	12,2
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	183	4,3
57	Professional, upper-level executive*	16	0,4
60	Self-employed professionals	21	0,5
71	Self-employed without employees	40	0,9
71	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	40	0,9
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	5	0,1

	74	Self-employed 20+ employees	5	0,1
	79	Self-employed, number of employees unknown	9	0,2
	86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	60	1,4
	87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	104	2,4
	89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	11	0,3
	92	Homemaker	1339	31,3
		Total	4279	100
	99	Unclassified	136	
			4415	
Z121	NYK80 MOTHER			X133, Y30
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother’s (foster mother’s) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 (“Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK”). Not shown.			
Z122	NYK85 MOTHER			X134
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother’s (foster mother’s) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 (“Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK”). A list of codes was published by SCB’s Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.			
Z123	SSYK MOTHER			NEW
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother’s (foster mother’s) main occupation? Coded according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.			
Z124	ISCO88 MOTHER			NEW
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother’s (foster mother’s) main occupation? Coded according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.			
Z126	SIOPS MOTHER			NEW
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother’s (foster mother’s) main occupation? Coded according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.			
Z127	MOTHER’S EGP			X849, Y671
	Mother’s profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP). Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.			
	1	Ib Higher-grade professionals	21	0,7
	2	II Lower-grade professionals	204	6,9
	3	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	542	18,4
	4	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	390	13,3
	5	IVa Small proprietors with employees	610	20,7
	6	IVb Small proprietors without employees	54	1,8

7	IVc Farmers	40	1,4
8	IVd Smallholders	104	3,5
9	Vs Supervisors	71	2,4
10	VIs Skilled manual workers	22	0,7
12	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	69	2,3
14	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	788	26,8
15	Ib Higher-grade professionals	25	0,9
	Total	2940	100
99	Unclassified	1475	
		4415	

Z128 **MOTHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES** **jfr X135, jfr Y32, jfr U152**

If mother self-employed: How many employees had the company besides your mother? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Yes, no employees	72	1,6
2	Yes, 1-9 employees	43	1,0
3	Yes, 10-19 employees	5	0,1
4	Yes, 20 or more employees	4	0,1
5	No	4285	97,2
	Total	4409	100
9	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z129 **MOTHER FARMER: AREA** **X136, Y33, jfr U153**

If mother a farmer: How large was the farm? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	Small farm	11	40,7
2	Average farm	14	51,8
3	Large farm	2	7,4
	Total	27	100
9	No answer	1	
0	Question not asked (mother not farmer))	2244	
	Question not asked	2143	
		4415	

Z130 **RESPONDENT'S AGE WHEN MOTHER STARTED GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT** **X137**

If your mother was employed at any time during your childhood, how old were you when you mother began to work outside the home for the first time after your birth?

0		43	4,8
1		298	33,3
2		169	18,9
3		81	9,0
4		43	4,8
5		30	3,3

6		44	4,9
7		47	5,2
8		21	2,3
9		18	2,0
10		25	2,8
11		14	1,6
12		23	2,6
13		17	1,9
14		6	0,7
15		10	1,1
16		2	0,2
17		1	0,1
18		2	0,2
20		1	0,1
21		1	0,1
	Total	896	100
88	Mother was gainfully employed in the home	71	
89	Respondent was over three years old	183	
90	Respondent was under three years old	125	
98	Doesn't know	152	
99	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	2982	
		4415	

Z131	CHILDHOOD FAMILY'S ECONOMY	X138, Y36, U25, V19, W28
	Did your family experience economic hardship while you were growing up? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.	
1	Yes	663 15,1
2	No	3734 84,9
	Total	4397 100
8	No answer	18
		4415

Z132	PARENTS' HOME-OWNING	jfr X140, Y39
	Did your parents own their own home (co-operative apartment, detached house, semi-detached house, row-house, farmhouse etc.) during the greater part of your childhood? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.	
1	Yes	1914 78,0
2	No	540 22,0
	Total	2454 100
8	No answer	3
	Question not asked	1958
		4415

Z133	YEAR OF BIRTH – MOTHER		X237	
	In what year was your mother born? Here this variable is divided into categories.			
	1890-1899		39	0,9
	1900-1909		279	6,6
	1910-1919		606	14,3
	1920-1929		715	16,9
	1930-1939		705	16,6
	1940-1949		857	20,2
	1950-1959		720	17,0
	1960-1969		309	7,3
	1970-1979		8	0,2
	Total		4238	100
	8888	Doesn't know	172	
	9999	No answer	5	
			4415	
Z134	MOTHER - ALIVE		X238, jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21	
	Is your mother alive?			
	1	Yes	2829	64,2
	2	No	1578	35,8
		Total	4407	100
	8	Doesn't know	5	
	9	No answer	3	
			4415	
Z135	YEAR OF DEATH – MOTHER		X239	
	If your mother is dead, in what year did she die? Here this variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z134 EQ 2.			
	<1949		15	1,0
	1950-1959		22	1,4
	1960-1969		47	3,1
	1970-1979		106	6,9
	1980-1989		253	16,5
	1990-1999		443	28,9
	2000-2011		645	42,1
	Total		1531	100,0
	8888	Doesn't know	47	
		Not applicable	2837	
			4415	

Z136**CIVIL STATUS – MOTHER****X240**

Does your mother live together with your father/a partner or is she single?

The table is valid for Z134 EQ 1.

1	Married/cohabiting with father	1375	48,6
2	Married/cohabiting with new partner	384	13,6
3	Single	1065	37,6
4	Doesn't know	5	0,2
	Total	2829	100
	Not applicable	1586	
		4415	

Z137**DISTANCE – MOTHER****X241**

Where does your mother live? Distance to respondent. This variable is divided into categories and refers to kilometres.

The table is valid for Z134 EQ 1.

0		265	11,8
1-9		707	31,4
10-49		604	26,8
50-99		194	8,6
100-199		183	8,1
200-299		102	4,5
300-399		74	3,3
400-499		54	2,4
500-599		34	1,5
600-699		13	0,6
700-799		10	0,4
800-899		6	0,3
>900		6	0,3
	Total	2252	100,0
77777	Living in another country	280	
77888	Living in the same household	220	
99999	No answer	77	
	Not applicable	1586	
		4415	

Z138**RELATIONS MOTHER****X242**

How often do you usually see your mother?

1	Several times a week	473	18,1
2	About once a week	588	22,6
3	1-3 times a month	718	27,6
4	Less often	771	29,6
5	Never	57	2,2
	Total	2607	
7	Living in the same household	220	

	9	No answer		2
		Not applicable		1586
				4415
Z139	TELEPHONE CONTACT MOTHER			X243
	How often do you usually have contact with your mother through telephone, e-mail, SMS, chatting on the internet or similar?			
	1	Several times a week	1285	49,3
	2	About once a week	790	30,3
	3	1-3 times a month	344	13,2
	4	Less often	102	3,9
	5	Never	86	3,3
		Total	2607	
	7	Living in the same household	220	
	9	No answer	2	
		Not applicable	1586	
			4415	
Z140	YEAR OF BIRTH – FATHER			X244
	In what year was your father born? This variable is divided into categories.			
		1870-1879	1	0,0
		1880-1889	7	0,2
		1890-1899	100	2,4
		1900-1909	415	10,0
		1910-1919	642	15,4
		1920-1929	684	16,4
		1930-1939	693	16,6
		1940-1949	845	20,3
		1950-1959	598	14,4
		1960-1969	181	4,3
		1980-1989	1	0,0
		Total	4,167	100,0
	8888	Doesn't know	243	
	9999	No answer	5	
			4,415	
Z141	FATHER – ALIVE			X245, jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
	Is your father alive?			
	1	Yes	2250	51,3
	2	No	2133	48,7
		Total	4383	100
	8	Doesn't know	28	
	9	No answer	4	
			4415	

Z142	YEAR OF DEATH – FATHER		X246
	If your father is dead, in what year did he die? Here this variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z141 EQ 2.		
	<1950	13	0,5
	1950-59	45	2,2
	1960-69	95	4,6
	1970-79	267	13,0
	1980-89	411	20,0
	1990-99	520	25,3
	2000-09	573	27,9
	2010	129	6,3
	Total	2054	100
8888	Doesn't know	78	
9999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	2282	
		4415	
Z143	CIVIL STATUS – FATHER		X247
	Does your father live together with a partner or is he single?		
	The table is valid for Z141 EQ 1.		
	1 Married/cohabiting with mother	1376	62,0
	2 Married/cohabiting with new partner	439	19,8
	3 Single	406	18,3
	Total	2221	100
	4 Doesn't know	29	
	Not applicable	2165	
		4415	
Z144	DISTANCE – FATHER		X248
	Where does your father live? Distance to respondent. This variable is divided into categories and refers to kilometres.		
	0	206	11,3
	1-9	554	30,5
	10-49	484	26,7
	50-99	150	8,3
	100-199	154	8,5
	200-299	88	4,8
	300-399	59	3,3
	400-499	53	2,9
	500-599	33	1,8
	600-699	11	0,6
	700-799	10	0,6
	800-899	8	0,4
	900-999	5	0,3

	Total	1815	100,0
77777	Living in another country	214	
77888	Living in the same household	149	
99999	No answer	72	
	Not applicable	2,165	
		4,415	

Z145 RELATIONS FATHER X249

How often do you usually see your father?

1	Several times a week	350	16,7
2	About once a week	386	18,4
3	1-3 times a month	570	27,1
4	Less often	698	33,2
5	Never	96	4,6
	Total	2100	100
7	Living in the same household	149	
9	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	2165	
		4415	

Z146 TELEPHONE CONTACT FATHER X250

How often do you usually have contact with your father through telephone, e-mail, SMS, chatting on the internet or similar?

1	Several times a week	707	33,7
2	About once a week	652	31,0
3	1-3 times a month	412	19,6
4	Less often	206	9,8
5	Never	124	5,9
	Total	2101	100
7	Living in the same household	149	
	Not applicable	2165	
		4415	

Z147 NUMBER OF HOME TOWNS X142, jfr Y44, jfr U30, jfr V24, jfr W9

In how many places did you live during your childhood, i.e. up to age 16? Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

1	2034	46,2
2	1108	25,2
3	623	14,1
4	292	6,6
5	160	3,6
6	73	1,7
7	42	1,0
8	27	0,6
9	13	0,3

23	Jämtlands	75	1,7
24	Västerbottens	122	2,8
25	Norrbotens	132	3,0
30	Norway	36	0,8
31	Finland	67	1,5
32	Former Yugoslavia	49	1,1
33	Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	57	1,3
34	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	46	1,0
35	Spain, Italy, Greece	3	0,1
36	Other countries	312	7,1
	Total	4414	100
99	No answer	1	
		4415	

Z150 HOME MUNICIPALITY X145, Y48, U34, V28, W13

In what municipality did you live (most of the time) during your childhood (i.e., up to age 16)? Frequencies not shown. Question not asked to panel, but information from previous LNU has been added when present.

Z151 NUMBER OF MONTHS AT DAY-CARE CENTRE X146, Y51

Before you began elementary school, were you ever at a day-care centre? If yes: For about how many years and months altogether? Question not asked to panel.

The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5.

1-11		9	2,0
12-23		36	8,1
24-35		88	19,8
36-47		108	24,3
48-59		110	24,8
60-71		66	14,9
>72		27	6,1
	Total	444	100,0
888	Never been to a day-care centre	362	
999	No answer	62	
	Not applicable	3547	
		4415	

Z152 WENT TO CHILDMINDER jfr X147, jfr Y52

Before you began elementary school, did you ever spend time at the home of a child minder?

The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5.

1	Yes	343	39,9
2	No	516	60,1
	Total	859	100
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	3547	
		4415	

Z153	WENT TO PREPARATORY SCHOOL		jfr X148, jfr Y53	
	Did you go to any preparatory school for six-year olds?			
	The table is valid for Z2 EQ 5.			
	1	Yes	600	70,9
	2	No	246	29,1
		Total	846	100
	9	No answer	22	
		Not applicable	3547	
			4415	
Z154	CIVIL STATUS ACCORDING TO INTERVIEW		jfr X149, jfr Y57, jfr U90, jfr V68, jfr W36	
	Spouse or partner currently living in household.			
	1	Unmarried	1166	26,4
	2	Divorced	175	4,0
	3	Widow(er)	77	1,7
	4	Cohabitant	907	20,5
	5	Married	2080	47,1
	6	Married, not cohabiting	10	0,2
		Total	4415	100
Z155	YEAR/MONTH START OF CURRENT COHABITATION		X150	
	What year and what month did your current cohabitation start? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
		<1940	1	0,0
		1950-59	55	1,9
		1960-69	371	12,9
		1970-79	446	15,5
		1980-89	479	16,6
		1990-99	603	21,0
		2000-09	812	28,2
		>2009	111	3,8
		Total	2985	100
	999999	No answer	2	
		Not applicable	1428	
			4415	

Z156	YEAR/MONTH OF MARRIAGE		NEW
	What year and month did you and your partner get married? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z154 EQ 5.		
	<1959	49	2,4
	1960-69	339	16,3
	1970-79	306	14,7
	1980-89	377	18,2
	1990-99	366	17,6
	>2000	639	30,8
	Total	2077	100
999999	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	2334	
		4415	
Z157	NUMBER OF PERSONS IN HOUSEHOLD		X151, Y58, U91, jfr V57, jfr W90
	Number of persons currently living in the household.		
	1	936	21,2
	2	1665	37,7
	3	704	15,9
	4	744	16,9
	5	285	6,5
	6	59	1,3
	7	13	0,3
	8	7	0,2
	9	1	0,0
	10	1	0,0
	Total	4415	100
Z158	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S SEX		X152
	What is your partner's/cohabitant's sex?		
	The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.		
	1 Man	1464	49,0
	2 Woman	1523	51,0
	Total	2987	100
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z159	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S YEAR OF BIRTH		X153
	What is your partner's/cohabitant's year of birth? This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.		
	1910-29	9	0,3
	1930-39	158	5,3
	1940-49	531	17,8
	1950-59	610	20,5
	1960-69	622	20,9
	1970-79	635	21,3
	1980-89	375	12,6
	1990-99	42	1,4
	Total	2982	100
9999	Doesn't know	5	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	
Z160	NUMBER OF CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD		X154
	Number of children currently living in the household.		
	0	2716	61,5
	1	624	14,1
	2	742	16,8
	3	270	6,1
	4	48	1,1
	5	8	0,2
	6	5	0,1
	8	2	0,0
	Total	4415	100
Z161	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD		X155, jfr Y59, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
	Number of own children currently living in the household.		
	0	2768	62,8
	1	626	14,2
	2	727	16,5
	3	237	5,4
	4	38	0,9
	5	6	0,1
	6	4	0,1
	8	2	0,0
	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z162	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD		X156, jfr Y60, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
	Number of spouse's children currently living in the household.		
	0	4300	97,5
	1	73	1,7
	2	30	0,7
	3	5	0,1
	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z163	NUMBER OF CHILDREN BORN 1992-2010 IN HOUSEHOLD		X157
	Number of children born 1992-2010 currently living in the household.		
	0	2900	65,7
	1	596	13,5
	2	653	14,8
	3	218	4,9
	4	35	0,8
	5	8	0,2
	6	3	0,1
	8	2	0,0
	Total	4415	100

Z164	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN BORN 2000-2009 IN HOUSEHOLD		X160, jfr Y81
	Number of younger children born 2000-2009 currently living in the household.		
	0	3481	78,8
	1	484	11,0
	2	366	8,3
	3	75	1,7
	4	6	0,1
	5	3	0,1
	Total	4415	100

Z165	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009		X161, jfr Y61, jfr U103
	Number of own children living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 2009.		
	0	2811	63,8
	1	616	14,0
	2	708	16,1
	3	221	5,0
	4	42	1,0
	5	4	0,1
	6	4	0,1
	7	2	0,0

	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z166	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009 BORN 1992-2009		X162
	Number of own children born 1992-2009 living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 2009.		
	0	3051	69,2
	1	562	12,7
	2	599	13,6
	3	160	3,6
	4	29	0,7
	5	3	0,1
	6	2	0,0
	7	2	0,0
	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z167	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009		X163, jfr Y62, jfr U103
	Number of spouse's or partner's children living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 2009.		
	0	4301	97,6
	1	75	1,7
	2	27	0,6
	3	5	0,1
	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z168	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 2009 BORN 1992-2009		X164
	Number of spouse's or partner's children born 1992-2009 living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 2009.		
	0	4323	98,1
	1	59	1,3
	2	23	0,5
	3	3	0,1
	Total	4408	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
99	No answer	6	
		4415	

Z169	FAMILY TYPE		X165
	What does your family look like?		
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 0.		
	1 Two cohabitants w common child(ren) only	1298	76,4
	2 Single woman with child(ren)	150	8,8
	3 Single man with child(ren)	70	4,1
	4 Two cohabitants w woman's child(ren) only	75	4,4
	5 Two cohabitants w man's child(ren) only	27	1,6
	6 Two cohabitants w own, and possibly common, child(ren)	72	4,2
	7 Other	7	0,4
	Total	1699	100
	Not applicable	2716	
		4415	

Z170	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1		X166, Y63
	Year of birth for the youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 0.		
	1960-1969	5	0,3
	1970-1979	10	0,6
	1980-1989	86	5,1
	1990-1999	597	35,2
	2000-2011	998	58,8
	Total	1696	100
	Not applicable	2719	
		4415	

Z171	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2		X167, Y64
	Year of birth for the second youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 1.		
	1960-1969	1	0,1
	1970-1979	3	0,3
	1980-1989	65	6,1
	1990-1999	507	47,2
	2000-2011	498	46,4
	Total	1074	100
	Not applicable	3341	
		4415	

Z172	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3		X168, Y65
	Year of birth for the third youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		

Z176	SEX CHILD 2			X172
		Sex of the second youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
		The table is valid for Z160 GT 1.		
	1	Man	553	51,5
	2	Woman	521	48,5
		Total	1074	100
		Not applicable	3341	
			4415	
Z177	SEX CHILD 3			X173
		Sex of the third youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
		The table is valid for Z160 GT 2.		
	1	Man	182	54,7
	2	Woman	151	45,3
		Total	333	100
		Not applicable	4082	
			4415	
Z178	SEX CHILD 4			X174
		Sex of the fourth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
		The table is valid for Z160 GT 3.		
	1	Man	22	34,9
	2	Woman	41	65,1
		Total	63	100
		Not applicable	4352	
			4415	
Z179	SEX CHILD 5			X175
		Sex of the fifth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
		The table is valid for Z160 GT 4.		
	1	Man	6	40,0
	2	Woman	9	60,0
		Total	15	100
		Not applicable	4400	
			4415	

Z180	LIVES WITH PARENT			X176, Y68
	Currently cohabiting with parent.			
	0	No	4172	94,5
	1	Yes	243	5,5
		Total	4415	100
Z181	HOUSEHOLD WITH THREE GENERATIONS			X177, Y69
	Currently living in a household with three generations.			
	0	Not living in household with three generations	4401	99,7
	1	Respondent's grandparent	3	0,1
	2	Respondent's child(ren) and parent	7	0,2
	3	Respondent's grandchild(ren)	3	0,1
	4	Respondent's child(ren) and grandchild(ren)	1	0,0
		Total	4415	100
Z182	MARRIED/COHABITING 2009 AND 2010			X178, Y71, U110
	Spouse or partner in household during the main part of 2009 (at least nine months) and during 2010 at time of interview.			
	1	Cohabiting 2009-2010	2767	62,8
	2	Single 2009 - Cohabiting 2010	219	5,0
	3	Cohabiting 2009 - Single 2010	101	2,3
	4	Single 2009 - 2010	1317	29,9
	5	Cohabiting 2009-2010 with different partners	1	0,0
		Total	4405	100
	9	No answer	10	
			4415	
Z183	OTHER CHILDREN 2009, NOT IN HOUSEHOLD 2010			X179, Y70
	Number of children moving out october 2009 or later.			
	0		4272	96,7
	1		125	2,8
	2		17	0,4
	3		1	0,1
		Total	4415	100
Z184	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE			X181, jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710
	What is your spouse's/partner's employment status?			
	The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
	1	Employed	1825	61,2
	2	Self-employed	256	8,6
	3	Farmer	12	0,4

Z187	NYK85 SPOUSE	X184																																																																				
	Spouse's/partner's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.																																																																					
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Z192	SPOUSE'S EGP	X185, Y672																																																																				
	Spouse's/partner's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP). The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.																																																																					
	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals</td> <td>139</td> <td>4,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Ib Higher-grade professionals</td> <td>365</td> <td>12,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>II Lower-grade professionals</td> <td>733</td> <td>25,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade</td> <td>438</td> <td>14,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade</td> <td>328</td> <td>11,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>IVa Small proprietors with employees</td> <td>54</td> <td>1,8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>IVb Small proprietors without employees</td> <td>24</td> <td>0,8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>IVc Farmers</td> <td>64</td> <td>2,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>IVd Smallholders</td> <td>2</td> <td>0,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>Vs Supervisors</td> <td>333</td> <td>11,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Vj Supervisors in primary production</td> <td>8</td> <td>0,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>VIs Skilled manual workers</td> <td>427</td> <td>14,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>15</td> <td>VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production</td> <td>15</td> <td>0,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>2930</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Unclassified</td> <td>57</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>1428</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	139	4,7	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	365	12,5	3	II Lower-grade professionals	733	25,0	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	438	14,9	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	328	11,2	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	54	1,8	9	IVb Small proprietors without employees	24	0,8	10	IVc Farmers	64	2,2	11	IVd Smallholders	2	0,1	12	Vs Supervisors	333	11,4	3	Vj Supervisors in primary production	8	0,3	14	VIs Skilled manual workers	427	14,6	15	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	15	0,5		Total	2930	100	99	Unclassified	57			Not applicable	1428				4415		
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Z193	SPOUSE SELF-EMPLOYED: EMPLOYEES	X187, jfr Y75, jfr U120																																																																				
	If spouse/partner self-employed or a farmer: Does/did s/he have any employees?																																																																					
	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>No employees</td> <td>182</td> <td>54,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>1-9 employees</td> <td>108</td> <td>32,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-19 employees</td> <td>28</td> <td>8,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>20 or more employees</td> <td>18</td> <td>5,4</td> </tr> </table>	1	No employees	182	54,2	2	1-9 employees	108	32,1	3	10-19 employees	28	8,3	4	20 or more employees	18	5,4																																																					
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	Total	336	100
9	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	4076	
		4415	

Z194 **SPOUSE'S CURRENT WORKING HOURS** **X189, Y77, U111**

If spouse/partner: How many hours per week does your spouse/partner currently work? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

0		790	26,6
1-9		38	1,3
10-19		43	1,4
20-29		164	5,5
30-39		440	14,8
40-49		1316	44,3
50-59		109	3,7
60-69		54	1,8
70-79		12	0,4
80-89		5	0,2
>90		1	0,0
	Total	2972	100
888	Doesn't know	13	
999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z195 **SPOUSE'S/PARTNER'S HIGHEST EDUCATION** **NEW**

What is your spouse's highest completed education?

The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5

1	No education/unfinished compulsory school	30	1,0
2	Elementary or compulsory school (6-9 years)	407	13,8
3	Gymnasium, 2-3 year vocational track	783	26,5
4	General track at level of Gymnasium, girl's school	83	2,8
5	Vocational school: social, ekoc., tech. (2 years)	143	4,8
6	Gymnasium, 3- to 4-year with exam (incl voc)	328	11,1
7	At least 1 year above 3-4 year Gymnasium/exam	290	9,8
8	University degree	871	29,5
9	Other	20	0,7
	Total	2955	100
99	No answer	32	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z196	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN MUNICIPAL CHILDCARE	X200, jfr Y82
	Number of younger children (born 2000-2010) with municipal childcare (municipal day-care, after-school leisure centre, or municipal child minder, incl. three-family system)?	
	0	336 33,8
	1	372 37,4
	2	248 24,9
	3	36 3,6
	4	1 0,1
	5	1 0,1
	Total	994 100
99	No answer	3
	Not applicable	3418
		4415
Z197	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN PRIVATE CHILDCARE	X201
	Number of younger children (born 2000-2010) with private childcare (private child minder, parental cooperative or other private day-care or own nanny/au pair)?	
	0	927 93,3
	1	48 4,8
	2	17 1,7
	3	1 0,1
	4	1 0,1
	Total	994 100
99	No answer	3
	Not applicable	3418
		4415
Z198	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN MANAGING ALONE	X203, Y85
	Number of younger children (born 2000-2010) in the household who at times manages alone during some part of the day.	
	0	910 91,5
	1	77 7,7
	2	6 0,6
	3	1 0,1
	Total	994 100
99	No answer	3
	Not applicable	3418
		4415

Z199	NUMBER OF COMMON (WITH SPOUSE/PARTNER) CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	jfr X220
Number of children living in the household who are your and your spouse's/partner's mutual children.		
0	No common child	1642 54,8
1		520 17,3
2		609 20,3
3		190 6,3
4		30 1,0
5		4 0,1
6		2 0,1
8		1 0,0
	Total	2998 100
	Not applicable	1417
		4415
Z200	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Is the child your biological child, adoptee, step- or foster child?		
The table is valid for Z160 GT 0.		
1	Biological child	1620 95,7
2	Adoptee	19 1,1
3	Spouse's/partner's child	48 2,8
4	Other	6 0,4
	Total	1693 100
9	No answer	3
	Not applicable	2719
		4415
Z201	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Is the child's other parent currently living in your household?		
The table is valid for Z200 EQ 1 OR 2.		
1	Yes	1355 82,7
2	No	268 16,4
3	Other parent dead	16 1,0
	Total	1639 100
	Not applicable	2776
		4415
Z202	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
How many days during a typical month does the child approximately stay with the other parent?		
The table is valid for Z200 EQ 3 OR Z201 EQ 2.		
0		66 25,0
1		14 5,3

2		5	1,9
3		6	2,3
4		14	5,3
5		2	0,8
6		9	3,4
7		3	1,1
8		6	2,3
9		1	0,4
10		5	1,9
12		1	0,4
13		1	0,4
14		3	1,1
15		120	45,5
16		1	0,4
20		3	1,1
25		1	0,4
26		2	0,8
27		1	0,4
	Total	264	100
97	Other parent dead	14	
	Not applicable	4137	
		4415	

Z203

SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

NEW

How often does the child see you/the other parent?

The table is valid for Z201 EQ 2 och Z202 NE 15.

1	Several times a week	27	22,0
2	About once a week	18	14,6
3	1-3 times a week	35	28,5
4	Less often	27	22,0
5	Never	16	13,0
	Total	123	100
9	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4291	
		4415	

Z204

RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – NEW CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

How often do you and his/her other parent do something together with the child?

The table is valid for Z201 EQ 2 och Z203 NE 5.

1	Several times a week	11	5,3
2	About once a week	13	6,2
3	1-3 times a week	25	12,0
4	Less often	78	37,3
5	Never	82	39,2
	Total	209	100

	9	No answer	2	
		Not applicable	4204	
			4415	
Z205	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			NEW
	How often do you discuss matters regarding the child with his/her other parent?			
	The table is valid for Z201 EQ 2.			
	1	Several times a week	49	21,8
	2	About once a week	53	23,6
	3	1-3 times a week	47	20,9
	4	Less often	43	19,1
	5	Never	33	14,7
		Total	225	100
	9	No answer	2	
		Not applicable	4188	
			4415	
Z206	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			NEW
	Distance to the other biological parent. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z201 EQ 2.			
	0		10	4,9
	1-4		84	40,8
	5-9		27	13,1
	10-19		21	10,2
	20-29		17	8,3
	30-39		8	3,9
	40-49		3	1,5
	50-99		11	5,3
	100-499		19	9,2
	500>		6	2,9
		Total	206	100
	7777	Living abroad	13	
	9999	No answer	8	
		Not applicable	4188	
			4415	
Z207	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			X221
	Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. Here this variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z200 EQ 1 OR 2.			
	0		31	2,2
	1-9		37	2,7
	10-19		45	3,2
	20-29		47	3,4
	30-39		64	4,6

40-49		78	5,6
50-59		302	21,7
60-69		256	18,4
70-79		243	17,5
80-89		148	10,6
90-99		40	2,9
100-199		94	6,8
>199		6	0,4
	Total	1391	100
999	No answer	78	
	Not applicable	2946	
		4415	

Z208

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

X222

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z200 EQ 1 OR 2.

0		145	10,1
1-9		381	26,5
10-19		135	9,4
20-29		94	6,6
30-39		101	7,0
40-49		64	4,5
50-59		200	13,9
60-69		94	6,5
70-79		152	10,6
80-89		18	1,3
90-99		7	0,5
100-199		44	3,1
>199		2	0,1
	Total	1437	100
999	No answer	32	
	Not applicable	2946	
		4415	

Z209

AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

NEW

At what age did the child start in kindergarten, pre-school, child-minder or other child care? Given in months. Decimals (not tabulated) indicate that the child's age may vary up to 12 months at the most. As an example, the value 12.5 indicates that the child was between 12 and 23 months old. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		5	0,4
1-11		21	1,6
12-17		411	31,3
18-23		439	33,4
24-29		173	13,2
30-25		58	4,4
36-41		80	6,1
42-47		35	2,7
48-53		34	2,6

54-59		10	0,8
>60		47	3,6
	Total	1313	100
777	Never been in child care	168	
888	Doesn't know	28	
999	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	2903	
		4415	

Z210

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

jfr X231

Does the child have any kind of problems from illnesses or disabilities that affect the child's normal way of living such as asthma, diabetes, ADHD, dyslexia, hearing problems?

0	No problems/illnesses/disabilities	1320	87,5
1	Allergy	35	2,3
2	Asthma	68	4,5
3	Autism	4	0,3
4	Cerebral palsy	1	0,1
7	Diabetes	4	0,3
8	Down's syndrome	1	0,1
9	Dyslexia	14	0,9
10	Eczema	4	0,3
11	Epilepsy	1	0,1
13	Cardiovascular disease	1	0,1
15	Hearing problem	6	0,4
17	Psoriasis	1	0,1
18	Rheumatism	3	0,2
22	Mental retardation	4	0,3
23	ADHD	13	0,9
25	Goitre	1	0,1
26	Aspberger's syndrome	1	0,1
77	Some other problem/illness/disability	27	1,8
	Total	1	100
99	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	2719	
		4415	

Z211

SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

NEW

Does the child receive any special support in school due to reading-, writing-, or some other learning problems?
Or does the child attend a special school/class?

1	Yes	61	8,0
2	No	703	92,0
	Total	764	100
9	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	3649	
		4415	

Z212	SUPERVISION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW
	What supervision arrangement do you mainly have for the child during your/and or your spouse's/partner's working hours?		
	1 Child manages alone	53	5,3
	2 Parent is home	292	29,5
	3 Grandparent or other relative	7	0,7
	4 Private child minder	3	0,3
	5 Cooperative child care or other private day care center/pre-school	56	5,7
	6 Communal child minder (incl. Three family system)	26	2,6
	7 Municipal day care center/pre-school	358	36,1
	8 Preparatory school	29	2,9
	9 After school centre	167	16,9
	Total	991	100
	Not applicable	3424	
		4415	
Z213	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)		NEW
	What is the child's highest education?		
	1 Compulsory school	24	13,0
	2 Vocational school	13	7,1
	3 2-year theoretical gymnasium	4	2,2
	4 3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	118	64,1
	5 Higher education	12	6,5
	6 University degree	4	2,2
	7 Other education	9	4,9
	Total	184	100
	Not applicable	4231	
		4415	
Z214	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)		NEW
	Is the child currently studying? If yes: at what level?		
	2 Vocational school	10	14,5
	3 2-year theoretical gymnasium	16	23,2
	4 3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	23	33,3
	5 Higher education	13	18,8
	6 University degree	7	10,1
	Total	69	100
	Not applicable	4346	
		4415	

Z215	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	What is the child's main employment status?	
	1 Employed	80 43,7
	2 Self-employed	3 1,6
	3 Unemployed	20 10,9
	4 Student	62 33,9
	5 Military Service	2 1,1
	6 Other	16 8,7
	Total	183 100
	9 No answer	1
	Not applicable	4231
		4415
Z216sei	SEI CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".	
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	1 4,5
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	5 22,7
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	6 27,3
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	1 4,5
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	1 4,5
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	3 13,6
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	5 22,7
	Total	22 100
	Not applicable	4393
		4415
Z216nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NY
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.	
Z216nyk85	NYK85 BARN 1 (BARN FÖDDA 1985 OR EARLIER)	NY
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.	
Z216ssyk	SSYK BARN 1 (BARN FÖDDA 1985 OR EARLIER)	NY
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.	

Z216isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.		
Z216siops	SIOPS CHILD 1 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
The child's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.		
Z216egp	EGP CHILD 1 (CHILDREN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).		
3	II Lower-grade professionals	5 22,7
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	4 18,2
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	2 9,1
12	VI Skilled manual workers	6 27,3
14	VII Unskilled manual workers	5 22,7
	Total	22 100
	Not applicable	4393
		4415
Z217	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Is the child your biological child, adoptee, step- or foster child?		
The table is valid for Z160 GT 1.		
1	Biological child	999 93,4
2	Adoptee	12 1,1
3	Spouse's/partner's child	54 5,0
4	Other	5 0,5
	Total	1070 100
8	Doesn't know	1
9	No answer	2
	Not applicable	3342
		4415
Z218	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
Is the child's other parent currently living in your household?		
The table is valid for Z217 EQ 1 OR 2.		
1	Yes	835 82,6
2	No	165 16,3
3	Other parent dead	11 1,1
	Total	1011 100
	Not applicable	3404
		4415

Z219	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW
	How many days during a typical month does the child approximately stay with the other parent?		
	The table is valid for Z217 EQ 3 OR Z218 EQ 2.		
	0	53	29,4
	1	6	3,3
	2	4	2,2
	3	3	1,7
	4	13	7,2
	5	4	2,2
	6	2	1,1
	7	4	2,2
	8	2	1,1
	10	1	0,6
	12	1	0,6
	14	4	2,2
	15	77	42,8
	18	1	0,6
	20	3	1,7
	24	1	0,6
	30	1	0,6
	Total	180	100
97	Other parent dead	5	
	Not applicable	4230	
		4415	
Z220	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW
	How often does the child see you/the other parent?		
	The table is valid for Z218 EQ 2 AND Z219 NE 15.		
	1	Several times a week	12 16,0
	2	About once a week	7 9,3
	3	1-3 times a week	24 32,0
	4	Less often	16 21,3
	5	Never	16 21,3
	Total	75	100
	Not applicable	4340	
		4415	
Z221	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – NEW CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		
	How often do you and his/her other parent do something together with the child?		
	The table is valid for Z218 EQ 2 AND Z220 NE 5.		
	1	Several times a week	4 3,4

2	About once a week	5	4,2
3	1-3 times a week	18	15,1
4	Less often	45	37,8
5	Never	47	39,5
	Total	119	100
	Not applicable	4296	
		4415	

Z222 RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW

How often do you discuss matters regarding the child with his/her other parent?

The table is valid for Z218 EQ 2.

1	Several times a week	25	18,5
2	About once a week	31	23,0
3	1-3 times a week	28	20,7
4	Less often	25	18,5
5	Never	26	19,3
	Total	135	100
	Not applicable	4280	
		4415	

Z223 DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW

Distance to the other biological parent. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z218 EQ 2.

0		8	6,8
1-4		41	35,0
5-9		20	17,1
10-19		11	9,4
20-29		13	11,1
30-39		2	1,7
40-49		2	1,7
50-99		8	6,8
100-499		9	7,7
500>		3	2,6
	Total	117	100
7777	Living in another country	13	
9999	No answer	5	
	Not applicable	4280	
		4415	

Z224**PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****X223**

Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		20	2,4
1-9		11	1,3
10-19		14	1,7
20-29		13	1,6
30-39		15	1,8
40-49		31	3,8
50-59		157	19,2
60-69		154	18,8
70-79		195	23,8
80-89		105	12,8
90-99		26	3,2
100-199		72	8,8
200>		6	0,7
	Total	819	100
999	No answer	52	
	Not applicable	3544	
		4415	

Z225**PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****X224**

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		63	7,4
1-9		201	23,7
10-19		95	11,2
20-29		65	7,7
30-39		49	5,8
40-49		38	4,5
50-59		125	14,7
60-69		46	5,4
70-79		112	13,2
80-89		12	1,4
90-99		5	0,6
100-199		36	4,2
200>		2	0,2
	Total	849	100
999	No answer	22	
	Not applicable	3544	
		4415	

Z226**AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****NEW**

At what age did the child start in kindergarten, pre-school, child-minder or other child care? Given in months. Decimals (not tabulated) indicate that the child's age may vary up to 12 months at the most. As an example, the value 12.5 indicates that the child was between 12 and 23 months old. Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z217 EQ 1 OR 2.

0		3	0,4
1-11		10	1,2
12-17		288	35,7
18-23		276	34,2
24-29		120	14,9
30-35		32	4,0
36-41		34	4,2
42-27		4	0,5
48-53		16	2,0
54-59		6	0,7
>60		18	2,2
	Total	807	100,0
777	Never been in child care	89	
888	Doesn't know	23	
999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	3494	
		4415	

Z227**ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****jfr X232**

Does the child have any kind of problems from illnesses or disabilities that affect the child's normal way of living such as asthma, diabetes, ADHD, dyslexia, hearing problems?

0	No problems/illnesses/disabilities	961	89,7
1	Allergy	23	2,1
2	Asthma	31	2,9
3	Autism	5	0,5
7	Diabetes	2	0,2
8	Down's syndrome	2	0,2
9	Dyslexia	13	1,2
10	Eczema	2	0,2
11	Epilepsy	1	0,1
12	Late birth	3	0,3
13	Cardiovascular disease	1	0,1
15	Hearing problem	2	0,2
16	Vision problem	1	0,1
22	Mental retardation	4	0,4
23	ADHD	9	0,8
26	Aspberger's syndrome	2	0,2
77	Some other problem/illness/disability	9	0,8
	Total	1071	100
99	Missing	2	
	Not applicable	3342	
		4415	

Z228	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Does the child receive any special support in school due to reading-, writing-, or some other learning problems? Or does the child attend a special school/class?		
1	Yes	50 7,8
2	No	588 92,2
	Total	638 100
9	No answer	1
	Not applicable	3776
		4415
Z229	SUPERVISION – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
What supervision arrangement do you mainly have for the child during your/and or your spouse's/partner's working hours?		
1	Child manages alone	24 4,8
2	Parent is home	90 18,2
3	Grandparent or other relative	2 0,4
5	Private child minder	27 5,5
6	Cooperative child care or other private day care center/pre-school	13 2,6
7	Communal child minder (incl. Three family system)	142 28,7
8	Municipal day care center/pre-school	36 7,3
9	Preparatory school	160 32,3
10	Own nanny (employed)	1 0,2
	Total	495 100
99	No answer	2
	Not applicable	3918
		4415
Z230	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
What is the child's highest education?		
1	Compulsory school	16 10,6
2	Vocational school	6 4,0
3	2-year theoretical gymnasium	4 2,6
4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	111 73,5
5	Higher education	6 4,0
6	University degree	5 3,3
7	Other education	3 2,0
	Total	151 100
8	Doesn't know	1
9	No answer	1
	Not applicable	4262
		4415

Z231	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)		NEW
	Is the child currently studying? If yes: at what level?		
	2 Vocational school	10	14,7
	3 Theoretical gymnasium	20	29,4
	4 Higher education	11	16,2
	5 University degree	23	33,8
	6 Other education	4	5,9
	Total	68	100
	Not applicable	4347	
		4415	
Z232	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)		NEW
	What is the child's main employment status?		
	1 Employed	56	37,1
	2 Self-employed	1	0,7
	3 Unemployed	22	14,6
	4 Student	61	40,4
	5 Military Service	4	2,6
	6 Other	7	4,6
	Total	151	100
	9 No answer	2	
	Not applicable	4262	
		4415	
Z233sei	SEI CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)		NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	7	41,2
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	1	5,9
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	2	11,8
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	1	5,9
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	1	5,9
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	4	23,5
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	1	5,9
	Total	17	100
	Not applicable	4398	
		4415	

Z233nyk80	NYK80 BARN 2 (BARN FÖDDA 1985 ELLER TIDIGARE)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.																																					
Z233nyk85	NYK80 CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.																																					
Z233ssyk	NYK85 CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.																																					
Z233isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.																																					
Z233siops	SIOPS CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.																																					
Z233egp	EGP CHILD 2 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW																																				
	The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).																																					
	<table> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Higher-grade professionals</td> <td>1</td> <td>5,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade</td> <td>4</td> <td>23,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade</td> <td>3</td> <td>17,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Routine non-manual employees, lower grade</td> <td>4</td> <td>23,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>VI Skilled manual workers</td> <td>1</td> <td>5,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>VII Unskilled manual workers</td> <td>4</td> <td>23,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>17</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>4398</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	2	Higher-grade professionals	1	5,9	3	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	4	23,5	4	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	3	17,6	5	Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	4	23,5	12	VI Skilled manual workers	1	5,9	14	VII Unskilled manual workers	4	23,5		Total	17	100		Not applicable	4398				4415		
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	Total	17	100																																			
	Not applicable	4398																																				
		4415																																				
Z234	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW																																				
	Is the child your biological child, adoptee, step- or foster child?																																					
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 2.																																					
	<table> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Biological child</td> <td>293</td> <td>88,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Adoptee</td> <td>2</td> <td>0,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Spouse's/partner's child</td> <td>34</td> <td>10,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> <td>2</td> <td>0,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>331</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>2</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Biological child	293	88,5	2	Adoptee	2	0,6	3	Spouse's/partner's child	34	10,3	4	Other	2	0,6		Total	331	100	9	No answer	2														
1	Biological child	293	88,5																																			
2	Adoptee	2	0,6																																			
3	Spouse's/partner's child	34	10,3																																			
4	Other	2	0,6																																			
	Total	331	100																																			
9	No answer	2																																				

	Not applicable	4082	
		4415	
Z235	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)		NEW
	Is the child's other parent currently living in your household?		
	The table is valid for Z234 EQ 1 OR 2.		
1	Yes	227	76,9
2	No	65	22,0
3	Other parent dead	3	1,0
	Total	295	100
	Not applicable	4120	
		4415	
Z236	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW
	How many days during a typical month does the child approximately stay with the other parent?		
	The table is valid for Z234 EQ 3 OR Z235 EQ 2.		
0		29	37,2
1		2	2,6
2		2	2,6
3		1	1,3
4		2	2,6
8		2	2,6
10		1	1,3
12		1	1,3
14		3	3,8
15		32	41,0
18		1	1,3
25		1	1,3
30		1	1,3
	Total	78	100
97	Other parent dead	2	
	Not applicable	4335	
		4415	
Z237	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW
	How often does the child see you/the other parent?		
	The table is valid for Z235 EQ 2 AND Z237 NE 15.		
1	Several times a week	3	11,1
2	About once a week	1	3,7
3	1-3 times a week	8	29,6
4	Less often	7	25,9
5	Never	8	29,6
	Total	27	100

	Not applicable		4388	
			4415	
Z238	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – NEW CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			
	How often do you and his/her other parent do something together with the child?			
	The table is valid for Z235 EQ 2 AND Z237 NE 5.			
	1	Several times a week	2	4,7
	3	1-3 times a week	8	18,6
	4	Less often	14	32,6
	5	Never	19	44,2
		Total	43	100
		Not applicable	4372	
			4415	
Z239	RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW			
	How often do you discuss matters regarding the child with his/her other parent?			
	The table is valid for Z235 EQ 2.			
	1	Several times a week	4	7,8
	2	About once a week	14	27,5
	3	1-3 times a week	9	17,6
	4	Less often	10	19,6
	5	Never	14	27,5
		Total	51	100
		Not applicable	4364	
			4415	
Z240	DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW			
	Distance to the other biological parent. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z235 EQ 2.			
	0		4	9,5
	1-4		15	35,7
	5-9		9	21,4
	1019		2	4,8
	20-29		1	2,4
	30-39		4	9,5
	40-49		1	2,4
	50-59		2	4,8
	100-499		4	9,5
		Total	42	100
	7777	Living abroad	6	
	9999	No answer	3	

	Not applicable	4364	
		4415	

Z241 PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) X225

Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		9	4,1
1-9		4	1,8
10-19		3	1,4
20-29		3	1,4
30-39		3	1,4
40-49		5	2,3
50-59		46	21,0
60-69		48	21,9
70-79		40	18,3
80-89		32	14,6
90-99		4	1,8
100-199		22	10,0
	Total	219	100
999	No answer	18	
	Not applicable	4178	
		4415	

Z242 PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) X226

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		21	9,1
1-9		52	22,6
10-19		23	10,0
20-29		20	8,7
30-39		13	5,7
40-49		4	1,7
50-59		31	13,5
60-69		15	6,5
70-79		36	15,7
80-89		4	1,7
90-99		3	1,3
100-199		8	3,5
	Total	230	100
999	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	4178	
		4415	

Z243**AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****NEW**

At what age did the child start in kindergarten, pre-school, child-minder or other child care? Given in months. Decimals (not tabulated) indicate that the child's age may vary up to 12 months at the most. As an example, the value 12.5 indicates that the child was between 12 and 23 months old. Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z234 EQ 1 OR 2.

0		2	0,9
12-17		78	36,1
18-23		71	32,9
24-29		41	19,0
30-35		6	2,8
36-41		11	5,1
48-43		4	1,9
>60		3	1,4
	Total	216	100
777	Never been in child care	42	
888	Doesn't know	7	
999	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4149	
		4415	

Z244**ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****jfr X233**

Does the child have any kind of problems from illnesses or disabilities that affect the child's normal way of living such as asthma, diabetes, ADHD, dyslexia, hearing problems?

0	No problems/illnesses/disabilities	291	87,4
1	Allergy	10	3,0
2	Asthma	14	4,2
3	Autism	1	0,3
4	Cerebral palsy	1	0,3
8	Down's syndrome	1	0,3
9	Dyslexia	3	0,9
11	Epilepsy	2	0,6
18	Rheumatism	1	0,3
22	Mental retardation	1	0,3
23	ADHD	3	0,9
77	Some other problem/illness/disability	5	1,5
	Total	333	100
	Not applicable	4082	
		4415	

Z245	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW	
	Does the child receive any special support in school due to reading-, writing-, or some other learning problems? Or does the child attend a special school/class?			
	1	Yes	19	7,9
	2	No	223	92,1
		Total	242	100
		Not applicable	4173	
			4415	
Z246	SUPERVISION – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW	
	What supervision arrangement do you mainly have for the child during your/and or your spouse's/partner's working hours?			
	1	Child manages alone	12	11,7
	2	Parent is home	35	34,3
	5	Cooperative child care or other private day care center/pre- school	2	2,0
	7	Municipal day care center/pre-school	8	7,8
	8	Preparatory school	4	3,9
	9	After school centre	39	38,2
		Total	100	100
	99	No answer	2	
			4313	
			4415	
Z247	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)		NEW	
	What is the child's highest education?			
	1	Compulsory school	10	15,2
	2	Vocational school	5	7,6
	4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	47	71,2
	5	Higher education	1	1,5
	6	University degree	2	3,0
	7	Other education	1	1,5
		Total	66	100
	9	No answer	1	
		Not applicable	4348	
			4415	

Z248	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	Is the child currently studying? If yes: at what level?	
	2 Vocational school	7 25,0
	3 2-year theoretical gymnasium	9 32,1
	4 3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	6 21,4
	5 Higher education	5 17,9
	6 University degree	1 3,6
	Total	28 100
	Not applicable	4387
		4415
Z249	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	What is the child's main employment status?	
	1 Employed	21 31,8
	2 Self-employed	1 1,5
	3 Unemployed	15 22,7
	4 Student	26 39,4
	6 Other	3 4,5
	Total	66 100
	9 No answer	1
	Not applicable	4348
		4415
Z250sei	SEI CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".	
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	1 20,0
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	3 60,0
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	1 20,0
	Total	5 100
	Not applicable	4410
		4415
Z250nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.	
Z250nyk85	NYK85 CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.	

Z250ssyk	SSYK CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.	
Z250isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.	
Z250siops	SIOPS CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.	
Z250egp	EGP CHILD 3 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).	
	4 IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	1 20,0
	5 IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	1 20,0
	14 VIIs Unskilled manual workers	3 60,0
	Total	5 100
	Not applicable	4410
		4415
Z251	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
	Is the child your biological child, adoptee, step- or foster child?	
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 3.	
	1 Biological child	54 85,7
	3 Spouse's/partner's child	9 14,3
	Total	63 100
	Not applicable	4352
		4415
Z252	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
	Is the child's other parent currently living in your household?	
	The table is valid for Z251 EQ 1 OR 2.	
	1 Yes	37 68,5
	2 No	16 29,6
	3 Other parent dead	1 1,9
	Total	54 100
	Not applicable	4361
		4415

Z253	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW	
	How many days during a typical month does the child approximately stay with the other parent?			
	The table is valid for Z251 EQ 3 OR Z252 EQ 2.			
	0		9	40,9
	1		1	4,5
	3		1	4,5
	8		1	4,5
	10		1	4,5
	12		1	4,5
	15		6	27,3
	25		2	9,1
		Total	22	100
97		Not applicable	4393	
			4415	
Z254	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW	
	How often does the child see you/the other parent?			
	The table is valid for Z252 EQ 2 AND Z253 NE 15.			
	1	Several times a week	2	18,2
	3	1-3 times a week	4	36,4
	4	Less often	2	18,2
	5	Never	3	27,3
		Total	11	100
		Not applicable	4404	
			4415	
Z255	RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)		NEW	
	How often do you and his/her other parent do something together with the child?			
	The table is valid for Z252 EQ 2 AND Z254 NE 5.			
	1	Several times a week	1	8,3
	4	Less often	5	41,7
	5	Never	6	50,0
		Total	12	100
		Not applicable	4403	
			4415	

Z256**RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW**

How often do you discuss matters regarding the child with his/her other parent?

The table is valid for Z252 EQ 2.

1	Several times a week	1	6,7
2	About once a week	2	13,3
3	1-3 times a week	5	33,3
4	Less often	2	13,3
5	Never	5	33,3
	Total	15	100
	Not applicable	4400	
		4415	

Z257**DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW**

Distance to the other biological parent. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z252 EQ 2.

0		1	8,3
1-4		4	33,3
5-9		1	8,3
10-19		2	16,7
20-29		1	8,3
30-39		1	8,3
100-499		1	8,3
500>		1	8,3
	Total	12	100
9999	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	4400	
		4415	

Z258**PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)****X227**

Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. Here this variable is divided into categories.

0		2	5,6
40-49		2	5,6
50-59		11	30,6
60-69		6	16,7
70-79		3	8,3
80-89		5	13,9
100-199		7	19,4
	Total	36	100
	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	4373	
		4415	

Z259	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X228
<p>Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the child. Here this variable is divided into categories.</p>		
0		3 7,7
1-9		14 35,9
10-19		3 7,7
20-29		2 5,1
30-39		1 2,6
50-59		5 12,8
60-69		2 5,1
70-79		4 10,3
100-199		5 12,8
	Total	39 100
999	No answer	3
	Not applicable	4373
		4415
Z260	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
<p>At what age did the child start in kindergarten, pre-school, child-minder or other child care? Given in months. Decimals (not tabulated) indicate that the child's age may vary up to 12 months at the most. As an example, the value 12.5 indicates that the child was between 12 and 23 months old. Here this variable is divided into categories.</p>		
<p>The table is valid for Z251 EQ 1 OR 2.</p>		
12-17		11 28,2
18-23		12 30,8
24-29		7 17,9
30-35		3 7,7
36-41		3 7,7
48-53		2 5,1
>60		1 2,6
	Total	39 100
	Never been in child care	8
	Doesn't know	2
	Not applicable	4366
		4415
Z261	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	jfr X234
<p>Does the child have any kind of problems from illnesses or disabilities that affect the child's normal way of living such as asthma, diabetes, ADHD, dyslexia, hearing problems?</p>		
0	No problems/illnesses/disabilities	55 87,3
1	Asthma	3 4,8
15	Hearing problem	2 3,2
23	ADHD	1 1,6
25	Goitre	1 1,6
77	Some other problem/illness/disability	1 1,6
	Total	63 100

	Not applicable		4352	
			4415	
Z262	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			NEW
	Does the child receive any special support in school due to reading-, writing-, or some other learning problems? Or does the child attend a special school/class?			
1	Yes	2	4,3	
2	No	44	95,7	
	Total	46	100	
9	No answer	1		
	Not applicable	4368		
		4415		
Z263	SUPERVISION – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)			NEW
	What supervision arrangement do you mainly have for the child during your/and or your spouse's/partner's working hours?			
1	Child manages alone	2	16,7	
2	Parent is home	6	50,0	
5	Cooperative child care or other private day care center/pre- school	1	8,3	
7	Municipal day care center/pre-school	1	8,3	
9	After school centre	2	16,7	
	Total	12	100	
88	No answer	1		
	Not applicable	4402		
		4415		
Z264	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	What is the child's highest education?			
1	Compulsory school	1	7,1	
4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	12	85,7	
7	Other education	1	7,1	
	Total	14	100	
	Not applicable	4401		
		4415		
Z265	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	Is the child currently studying? If yes: at what level?			
1	Vocational school	1	16,7	
2	2-year theoretical gymnasium	1	16,7	
3	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	1	16,7	
4	Higher education	2	33,3	
5	University degree	1	16,7	
	Total	6	100	

	Not applicable		4409	
			4415	
Z266	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	What is the child's main employment status?			
	1	Employed	4	28,6
	3	Unemployed	2	14,3
	4	Student	6	42,9
	6	Other	2	14,3
		Total	14	100
		Not applicable	4401	
			4415	
Z267sei	SEI CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".			
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	2	66,7
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	1	33,3
		Total	3	100
		Not applicable	4412	
			4415	
Z267nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
Z267nyk85	NYK85 CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.			
Z267ssyk	SSYK CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.			
Z267isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.			
Z267siops	SIOPS CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)			NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.			

Z267egp	EGP CHILD 4 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).	
	3 II Lower-grade professionals	1 33,3
	5 IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	1 33,3
	14 VIIs Unskilled manual workers	1 33,3
		3 100
	Not applicable	4412
		4415
Z268	BIOLOGICAL CHILD – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
	Is the child your biological child, adoptee, step- or foster child?	
	The table is valid for Z160 GT 4.	
	1 Biological child	13 86,7
	3 Spouse's/partner's child	2 13,3
	Total	15 100
	Not applicable	4400
		4415
Z269	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN ANY YEAR OF BIRTH)	NEW
	Is the child's other parent currently living in your household?	
	The table is valid for Z268 EQ 1 OR 2.	
	1 Yes	7 53,8
	2 No	6 46,2
	Total	13 100
	Not applicable	4402
		4415
Z270	DAYS WITH OTHER PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
	How many days during a typical month does the child approximately stay with the other parent?	
	The table is valid for Z268 EQ 3 OR Z269 EQ 2.	
	0	4 57,1
	6	1 14,3
	10	1 14,3
	25	1 14,3
	Total	7 100
	Not applicable	4408
		4415
Z271	SEES OTHER PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
	How often does the child see you/the other parent?	

The table is valid for Z269 EQ 2 och Z271 NE 15.

1	Several times a week	1	20,0
2	About once a week	1	20,0
3	1-3 times a week	3	60,0
	Total	5	100
	Not applicable	4410	
		4415	

Z272

RESPONDENT, CHILD AND OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT DOES THINGS TOGETHER – NEW CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)

How often do you and his/her other parent do something together with the child?

The table is valid for Z269 EQ 2 och Z271 NE 5.

2	About once a week	1	20,0
5	Never	4	80,0
	Total	5	100
	Not applicable	4410	
		4415	

Z273

RESPONDENT DISCUSS WITH OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW

How often do you discuss matters regarding the child with his/her other parent?

The table is valid for Z269 EQ 2.

1	Several times a week	1	20,0
3	1-3 times a week	3	60,0
4	Less often	1	20,0
	Total	5	100
9	Not applicable	4410	
		4415	

Z274

DISTANCE TO OTHER BIOLOGICAL PARENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER) NEW

Distance to the other biological parent. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z269 EQ 2.

0		4	57,1
5-9		1	14,3
10-19		1	14,3
20-29		1	14,3
	Total	7	100
99	Not applicable	4408	
		4415	

Z275	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X229
Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. Here this variable is divided into categories.		
0		2 28,6
50-59		1 14,3
60-69		1 14,3
70-79		2 28,6
100-199		1 14,3
	Total	7 100
	No answer	4
	Not applicable	4404
		4415
Z276	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X230
Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the child. Here this variable is divided into categories.		
0		3 33,3
1-9		1 11,1
50-59		1 11,1
60-69		1 11,1
70-79		2 22,2
100-199		1 11,1
	Total	9 100
999	No answer	2
	Not applicable	4404
		4415
Z277	AGE CHILD CARE – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
At what age did the child start in kindergarten, pre-school, child-minder or other child care? Given in months. Decimals (not tabulated) indicate that the child's age may vary up to 12 months at the most. As an example, the value 12.5 indicates that the child was between 12 and 23 months old. Here this variable is divided into categories.		
The table is valid for Z268 EQ 1 OR 2.		
12-17		1 16,5
18-23		3 50,0
36-41		1 16,5
≥60		1 16,5
	Total	6 100
777	Har aldrig gått i barnomsorg	5
888	Doesn't know	2
	Not applicable	4402
		4415

Z278	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	X235
Does the child have any kind of problems from illnesses or disabilities that affect the child's normal way of living such as asthma, diabetes, ADHD, dyslexia, hearing problems?		
0	No problems/illnesses/disabilities	15 100,0
	Total	15 100
	Not applicable	4400
		4415
Z279	SPECIAL SUPPORT IN SCHOOL – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
Does the child receive any special support in school due to reading-, writing-, or some other learning problems? Or does the child attend a special school/class?		
1	Yes	1 8,3
2	No	11 91,7
	Total	12 100
9	No answer	1
	Not applicable	4402
		4415
Z280	SUPERVISION – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1992 OR LATER)	NEW
What supervision arrangement do you mainly have for the child during your/and or your spouse's/partner's working hours?		
1	Child manages alone	1 25,0
2	Parent is home	1 25,0
9	After school centre	2 50,0
	Total	4 100
	Not applicable	4411
		4415
Z281	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
What is the child's highest education?		
4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	2 100,0
	Total	2 100
	Not applicable	4413
		4415
Z282	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
Is the child currently studying? If yes: at what level?		
999	No answer	13 15,4
	Total	13 100
	Not applicable	4402
		4415

Z283	EMPLOYMENT STATUS – CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1991 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	What is the child's main employment status?	
	1 Employed	1 50,0
	3 Unemployed	1 50,0
	Total	2 100
	Not applicable	4413
		4415
Z284sei	SEI CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".	
	Not applicable	4415
		4415
Z284nyk80	NYK80 CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.	
Z284nyk85	NYK85 CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5. Not shown.	
Z284ssyk	SSYK CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.	
Z284isco88	ISCO88 CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.	
Z284siops	SIOPS CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.	
Z284egp	EGP CHILD 5 (CHILDREN BORN 1985 OR EARLIER)	NEW
	The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).	
	Not applicable	4415
		4415

Z285	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY		jfr X236
	Number of children born 2004 or later with any illness, problem or disability.		
	The table is valid for respondents with children born 2004 or later.		
	0	669	89,7
	1	75	10,0
	2	2	0,2
	Total	746	100
	Not applicable	3669	
		4415	
Z286	CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		X204, Y89, U124, jfr V954, jfr W59
	Do you have or have you had children who are not living with you? (Also adoptive- and stepchildren and deceased children – but not foster children if not counted as own).		
	1 Yes	1819	41,2
	2 No	2595	58,8
	Total	4414	100
	9 No answer	1	
		4415	
Z287	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		X205, Y90, U125, jfr V954, jfr W59
	How many of your children are not living with you now?		
	The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
	1	453	24,9
	2	850	46,8
	3	375	20,6
	4	109	6,0
	5	22	1,2
	6	7	0,4
	7	1	0,1
	10	1	0,1
	11	1	0,1
	Total	1819	100
	Not applicable	2596	
		4415	
Z288	NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		X206, Y91, U126, jfr V958
	Number of children born 2004 or later not living at home.		
	The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
	0	1791	98,5
	1	24	1,3
	2	4	0,2
	Total	1819	100

	Not applicable	2596	
		4415	
Z289	NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		X207, Y92, jfr U127, jfr V958
	Number of children born 1992-2003 not living in the household.		
	The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
	0	1701	93,5
	1	95	5,2
	2	19	1,0
	3	3	0,2
	4	1	0,1
	Total	1819	100
	Not applicable	2596	
		4415	
Z290	NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		X208, Y93, jfr U129, jfr V956, jfr W61
	Number of children born 1984-1991 not living in the household.		
	The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
	0	1198	65,9
	1	425	23,4
	2	164	9,0
	3	29	1,6
	4	3	0,2
	Total	1819	100
	Not applicable	2596	
		4415	
Z291	NUMBER OF DECEASED CHILDREN		X209, jfr Y94, jfr U130, jfr V957, jfr W62
	Number of deceased children born 1984 or later.		
	The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
	0	1809	99,5
	1	10	0,5
	Total	1819	100
	Not applicable	2596	
		4415	

Z292	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD WHO LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT	X210
Number of children who are living with their other parent.		
The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
0		1723 94,7
1		65 3,6
2		26 1,4
3		4 0,2
4		1 0,1
	Total	1819 100
	Not applicable	2596
		4415
Z293	SEX – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
Sex of the first child living away.		
The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
1	Son	878 48,3
2	Daughter	941 51,7
	Total	1819 100
	Not applicable	2596
		4415
* For information about additional childs living away, see Z293_a to _j.		
Z294	YEAR OF BIRTH – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
Year of birth of the first child living away. This variable is divided into categories.		
The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
1950-59		15 0,8
1960-69		288 15,9
1970-79		563 31,0
1980-89		705 38,9
1990-99		192 10,6
≥2000		51 2,8
	Total	1814 100
8888	Doesn't know	5
	Not applicable	2596
		4415
* For information about additional childs living away, see Z294_a to _j.		

Z295	BIOLOGICAL CHILD - CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
Is s/he [first child living away] your biological child, adoptee, stepchild or foster child?		
The table is valid for Z286 EQ 1.		
1	Biological child	1734 95,3
2	Adoptee	25 1,4
3	Spouse's/partner's child	34 1,9
4	Other	7 0,4
5	Deceased	19 1,0
	Total	1819 100
	Not applicable	2596
		4415
* For information about additional childs living away, see Z295_a to _j.		
Z296	OTHER PARENT IN HOUSEHOLD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
Is his/her [first child living away] other parent currently living in your household?		
The table is valid for Z295 EQ 1 OR 2 och for respondents who do not live alone in the household.		
1	Yes	952 69,3
2	No	393 28,6
3	Other parent dead	29 2,1
	Total	1374 100
8	Doesn't know	1
	Not applicable	3040
	Total	4415
* For information about additional childs living away, see Z296_a to _j.		
Z297	LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT - CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
Is s/he [first child living away] currently living with his/her other parent?		
The table is valid for Z295 EQ 1 OR 2 och Z296 EQ 2 and for child born 1992 or later.		
1	Yes	94 82,5
2	No	20 17,5
	Total	114 100
	Not applicable	4301
		4415
* For information about additional childs living away, see Z297_a to _j.		

Z298	END OF LIVING TOGETHER WITH CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
<p>What year did you end living with child [first child living away]? This variable is divided into categories</p> <p>The table is valid for Z295 NE 5 OR 9.</p>		
1960-69		5 0,3
1970-79		60 3,5
1980-89		288 16,6
1990-99		529 30,5
≥2000		852 49,1
	Total	1734 100
7777	Never lived together	32
8888	Doesn't know	31
	Not applicable	2618
		4415
<p>* For information about additional child's living away, see Z298_a to _j.</p>		
Z299	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
<p>Total number of days with parental leave for this child [first child living away] of the respondent and the other parent.</p> <p>The table is valid for Z295 EQ 1 OR 2 and for child born 1992 or later.</p>		
0		10 16,0
1-9		4 4,3
10-9		1 1,1
20-29		1 1,1
30-39		1 1,1
50-59		39 41,5
60-69		9 9,6
70-79		17 18,1
80-89		9 9,6
100-199		3 3,2
	Total	94 100
888	Doesn't know	28
999	No answer	1
	Not applicable	4292
		4415
<p>* For information about additional child's living away, see Z299_a to _j.</p>		
Z300	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*	NEW
<p>Approximately how many days have you been on parental leave for this child [first child living away]?</p> <p>The table is valid for Z295 EQ 1 OR 2 and for child born 1992 or later.</p>		
0		50 42,4
1-9		37 31,4
10-9		6 5,1

20-29		7	5,9
40-49		1	8,0
50-59		8	6,8
60-69		2	1,7
70-79		7	5,9
	Total	118	100
888	Doesn't know	5	
	Not applicable	4292	
		4415	

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z300_a to _j.

Z301

SEES CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*

NEW

How often do you see him/her [first child living away]?

The table is valid for Z295 NE 5.

1	Several times a week	419	23,3
2	About once a week	365	20,3
3	1-3 times a week	527	29,3
4	Less often	452	25,1
5	Aldrig	35	1,9
	Total	1798	100
8	Doesn't know	2	
	Not applicable	2615	
		4415	

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z301_a till _j.

Z302

CONTACT WTH CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*

NEW

How often do you call, e-mail, message, digitally chat with or in other similar ways communicate with him/her [first child living away]?

The table is valid for Z295 NE 5.

1	Several times a week	1061	59,0
2	About once a week	451	25,1
3	1-3 times a week	178	9,9
4	Less often	66	3,7
5	Aldrig	41	2,3
	Total	1797	100
8	Doesn't know	3	
	Not applicable	2615	
		4415	

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z302_a till _j.

Z303	DISTANCE TO CHILD – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1 *		NEW
	Distance to first child living away in kilometers. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z295 NE 5.		
	0	153	9,7
	1-4	274	17,3
	5-9	170	10,7
	10-19	242	15,3
	20-29	109	6,9
	30-39	67	4,2
	40-49	41	2,6
	50-99	147	9,3
	100-499	339	21,4
	≥500	43	2,7
	Total	1585	100
77777	Lives abroad	129	
99999	No answer	86	
	Not applicable	2615	
		4415	
	* For information about additional childs living away, see Z303_a till _j.		

Z304	HIGHEST EDUCATION – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*		NEW
	Highest education of first child living away.		
	The table is valid for children born 1991 or earlier.		
	1 Compulsory school	87	5,3
	2 Vocational school	170	10,3
	3 2-year theoretical gymnasium	7	4,3
	4 3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	732	44,4
	5 Higher education	299	18,1
	6 University degree	285	17,3
	7 Other education	5	0,3
	Total	1,649	100
	8 Doesn't know	20	
	Not applicable	2746	
		4415	
	* For information about additional childs living away, see Z304_a till _j.		

Z305	CURRENT EDUCATION – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*		NEW
	Level of ongoing studies, first child living away.		
	The table is valid for children born 1991 or earlier who currently studies.		
	1 Compulsory school	2	0,7
	2 Vocational school	28	9,2
	3 2-year theoretical gymnasium	23	7,5

4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	113	37,0
5	Higher education	136	44,6
6	University degree	3	1,0
	Total	305	100
8	Doesn't know	2	
	Not applicable	4108	
		4415	

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z305_a till _j.

Z306sei

SEI – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*

NEW

The child's profession/occupation according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".

The table is valid for children born 1985 or earlier.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	52	4,4
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	187	16,0
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	125	10,7
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	82	7,0
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	47	4,0
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	28	2,4
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	93	8,0
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	6	0,5
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	305	26,1
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	105	9,0
57	Professional, upper-level executive	22	1,9
60	Self-employed professionals	98	8,4
79	Self-employed, number of employees unknown	17	1,5
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	2	0,2
	Total	1169	100
99	Unclassified	6	
	Not applicable	3240	
		4415	

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306sei_a till _j.

Z306nyk80

NYK80 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*

The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.

Regards children born 1985 or earlier.

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306nyk80_a till _j.

<p>Z306nyk85</p>	<p>NYK85 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*</p> <p>The child's profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.. Not shown.</p> <p>Regards children born 1985 or earlier.</p> <p>* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306nyk85_a till _j.</p>																																																
<p>Z306ssyk</p>	<p>SSYK – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*</p> <p>The child's profession/occupation according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.</p> <p>Regards children born 1985 or earlier.</p> <p>* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306ssyk_a till _j.</p>																																																
<p>Z306isco88</p>	<p>ISCO88 – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*</p> <p>The child's profession/occupation according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.</p> <p>Regards children born 1985 or earlier.</p> <p>* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306isco88_a till _j.</p>																																																
<p>Z306siops</p>	<p>SIOPS – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*</p> <p>The child's profession/occupation according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.</p> <p>Regards children born 1985 or earlier.</p> <p>* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306siops_a till _j.</p>																																																
<p>Z306egp</p>	<p>EGP – CHILD LIVING AWAY 1*</p> <p>The child's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).</p> <p>The table is valid for children born 1985 or earlier.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="359 1601 1484 2016"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals</td> <td>98</td> <td>8,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Ib Higher-grade professionals</td> <td>127</td> <td>10,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>II Lower-grade professionals</td> <td>308</td> <td>26,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade</td> <td>177</td> <td>15,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade</td> <td>133</td> <td>11,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>IVa Small proprietors with employees</td> <td>17</td> <td>1,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>IVd Smallholders</td> <td>2</td> <td>0,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>Vs Supervisors</td> <td>27</td> <td>2,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>VIs Skilled manual workers</td> <td>125</td> <td>10,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13</td> <td>VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production</td> <td>1</td> <td>0,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>VIIs Unskilled manual workers</td> <td>153</td> <td>13,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>15</td> <td>VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production</td> <td>1</td> <td>0,1</td> </tr> </table>	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	98	8,4	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	127	10,9	3	II Lower-grade professionals	308	26,4	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	177	15,1	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	133	11,4	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	17	1,5	9	IVd Smallholders	2	0,2	10	Vs Supervisors	27	2,3	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	125	10,7	13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	1	0,1	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	153	13,1	15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	1	0,1
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	98	8,4																																														
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	Total	1169
99	Unclassified	6
	Not applicable	3240
		4415

* For information about additional childs living away, see Z306egp_a till _j.

Z307

NOT LIVING WITH PARTNER

NEW

Do you have a steady partner whom you do not live with?

The table is valid for Z154 NE 4 OR 5.

1	Yes	392	27,5
2	No	1034	72,5
	Total	1426	100
8	Doesn't know	1	
9	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	2987	
		4415	

Z308

DURATION OF LIVE-APART-RELATIONSHIP

NEW

Approximately how many years has the relationship been ongoing?

The table is valid for Z307 EQ 1.

0		96	24,7
1-4		201	51,7
5-9		53	13,6
10-14		13	3,3
15-20		6	1,5
20-24		5	1,3
25-29		3	0,8
30-34		2	0,5
35-39		5	1,3
40-44		2	0,5
45-49		2	0,5
≥50		1	0,3
	Total	389	100
88	Doesn't know	2	
99	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4023	
		4415	

Z309	PREVIOUSLY COHABITING		X190, Y99
	Have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months?		
1	Yes	1783	40,4
2	No	2629	59,6
	Total	4412	100
9	No answer	3	
		4415	
Z310	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS		X191, Y100
	Number of times that respondent previously has been cohabiting for at least 6 months.		
0		2629	59,6
1		1366	31,0
2		333	7,5
3		61	1,4
4		19	0,4
5		4	0,1
	Total	4412	100
9	No answer	3	
		4415	
Z311	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS MARRIAGES		X192
	Number of times that respondent has been married previously.		
0		681	58,3
1		465	39,8
2		22	1,9
	Total	1168	100
9	No answer	4	
97	Calculation not possible, question not asked before 2000	611	
	Not applicable	2632	
		4415	
Z312	YEAR/MONTH FOR FIRST COHABITATION		X193, jfr Y101
	Year and month when respondent first got married or started cohabiting for at least six months for the first time. If respondent has not previously been married or cohabiting the information refers to the current marriage/cohabitation. Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1950-59	100	2,6
	1960-69	679	17,8
	1970-69	747	19,5
	1980-89	775	20,3
	1990-99	743	19,4
	2000-09	710	18,6
	≥2010	68	1,8

	Total	3822	100
8	Doesn't know	9	
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	575	
		4415	

Z313	DURATION FIRST COHABITATION		X194, Y102
	Number of years or part of a year that the first marriage or cohabitation lasted. If respondent has not been previously married or cohabiting the information refers to how long (number of years) the current marriage/cohabitation has lasted. This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	1019	27,1
	1-4	575	15,3
	5-9	384	10,2
	10-14	324	8,6
	15-20	309	8,2
	20-24	216	5,7
	25-29	188	5,0
	30-34	237	6,3
	35-39	258	6,9
	40-44	168	4,5
	45-49	79	2,1
	≥50	5	0,1
	Total	3893	100
88	Doesn't know	24	
99	No answer	54	
	Not applicable	575	
		4415	

Z314	CIVIL STATUS FIRST COHABITATION		X195
	What was your civil status in the first cohabitation?		
	1 Married	575	38,3
	2 Not married	930	61,8
	Total	1505	100
	3 Question not asked before 2000	2314	
	7 Never cohabited	587	
	9 No answer	9	
		4415	

Z315	YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED		jfr X196, jfr Y103
	Year and month when respondent's last marriage or cohabitation lasting for at least six months ended. Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1950-59	1	0,1
	1960-69	17	1,0
	1970-69	149	8,5
	1980-89	250	14,3

1990-99		504	28,7
2000-09		728	41,5
≥2010		104	5,9
	Total	1753	100
777777	Never cohabited	587	
797979	Never ended a cohabitation	2044	
888888	Doesn't know	20	
999999	No answer	11	
		4415	

Z316

DURATION LAST COHABITATION

X197

Number of years or part of a year that the last marriage or cohabitation lasted. If respondent has not been previously married or cohabiting the information refers to how long (number of years) the current marriage/cohabitation has lasted. This variable is divided into categories.

1		277	7,5
2		259	7,0
3		199	5,4
4		174	4,7
5		151	4,1
6		133	3,6
7		114	3,1
8		104	2,8
9		97	2,6
10-19		745	20,1
20-29		520	14,0
30-39		420	11,3
40-49		426	11,5
≥50		83	2,2
	Total	3702	100
77	Never cohabited	587	
99	Doesn't know	126	
		4415	

Z317

REASON FOR SEPARATION LAST COHABITATION

X198, Y104

Reason the last cohabitation (lasting for at least six months) ended. Was this because of divorce/separation, death or some other reason?

1	Separation	1556	87,8
2	Death	152	8,6
3	Other	64	3,6
	Total	1772	100
77	Never cohabited	587	
79	Never ended a cohabitation	2044	
9	No answer	12	
		4415	

Z318	CIVIL STATUS LAST COHABITATION		X199
	What was your civil status in the last ended cohabitation?		
	1 Married	403	38,0
	2 Not married	655	62,0
	Total	1058	
	3 Unknown, Question not before 2000	722	
	77 Never cohabited	587	
	79 Never ended a cohabitation	2044	
	99 No answer	4	
		4415	
Z319	INITIATOR IN DECISION TO SEPARATE		NEW
	In your last ended cohabitation, who mostly initiated the separation, you or your partner?		
	1 You much more than your partner	322	40,9
	2 You to some extent more than your partner	79	10,0
	3 To the same extent	192	24,4
	4 Your partner to some extent more than you	85	20,8
	5 Your partner much more than you	109	13,8
	Total	787	100
	66 Unknown, Question not asked before 2000	769	
	77 Never cohabited	587	
	78 End of cohabitation due to death/other	222	
	79 Never ended a cohabitation	2044	
	88 Doesn't know	2	
	99 No answer	4	
Z320	NUMBER OF CLOSE FRIENDS		X251
	How many close friends would you say that you have? (Include friends at work, neighbours and relatives, but not family members.) This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	154	3,5
	1-4	1388	31,6
	5-9	1419	32,3
	10-14	884	20,1
	15-20	170	3,9
	20-24	208	4,7
	25-29	57	1,3
	30-34	53	1,2
	35-39	3	0,1
	40-44	18	0,4
	50-54	24	0,5
	60-64	2	0,0
	80-84	1	0,0
	97 More than 99 friends	13	0,3
	Total	4394	100
	999 No answer	21	

Z321**CLOSE FRIENDS – MEN****X253**

How many of your close friends are men? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.

0		971	22,9
1-4		1792	42,3
5-9		998	23,5
10-14		307	7,2
15-20		81	1,9
20-24		42	1,0
25-29		21	0,5
30-34		4	0,1
35-39		6	0,1
40-44		1	0,0
45-49		1	0,0
50-54		6	0,1
70-74		2	0,0
75-79		1	0,0
80-84		1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	4	0,1
	Total	4238	100
999	No answer	23	
	Not applicable	154	
		4415	

Z322**CLOSE FRIENDS – BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY****X254**

How many of your close friends were not born in Sweden? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.

0		2812	66,4
1-4		1127	26,6
5-9		177	4,2
10-14		69	1,6
15-20		22	0,5
20-24		9	0,2
25-29		9	0,2
30-34		3	0,1
50-54		2	0,0
75-79		1	0,0
80-84		1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	2	0,0
	Total	4234	100
999	No answer	27	
	Not applicable	154	
		4415	

Z323	CLOSE FRIENDS – UNEMPLOYED	X256
How many of your close friends are currently unemployed? This variable is divided into categories.		
The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.		
0		3433 81,7
1-4		694 16,5
5-9		52 1,2
10-14		14 0,3
15-20		5 0,1
20-24		2 0,0
25-29		1 0,0
30-34		2 0,0
97	More than 99 friends	1 0,0
	Total	4204 100
999	No answer	57
	Not applicable	154
		4415
Z324	SEES CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	X259
How often do you usually see some of these close friends (this friend)?		
The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.		
1	Several times a week	1338 31,6
2	About once a week	1211 28,6
3	1-3 times a week	1217 28,7
4	Less often	462 10,9
5	Never	11 0,3
	Total	4239 100
8	Doesn't know	18
9	No answer	4
	Not applicable	154
		4415
Z325	TELEPHONE CONTACT WITH CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	X260
How often do you usually talk to your close friends on the telephone?		
The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.		
1	Several times a week	1987 46,9
2	About once a week	1254 29,6
3	1-3 times a week	759 17,9
4	Less often	206 4,9
5	Never	31 0,7
	Total	4237 100
8	Doesn't know	20
9	No answer	4
	Not applicable	154

Z326	SEI CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Närmaste väns yrke enligt Socioekonomisk indelning (SEI).		
	The table is valid for Z320 GT 0.		
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	228 5,7
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	764 19,2
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	427 10,7
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	264 6,6
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	138 3,5
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	53 1,3
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	246 6,2
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	35 0,9
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	972 24,5
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	354 8,9
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	116 2,9
	60	Self-employed professionals	198 5,0
	79	Self-employed, number of employees unknown	133 3,3
	89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	45 1,1
		Total	3973 100
	77	Closest friend never worked	191
	99	No answer	97
		Not applicable	154
			4415
Z327	NYK80 CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.		
Z328	NYK85 CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.		
Z329	SSYK CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.		
Z330	ISCO88 CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.		

Z331	SIOPS CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.		
Z332	EGP CLOSEST FRIEND		NEW
	Profession/occupation for closest friend according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	198 5,0
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	470 11,8
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	984 24,8
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	522 13,1
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	485 12,2
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	133 3,3
	8	IVd Smallholders	45 1,1
	10	Vs Supervisors	57 1,4
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3 0,1
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	422 10,6
	13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	6 0,2
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	648 16,3
		Total	3973 100
	77	Closest friend never worked	191
	99	No answer	97
		Not applicable	154
			4415
Z342	YEARS OF EDUCATION, RESPONDENT		X261, Y131, U137, V229, W538
	How many years altogether have you been to school or vocational training full-time? (Include all education from elementary school on.)		
	0		4 0,1
	2		2 0,0
	3		3 0,1
	4		7 0,2
	5		9 0,2
	6		16 0,4
	7		152 3,4
	8		120 2,7
	9		275 6,2
	10		256 5,8
	11		436 9,9
	12		808 18,3
	13		466 10,6
	14		374 8,5
	15		382 8,7
	16		363 8,2
	17		302 6,8
	18		193 4,4
	19		87 2,0

20		63	1,4
21		27	0,6
22		31	0,7
23		12	0,3
24		9	0,2
25		5	0,1
26		3	0,1
27		2	0,0
28		1	0,0
33		1	0,0
35		1	0,0
	Total	4410	100
99	No answer	5	
		4415	

Z343	TOTAL VOCATIONAL EDUCATION, RESPONDENT		jfr Y133, U139, V231, jfr W833
	How many years, in total, was your fulltime vocational education?		
0		74	2,9
1		455	17,5
2		692	26,7
3		696	26,8
4		324	12,5
5		189	7,3
6		77	3,0
7		34	1,3
8		12	0,5
9		16	0,6
10		7	0,3
11		3	0,1
12		3	0,1
13		3	0,1
14		2	0,1
15		3	0,1
16		1	0,0
17		3	0,1
	Total	2592	100
77	Has no vocational education	1808	
99	No answer	15	
		4415	

Z344	HIGHEST COMPLETED EDUCATION IN SWEDEN		NEW
	Did you complete your highest education in Sweden?		
1	Yes	4027	91,4
2	No	380	8,6
	Total	4407	100
7	Has no completed education	5	
9	No answer	3	
		4415	

Z345**COUNTRY OF HIGHEST EDUCATION****NEW**

In what country did you complete your highest education?

The table is valid for Z344 EQ 2.

AFGHANISTAN	1	0,3
ALGERIA	2	0,5
AUSTRALIA	3	0,8
BANGLADESH	3	0,8
BELGIUM	1	0,3
BOLIVIA	1	0,3
BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA	17	4,5
BULGARIA	3	0,8
BURMA	1	0,3
BURUNDI	2	0,5
CHILE	4	1,1
COLOMBIA	1	0,3
DENMARK	19	5,0
ENGLAND	10	2,6
ERITREA	2	0,5
ESTONIA	1	0,3
ETHIOPIA	2	0,5
PHILLIPINES	2	0,5
FINLAND	35	9,3
FRANCE	4	1,1
GAMBIA	1	0,3
GEORGIA	1	0,3
GREECE	2	0,5
GUINEA	1	0,3
HOLLAND	2	0,5
INDIA	2	0,5
INDONESIA	1	0,3
IRAQ	36	9,5
IRAN	11	2,9
ICELAND	1	0,3
JAPAN	1	0,3
JORDAN	1	0,3
KAMERUN	1	0,3
KENYA	1	0,3
CHINA	6	1,6
KONGO, DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	1	0,3
KOREA, SOUTH-	2	0,5
KOSOVO	9	2,4
CROATIA	2	0,5
CUBA	1	0,3
KURDISTAN	1	0,3
LATVIA	2	0,5
LEBANON	10	2,6
LITHUANIA	1	0,3

	MADAGASCAR	1	0,3
	MACEDONIA	1	0,3
	MALAYSIA	2	0,5
	MOROCCO	1	0,3
	MONTENEGRO	1	0,3
	NORWAY	23	6,1
	NEW ZEALAND	1	0,3
	PAKISTAN	4	1,1
	PERU	2	0,5
	POLAND	19	5,0
	ROMANIA	6	1,6
	RUSSIA	5	1,3
	SWITZERLAND	3	0,8
	SENEGAL	1	0,3
	SERBIA	2	0,5
	SIERRA LEONE	1	0,3
	SLOVAKIA	1	0,3
	SOMALIA	5	1,3
	SPAIN	1	0,3
	GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND	8	2,1
	SUDAN	1	0,3
	SWEDEN	2	0,5
	SYRIA	5	1,3
	TANZANIA	1	0,3
	THAILAND	9	2,4
	CZECH REPUBLIC	1	0,3
	TUNISIA	2	0,5
	TURKEY	20	5,3
	GERMANY	16	4,2
	UGANDA	3	0,8
	HUNGARY	3	0,8
	URUGUAY	1	0,3
	USA	12	3,2
	VENEZUELA	2	0,5
	VIETNAM	1	0,3
	Total	378	100
888	Doesn't know	2	
	Not applicable	4035	
		4415	

Z346	YEARS OF EDUCATION ABROAD	Y157	
	How many years in total have you studied in country other than Sweden? Regards respondents who studied abroad.		
	0	106	12,1
	1	179	20,4
	2	59	6,7
	3	26	3,0
	4	27	3,1
	5	28	3,2

6		29	3,3
7		23	2,6
8		32	3,6
9		48	5,5
10		23	2,6
11		38	4,3
12		74	8,4
13		30	3,4
14		32	3,6
15		23	2,6
16		37	4,2
17		21	2,4
18		20	2,3
19		7	0,8
20		6	0,7
21		3	0,3
22		1	0,1
23		2	0,2
24		2	0,2
26		1	0,1
35		1	0,1
	Total	878	100
88	Doesn't know	7	
99	Doesn't know	3	
	Not applicable	3527	
		4415	

Z347

COUNTRY OF FOREIGN EDUCATION (not necessarily highest)

NEW

Country of foreign education.

AFGHANISTAN	3	0,3
ALGERIA	3	0,3
ARGENTINA	1	0,1
AUSTRALIA	17	1,9
BANGLADESH	6	0,7
BELGIUM	1	0,1
BOLIVIA	1	0,1
BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA	23	2,6
BRASILIA	4	0,5
BULGARIA	4	0,5
BURMA	1	0,1
BURUNDI	3	0,3
CHILE	11	1,2
COLOMBIA	1	0,1
DENMARK	30	3,4
EL SALVADOR	1	0,1
IVORY COAST	1	0,1
ENGLAND	57	6,5
ERITREA	4	0,5
ESTONIA	2	0,2

ETHIOPIA	4	0,5
PHILLIPINES	4	0,5
FINLAND	62	7,0
FRANCE	42	4,8
GAMBIA	2	0,2
GEORGIA	1	0,1
GREECE	5	0,6
GUATEMALA	1	0,1
GUINEA	1	0,1
HOLLAND	9	1,0
INDIA	6	0,7
INDONESIA	1	0,1
IRAQ	48	5,4
IRAN	29	3,3
IRELAND	4	0,5
ICELAND	2	0,2
ISRAEL	1	0,1
ITALY	5	0,6
JAPAN	6	0,7
JORDAN	2	0,2
YUGOSLAVIA	1	0,1
KAMBODJA	1	0,1
KAMERUN	2	0,2
CANADA	7	0,8
KENYA	1	0,1
CHINA	12	1,4
KONGO, DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	2	0,2
KOREA, SOUTH-	5	0,6
KOSOVO	11	1,2
CROATIA	3	0,3
CUBA	1	0,1
KURDISTAN	1	0,1
LATVIA	3	0,3
LEBANON	17	1,9
LITHUANIA	1	0,1
MADAGASCAR	1	0,1
MACEDONIA	5	0,6
MALAWI	1	0,1
MALAYSIA	2	0,2
MALTA	2	0,2
MOROCCO	2	0,2
MAURITIUS	1	0,1
MEXICO	2	0,2
MONTENEGRO	1	0,1
NETHERLANDS	2	0,2
NIGERIA	2	0,2
NORWAY	37	4,2
NEW ZEALAND	2	0,2
PAKISTAN	8	0,9
PALESTINE	1	0,1
PERU	4	0,5

POLAND	29	3,3
PORTUGAL	1	0,1
ROMANIA	7	0,8
RUSSIA	10	1,1
SAUDI ARABIA	2	0,2
SWITZERLAND	9	1,0
SENEGAL	2	0,2
SERBIA	6	0,7
SIERRA LEONE	2	0,2
SLOVAKIA	1	0,1
SOMALIA	7	0,8
SPAIN	25	2,8
GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND	15	1,7
SUDAN	4	0,5
SWEDEN	3	0,3
SYRIA	11	1,2
TANZANIA	1	0,1
THAILAND	12	1,4
CZECH REPUBLIC	4	0,5
TUNISIA	2	0,2
TURKEY	33	3,7
GERMANY	36	4,1
UGANDA	3	0,3
HUNGARY	5	0,6
URUGUAY	3	0,3
USA	86	9,7
UZBEKISTAN	1	0,1
VENEZUELA	3	0,3
VIETNAM	3	0,3
AUSTRIA	7	0,8
Total	883	100
888 Doesn't know	2	
Not applicable	3530	
	4415	

Z348

EDUCATIONAL LEVEL STUDIES ABROAD

Y158

Swedish educational level correspondent to highest education completed abroad.

0	Unfinished compulsory education	52	5,9
1	Lowest level of compulsory education	149	16,9
2	Vocational education, manual	76	8,6
3	Theoretical education at gymnasium level	169	19,2
4	Education after gymnasium, not university	101	11,5
5	University less than 3 years	175	19,8
6	University 3 years or longer, not post-graduate	148	16,8
7	Post-graduate education	12	1,4
	Total	882	100
8	Doesn't know	8	
	Not applicable	3525	
		4415	

Z349	MONTHS OF EDUCATION IN SWEDEN			jfr Y159
Number of months in school in Sweden. This variable is divided into categories.				
0		251	5,7	
1-59		165	3,8	
60-17		319	7,3	
108-131		477	10,8	
132-143		430	9,8	
144-155		755	17,2	
156-167		437	9,9	
168-186		697	15,8	
187-203		328	7,5	
≥204		539	12,3	
	Total	4398	100	
999	No answer	17		
		4415		
	Mean value	141,1		
	Standard deviation	55,9		
Z350	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL HIGHEST EDUCATION			NEW
Respondent's highest education according to Swedish standard classification of education (SUN, three-digit).				
0	Pre-school education	4	0,1	
100	Other/unspec pre-gymnasial education shorter than 9 years	48	1,1	
106	Folkskola	222	5,0	
200	Other/unspec pre-gymnasial education, 9 (10) years	22	0,5	
204	Realskola	25	0,6	
206	Grundskola, year 7-9	214	4,9	
310	Unspec gymnasium, shorter than two years	16	0,4	
312	Gymnasium shorter than two years, theoretical/prep. for higher studies, no graduation	19	0,4	
313	Gymnasium shorter than two years, vocational, no graduation	8	0,2	
316	Gymnasium shorter than two years, theoretical/prep. for higher studies.	3	0,1	
317	Gymnasium shorter than two years, vocational.	198	4,5	
319	Unknown vocational education, track unknown	88	2,0	
320	Unspec gymnasium, two years	85	1,9	
322	Gymnasium, two years, theoretical/prep. for higher studies, no graduation	24	0,5	
323	Gymnasium, two years, vocational, no graduation	21	0,5	
326	Gymnasium, two years, theoretical/prep. for higher studies.	98	2,2	
327	Gymnasium, two years, vocational.	583	13,2	
330	Unspec gymnasium, three years	39	0,9	
332	Gymnasium, three years, theoretical/prep. for higher studies, no graduation	31	0,7	
333	Gymnasium, three years, vocational, no graduation	39	0,9	
336	Gymnasium, three years, theoretical/prep. for higher	388	8,8	

	studies.		
337	Gymnasium, three years, vocational.	492	11,2
410	Unspec education higher than gymnasium, shorter than two years	8	0,2
412	University education, 20 credits	124	2,8
413	Gymnasium level additional education	82	1,9
415	Post-gymnasium education education shorter than two years - not university	60	1,4
417	University education shorter than two years, vocational	15	0,3
520	Unspec post-gymnasium education two years	42	1,0
522	University education, 80 credits - no graduation	37	0,8
525	Post-gymnasium education two years - not university	115	2,6
526	University education two years, general	19	0,4
527	University education two years, vocational	161	3,6
539	Unspec post-gymnasium education three years	18	0,4
532	University education, 120 credits - no graduation	95	2,2
535	Post-gymnasium education three years – not university	29	0,7
536	University education three years, general	154	3,5
537	University education three years, vocational	259	5,9
549	Unspec post-gymnasium education four years	17	0,4
545	Post-gymnasium education four years – not university	5	0,1
546	University education four years, general	102	2,3
547	University education four years, vocational	276	6,3
555	Post-gymnasium education at least two years - not university	2	0,0
556	University education five years or longer, general	9	0,2
557	University education five years or longer, vocational	60	1,4
600	Other/unspec post-graduation education	1	0,0
620	Half-time of a postgraduate education (licentiate)	8	0,2
640	Doctoral degree	47	1,1
	Total	4412	100
999	Okänd	3	
		4415	

Z352	HIGHEST EDUCATION – RESPONDENT			jfr X305, jfr Y164, jfr U138, jfr V230, jfr W537
	Respondent's educational level according to Swedish standard classification of education (SUN, eight-digit).			
0	Unfinished grundskola (basic education)	4	0,1	
1	Folkskola (basic education)	270	6,1	
2	Grundskola (basic education)	261	5,9	
3	Vocational education at level of gymnasium	1744	39,5	
4	Theoretical education at level of gymnasium	388	8,8	
5	Postgymnasium	941	21,3	
6	University degree	748	17,0	
7	Post-graduation education	56	1,3	
	Total	4412	100	
9	No answer	3		
		4415		

Z354	YEAR/MONTH COMPLETED HIGHEST EDUCATION		jfr Y166
	Year when respondent finished his/her highest completed education according to interview or registers (Statistics Sweden). This variable is divided into categories.		
	1950-59	48	1,4
	1960-69	189	5,6
	1970-79	408	12,1
	1980-89	716	21,2
	1990-99	728	21,6
	2000-09	1160	34,4
	≥2010	122	3,6
	Total	3371	100
	7777 Register information missing	998	
	8888 Doesn't know	28	
	9999 Missing information	18	
		4415	
Z355	STUDIES NOW: TYPE OF STUDIES		jfr Y168, jfr U568, jfr V596, jfr W368
	Respondent's current study situation.		
	1 Course in Swedish (SFI)	22	4,6
	2 Grundskola (compulsory education)/at level of Grundskola	2	0,4
	3 Gymnasium, prep. for higher studies	12	2,5
	4 Gymnasium, vocational	13	2,7
	5 Gymnasium, special school	1	0,2
	6 Gymnasium, track unknown	5	1,1
	7 Komvux, at level of gymnasium	53	11,2
	8 Active labour market education	10	2,1
	9 Separate university course	87	18,3
	10 University program (leading to graduation)	192	40,4
	11 Postgraduate studies	14	2,9
	12 Other education	64	13,5
	Total	475	100
	Not applicable	3940	
		4415	
Z359	NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT		X311, Y183, U478, V517, W293
	Approximately how many years altogether have you spent in gainful employment? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	136	3,2
	1-4	432	10,1
	5-9	449	10,5
	10-14	413	9,6
	15-19	406	9,5
	20-24	421	9,8
	25-29	389	9,1
	30-34	394	9,2

35-39		427	10,0
40-44		422	9,9
45-49		260	6,1
50-54		117	2,7
55-59		11	0,3
≥60		4	0,1
	Total	4281	100
88	Never had gainful employment	93	
98	Not applicable	13	
99	No answer	28	
		4415	

Z360

EVER WORKED 6 MONTHS

X312

Have you ever had a job that lasted at least 6 months?

1	Yes	4105	93,1
2	No	302	6,9
	Total	4407	100
9	No answer	8	
		4415	

Z361

COUNTRY OF FIRST JOB LASTING 6 MONTHS

NEW

Country of first job that lasted at least 6 months.

The table is valid for Z360 EQ 1.

AFGHANISTAN	1	0,0
ALGERIA	1	0,0
AUSTRALIA	1	0,0
BANGLADESH	3	0,1
BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA	8	0,2
BRASILIA	1	0,0
BULGARIA	2	0,1
CHILE	1	0,0
DENMARK	11	0,3
IVORY COAST	1	0,0
ENGLAND	10	0,2
ESTONIA	1	0,0
ETHIOPIA	3	0,1
PHILLIPINES	1	0,0
FINLAND	8	0,2
FRANCE	3	0,1
GUINEA	1	0,0
HOLLAND	3	0,1
INDIA	1	0,0
INDONESIA	1	0,0
IRAQ	27	0,7
IRAN	5	0,1
IRELAND	1	0,0

ICELAND	2	0,1
ITALY	1	0,0
KAMBODJA	1	0,0
KENYA	1	0,0
CHINA	3	0,1
KONGO, DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	1	0,0
KOSOVO	8	0,2
CUBA	1	0,0
LATVIA	3	0,1
LEBANON	5	0,1
LITHUANIA	1	0,0
MADAGASCAR	1	0,0
MACEDONIA	1	0,0
MOROCCO	1	0,0
NIGERIA	1	0,0
NORWAY	17	0,4
PERU	1	0,0
POLAND	7	0,2
ROMANIA	6	0,2
RUSSIA	3	0,1
SWITZERLAND	6	0,2
SIERRA LEONE	1	0,0
SOMALIA	4	0,1
SPAIN	1	0,0
GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND	2	0,1
SWEDEN	3890	94,8
SYRIA	2	0,1
THAILAND	10	0,2
CZECH REPUBLIC	1	0,0
TUNISIA	1	0,0
TURKEY	6	0,2
GERMANY	8	0,2
UGANDA	1	0,0
HUNGARY	1	0,0
URUGUAY	2	0,1
USA	6	0,2
UZBEKISTAN	1	0,0
VENEZUELA	1	0,0
AUSTRIA	1	0,0
Total	4105	
Not applicable	310	
	4415	

Z362	YEAR/MONTH START OF FIRST JOB ABROAD			NEW
	Year and month when first job in country other than Sweden started. This variable is divided into categories.			
	1950-59	4	1,9	
	1960-69	14	6,7	
	1970-69	19	9,0	
	1980-89	50	23,8	
	1990-99	64	30,5	
	≥2000	60	28,1	
	Total	211	100	
999999	No answer	4		
	Not applicable	4200		
		4415		
Z363	YEAR/MONTH END OF FIRST JOB ABROAD			NEW
	Year and month when first job in country other than Sweden ended. This variable is divided into categories.			
	1950-59	2	1,0	
	1960-69	7	3,5	
	1970-69	11	5,5	
	1980-89	34	16,9	
	1990-99	64	31,8	
	≥2000	83	41,3	
	Total	201	100	
999999	No answer	10		
777777	Pågående	4		
	Not applicable	4200		
		4415		
Z364	YEAR/MONTH START OF LAST JOB ABROAD			NEW
	Year and month when last job in country other than Sweden started. This variable is divided into categories.			
	1950-59	1	1,0	
	1960-69	2	2,0	
	1970-69	6	6,1	
	1980-89	8	8,1	
	1990-99	39	39,4	
	≥2000	43	43,4	
	Total	99	100	
999999	No answer	2		
	Not applicable	4314		
		4415		

Z365	YEAR/MONTH END OF LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW	
	Year and month when last job in other country than Sweden ended. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1960-69	1	1,1
	1970-69	1	1,1
	1980-89	6	6,6
	1990-99	18	19,8
	≥2000	65	71,4
	Total	91	100
	777777 Ongoing	9	
	999999 No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4314	
		4415	

Z366	COUNTRY OF LAST JOB ABROAD	NEW	
	Country of last job in country other than Sweden.		
	AFGHANISTAN	1	0,0
	ANGOLA	1	0,0
	BANGLADESH	3	0,1
	BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA	1	0,0
	BRASILIA	1	0,0
	BULGARIA	1	0,0
	CHILE	1	0,0
	DENMARK	10	0,2
	ENGLAND	4	0,1
	ETHIOPIA	2	0,1
	FINLAND	1	0,0
	FRANCE	2	0,1
	UNITED ARAB EMIRATES	1	0,0
	HOLLAND	2	0,1
	INDONESIA	1	0,0
	IRAQ	4	0,1
	IRAN	3	0,1
	ICELAND	1	0,0
	CAP VERDE	1	0,0
	KENYA	1	0,0
	CHINA	1	0,0
	KOSOVO	2	0,1
	LATVIA	3	0,1
	LEBANON	3	0,1
	MACEDONIA	1	0,0
	MOROCCO	1	0,0
	NORWAY	10	0,2
	PERU	1	0,0
	POLAND	2	0,1
	ROMANIA	3	0,1
	RUSSIA	1	0,0
	SAUDI ARABIA	1	0,0

	SWITZERLAND	2	0,1
	SOMALIA	1	0,0
	SOUTH AFRICA	1	0,0
	SYRIA	2	0,1
	THAILAND	7	0,2
	TURKEY	3	0,1
	GERMANY	7	0,2
	UGANDA	1	0,0
	HUNGARY	2	0,1
	USA	3	0,1
	UZBEKISTAN	1	0,0
	Total	101	100,0
	Not applicable	4314	
		4415	

Z367	BEGAN WORKING (IN SWEDEN): YEAR	X313, Y184, jfr U144	
	What year and month did you begin your first job that lasted at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1940-49	9	0,2
	1950-59	408	10,2
	1960-69	640	16,0
	1970-79	739	18,4
	1980-89	765	19,1
	1990-99	685	17,1
	2000-2009	732	18,2
	2010	34	0,8
	Total	4012	100
	999999 No answer	23	0,2
	Not applicable	380	
	Total	4415	

Z368	STILL AT FIRST JOB (IF AT LEAST 6 MONTHS OF DURATION)	X314, jfr Y185	
	Do you still have the same position at the same workplace today?		
	1 Yes	536	13,3
	2 No	3480	86,7
	Total	4016	100
	No answer	17	
	Not applicable	382	
		4415	

Z369	TIME IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	X315, Y186, jfr U478	
	Total number of months in gainful employment from the first job that lasted at least 6 months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.		
	6-99	719	19,2
	100-199	730	19,5
	200-299	619	16,5

998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
999	No answer	16
		4415
	Mean value	4,3
	Standard deviation	15,3

Z372

LAST UNEMPLOYED AT LEAST 1 MONTH, YEAR

Y191

If you have ever been unemployed for at least 1 month, when did that happen? This variable is divided into categories.

0	Not unemployed	2678	70,7
1955-60		5	0,1
1960-64		6	0,2
1965-69		12	0,3
1970-74		17	0,4
1975-79		17	0,4
1980-84		41	1,1
1985-89		56	1,5
1990-94		115	3,0
1995-99		235	6,2
2000-04		189	5,0
2005-09		202	5,3
≥2010		215	5,7
	Total	3788	100
9995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
9997	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
9998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
9999	No answer	12	
		4415	

Z373

NUMBER OF TIMES UNEMPLOYED AT LEAST 1 MONTH

Y192

Number of times the respondent has been unemployed for at least one month. This variable is divided into categories

0	2678	70,5
1	631	16,6
2	234	6,2
3	115	3,0
4	61	1,6
5	28	0,7
6	21	0,6
7	12	0,3
8	6	0,2
9	7	0,2
11	1	0,0
12	2	0,1
13	1	0,0
15	1	0,0

	Mean value	80,2
	Standard deviation	111,5

Z376	SENIORITY, CURRENT JOB, MONTHS		X324, Y196
	Number of months that respondent has had his/her current job, according to the occupational biography. Here this variable is divided into categories. Regards only employees.		
	1-99	1467	60,4
	100-199	574	23,6
	200-299	238	9,8
	300-399	96	4,0
	400-499	47	1,9
	500-599	7	0,3
	600-699	1	0,0
	Total	2430	100
	994 Not employed at interview	1392	
	995 Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	5	
	997 Never worked ≥ 6 months	444	
	998 Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	124	
	999 No answer	20	
		4415	
	Mean value	64,5	
	Standard deviation	98,2	

Z377	NUMBER OF GAINFUL EMPLOYMENTS, TOTAL		X325, Y197
	Total number of gainful employments from the first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography.		
	1	266	7,0
	2	389	10,3
	3	456	12,0
	4	506	13,3
	5	465	12,3
	6	378	10,0
	7	357	9,4
	8	264	7,0
	9	188	5,0
	10	161	4,2
	11	115	3,0
	12	73	1,9
	13	57	1,5
	14	44	1,2
	15	25	0,7
	16	11	0,3
	17	11	0,3
	18	9	0,2
	19	10	0,3
	20	5	0,1
	21	1	0,0

Z379**NUMBER OF EMPLOYMENTS****Y201**

Total number of employments from the first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography.

0		29	0,8
1		458	12,1
2		577	15,2
3		606	15,9
4		521	13,7
5		453	11,9
6		337	8,9
7		250	6,6
8		184	4,8
9		114	3,0
10		100	2,6
11		61	1,6
12		35	0,9
13		23	0,6
14		15	0,4
15		10	0,3
16		8	0,2
17		8	0,2
18		4	0,1
19		4	0,1
20		1	0,0
23		1	0,0
24		1	0,0
	Total	3800	100
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
		4415	

Z380**TIME AWAY FROM GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS****X329, Y202**

Total number of months without gainful employment since first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0		845	22,4
1-99		2332	61,9
100-199		418	11,1
200-299		131	3,5
300-399		32	0,8
400-499		7	0,2
500-599		3	0,1
	Total	3768	100
995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
997	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
999	No answer	32	
		4415	

Mean value	21,7
Standard deviation	57,4

Z381 **TIME IN PARENTAL LEAVE, MONTHS** **Y203**

Total number of months in parental leave since first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0		2661	70,0
1		33	0,9
2		23	0,6
3		29	0,8
4		13	0,3
5		19	0,5
6		34	0,9
7		38	1,0
8		26	0,7
9		25	0,7
10-19		320	8,4
20-29		214	5,6
30-39		173	4,6
40-49		87	2,3
50-59		52	1,4
60-69		26	0,7
70-79		10	0,3
80-89		2	0,1
90-99		4	0,1
100-149		6	0,2
≥150		4	0,1
	Total	3799	
995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
997	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
999	No answer	1	
		4415	
	Mean value	6,3	
	Standard deviation	13,9	

Z382 **TIME IN HOUSEHOLD WORK, MONTHS** **Y204**

Total number of months in household work since first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0		3405	89,6
2		6	0,2
3		11	0,3
4		9	0,2
5		4	0,1
6		8	0,2

7		6	0,2
8		1	0,0
9		8	0,2
10-19		54	1,4
20-29		32	0,8
30-39		26	0,7
40-49		21	0,6
50-59		23	0,6
60-69		18	0,5
70-79		24	0,6
80-89		14	0,4
90-99		10	0,3
100-149		66	1,7
150-199		23	0,6
200-249		18	0,5
250-299		7	0,2
≥300		5	0,1
	Totalt	3799	100
995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
997	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
999	No answer	1	
		4415	
	Mean value	6,8	
	Standard deviation	28,6	

Z383

TIME IN SCHOOL, MONTHS

Y205

Total number of months in school since first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0	2257	59,5
1	18	0,5
2	21	0,6
3	20	0,5
4	38	1,0
5	40	1,1
6	35	0,9
7	18	0,5
8	18	0,5
9	35	0,9
10-19	336	8,9
20-29	262	6,9
30-39	222	5,8
40-49	173	4,6
50-59	116	3,1
60-69	87	2,3
70-79	38	1,0
80-89	20	0,5
90-99	19	0,5

100-149		21	0,6
≥150		1	0,0
	Total	3795	100
995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
997	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
999	No answer	5	
		4415	
	Mean value	11,2	
	Standard deviation	19,5	

Z384	NUMBER OF TIMES IN SCHOOL, MONTHS			Y206
	Total number of periods in school.			
	0	2254	59,3	
	1	890	23,4	
	2	346	9,1	
	3	142	3,7	
	4	86	2,3	
	5	39	1,0	
	6	22	0,6	
	7	10	0,3	
	8	8	0,2	
	9	1	0,0	
	10	1	0,0	
	12	1	0,0	
	Total	3800	100	
	95 Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6		
	97 Never worked ≥6 months	480		
	98 Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129		
		4415		

Z385	NUMBER OF TIMES AWAY FROM WORK, AT LEAST 1 MONTH			Y207
	Total number of periods away from work.			
	0	834	21,9	
	1	797	21,0	
	2	662	17,4	
	3	506	13,3	
	4	339	8,9	
	5	222	5,8	
	6	116	3,1	
	7	83	2,2	
	8	82	2,2	
	9	46	1,2	
	10	30	0,8	
	11	19	0,5	
	12	20	0,5	

13		14	0,4
14		10	0,3
15		6	0,2
16		3	0,1
17		3	0,1
18		1	0,0
19		1	0,0
20		3	0,1
21		3	0,1
	Total	3800	100
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
		4415	

Z386

LAST TIME AWAY FROM WORK, YEAR

Y208

Year when respondent last was away from work. This variable is divided into categories.

0		833	30,1
1955-59		2	0,1
1960-64		6	0,2
1965-69		27	1,0
1970-74		60	2,2
1975-79		74	2,7
1980-84		103	3,7
1985-89		136	4,9
1990-94		235	8,5
1995-99		361	13,0
2000-04		325	11,7
2005-09		453	16,4
≥ 2010		153	5,5
	Total	2768	100
9993	Not in gainful employment at interview	1069	
9995	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	5	
9997	Never worked ≥ 6 months	444	
9998	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	124	
9999	No answer	5	
		4415	

Z387

SEI AGE 25

X336, Y209

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	285	8,9
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	731	22,7
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	450	14,0
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	187	5,8
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	281	8,7
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	49	1,5

36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	298	9,3
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	59	1,8
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	535	16,6
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	175	5,4
57	Professional, upper-level executive	6	0,2
60	Self-employed professionals	52	1,6
71	Self-employed without employees	22	0,7
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	19	0,6
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	1	0,0
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	4	0,1
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	36	1,1
86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	2	0,1
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	15	0,5
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	7	0,2
	Total	3214	100
90	Not started working at 25	325	
91	Not 25 yet at interview	249	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	Unclassified	12	
		4415	
Z388	NYK80 AGE 25		Y210
Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z389	NYK85 AGE 25		NEW
Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z394	EGP AGE 25		Y211
Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.			
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	77	2,4
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	159	5,0
3	II Lower-grade professionals	579	18,1
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	489	15,3
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	621	19,4
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	20	0,6
9	IVd Smallholders	25	0,8
10	Vs Supervisors	59	1,8
11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3	0,1
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	461	14,4
13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	6	0,2
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	677	21,1
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	28	0,9
	Total	3204	100

	90	Not started working at 25	325	
	91	Not 25 yet at interview	249	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	22	
			4415	
Z395	SECTOR AGE 25			Y212
	Sector of the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.			
	1	Public sector	1002	34,0
	2	Private sector	1946	66,0
		Total	2948	100
	3	Self-employed or farmer	131	
	90	Not started working at 25	325	
	91	Not 25 yet at interview	248	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	87	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	148	
			4415	
Z396	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 25			X341, Y213
	Type of main activity at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.			
	1	Employed	2422	75,2
	2	Self-employed	97	3,0
	3	Farmer	21	0,7
	4	Unemployed	52	1,6
	5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	6	0,2
	6	Studying	302	9,4
	7	Military service	1	0,0
	8	Parental leave	140	4,3
	9	Housework	133	4,1
	10	Pensioner	1	0,0
	11	Other	36	1,1
	12	Abroad	10	0,3
	13	Unknown	2	0,0
		Total	3221	100
	90	Not started working at 25	325	
	91	Not 25 yet at interview	248	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	6	
			4415	

Z399**SEI AGE 30****X347, Y215**

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	210	6,7
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	555	17,7
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	377	12,0
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	184	5,9
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	211	6,7
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	48	1,5
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	290	9,3
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	52	1,7
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	606	19,4
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	284	9,1
57	Professional, upper-level executive	35	1,1
60	Self-employed professionals	97	3,1
71	Self-employed without employees	37	1,2
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	40	1,3
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	3	0,1
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	5	0,2
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	72	2,3
86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	2	0,1
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	14	0,4
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	9	0,3
	Total	3131	100
90	Not started working at 30	121	
91	Not 30 yet at interview	535	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	Unclassified	13	
		4415	

Z400**NYK80 AGE 30****Y216**

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.

Z401**NYK85 AGE 30****NEW**

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.

Z406	EGP AGE 30		Y217
	Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	137	4,4
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	285	9,1
3	II Lower-grade professionals	650	20,8
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	490	15,7
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	461	14,8
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	28	0,9
9	IVd Smallholders	22	0,7
10	Vs Supervisors	64	2,1
11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3	0,1
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	406	13,0
13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	5	0,2
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	550	17,6
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	18	0,6
	Total	3119	100
90	Not started working at 30	121	
91	Not 30 yet at interview	535	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	25	
		4415	
Z407	SECTOR AGE 30		Y218
	Sector of the last gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Public sector	1072	38,3
2	Private sector	1726	61,7
	Total	2798	100
3	Self-employed or farmer	235	
90	Not started working at 30	121	
91	Not 30 yet at interview	535	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
87	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	111	
		4415	
Z408	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 30		X352, Y219
	Type of main activity at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Employed	2417	77,0
2	Self-employed	189	6,0
3	Farmer	26	0,8
4	Unemployed	55	1,8
5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	2	0,1

1	Respondent only	54	2,0
2	2-9 employees	436	16,3
3	10-19	339	12,7
4	20-49	492	18,4
5	50-99	347	13,0
6	100-499	529	19,8
7	500-999	161	6,0
8	1000-w	320	11,9
	Total	2678	100
90	Not started working at 30	121	
91	Not 30 yet at interview	535	
94	Self-employed or farmer	234	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	232	

Z411 SEI AGE 35 X358, Y221

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	183	6,4
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	443	15,5
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	288	10,1
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	164	5,7
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	171	6,0
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	60	2,1
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	237	8,3
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	54	1,9
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	577	20,2
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	297	10,4
57	Professional, upper-level executive	72	2,5
60	Self-employed professionals	98	3,4
71	Self-employed without employees	39	1,4
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	44	1,5
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	8	0,3
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	7	0,2
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	92	3,2
86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	4	0,1
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	14	0,5
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	8	0,3
	Total	2860	100
90	Not started working at 35	54	
91	Not 35 yet at interview	877	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	Unclassified	9	
		4415	

Z412	NYK80 AGE 35	Y222
Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z413	NYK85 AGE 35	NEW
Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z418	EGP AGE 35	Y223
Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	128 4,5
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	356 12,5
3	II Lower-grade professionals	622 21,8
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	429 15,1
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	365 12,8
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	37 1,3
9	IVd Smallholders	24 0,8
10	Vs Supervisors	81 2,8
11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3 0,1
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	320 11,2
13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	6 0,2
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	462 16,2
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	17 0,6
	Total	2850 100
90	Not started working at 35	54
91	Not 35 yet at interview	877
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
99	No answer	19
		4415
Z419	SECTOR AGE 35	Y224
Sector of the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Public sector	1051 41,8
2	Private sector	1461 58,2
	Total	2512 100
3	Self-employed or farmer	278
90	Not started working at 35	54
91	Not 35 yet at interview	877
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
87	Never worked ≥6 months	480
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
99	No answer	79
		4415

Z420	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 35	X363, Y225	
	Type of main activity at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
1	Employed	2282	79,6
2	Self-employed	228	8,0
3	Farmer	29	1,0
4	Unemployed	44	1,5
5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	2	0,1
6	Studying	88	3,1
8	Parental leave	87	3,0
9	Housework	71	2,5
10	Pensioner	8	0,3
11	Other	23	0,8
12	Abroad	4	0,1
13	Unknown	1	0,0
	Total	2867	100
90	Not started working at 35	54	
91	Not 35 yet at interview	877	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	2	
		4415	
Z421	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 35	X364, Y226	
	Age when respondent last had a gainful employment, at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
15		1	0,0
19		2	0,1
20		4	0,1
21		9	0,3
22		6	0,2
23		6	0,2
24		13	0,5
25		10	0,3
26		7	0,2
27		12	0,4
28		6	0,2
29		12	0,4
30		17	0,6
31		14	0,5
32		28	1,0
33		28	1,0
34		78	2,7
35		2609	91,2
	Total	2862	100
90	Not started working at 35	54	

91	Not 35 yet at interview	877
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
99	No answer	7
		4415

Z422

SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 35

NEW

Number of employees in the workplace of the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Respondent only	43	1,9
2	2-9 employees	343	14,9
3	10-19	294	12,8
4	20-49	444	19,3
5	50-99	291	12,6
6	100-499	460	20,0
7	500-999	153	6,6
8	1000-w	277	12,0
	Total	2305	100
90	Not started working at 35	54	
91	Not 35 yet at interview	877	
94	Företagare el jordbrukare	275	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	289	
		4415	

Z423

SEI AGE 40

X369, Y227

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	145	5,8
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	410	16,5
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	218	8,8
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	152	6,1
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	128	5,2
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	47	1,9
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	210	8,5
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	49	2,0
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	475	19,1
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	280	11,3
57	Professional, upper-level executive	80	3,2
60	Self-employed professionals	76	3,1
71	Self-employed without employees	39	1,6
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	44	1,8
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	8	0,3
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	6	0,2

	79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	92	3,7
	86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	3	0,1
	87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	14	0,6
	89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	7	0,3
		Total	2483	100
	90	Not started working at 40	25	
	91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	Unclassified	6	
			4415	
Z424		NYK80 AGE 40		Y228
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z425		NYK85 AGE 40		NEW
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z430		EGP AGE 40		Y229
		Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	101	4,1
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	352	14,2
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	513	20,7
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	378	15,3
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	285	11,5
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	42	1,7
	9	IVd Smallholders	22	0,9
	10	Vs Supervisors	83	3,4
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	2	0,1
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	251	10,1
	13	VJj Skilled manual workers in primary production	4	0,2
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	430	17,4
	15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	11	0,4
		Total	2474	100
	90	Not started working at 40	25	
	91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	15	
			4415	

Z431	SECTOR AGE 40			Y230
Sector of the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.				
1	Public sector	941		43,5
2	Private sector	1222		56,5
	Total	2163		100
3	Self-employed or farmer	271		
90	Not started working at 40	25		
91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286		
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6		
87	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480		
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129		
99	No answer	55		
		4415		

Z432	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 40			X374, Y231
Type of main activity at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.				
1	Employed	2042		82,1
2	Self-employed	227		9,1
3	Farmer	27		1,1
4	Unemployed	35		1,4
6	Studying	59		2,4
8	Parental leave	25		1,0
9	Housework	27		1,1
10	Pensioner	20		0,8
11	Other	22		0,9
12	Abroad	4		0,2
	Total	2488		100
90	Not started working at 40	25		
91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286		
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6		
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480		
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129		
99	No answer	1		
		4415		

Z433	AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 40			X375, Y232
Age when respondent last had a gainful employment, at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.				
19		2		0,1
20		2		0,1
21		4		0,2
22		2		0,1
23		2		0,1
24		4		0,2
25		4		0,2

26		3	0,1
27		4	0,2
28		1	0,1
29		3	0,1
30		5	0,2
31		3	0,1
32		7	0,3
33		6	0,2
34		10	0,4
35		5	0,2
36		9	0,4
37		14	0,6
38		20	0,8
39		56	2,3
40		2318	93,3
	Total	2484	100
90	Not started working at 40	25	
91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	5	
		4415	

Z434

SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 40

NEW

Number of employees in the workplace of the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Respondent only	33	1,7
2	2-9 employees	281	14,7
3	10-19	260	13,6
4	20-49	347	18,2
5	50-99	245	12,8
6	100-499	369	19,3
7	500-999	131	6,9
8	1000-w	243	12,7
	Total	1909	100
90	Not started working at 40	25	
91	Not 40 yet at interview	1286	
94	Företagare el jordbrukare	270	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	310	
		4415	

Z435	SEI AGE 45		X380, Y233
	Number of employees in the workplace of the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	122 5,8
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	318 15,1
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	188 8,9
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	135 6,4
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	106 5,0
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	39 1,9
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	183 8,7
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	43 2,0
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	402 19,1
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	242 11,5
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	78 3,7
	60	Self-employed professionals	56 2,7
	71	Self-employed without employees	34 1,6
	72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	39 1,9
	73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	7 0,3
	74	Self-employed 20+ employees	6 0,3
	79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	87 4,1
	86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	3 0,1
	87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	10 0,5
	89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	10 0,5
		Total	100
	90	Not started working at 45	5
	91	Not 45 yet at interview	1684
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
	97	Never worked ≥6 months	480
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
	99	No answer	3
			4415
Z436	NYK80 AGE 45		Y234
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z437	NYK85 AGE 45		NEW
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z442	EGP AGE 45		Y235
	Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	77 3,7
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	316 15,0
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	436 20,7

4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	337	16,0
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	226	10,7
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	38	1,8
9	IVd Smallholders	18	0,9
10	Vs Supervisors	71	3,4
11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3	0,1
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	210	10,0
13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	5	0,2
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	357	17,0
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	9	0,4
	Total	2103	100
90	Not started working at 45	5	
91	Not 45 yet at interview	1684	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	8	
		4415	

Z443

SECTOR AGE 45

Y236

Sector of the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Public sector	829	45,4
2	Private sector	995	54,6
	Total	1824	100
3	Self-employed or farmer	253	
90	Not started working at 45	5	
91	Not 45 yet at interview	1684	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
87	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	34	
		4415	

Z444

TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 45

X385, Y237

Type of main activity at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Employed	1707	80,9
2	Self-employed	215	10,2
3	Farmer	26	1,2
4	Unemployed	43	2,0
5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	2	0,1
6	Studying	30	1,4
8	Parental leave	3	0,1
9	Housework	18	0,9
10	Pensioner	34	1,6
11	Other	30	1,4
12	Abroad	3	0,1
	Total	2111	100

Z446**SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 45****NEW**

Number of employees in the workplace of the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Respondent only	24	1,6
2	2-9 employees	235	15,6
3	10-19	197	13,1
4	20-49	299	19,9
5	50-99	211	14,0
6	100-499	276	18,3
7	500-999	85	5,6
8	1000-w	179	11,9
	Total	1506	100
90	Not started working at 45	5	
91	Not 45 yet at interview	1684	
94	Företagare el jordbrukare	253	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	352	
		4415	

Z447**SEI AGE 50****X391, Y239**

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	103	6,0
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	248	14,5
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	146	8,5
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	108	6,3
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	76	4,4
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	32	1,9
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	150	8,8
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	42	2,5
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	309	18,1
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	209	12,2
57	Professional, upper-level executive	77	4,5
60	Self-employed professionals	41	2,4
71	Self-employed without employees	27	1,6
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	33	1,9
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	5	0,3
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	7	0,4
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	78	4,6
86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	3	0,2
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	8	0,5
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	7	0,4
	Total	1709	100
90	Not started working at 50	3	
91	Not 50 yet at interview	2086	

	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	Unclassified	2	
			4415	
Z448	NYK80 AGE 50			Y240
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z449	NYK85 AGE 50			NEW
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z454	EGP AGE 50			Y241
	Class (EGP) for the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.			
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	58	3,4
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	286	16,8
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	342	20,0
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	282	16,5
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	164	9,6
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	23	1,3
	9	IVd Smallholders	17	1,0
	10	Vs Supervisors	60	3,5
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3	0,2
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	168	9,8
	13	Vlj Skilled manual workers in primary production	2	0,1
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	291	17,1
	15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	10	0,6
		Total	1706	100
	90	Not started working at 50	3	
	91	Not 50 yet at interview	2086	
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	5	
			4415	
Z455	SECTOR AGE 50			Y242
	Sector of the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.			
	1	Public sector	699	47,2
	2	Private sector	781	52,8
		Total	1480	100
	3	Self-employed or farmer	209	
	90	Not started working at 50	3	

91	Not 50 yet at interview	2086
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
87	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
99	No answer	22
		4415

Z456 **TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 50** **X396, Y243**

Type of main activity at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Employed	1381	80,7
2	Self-employed	176	10,3
3	Farmer	23	1,3
4	Unemployed	29	1,7
5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	3	0,2
6	Studying	10	0,6
8	Parental leave	1	0,1
9	Housework	9	0,5
10	Pensioner	52	3,0
11	Other	25	1,5
12	Abroad	2	0,1
	Total	1711	100
90	Not started working at 50	3	
91	Not 50 yet at interview	2086	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
		4415	

Z457 **AGE AT LAST JOB AGE 50** **X397, Y244**

Age when respondent last had a gainful employment, at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

19	1	0,1
20	2	0,1
21	1	0,1
29	1	0,1
30	2	0,1
34	2	0,1
35	1	0,1
36	2	0,1
37	2	0,1
38	1	0,1
39	5	0,3
40	2	0,1
41	5	0,3
42	7	0,4
43	8	0,5
44	12	0,7

45		6	0,4
46		11	0,6
47		13	0,8
48		21	1,2
49		15	0,9
50		1587	93,0
	Total	1707	100
90	Not started working at 50	3	
91	Not 50 yet at interview	2086	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	4	
		4415	

Z458**SIZE OF WORKPLACE AGE 50****NEW**

Number of employees in the workplace of the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

1	Respondent only	24	1,6
2	2-9 employees	235	15,6
3	10-19	197	13,1
4	20-49	299	19,9
5	50-99	211	14,0
6	100-499	276	18,3
7	500-999	85	5,6
8	1000-w	179	11,9
	Total	1506	100
90	Not started working at 50	5	
91	Not 50 yet at interview	1684	
94	Self-employed or farmer	253	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	315	
		4415	

Z459**SEI FIRST JOB ABROAD****NEW**

Socioekonomisk grupp (SEI) för det första innehavda förvärvsarbetet i annat land än Sverige, enligt sysselsättningsbiografen.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	18	8,5
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	49	23,1
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	28	13,2
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	12	5,7
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	13	6,1
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	3	1,4
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	23	10,8
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	3	1,4

	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	32	15,1
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	15	7,1
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	1	0,5
	60	Self-employed professionals	10	4,7
	79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	2	0,9
	89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	3	1,4
		Total	212	100
	94	No work abroad	4081	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
	99	Unclassified	3	
			4415	
Z460		NYK80 FIRST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the first gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z461		NYK85 FIRST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the first gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z462		EGP FIRST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Class (EGP) for the first gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography.		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	10	4,7
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	16	7,5
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	33	15,5
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	36	16,9
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	51	23,9
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	2	0,9
	9	IVd Smallholders	3	1,4
	10	Vs Supervisors	4	1,9
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	28	13,1
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	30	14,1
		Total	213	100
	94	No work abroad	4081	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
	99	No answer	2	
		Total	4415	
Z463		FIRM SIZE (SELF-EMPLOYED) FIRST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Number of employees in own firm for the first job in country other than Sweden.		
	1	None	4	44,4
	2	1-9 employees	5	55,6
		Total	9	100

	3	Not self-employed	190	
	94	No work abroad	4081	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
	99	No answer	16	
			4415	
Z464		SEI LAST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography.		
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	17	8,1
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	48	22,9
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	21	10,0
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	10	4,8
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	11	5,2
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	4	1,9
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	21	10,0
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	2	1,0
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	33	15,7
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	18	8,6
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	4	1,9
	60	Self-employed professionals	12	5,7
	79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	8	3,8
	89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	1	0,5
		Total	210	100
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
	99	Unclassified	5	
		Not applicable	4081	
			4415	
Z465		NYK80 LAST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z466		NYK85 LAST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for the last gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.		
Z467		EGP LAST JOB ABROAD		NEW
		Class (EGP) classification for the last gainful employment in country other than Sweden, according to the occupational biography.		
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	10	4,7
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	16	7,5
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	33	15,5

4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	36	16,9
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	51	23,9
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	2	0,9
9	IVd Smallholders	3	1,4
10	Vs Supervisors	4	1,9
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	28	13,1
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	30	14,1
	Total	213	100
94	No work abroad	4081	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
99	No answer	2	
	Total	4415	

Z468	FIRM SIZE (SELF-EMPLOYED) LAST JOB ABROAD		NEW
	Number of employees in own firm for the last job in country other than Sweden.		
1	None	9	69,2
2	1-9 employees	4	30,8
	Total	13	100
3	Not self-employed	191	
94	No work abroad	4081	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	119	
99	No answer	11	
		4415	

Z469	SEI FIRST JOB		X402, Y245
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for respondent's first job that lasted at least six months, according to the occupational biography.		
11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	519	13,7
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	1167	30,8
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	510	13,5
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	233	6,2
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	349	9,2
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	22	0,6
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	240	6,3
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	35	0,9
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	445	11,8
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	176	4,6
57	Professional, upper-level executive	5	0,1
60	Self-employed professionals	51	1,3
71	Self-employed without employees	8	0,2
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	1	0
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	1	0
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	18	0,5
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	1	0,0
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	4	0,1
	Total	3785	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	

	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	Unclassified	15	
			4415	
Z470	NYK80 FIRST JOB			X403, Y246
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's first job lasting at least six months, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z471	NYK85 FIRST JOB			X404
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's first job lasting at least six months, according to the occupational biography. Not shown.			
Z476	EGP FIRST JOB			X405, Y247
	Class (EGP) for respondent's first job that lasted at least six months, according to the occupational biography.			
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	69	1,8
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	164	4,3
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	471	12,5
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	451	11,9
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	910	24,1
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	9	0,2
	9	IVd Smallholders	6	0,2
	10	Vs Supervisors	37	1,0
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	1	0,0
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	496	13,1
	13	Vlj Skilled manual workers in primary production	20	0,5
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	1068	28,3
	15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	76	2,0
		Total	3778	100
	95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
	97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
	98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
	99	No answer	22	
			4415	
Z479	SIZE OF WORKPLACE FIRST JOB			jfr Y249
	Number of employees in the workplace of respondent's first job that lasted at least six months.			
	1	Respondent only	142	4,1
	2	2-9 employees	807	23,3
	3	10-19	528	15,2
	4	20-49	595	17,1
	5	50-99	337	9,7
	6	100-499	573	16,5
	7	500-999	179	5,2
	8	1000-w	309	8,9

		Total	3470	100
94		Self-employed or farmer	51	
95		Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97		Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98		Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99		No answer	279	
			4415	
Z480		SECTOR FIRST JOB		Y250
		Sector of respondent's first job that lasted at least six months, according to the occupational biography.		
1		Public sector	1125	30,3
2		Private sector	2586	69,7
		Total	3711	100
3		Self-employed or farmer	39	
95		Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97		Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98		Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	135	
99		No answer	44	
			4415	
Z481		SEI CURRENT JOB		X412, Y251
		Socio-economic group (SEI) for respondent's current job.		
11		Unskilled manual worker, goods production	138	4,5
12		Unskilled manual worker, service production	434	14,3
21		Skilled manual worker, goods production	261	8,6
22		Skilled manual worker, service production	195	6,4
33		Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	96	3,2
35		Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	44	1,4
36		Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	258	8,5
45		Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	30	1,0
46		Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	680	22,3
56		Professional, higher non-manual worker	423	13,9
57		Professional, upper-level executive	101	3,3
60		Self-employed professionals	30	1,0
71		Self-employed without employees	173	5,7
72		Self-employed, 1-9 employees	106	3,5
73		Self-employed, 10-19 employees	11	0,4
74		Self-employed, unknown size of firm	13	0,4
79		Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	15	0,5
89		Farmer, unknown size of farm	36	1,2
		Total	3044	100
99		Unclassified	2	
		Not applicable	1369	
			4415	

Z482	NYK80 CURRENT JOB	X413, Y252																																																																								
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's current job. Not shown.																																																																									
Z483	NYK85 CURRENT JOB	X414																																																																								
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's current job. Not shown.																																																																									
Z484	SSYK CURRENT JOB	NEW																																																																								
	Profession according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.																																																																									
Z488	EGP CURRENT JOB	X415, Y253																																																																								
	Class (EGP) for respondent's current job.																																																																									
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Z489	SNI CURRENT JOB	NEW																																																																								
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Z491	WORKPLACE SIZE, CURRENT JOB	X417, jfr Y255																																																																								
	Number of employees at respondent's current workplace.																																																																									
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6	100-499	411	17,9																																																																							

7	500-999	137	6,0
8	1000-w	237	10,3
	Total	2291	100
93	Not gainfully employed at interview	1069	
94	Self-employed or farmer	324	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	5	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	349	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	124	
99	No answer	253	
		4415	

Z492	SECTOR, CURRENT JOB		X418, Y256
	Sector (private/public) for respondent's current job.		
1	Public sector	996	39,7
2	Private sector	1515	60,3
	Total	2511	100
93	Not gainfully employed at interview	1069	
94	Self-employed or farmer	324	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	5	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	349	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	124	
99	No answer	33	
		4415	

Z493	EMPLOYMENT STATUS WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED		NEW
	Respondent's employment status when current cohabitation started.		
1	Employed	1461	82,1
2	Self-employed	90	5,1
3	Farmer	11	0,6
4	Unemployed	27	1,5
5	Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	2	0,1
6	Studying	123	6,9
7	Military service	9	0,5
8	Parental leave	10	0,6
9	Housework	13	0,7
10	Pensioner	6	0,3
11	Other	20	1,1
12	Abroad	7	0,4
	Total	1779	100
91	Current cohabitation started<first occupation	331	
92	Not cohabiting	1664	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥ 6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	26	
		4415	

Z494	SEI WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for respondent's job when current cohabitation started.	
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	126 8,1
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	302 19,4
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	196 12,6
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	89 5,7
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	121 7,8
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	22 1,4
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	138 8,9
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	24 1,5
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	292 18,8
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	113 7,3
	57 Professional, upper-level executive	30 1,9
	60 Self-employed professionals	33 2,1
	71 Self-employed without employees	9 0,6
	72 Self-employed, 1-9 employees	9 0,6
	73 Self-employed, 10-19 employees	3 0,2
	79 Self-employed, unknown size of firm	35 2,3
	86 Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	1 0,1
	87 Farmer, unknown size of farm	7 0,5
	89 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	4 0,3
	Total	1554 100
	91 Current cohabitation started<first occupation	331
	92 Not cohabiting	1664
	93 Not gainfully employed when cur. cohab. started	243
	95 Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6
	97 Never worked ≥6 months	480
	98 Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129
	99 Unclassified	8
		4415
Z495	NYK80 WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's job when current cohabitation started. Redovisas ej	
Z496	NYK85 WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED	NEW
	Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK for respondent's job when current cohabitation started. Not shown.	

Z501	EGP WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED			NEW
	Class (EGP) for respondent's job when current cohabitation started.			
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	46		3,0
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	129		8,5
3	II Lower-grade professionals	309		20,3
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	227		14,9
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	268		17,6
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	11		0,7
9	IVd Smallholders	10		0,7
10	Vs Supervisors	35		2,3
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	193		12,7
13	VJj Skilled manual workers in primary production	4		0,3
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	279		18,4
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	9		0,6
	Total	1520		100
91	Current cohabitation started<first occupation	331		
92	Not cohabiting	1664		
93	Not gainfully employed when cur. cohab. started	243		
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6		
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480		
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129		
99	No answer	42		
		4415		

Z504	SIZE OF WORKPLACE WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED			NEW
	Number of employees in the workplace of respondent's job when current cohabitation started.			
1	Respondent only	11		0,8
2	2-9 employees	263		19,3
3	10-19	203		14,9
4	20-49	244		17,9
5	50-99	147		10,8
6	100-499	256		18,8
7	500-999	87		6,4
8	1000-w	153		11,2
	Total	1364		100
91	Current cohabitation started<first occupation	331		
92	Not cohabiting	1664		
93	Not gainfully employed when cur. cohab. started			
94	Self-employed or farmer when cur. cohab. started	102		
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6		
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480		
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129		
99	No answer	339		
		4415		

Z505	SECTOR WHEN CURRENT COHABITATION STARTED		NEW
	Sector (private/public) for respondent's job when current cohabitation started.		
1	Public sector	481	34,0
2	Private sector	932	66,0
	Total	1413	100
3	Self-employed or farmer	101	
91	Current cohabitation started<first occupation	331	
92	Not cohabiting	1664	
93	Not gainfully employed when cur. cohab. started	243	
95	Excludes 1991/2000: More than 15 jobs	6	
97	Never worked ≥6 months	480	
98	Born before 1939 / excluded 2010: other reason	129	
99	No answer	48	
		4415	
Z506	GENERAL HEALTH		X435, Y257
	How do you judge your general state of health? Is it...		
1	Good	3300	74,9
2	Bad	228	5,2
3	Something in-between	879	19,9
	Total	4407	100
9	No answer	8	
		4415	
Z507	WALK 100 M		X436, Y258, U160, V235, W101
	Can you walk 100 meters relatively quickly without trouble?		
1	Yes	4168	94,6
2	No	239	5,4
	Total	4407	100
9	No answer	8	
		4415	
Z508	RUN 100 M		X437, Y259, U161, V236, W102
	Can you run 100 meters without much trouble?		
1	Yes	3621	82,5
2	No	769	17,5
	Total	4390	100
9	No answer	25	
		4415	

Z509	WALK STAIRS			X438, Y260, U162, V237, W103
	Can you walk up and down stairs without trouble?			
	1	Yes	4047	91,9
	2	No	359	8,1
		Total	4406	100
	9	No answer	9	
			4415	
Z510	TURN TAP			X439, Y261
	Can you turn the tap off and on without trouble?			
	1	Yes	4243	96,3
	2	No	164	3,7
		Total	4407	100
	9	No answer	8	
			4415	
Z511	LENGTH IN CM			X440, Y262
	How tall are you?			
	<150		6	0,1
	150-159		327	7,4
	160-169		1323	30,1
	170-179		1535	34,9
	180-189		1025	23,3
	190-199		174	4,0
	200-209		5	0,1
	≥210		1	0,0
		Total	4396	100
	999	No answer	19	
			4415	
		Mean value	172,9	
		Standard deviation	9,6	
Z512	WEIGHT IN KG			X441, Y263
	What is your weight? This variable is divided into categories.			
	<40		2	0,0
	40-49		40	0,9
	50-59		475	10,9
	60-69		937	21,6
	70-79		1105	25,4
	80-89		971	22,4
	90-99		500	11,5
	100-109		203	4,7

	110-119		67	1,5
	120-129		29	0,7
	130-139		8	0,2
	140-491		4	0,1
	≥150		1	0,0
	Total		4342	100
999	No answer		73	
	Mean value		76,2	
	Standard deviation		14,8	
Z513	HEADACHE			X452, Y277, U190, V257, W120
	Have you in the last 12 months had headaches, migraine?			
	1	No	2660	60,3
	2	Yes, mild	1362	30,9
	3	Yes, severe	385	8,7
	4	Yes, level is missing	1	0
	Total		4408	100
	9	No answer	7	
			4415	
Z514	COLD			X453, Y278, U191, V258, W121
	Have you in the last 12 months had colds or influenza?			
	1	No	1846	41,9
	2	Yes, mild	2141	48,6
	3	Yes, severe	420	9,5
	4	Yes, level is missing	1	0
	Total		4408	100
	9	No answer	7	
			4415	
Z515	POOR VISION			X454, Y279, U192, V259, W122
	Have you in the last 12 months had poor vision/disease of the eyes that were not helped by eyeglasses?			
	1	No	4100	93
	2	Yes, mild	198	4,5
	3	Yes, severe	110	2,5
	Total		4408	100
	9	No answer	7	
			4415	

Z516	IMPAIRED HEARING			X455, Y280, U193, V260, W123
	Have you in the last 12 months had impaired hearing?			
	1 No	3889	88,2	
	2 Yes, mild	404	9,2	
	3 Yes, severe	115	2,6	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z517	CHEST PAIN			X456, Y281, U194, V261, W124
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches or pain in the chest?			
	1 No	4173	94,7	
	2 Yes, mild	162	3,7	
	3 Yes, severe	72	1,6	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z518	BRONCHITIS			X457, Y282, U195, V262, W125
	Have you in the last 12 months had chronic bronchitis (asthma)?			
	1 No	4199	95,3	
	2 Yes, mild	153	3,5	
	3 Yes, severe	56	1,3	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z519	GOITRE			X458, Y283, U196, V263, W126
	Have you in the last 12 months had enlargement of the thyroid (goitre)?			
	1 No	4321	98,0	
	2 Yes, mild	72	1,6	
	3 Yes, severe	15	0,3	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z520	TUBERCULOSIS			X459, Y284, U197, V264, W127
	Have you in the last 12 months had tuberculosis (all forms)?			
	1 No	4407	100,0	
	3 Yes, severe	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z521	ACHES IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES			X460, Y285, U198, V265, W128
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches in shoulders or shoulder blades?			
	1 No	3209	72,8	
	2 Yes, mild	832	18,9	
	3 Yes, severe	363	8,2	
	4 Yes, level is missing	4	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z522	HEART ATTACK			X461, Y286, U199, V266, W129
	Have you in the last 12 months had coronary thrombosis, heart attack?			
	1 No	4386	99,5	
	2 Yes, mild	8	0,2	
	3 Yes, severe	14	0,3	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z523	STROKE			X462
	Have you in the last 12 months had cerebral thrombosis, stroke?			
	1 No	4377	99,3	
	2 Yes, mild	15	0,3	
	3 Yes, severe	16	0,4	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z524	CARDIAC WEAKNESS			X463, Y287, U200, V267, W130
	Have you in the last 12 months had a weak heart?			
	1 No	4325	98,1	
	2 Yes, mild	61	1,4	
	3 Yes, severe	22	0,5	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z525	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE			X464, Y288, U201, V268, W131
	Have you in the last 12 months had high blood pressure?			
	1 No	3785	85,9	
	2 Yes, mild	549	12,5	
	3 Yes, severe	68	1,5	
	4 Yes, level is missing	6	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z526	STOMACH PAINS			X465, Y289, U202, V269, W132
	Have you in the last 12 months had stomach pains?			
	1 No	3670	83,3	
	2 Yes, mild	489	11,1	
	3 Yes, severe	248	5,6	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	4		
		4415		
Z527	GASTRIC ULCER			X466, Y290, U203, V270, W133
	Have you in the last 12 months had a gastric ulcer?			
	1 No	4336	98,4	
	2 Yes, mild	42	1,0	
	3 Yes, severe	30	0,7	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z528	PAIN IN BACK/HIPS			X467, Y291, U204, V271, W134
	Have you in the last 12 months had backache, pain in back or hips or sciatica?			
	1 No	3007	68,2	
	2 Yes, mild	848	19,2	
	3 Yes, severe	548	12,4	
	4 Yes, level is missing	5	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z529	BILIARY TROUBLE			X468, Y292, U205, V272, W135
	Have you in the last 12 months had biliary/gall trouble or gall stones?			
	1 No	4335	98,3	
	2 Yes, mild	45	1,0	
	3 Yes, severe	27	0,6	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z530	KIDNEY TROUBLE			X469, Y293, U206, V273, W136
	Have you in the last 12 months had kidney trouble or kidney stones?			
	1 No	4332	98,3	
	2 Yes, mild	39	0,9	
	3 Yes, severe	36	0,8	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z531	HAEMORRHOIDS			X470, Y294, U207, V274, W137
	Have you in the last 12 months had haemorrhoids or anal discomfort?			
	1 No	4194	95,1	
	2 Yes, mild	171	3,9	
	3 Yes, severe	42	1,0	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z532	TROUBLE WITH URINATION			X471, Y295, U208, V275, W138
	Have you in the last 12 months had cystitis, trouble with urination? <i>For men:</i> prostate trouble?			
	1 No	4251	96,4	
	2 Yes, mild	105	2,4	
	3 Yes, severe	52	1,2	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z533	MENSTRUATION TROUBLE			X472, Y296, jfr U209, jfr V276, jfr W139
	To women born in 1950 or later: Have you in the last 12 months had menstruation trouble?			
	1 No	1340	83,6	
	2 Yes, mild	135	8,4	
	3 Yes, severe	128	8,0	
	Total	1603	100	
	9 No answer	3		
	Not applicable	2804		
		4415		
Z534	PREGNANCY COMPLICATIONS			X473, Y297, jfr U210, jfr V278, jfr W141
	To women born in 1950 or later: Have you in the last 12 months had pregnancy complications?			
	1 No	1564	97,6	
	2 Yes, mild	16	1,0	
	3 Yes, severe	23	1,4	
	Total	1603	100	
	9 No answer	3		
	Not applicable	2809		
		4415		
Z535	VAGINAL TROUBLE			X474, Y298, U211, V277, W140
	To all women: Have you in the last 12 months had other vaginal trouble (discharges, pains, prolaps of uterus, etc.)?			
	1 No	2057	95,5	
	2 Yes, mild	65	3,0	
	3 Yes, severe	33	1,5	
	Total	2155	100	
	9 No answer	3		
	Not applicable	2257		
		4415		

Z536	INGUINAL HERNIA			X475, Y299, U212, V279, W142
	Have you in the last 12 months had inguinal hernia?			
	1 No	4366	99,0	
	2 Yes, mild	26	0,6	
	3 Yes, severe	16	0,4	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z537	VARICOSE VEINS			X476, Y300, U213, V280, W143
	Have you in the last 12 months had varicose veins, varicose ulcers?			
	1 No	4269	96,8	
	2 Yes, mild	100	2,3	
	3 Yes, severe	39	0,9	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z538	SWOLLEN LEGS			X477, Y301, U214, V281, W144
	Have you in the last 12 months had swollen legs?			
	1 No	4151	94,2	
	2 Yes, mild	189	4,3	
	3 Yes, severe	68	1,5	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z539	ACHES IN JOINTS			X478, Y302, U215, V282, W145
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches or pain in hands, elbows, legs or knees?			
	1 No	3467	78,7	
	2 Yes, mild	593	13,5	
	3 Yes, severe	345	7,8	
	4 Yes, level is missing	3	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z540	GENERAL TIREDNESS			X479, Y303, U216, V283, W146
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from general tiredness?			
	1 No	3506	79,5	
	2 Yes, mild	654	14,8	
	3 Yes, severe	246	5,6	
	4 Yes, level is missing	2	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z541	INSOMNIA			X480, Y304, U217, V284, W147
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from insomnia?			
	1 No	3582	81,3	
	2 Yes, mild	512	11,6	
	3 Yes, severe	311	7,1	
	4 Yes, level is missing	3	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z542	NERVOUS TROUBLE			X481, Y305, U218, V285, W148
	Have you in the last 12 months had nervous trouble (anxiety, uneasiness, anguish)?			
	1 No	3878	88,0	
	2 Yes, mild	322	7,3	
	3 Yes, severe	207	4,7	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z543	DEPRESSIONS			X482, Y306, U219, V286, W149
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from depressions or deep dejection?			
	1 No	4068	92,3	
	2 Yes, mild	192	4,4	
	3 Yes, severe	146	3,3	
	4 Yes, level is missing	2	0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z544	MENTAL ILLNESS			X483, Y307, U220, V287, W150
	Have you in the last 12 months had a mental illness?			
	1 No	4345	98,6	
	2 Yes, mild	26	0,6	
	3 Yes, severe	35	0,8	
	4 Yes, level is missing	2	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z545	SWEATING			X484, Y308, U221, V288, W151
	Have you in the last 12 months had flushing (hot flashes) or copious sweating?			
	1 No	4158	94,3	
	2 Yes, mild	181	4,1	
	3 Yes, severe	69	1,6	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z546	COUGH			X485, Y309, U222, V289, W152
	Have you in the last 12 months had a cough?			
	1 No	3722	84,4	
	2 Yes, mild	550	12,5	
	3 Yes, severe	135	3,1	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z547	DIFFICULTY BREATHING			X486, Y310, U223, V290, W153
	Have you in the last 12 months had difficulty in breathing or breathlessness?			
	1 No	4207	95,4	
	2 Yes, mild	134	3,0	
	3 Yes, severe	67	1,5	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z548	DIZZINESS			X487, Y311, U224, V291, W154
	Have you in the last 12 months had giddiness?			
	1 No	4025	91,3	
	2 Yes, mild	299	6,8	
	3 Yes, severe	82	1,9	
	4 Yes, level is missing	2	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z549	NAUSEA			X488, Y312, U225, V292, W155
	Have you in the last 12 months had a feeling of being unwell, out of sorts?			
	1 No	4054	92,0	
	2 Yes, mild	275	6,2	
	3 Yes, severe	78	1,8	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z550	WEIGHT LOSS			X489, Y313, U226, V293, W156
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from weight loss?			
	1 No	4329	98,2	
	2 Yes, mild	59	1,3	
	3 Yes, severe	17	0,4	
	4 Yes, level is missing	3	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		
Z551	VOMITING			X490, Y314, U227, V294, W157
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from vomiting?			
	1 No	4161	94,4	
	2 Yes, mild	188	4,3	
	3 Yes, severe	58	1,3	
	4 Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
	9 No answer	7		
		4415		

Z552	DIARRHOEA			X491, Y315, U228, V295, W158
	Have you in the last 12 months had diarrhoea?			
1	No	4049	91,9	
2	Yes, mild	258	5,9	
3	Yes, severe	101	2,3	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z553	CONSTIPATION			X492, Y316, U229, V296, W159
	Have you in the last 12 months had constipation?			
1	No	4210	95,5	
2	Yes, mild	140	3,2	
3	Yes, severe	58	1,3	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z554	OVEREXERTION			X493, Y317, U230, V297, W160
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from overexertion?			
1	No	4202	95,3	
2	Yes, mild	154	3,5	
3	Yes, severe	51	1,2	
4	Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z555	RASHES			X494, Y318, U231, V298, W161
	Have you in the last 12 months had rashes, eczema or psoriasis?			
1	No	3985	90,4	
2	Yes, mild	337	7,6	
3	Yes, severe	86	2,0	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		

Z556	CANCER			X495, Y319, U232, V299, W162
		Have you in the last 12 months had a malignant tumour, cancer?		
1	No	4352	98,7	
2	Yes, mild	22	0,5	
3	Yes, severe	33	0,7	
4	Yes, level is missing	1	0	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z557	ANAEMIA			X496, Y320, U233, V300, W163
		Have you in the last 12 months had anaemia?		
1	No	4345	98,6	
2	Yes, mild	44	1,0	
3	Yes, severe	18	0,4	
4	Yes, level is missing	1	0,0	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z558	DIABETES			X497, Y321, U234, V301, W164
		Have you in the last 12 months had diabetes, blood sugar?		
1	No	4224	95,8	
2	Yes, mild	133	3,0	
3	Yes, severe	48	1,1	
4	Yes, level is missing	3	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		
Z559	OVERWEIGHT			X498, Y322, U235, V302, W165
		Have you in the last 12 months suffered from overweight, obesity?		
1	No	3920	88,9	
2	Yes, mild	399	9,1	
3	Yes, severe	86	2,0	
4	Yes, level is missing	3	0,1	
	Total	4408	100	
9	No answer	7		
		4415		

Z560	ORGANIC NERVE DISORDER		X499, Y323, U236, V303, W166
	Have you in the last 12 months had an organic nerve disorder (CP, MS, Polio etc.)?		
1	No	4379	99,3
2	Yes, mild	14	0,3
3	Yes, severe	13	0,3
4	Yes, level is missing	2	0,0
	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	
Z561	DISCOMFORT AFTER INJURY		X500, Y324, jfr U189
	Have you in the last 12 months had lasting disability/discomfort after an accident or injury?		
1	No	4140	93,9
2	Yes, mild	143	3,2
3	Yes, severe	124	2,8
4	Yes, level is missing	1	0,0
	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	
Z562	ALLERGY		X501, Y325
	Have you in the last 12 months had an allergy?		
1	No	3737	84,8
2	Yes, mild	518	11,8
3	Yes, severe	152	3,4
4	Yes, level is missing	1	0,0
	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	
Z563	URINARY TRACT INFECTION		X502, Y326
	Have you in the last 12 months had infection of the urinary tract?		
1	No	4210	95,5
2	Yes, mild	126	2,9
3	Yes, severe	72	1,6
	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z564	OTHER ILLNESSES			jfr Y327, jfr Y328, jfr U237, jfr U238, jfr V304, jfr V305
	Have you in the last 12 months had any other illnesses?			
	1 No	3890	88,4	
	2 Yes, mild	276	6,3	
	3 Yes, severe	233	5,3	
	4 Yes, level is missing	3	0,0	
	Total	4402	100	
	9 No answer	13		
		4415		
Z565	HOSPITALIZED			X509, Y329, U253, V310, jfr W172
	Have you admitted to a hospital, nursing home or similar institution in the last 12 months?			
	1 Yes	513	11,6	
	2 No	3892	88,4	
	Total	4405	100	
	9 No answer	10		
		4415		
Z566	BEEN TO A DOCTOR			jfr X511, jfr Y331, jfr U255, V321, jfr W176
	Have you at any time in the last 12 months spoken with, visited, or been visited by a doctor for some illness or complaint on your own account? (Getting a doctor's certificate for a driver's licence or similar should not be counted. Neither should contact with a doctor while in hospital.)			
	1 Yes	2797	63,5	
	2 No	1606	36,5	
	Total	4403	100	
	9 No answer	12		
		4415		
Z567	VISITED A NURSE			X515, Y333, U257, V323, W177
	Have you in the last 12 months spoken with, visited or been visited by a district nurse, school nurse or equivalent? (The consultation or visit should be for your own problems, not e.g. your children's.)			
	1 Yes	1374	31,2	
	2 No	3031	68,8	
	Total	4405	100	
	9 No answer	10		
		4415		

Z568	CONDITION OF TEETH			X519, Y336, jfr U269, jfr V336, jfr W185
	Which of the following alternatives best describes the conditions of your teeth?			
1	No teeth	18	0,4	
2	Dentures, whole or part	117	2,7	
3	Own teeth but in bad condition	156	3,5	
4	Many fillings	1737	39,5	
5	Own teeth in good condition	2375	53,9	
	Total	4403	100	
9	No answer	12		
		4415		
Z569	SMOKING			X522, Y340, jfr U278, jfr V340, jfr W202, W203
	Do you smoke?			
1	Yes, <10 cigarettes/day	310	7,0	
2	Yes, >10 cigarettes/day	359	8,1	
3	No, have given up	1419	32,2	
4	No, have never smoked	2318	52,6	
5	Yes, No answer how many	1	0,0	
	Total	4407	100	
9	No answer	8		
		4415		
Z570	SMOKING NUMBER OF YEARS			X523, Y341, U279
	How many years have you been smoking altogether? The table is valid for Z569 NE 4. This variable is divided into categories.			
	<1	63	3,0	
	1-4	351	16,9	
	5-9	272	13,1	
	10-19	516	24,8	
	20-29	356	17,1	
	30-39	253	12,2	
	40-49	184	8,9	
	50-59	83	4,0	
	≥60	1	0,0	
	Total	2079	100	
99	No answer	17		
	Not applicable	2319		
		4415		
	Mean value	15,9		
	Standard deviation	14,4		

Z571	DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR ETC			X525, Y343, U280, jfr V341, jfr W204
	Do you at any time drink wine, strong cider/beer or liquor?			
1	Yes	3866	87,7	
2	No	541	12,3	
	Total	4407	100	
9	No answer	8		
		4415		

Z572	NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC			X526
	If yes: During the last 12 months, about how often have you consumed some amount of alcoholic beverage, that is: wine, strong beer, strong cider or liquor? The table is valid for Z571 EQ 1.			
1	Daily or almost daily	95	2,5	
2	2-4 times a week	718	18,6	
3	Once a week	1107	28,7	
4	2-3 times a month	837	21,7	
5	Once a month	445	11,5	
6	6-11 times a year	249	6,4	
7	Less often	392	10,2	
8	Never	18	0,5	
	Total	3861	100	
99	No answer	5		
	Not applicable	549		
		4415		

Z573	NUMBER OF GLASSES			X527
	If yes: On such occasions, how many glasses do you usually drink? One glass can be 1 glass of wine, 1 bottle or can of beer, or 1 schnapps or drink. The table is valid for Z571 EQ 1 and Z572 NE 8.			
1		794	20,8	
2		1501	39,3	
3		742	19,4	
4		310	8,1	
5		208	5,4	
6		98	2,6	
7		32	0,8	
8		44	1,2	
9		6	0,2	
10		61	1,6	
11		1	0,0	
12		10	0,3	
13		1	0,0	
14		2	0,1	
15		6	0,2	
20		6	0,2	
50		1	0,0	
	Total	3843	100	

	99	No answer	20	
		Not applicable	572	
			4415	
Z574		AGILITY		X528, Y346, U239, V734, W559
		Index based on the questions about agility (Z507 walk meter, Z508 run 100 meter and Z509 walk stairs). Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	1	Normal agility	3575	81,5
	2	Reduced agility	449	10,2
	3	Hampered agility	177	4,0
	4	Greatly hampered agility	187	4,3
		Total	4388	100
	9	No answer	27	
			4415	
Z575		INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING		X529, Y347, U241, V736
		Index based on questions about psychological well-being (Z540 general tiredness, Z541 insomnia, Z542 nervous trouble and Z543 depressions).		
	1		2894	65,7
	2		378	8,6
	3		101	2,3
	4		320	7,3
	5		42	1,0
	6		64	1,5
	7		162	3,7
	8		30	0,7
	9		60	1,4
	10		33	0,7
	11		25	0,6
	12		91	2,1
	13		45	1,0
	14		27	0,6
	15		31	0,7
	16		105	2,4
		Total	4408	100
	99	No answer	7	
			4415	
Z576		PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING		X530, Y348, U242, V737, W573
		Scale based on the logical index Z575 (1 4 5=1, 2 9=2, 2 6 10 13=3, 7 8 18=4, 11,14,15,16=5).		
	1	Normal	3256	73,9
	2	Tiredness	438	9,9
	3	Nervous	243	5,5
	4	Insomnia	283	6,4
	5	Depressions	188	4,3

	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z577 **OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX** **X531, Y349**

Added index based on the questions about psychological well-being Z540 (general tiredness) Z541 (insomnia) Z542 (nervous trouble) Z543 (depressions) and Z544 (overexertion).

0	No trouble	2863	65,0
1	1 mild trouble	669	15,2
2	2 mild trouble	216	4,9
3	1 severe, 3 mild	236	5,4
4	1 severe + 1 mild, 4 mild	111	2,5
5	1 severe + 2 mild, 5 mild	55	1,2
6	2 severe, 1 severe + 3 mild	61	1,4
7	2 severe + 1 mild, 1 severe + 4 mild	56	1,3
8	2 severe + 2 mild	25	0,6
9	3 severe, 2 severe + 3 mild	39	0,9
10	3 severe + 1 mild	30	0,7
11	3 severe + 2 mild	10	0,2
12	4 severe	25	0,6
13	4 severe + 1 mild	7	0,2
15	5 severe	5	0,1
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z578 **ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM** **X532, Y350, U243, V739, W567**

Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system Z521 (aches in shoulders/shoulder blades) Z528 (pain in back/hips) and Z539 (aches in joints).

0	No trouble	2240	50,8
1	1 mild trouble	845	19,2
2	2 mild, 1 severe	670	15,2
3	1 severe + 1 mild, 3 mild	297	6,7
4	1 severe + 2 mild, 2 severe	201	4,6
5	2 severe + 1 mild	72	1,6
6	3 severe	83	1,9
	Total	4408	100
9	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z579**OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE****X533, Y351**

Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system Z521 (aches in shoulders/shoulder blades) Z528 (pain in back/hips) and Z539 (aches in joints).

0	No trouble	2240	50,8
1	1 mild trouble	845	19,2
2	2 mild trouble	340	7,7
3	1 severe, 3 mild	438	9,9
4	1 severe + 1 mild	189	4,3
5	1 severe + 2 mild	80	1,8
6	2 severe	121	2,7
7	2 severe + 1 mild	72	1,6
8	3 severe	83	1,9
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z580**CIRCULATORY SYSTEM****X534, Y352,
U244, V740,
W566**

Added index based on the questions about the circulatory system Z517 (pain in the chest) Z524 (weak heart) Z525 (high blood pressure) Z537 (varicose veins) Z538 (swollen legs) Z547 (difficulty in breathing) and Z548 (giddiness).

0	No trouble	3153	71,5
1	1 mild trouble	710	16,1
2	2 mild, 1 severe	288	6,5
3	3 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	110	2,5
4	4 mild, 2 severe etc.	76	1,7
5	5 mild, 1 severe + 3 mild etc.	37	0,8
6	6 mild, 3 severe etc..	20	0,5
7	7 mild, 3 severe + 1 mild etc.	8	0,2
8	4 severe, 3 severe + 2 mild etc.	5	0,1
9	4 severe + 1 mild, etc.	1	0,0
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z581**OLLE'S CIRCULATORY INDEX****X535, Y353**

Added index based on the questions about the circulatory system Z517 (pain in the chest) Z524 (weak heart) Z525 (high blood pressure) Z537 (varicose veins) Z538 (swollen legs) Z547 (difficulty in breathing) and Z548 (giddiness).

0	No trouble	3359	76,2
1	1 mild trouble	710	16,1
2	2 mild trouble	115	2,6
3	3 mild, 1 severe	124	2,8
4	4 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	60	1,4
5	1 severe + 2 mild	9	0,2
6	2 severe, 1 severe + 3 mild	16	0,4
7	2 severe + 1 mild	12	0,3

8	2 severe + 2 mild	1	0,0
9	3 severe	2	0,0
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z582	STOMACH TROUBLE		X536, Y354, U245, V741, W568
	Added index based on the questions about stomach trouble Z526 (stomach pains) Z529 (gall trouble) Z549 (being unwell) Z551 (vomiting) and Z552 (diarrhoea).		
0	No trouble	3276	74,3
1	1 mild trouble	532	12,1
2	2 mild, 1 severe	321	7,3
3	3 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	131	3,0
4	4 mild, 2 severe, 1 severe + 2 mild	94	2,1
5	5 mild, 2 severe + 1 mild etc.	24	0,5
6	3 severe, 2 severe + 2 mild	19	0,4
7	3 severe + 1 mild, 2 severe + 3 mild	4	0,1
8	4 severe, 3 severe + 2 mild	6	0,1
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	8	
		4415	

Z583	OLLE'S STOMACH INDEX		X537, Y355
	Added index based on the questions about stomach trouble Z526 (stomach pains) Z529 (gall trouble) Z549 (being unwell) Z551 (vomiting) and Z552 (diarrhoea).		
0	No trouble	3308	75,0
1	1 mild trouble	524	11,9
2	2 mild trouble	143	3,2
3	3 mild, 1 severe	236	5,4
4	4 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	76	1,7
5	1 severe + 2 mild	22	0,5
6	1 severe + 3 mild	56	1,3
7	2 severe + 1 mild	16	0,4
8	2 severe + 2 mild	3	0,1
9	3 severe	14	0,3
10	3 severe + 1 mild	4	0,1
11	4 severe	6	0,1
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

Z584	DEFECATION TROUBLE		X538, Y356, U246, V742, W569
	Added index based on the questions about defecation trouble Z531 (haemorrhoids) and Z553 (constipation).		
0	Inga besvär	4039	91,6
1	1 lätt besvär	258	5,9
2	2 lätta, 1 svårt	86	2,0
3	1 lä + 1 sv	18	0,4
4	2 svåra	7	0,2
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	
Z585	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE		X539, Y357, U247, V743, jfr W637
	Added index (44 item) based on Z513-Z532, however not Z523, and Z536-560, where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1, "Yes, severe" is coded 2 and "Yes, level is missing" is coded 1.		
0		400	9,1
1		556	12,6
2		601	13,6
3		539	12,2
4		467	10,6
5		313	7,1
6		277	6,3
7		219	5,0
8		179	4,1
9		154	3,5
10		114	2,6
11		92	2,1
12		79	1,8
13		76	1,7
14		52	1,2
15		45	1
16		45	1,0
17		25	0,6
18		34	0,8
19		25	0,6
20		17	0,4
21		18	0,4
22		17	0,4
23		11	0,2
24		5	0,1
25		9	0,2
26		8	0,2
27		6	0,1
28		4	0,1
29		1	0,0
30		6	0,1
31		2	0,0
32		3	0,1

32		1	0,0
33		5	0,1
34		1	0,0
35		3	0,1
36		3	0,1
37		2	0
41		1	0
43		1	0
52		1	0
58		1	0
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	
	Mean value (>0)	5,8	
	Standard deviation (>0)	5,3	

Z587	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM		X542, Y359, U248, V744, jfr W638
	Added index (44 item) based on Z513-Z532, however not Z523, and Z536-560, where "No" is coded 0, and "Yes, mild", "Yes, severe" and "Yes, level is missing" is coded 1.		
0		372	8,4
1		634	14,4
2		669	15,2
3		594	13,5
4		480	10,9
5		357	8,1
6		291	6,6
7		220	5,0
8		208	4,7
9		133	3,0
10		92	2,1
11		84	1,9
12		50	1,1
13		56	1,3
14		44	1,0
15		28	0,6
16		20	0,5
17		24	0,5
18		18	0,4
19		17	0,4
21		5	0,1
22		1	0,0
23		2	0,0
24		2	0,0
25		2	0,0
29		2	0,1
	Total	4408	100
99	No answer	7	
		4415	

2	14	0,3
3	13	0,3
4	18	0,4
5	12	0,3
6	13	0,3
7	7	0,2
8	40	0,9
9	11	0,2
10	19	0,4
11	6	0,1
12	52	1,2
13	7	0,2
14	7	0,2
15	10	0,2
16	25	0,6
17	5	0,1
18	5	0,1
19	1	0,0
20	24	0,5
21	2	0,0
22	3	0,1
23	2	0,0
24	10	0,2
25	17	0,4
26	46	1,0
27	4	0,1
28	15	0,3
30	15	0,3
31	1	0,0
32	21	0,5
33	2	0,0
34	3	0,1
35	12	0,3
36	25	0,6
37	3	0,1
38	5	0,1
39	1	0,0
40	46	1,0
41	2	0,0
42	8	0,2
43	1	0,0
44	12	0,3
45	9	0,2
46	5	0,1
47	8	0,2
48	28	0,6
49	2	0,0
50	19	0,4
51	4	0,1
52	2415	54,9
53	265	6,0

	Total		4394	100	
99	No answer		21		
			4415		
	Mean value		35,1		
	Standard deviation		23,1		
Z590	TOTAL HOURS WORKED 2009				jfr X544, jfr Y360, jfr U283, jfr V789, jfr W940
	Total number of hours worked in gainful employment during 2009. The sum of full-time, part-time, farm work, assisting on farm, work in own firm, assisting in firm and freelance occupation. This variable is divided into categories.				
	The table is valid for Z589 GT 0.				
	0-499		301	9,2	
	500-599		160	4,9	
	1000-1499		285	8,7	
	1500-1999		645	19,7	
	2000-2499		1599	48,8	
	2500-2999		199	6,1	
	3000-3499		60	1,8	
	3500-3999		16	0,5	
	4000-4499		8	0,2	
	4500-4999		2	0,1	
	9999		3275	100,0	
	No answer		50		
	Not applicable		1090		
	Mean value		1798,5		
	Standard deviation		696,8		
Z591	EMPLOYED 2009				jfr X545 & X548, jfr Y361 & Y364, jfr U284 & U288, jfr V342 & V346, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
	Were you employed full-time (including vacation and sick-leave) during 2009?				
1	Ja		2985	67,8	
2	No		1417	32,2	
	Total		4402	100	
9	No answer		13		
			4415		
Z592	WEEKS FULL-TIME 2009				jfr X546 & X549, jfr Y362 & Y366, jfr U285 & U290, jfr V343 & V348, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
	Number of weeks during 2009: employed full-time.				
	The table is valid for Z591 EQ 1.				
	1		3	0,1	
	2		15	0,5	
	3		12	0,4	
	4		20	0,7	

5		11	0,4
6		13	0,4
7		6	0,2
8		38	1,3
9		10	0,3
10		19	0,6
11		6	0,2
12		50	1,7
13		6	0,2
14		8	0,3
15		11	0,4
16		23	0,8
17		6	0,2
18		5	0,2
19		1	0,0
20		23	0,8
21		2	0,1
22		3	0,1
23		2	0,1
24		9	0,3
25		16	0,5
26		46	1,5
27		4	0,1
28		16	0,5
30		15	0,5
31		1	0,0
32		21	0,7
33		2	0,1
34		3	0,1
35		11	0,4
36		25	0,8
37		4	0,1
38		4	0,1
39		1	0,0
40		40	1,3
41		2	0,1
42		7	0,2
43		1	0,0
44		12	0,4
45		8	0,3
46		5	0,2
47		8	0,3
48		23	0,8
49		2	0,1
50		17	0,6
51		4	0,1
52		2132	71,7
53		240	8,1
	Total	2972	100
99	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	1430	

			4415	
	Mean value		46,4	
	Standard deviation		13,2	
Z593	HOURS PER WEEK EMPLOYED 2009			jfr X547 & X550, jfr Y363 & Y365, jfr U286 & U289, jfr V344 & V347, jfr W205 & W207, jfr W206 & W208
	Numbers of hours on average per week during 2009: full-time employed. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z591 EQ 1.			
	0-9		61	2,1
	10-19		58	2
	20-29		225	7,6
	30-39		715	24,1
	40-49		1726	58,3
	50-59		135	4,6
	60-69		33	1,1
	70-79		7	0,2
	≥80		3	0,1
	Total		2963	100
888	Doesn't know		22	
999	No answer		4	
	Not applicable		1427	
			4415	
Z594	WORK IN OWN FIRM 2009			jfr X557, jfr Y375, jfr U304, jfr V364, jfr W214, jfr W215
	Did you work in your own or in partnership firm, during 2009?			
1	Yes		402	9,1
2	No		4000	90,9
	Total		4402	100
9	No answer		13	
			4415	
Z595	WEEKS IN OWN FIRM 2009			jfr X558 & X552, jfr Y376 & Y370, jfr U305 & U297, jfr V365 & V357, jfr W214 & W210, jfr W215 & W211
	Number of weeks during 2009: work in own or in partnership firm.			
	The table is valid for Z594 EQ 1.			
	1		2	0,5
	3		1	0,2
	5		1	0,2
	6		1	0,2
	8		5	1,2
	9		1	0,2
	10		2	0,5
	12		8	2,0
	13		1	0,2

15		2	0,5
16		5	1,2
20		3	0,7
24		1	0,2
25		4	1,0
26		5	1,2
28		1	0,2
30		1	0,2
32		1	0,2
35		3	0,7
36		2	0,5
38		3	0,7
40		11	2,7
44		1	0,2
45		1	0,2
46		1	0,2
47		2	0,5
48		5	1,2
50		3	0,7
52		298	74,1
53		27	6,7
	Total	402	100
	Not applicable	4013	
		4415	
	Mean value	47,2	
	Standard deviation	11,9	

Z596

HOURS PER WEEK IN OWN FIRM 2009

jfr X559 & X553, jfr Y377 & Y371, jfr U306 & U298, jfr V366 & V358, jfr W214 & W210, jfr W215 & W211

Numbers of hours per week during 2009: work in own or in partnership firm. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z594 EQ 1.

0-9		33	8,4
10-19		32	8,1
20-29		50	12,7
30-39		37	9,4
40-49		118	30,0
50-59		74	18,8
60-69		33	8,4
70-79		12	3,1
≥80		4	1,0
	Total	393	100
88	Doesn't know	8	
99	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	4013	
	Total	4415	

Z597	UNEMPLOYED DURING 2009			jfr X566, jfr Y384, jfr U316, jfr V376, jfr W220
	Were you seeking or waiting for employment, unemployed or laid off during 2009?			
	1	Yes	418	9,5
	2	No	3986	90,5
		Total	4404	100
	9	No answer	11	
		Total	4415	
Z598	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED 2009			jfr X567, jfr Y385, jfr U317, jfr V377, jfr W220
	Number of weeks during 2009: waiting for employment/unemployed/laid off. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z597 EQ 1.			
	0-9		85	20,5
	10-19		71	17,1
	20-29		68	16,4
	30-39		25	6,0
	40-49		36	8,7
	50-59		129	31,2
		Total	414	100
	99	No answer	4	
		Not applicable	3997	
			4415	
Z599	LAST WEEK: FULL-TIME			X570, Y398, jfr U332, jfr V345
	Were you employed full-time (also vacation, sick leave, parental leave, studies etc.) last week?			
	1	Yes	2105	47,8
	2	No	2300	52,2
		Total	4405	100
	9	No answer	10	
			4415	
Z600	LAST WEEK: PART-TIME			X571, Y399, jfr U333, jfr V349
	Were you employed part-time (also vacation, sick leave, parental leave, studies etc.) last week?			
	1	Yes	596	13,5
	2	No	3809	86,5
		Total	4405	100
	9	No answer	10	
			4415	

Z601	LAST WEEK: OWN FIRM OR FARM			jfr X574 & X572, jfr Y402 & Y400, jfr U338 & U336, jfr V367 & V359
	Did you work in own or part-owned firm or as a farmer last week?			
	1	Yes	414	9,4
	2	No	3992	90,6
		Total	4406	100
	9	No answer	9	
			4415	
Z602	LAST WEEK: FAMILY MEMBER'S FIRM OR FARM			jfr X575 & X573, jfr Y403 & Y401, jfr U339 & U337, jfr V371 & V363
	Did you assist in a family member's firm or farm at least 1 hour per day last week?			
	1	Yes	57	1,3
	2	No	4349	98,7
		Total	4406	100
	9	No answer	9	
			4415	
Z603	LAST WEEK: FREELANCE OCCUPATION OR SIDE-LINE			X576, Y404, U340, V375
	Did you work in a freelance occupation or a side-line/extra job last week?			
	1	Yes	123	2,8
	2	No	4283	97,2
		Total	4406	100
	9	No answer	9	
			4415	
Z604	LAST WEEK: LOOKING FOR WORK			X577, Y405, U341, V378
	Were you looking or waiting for work, unemployed or laid off last week?			
	1	Yes	232	5,3
	2	No	4174	94,7
		Total	4406	100
	9	No answer	9	
			4415	
Z605	LAST WEEK: PENSION			X578, Y406, U344, V387
	Were you pensioned (also disability pension or partial pension) last week?			
	1	Yes	1083	24,6
	2	No	3321	75,4
		Total	4404	100
	9	No answer	11	
			4415	

Z606	LAST WEEK: STUDYING			X580, Y408, U346, V393
	Were you studying last week?			
	1	Yes	421	9,6
	2	No	3984	90,4
		Total	4405	100
	9	No answer	10	
			4415	
Z607	LAST WEEK: OTHER			X582, Y410, U347, V396
	Did you have any other occupation last week?			
	1	Yes	183	4,2
	2	No	4224	95,8
		Total	4407	100
	9	No answer	8	
			4415	
Z608	SEI EMPLOYEES			X583, Y411, jfr U355, jfr V712
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to socio-economic classification (SEI).			
	The table is valid for employees last week.			
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	138	5,2
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	433	16,3
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	261	9,8
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	195	7,3
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	96	3,6
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	44	1,7
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	256	9,6
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	30	1,1
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	679	25,6
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	421	15,9
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	101	3,8
		Total	2654	100
	99	Unclassified	2	
		Not applicable	1759	
			4415	
Z609	NYK80 EMPLOYEES			X584, Y412, jfr U356
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
Z610	NYK85 EMPLOYEES			X585
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			

Z611	SSYK EMPLOYEES	NEW
What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to the Swedish standard classification of occupations (SSYK). Not shown.		
Z612	ISCO88 EMPLOYEES	NEW
What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to The International Standard Classification of Occupations, 1988 edition (ISCO88). Not shown.		
Z614	SIOPS EMPLOYEES	NEW
What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to the Standardized International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS). Not shown.		
Z615	NUMBER OF YEARS IN SIMILAR KIND OF WORK	NEW
For how many years have you had this kind of work, all positions and employers included.		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
	0	205 7,6
	1	163 6,1
	2	204 7,6
	3	205 7,6
	4	168 6,3
	5	164 6,1
	6	125 4,7
	7	105 3,9
	8	94 3,5
	9	77 2,9
	10	135 5,0
	11	71 2,6
	12	88 3,3
	13	57 2,1
	14	45 1,7
	15	67 2,5
	16	43 1,6
	17	32 1,2
	18	35 1,3
	19	25 0,9
	20	71 2,6
	21	27 1,0
	22	39 1,5
	23	35 1,3
	24	33 1,2
	25	50 1,9
	26	19 0,7
	27	20 0,7
	28	20 0,7

29		19	0,7
30		38	1,4
31		9	0,3
32		14	0,5
33		16	0,6
34		21	0,8
35		36	1,3
36		14	0,5
37		14	0,5
38		12	0,4
39		6	0,2
40		21	0,8
41		9	0,3
42		4	0,1
43		11	0,4
44		4	0,1
45		6	0,2
46		3	0,1
47		2	0,1
48		1	0,0
49		1	0,0
50		2	0,1
	Total	2685	100
88	Doesn't know	3	
99	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	
	Mean value	8,8	
	Standard deviation	11,3	

Z616	EMPLOYMENT CONTRACT		jfr X419
	Form of employment at current job.		
	The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Regular contract	2332	86,8
2	Fixed term contract	354	13,2
	Total	2686	100
9	No answer	3	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z617	ABSENT FROM WORK LAST 3 MONTHS		NEW
	Absent from current job last three months.		
	The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes	198	4,5

2	No	2479	56,1
3	Newly hired	9	0,2
	Total	2686	100
8	Doesn't know	3	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z618 REASON FOR ABSENCE LAST 3 MONTHS NEW

Reason for absence from current job last three months.

The table is valid for Z617 EQ 1.

1	On leave	117	59,1
2	Sick	59	29,8
3	Vacation	16	8,1
4	Labour shortage	6	3,0
	Total	198	100
	Not applicable	4217	
		4415	

Z619 ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, CURRENT JOB jfr X587 & X588

How good are the opportunities for advancement with your current employer?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	Very large	198	7,5
2	Relatively large	792	29,9
3	Relatively small	977	36,8
4	Very small	686	25,8
	Total	2662	100
9	No answer	36	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z620 ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, DIFFERENT EMPLOYERS jfr X587 & X588

How good are the opportunities for advancement in a job like yours, if you change employer?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	Very large	267	10,5
2	Relatively large	898	35,4
3	Relatively small	921	36,3
4	Very small	452	17,8
	Total	2538	100
9	No answer	151	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z621**YEAR OF EMPLOYMENT CURRENT JOB****jfr Y193, jfr
U350, jfr V400,
jfr W229**

Year when current employment started.

The table is valid for employees last week.

1960-65		5	0,2
1965-69		22	0,8
1970-74		79	3,0
1975-79		102	3,8
1980-84		111	4,2
1985-89		164	6,1
1990-94		166	6,2
1995-99		271	10,1
2000-04		467	17,5
2005-09		918	34,4
≥2010		367	13,7
	Total	2672	100
9999	No answer	17	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z622**NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES****X590, Y414, jfr
U357, jfr V404,
jfr W233**

How many persons do you supervise? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2015	75,3
1-10		408	15,2
11-20		121	4,5
21-30		43	1,6
31-40		18	0,7
41-50		16	0,6
51-60		8	0,3
70		6	0,2
80		11	0,4
100		3	0,1
200		14	0,5
300		6	0,2
400		2	0,1
500		3	0,1
≥800		3	0,1
	Total	2677	100,0
9999	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	1728	
		4415	

Z623 Has anyone of your subordinates a managing position? The table is valid for Z622 GT 0.	SUBORDINATES HAVE MANAGING POSITIONS <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>221</td> <td>33,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>449</td> <td>67,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>670</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>3745</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	221	33,0	2	No	449	67,0		Total	670	100		Not applicable	3745				4415		NEW																																																																				
1	Yes	221	33,0																																																																																							
2	No	449	67,0																																																																																							
	Total	670	100																																																																																							
	Not applicable	3745																																																																																								
		4415																																																																																								
Z624 Is any schooling or vocational training above elementary schooling necessary for your job? The table is valid for employees last week.	EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS <table border="0"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>2041</td> <td>76,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>637</td> <td>23,8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>2678</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>11</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>1726</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2041	76,2	2	No	637	23,8		Total	2678	100	9	No answer	11			Not applicable	1726				4415		X591, Y415, U358, V405, jfr W234																																																																
1	Yes	2041	76,2																																																																																							
2	No	637	23,8																																																																																							
	Total	2678	100																																																																																							
9	No answer	11																																																																																								
	Not applicable	1726																																																																																								
		4415																																																																																								
Z625 About how many years of education above elementary school are necessary? The table is valid for employees last week and Z624 EQ 1.	SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL <table border="0"> <tr><td>0</td><td></td><td>5</td><td>0,2</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td></td><td>78</td><td>3,9</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td></td><td>120</td><td>6,0</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td></td><td>721</td><td>35,9</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td></td><td>176</td><td>8,8</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td></td><td>168</td><td>8,4</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td></td><td>357</td><td>17,8</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td></td><td>202</td><td>10,0</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td></td><td>114</td><td>5,7</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td></td><td>15</td><td>0,7</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td></td><td>10</td><td>0,5</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td></td><td>9</td><td>0,4</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td></td><td>10</td><td>0,5</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td></td><td>7</td><td>0,3</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td></td><td>1</td><td>0,0</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td></td><td>8</td><td>0,4</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td></td><td>3</td><td>0,1</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td></td><td>2</td><td>0,1</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td></td><td>1</td><td>0,0</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td></td><td>2</td><td>0,1</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td></td><td>1</td><td>0,0</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td></td><td>1</td><td>0,0</td></tr> </table>	0		5	0,2	1		78	3,9	2		120	6,0	3		721	35,9	4		176	8,8	5		168	8,4	6		357	17,8	7		202	10,0	8		114	5,7	9		15	0,7	10		10	0,5	11		9	0,4	12		10	0,5	13		7	0,3	14		1	0,0	15		8	0,4	16		3	0,1	18		2	0,1	19		1	0,0	20		2	0,1	21		1	0,0	22		1	0,0	X592, Y416, U359, V406, jfr W234
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	Total	2011	100,0
99	No answer	30	
	Not applicable	2374	
		4415	
	Mean value (>0)	6,0	
	Standard deviation(>0)	11,6	

Z626 LEARNING TIME X593, Y417

Apart from the competence necessary to get a job such as yours, how long does it take to learn to do the job reasonably well?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	1 day or less	46	1,7
2	2-5 days	117	4,4
3	1-4 weeks	324	12,3
4	1-3 months	421	15,9
5	3 months - 1 year	653	24,7
6	1 to 2 years	531	20,1
7	More than 2 years	551	20,8
	Total	2643	100
9	No answer	46	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z627 USE OF PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE X594, Y418

To what extent can you in your daily work make use of what you've learnt through your education or previous job experience?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	To a very large extent	1006	37,6
2	To a large extent	747	27,9
3	To a certain extent	560	20,9
4	To a small extent	199	7,4
5	Not at all	164	6,1
	Total	2676	100
9	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z634	COMPENSATION FOR OVERTIME		X609
	Are you entitled to financial compensation for the overtime you work?		
	The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes	1860	69,9
2	No	802	30,1
	Total	2662	100
9	No answer	27	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	
Z635	NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK/YEAR		X627
	Do you ever stay overnight away from home because of your work, e.g., on a business trip? About how many nights are you away altogether during one year's time? This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for employees last week.		
0		1690	63,6
1-9		500	18,8
10-19		190	7,1
20-29		82	3,1
30-39		39	1,5
40-49		32	1,2
50-59		21	0,8
60-79		12	0,5
70-89		11	0,4
80-99		6	0,2
90-99		4	0,2
100-149		39	1,5
150-199		21	0,8
200-249		7	0,3
250-299		3	0,1
≥300		2	0,1
	Total	2659	100,0
999	No answer	30	
	Not applicable	1726	
Z636	TRAVELLING TIME MINUTES PER DAY		X651, jfr Y441, jfr U387, jfr V765, jfr W244, W636
	Number of minutes of total travel time to and from work during last week. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.		
0	No traveling time/lives in the work place	162	5,9
10-19		401	14,5
20-29		394	14,3
30-39		427	15,5
40-49		362	13,1

50-59		111	4,0
60-69		348	12,6
70-79		65	2,4
80-89		86	3,1
90-99		133	4,8
100-109		33	1,2
110-119		8	0,3
120-129		135	4,9
130-139		10	0,4
140-149		12	0,4
150-159		19	0,7
160-169		5	0,2
180-189		33	1,2
190-199		2	0,1
200-209		2	0,1
210-219		2	0,1
220-229		1	0,0
240-249		6	0,2
270-279		1	0,0
300-319		2	0,1
≥320		1	0,0
	Total	2761	100
997	Has no work place	167	
999	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	1357	
		4415	

Z637

FIXED MONTHLY SALARY BEFORE TAX

**X611, Y464,
U434, V720, jfr
W272, W275**

Salary in SEK per month before tax: fixed monthly salary. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		403	15,3
1-4999		11	0,4
5000-5999		33	1,3
10000-14999		92	3,5
15000-19999		258	9,8
20000-24999		663	25,2
25000-29999		487	18,5
30000-34999		267	10,1
35000-39999		141	5,4
40000-44999		97	3,7
45000-49999		55	2,1
50000-54999		41	1,6
55000-59999		21	0,8
60000-64999		21	0,8
65000-69999		8	0,3
≥70000		33	1,3
	Total	2631	100
	888888 Doesn't know	3	

999999	No answer	54
	Not applicable	1727
		4415

Z638 **WEEKLY WAGE BEFORE TAX** **X612, Y465,
U435, V721, jfr
W272, W275**

Salary in SEK per week before tax: fixed weekly wage.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2680	99,7
7000		1	0,3
	Total	1	100
888888	Doesn't know	3	
99999	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z639 **FIXED HOURLY WAGE** **X613, Y466,
U436, V722, jfr
W272, W275**

Salary in SEK per hour before tax: flat rate per hour. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2341	88,2
1-74		1	0,0
75-99		19	0,7
100-124		155	5,8
125-149		75	2,8
150-174		40	1,5
175-199		7	0,3
200-224		5	0,2
225-249		3	0,1
250-274		3	0,1
≥300		4	0,2
	Total	2653	100
888	Doesn't know	3	
999	No answer	32	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	
	Mean value	15,3	
	Standard deviation	45	

Z640**INDIVIDUAL PIECE-RATE****X614, Y467,
U437, jfr V723,
V724, jfr
W272, W275**

Average earnings in SEK per hour before tax: individual piece-rate.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2673	99,4
13		1	0,1
38		1	0,1
80		1	0,1
110		1	0,1
125		1	0,1
	Total	2678	100
888	Doesn't know	3	
999	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z641**GROUP PIECE-RATE****X615, Y468,
U438, V725, jfr
W272, W275**

Average earnings in SEK per hour before tax: group piece-rate.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2656	99,2
5		1	0,0
12		2	0,1
15		2	0,1
16		1	0,0
17		1	0,0
43		1	0,0
48		1	0,0
155		1	0,0
165		1	0,0
172		1	0,0
175		1	0,0
178		1	0,0
180		2	0,1
185		1	0,0
190		1	0,0
195		1	0,0
200		2	0,1
225		1	0,0
	Total	2678	100
888	Doesn't know	3	
999	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z642**MONTHLY SALARY W BONUS/COMMISSION****X616, jfr Y469,
jfr U439, jfr
V726, jfr
W272, W275**

Average monthly salary before tax: fixed salary with bonus or commission, not included in any alternative above. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2528	95,0
1-4999		68	2,6
5000-9999		25	0,9
10000-14999		12	0,5
15000-19999		4	0,2
20000-24999		4	0,2
25000-29999		3	0,1
30000-34999		4	0,2
35000-39999		6	0,2
≥40000		6	0,2
	Total	2660	100
888888	Doesn't know	3	
999999	No answer	25	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z643**COMP. FOR INCONVENIENT WORKING HOURS****X617, Y470,
U441, V729, jfr
W272**

Special compensation for uncomfortable working hours not included above, in SEK per month. This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2490	94,7
1-999		21	0,8
1000-1999		46	1,8
2000-2999		27	1,0
3000-3999		12	0,5
4000-4999		9	0,3
5000-5999		5	0,2
6000-6999		4	0,2
7000-7999		5	0,2
8000-8999		2	0,1
≥10000		7	0,3
	Total	2628	100
888888	Doesn't know	3	
999999	No answer	57	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z644**OTHER WAGE FORM SEK/MONTH****X618, Y471,
U442, V730, jfr
W272**

Salary in SEK per month: other wage form.

The table is valid for employees last week.

0		2646	98,9
400		1	0,0
500		1	0,0
1000		2	0,1
1300		1	0,0
1500		1	0,0
3808		1	0,0
4500		1	0,0
5000		1	0,0
5900		1	0,0
10000		1	0,0
11000		1	0,0
15000		1	0,0
15500		1	0,0
17000		1	0,0
17500		1	0,0
19000		2	0,1
20000		2	0,1
24000		1	0,0
28000		1	0,0
30000		3	0,1
32000		1	0,0
41500		1	0,0
50000		1	0,0
200000		1	0,0
	Total	2675	100
888888	Doesn't know	3	
999999	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z645**GROSS HOURLY WAGE****X619, jfr Y472,
jfr U443, jfr
V727, jfr W650**Gross salary in SEK per hour, calculated by adding Z637 – Z643 converted into hourly wage by using Z631.
This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for employees last week.

3-112		263	9,8
113-123		261	9,7
124-131		260	9,7
132-141		283	10,5
142-149		230	8,6
150-163		310	11,5
164-179		256	9,5
180-208		287	10,7

209-277		269	10,0
≥278		269	10,0
	Total	2583	100
8888	Doesn't know	3	
9999	No answer	102	
	Not applicable	1727	
		4415	

Z646	MONTHLY SALARY AFTER TAX		X620, Y473, U433, V490, jfr W276
	How much is your take-home pay (after tax) from your regular job each month? This variable is divided into categories.		
1-999		9	0,4
1000-1999		10	0,4
2000-2999		16	0,6
3000-3999		10	0,4
4000-4999		9	0,4
5000-5999		15	0,6
6000-6999		19	0,8
7000-7999		21	0,8
8000-8999		38	1,5
9000-9999		32	1,3
10000-10999		47	1,9
11000-11999		46	1,8
12000-12999		77	3,1
13000-13999		91	3,6
14000-14999		133	5,3
15000-15999		158	6,3
16000-16999		188	7,5
17000-17999		206	8,2
18000-18999		200	8,0
19000-19999		156	6,2
20000-20999		202	8,1
21000-21999		124	5,0
22000-22999		127	5,1
23000-23999		92	3,7
24000-24999		75	3,0
25000-29999		237	9,5
30000-34999		87	3,5
35000-39999		28	1,1
40000-44999		25	1,0
45000-45999		5	0,2
50000-59999		9	0,4
60000-69999		5	0,2
80000-89999		1	0,0
≥90000		1	0,0
	Total	2499	100
999999	No answer	150	
	Not applicable	1766	
		4415	

	Mean value		18583	
	Standard deviation		7108	
Z647	PUNCTUALITY DEMANDED			X628, Y482, U422, V470, W254
	Is punctuality demanded at your workplace?			
	The table is valid for employees last week.			
	1	Yes	1768	65,9
	2	No	915	34,1
		Total	2683	100
	9	No answer	6	
		Not applicable	1726	
			4415	
Z648	PUNCH CLOCK			X629, Y483, U423, V471, W255
	Is there a punch clock you must use?			
	The table is valid for employees last week.			
	1	Yes	739	27,5
	2	No	1945	72,5
		Total	2684	100
	9	No answer	5	
		Not applicable	1726	
			4415	
Z649	FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS			X630, Y484, U424
	Do you have any kind of flexible working hours, i.e. can you within certain limits decide yourself when you want to begin and end work?			
	The table is valid for employees last week.			
	1	Yes	1644	61,3
	2	No	1040	38,7
		Total	2684	100
	9	No answer	5	
		Not applicable	1726	
			4415	

Z650	LEVEL OF FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS	NEW
Can you make a decision to move your own working hours up to an hour, several hours or one to several days?		
Tabellen gäller om Z649 EQ 1.		
1	Up to an hour	524 32,0
2	Up to a few hours	458 27,9
3	Several hours	365 22,3
4	One to several days	292 17,8
	Total	1639 100
8	Doesn't know	5
	Not applicable	2771
		4,415
Z651	CAN GO ON AN ERRAND	X631, Y485, U427, V474, W258
If you need to go on a private errand, can you leave your workplace for about half an hour without informing a supervisor?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes	1661 62,1
2	No	1015 37,9
	Total	2676 100
9	No answer	13
	Not applicable	1726
		4415
Z652	CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK	X633, Y487, U429
Can you yourself determine your pace of work?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes	1704 63,7
2	No	973 36,3
	Total	2677 100
9	No answer	12
	Not applicable	1726
		4415
Z653	INFLUENCE WHAT TASKS	X634, Y489
To what extent do you have influence over what tasks you carry out?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	To a very large extent	585 21,9
2	To a large extent	742 27,7
3	To a certain extent	830 31,0
4	To a small extent	324 12,1

5	Not at all	196	7,3
	Total	2677	100
9	No answer	12	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z654 INFLUENCE WORKING METHODS X635, Y490

To what extent do you have influence over how you carry out your tasks?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	To a very large extent	880	32,9
2	To a large extent	951	35,5
3	To a certain extent	548	20,5
4	To a small extent	193	7,2
5	Not at all	105	3,9
	Total	2677	100
9	No answer	12	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z655 LEARNS NEW THINGS X636, Y491

To what extent does your work mean that you learn new things?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	To a very large extent	524	19,6
2	To a large extent	946	35,4
3	To a certain extent	816	30,5
4	To a small extent	296	11,1
5	Not at all	92	3,4
	Total	2674	100
9	No answer	15	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z656 GETS SUPPORT FROM WORKMATES X638, Y494

To what extent does your work mean that you can get support and help from workmates when needed?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	To a very large extent	875	32,7
2	To a large extent	1113	41,6
3	To a certain extent	484	18,1
4	To a small extent	138	5,2
5	Not at all	65	2,4
	Total	2675	100
9	No answer	14	
	Not applicable	1726	

4415

Z657**BOSS' NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES****X645**

How many persons are placed directly under your immediate supervisor/boss?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	Have no boss	63	2,4
2	1-3 persons	292	11,0
3	4-9 persons	594	22,4
4	10-19 persons	628	23,7
5	20-49 persons	723	27,3
6	50-99 persons	169	6,4
7	100 or more persons	107	4,0
8	Do not know how many are directly under boss	62	2,3
9	Do not know who boss is	9	0,3
	Total	2647	100
99	No answer	42	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z658**SEX OF BOSS****X646**

Is your immediate supervisor/boss a man or a woman?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	Man	1578	61,4
2	Woman	992	38,6
	Total	2570	100
9	Do not know who boss is	9	
77	Have no boss	63	
99	No answer	47	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z659**BOSS BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY****X647**

Was your immediate supervisor/boss born in Sweden or another country?

The table is valid for employees last week.

1	Born in Sweden	2307	90,9
2	Born in another country	232	9,1
	Total	2539	100
9	Do not know who boss is	9	
77	Have no boss	63	
99	No answer	78	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z660	BOSS IS TOP MANAGER AT WORKPLACE	NEW
Is your immediate supervisor/boss the top manager in the workplace?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes	995 38,8
2	No	1568 61,2
	Total	2563 100
8	Doesn't know	12
9	Do not know who boss is	9
77	Have no boss	63
99	No answer	42
	Not applicable	1726
		4415
Z661	RESPONDENT'S WORK DIFFICULT TO MONITOR	NEW
With what difficulty do you think your immediate supervisor/boss can gain knowledge of your work efforts?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Very difficult	181 7,1
2	Fairly difficult	541 21,2
3	Not particularly difficult	808 31,6
4	Fairly easy	661 25,9
5	Very easy	364 14,2
	Total	2555 100
8	Doesn't know	20
9	No answer	9
77	Have no boss	63
99	No answer	42
	Not applicable	1726
		4415
Z662	WORK EFFORTS, MOST IMPORTANT REASON	NEW
There are many reasons for putting effort into work. Which one of these reasons is most important for you?		
The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Own satisfaction	1356 50,8
2	Keep the job	137 5,1
3	Your effort is important to others	564 21,1
4	Higher salary / promotion	68 2,5
5	Interesting work tasks	450 16,8
6	Duty	96 3,6
	Total	2671 100
8	Doesn't know	13
9	No answer	5
	Not applicable	1726
		4415

Z663	WORK EFFORTS, SECOND MOST IMPORTANT REASON	NEW	
Which one of these reasons is second most important for you?			
The table is valid for employees last week.			
1	Own satisfaction	748	28,2
2	Keep the job	245	9,2
3	Your effort is important to others	616	23,2
4	Higher salary / promotion	190	7,2
5	Interesting work tasks	699	26,4
6	Duty	153	5,8
	Total	2651	100
8	Doesn't know	19	
9	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	1744	
		4415	
Z664	DIFFICULT TO REPLACE RESPONDENT	X648	
In your opinion, how difficult would it be for your employer to replace you if you quit?			
The table is valid for employees last week.			
1	Very difficult	301	11,3
2	Fairly difficult	1053	39,7
3	Not particularly difficult	818	30,8
4	Fairly easy	295	11,1
5	Very easy	187	7,0
	Total	2654	100
9	No answer	35	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	
Z665	DIFFICULT TO GET NEW JOB	X649	
If you for some reason had to leave your present employer, how difficult do you think it would be for you to find a new job as good as your current one?			
The table is valid for employees last week.			
1	Very difficult	358	13,6
2	Fairly difficult	923	35,0
3	Not particularly difficult	647	24,6
4	Fairly easy	526	20,0
5	Very easy	181	6,9
	Total	2635	100
9	No answer	54	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	

Z666	REMAINS WITH EMPLOYER, 1 YEAR FROM NOW		NEW
	The table is valid for employees last week.		
1	Yes, would like to stay	1794	68,9
2	Yes, no other option	331	12,7
3	Yes, other reason	74	2,8
4	No, employment's unsecure	48	1,8
5	No, would like to change	201	7,7
6	No, would like to change and employment's unsecure	30	1,2
7	No, other reason	125	4,8
	Total	2603	100
8	Doesn't know	81	
9	No answer	5	
	Not applicable	1726	
		4415	
Z667	HEAVY LIFTING		X653, Y507, U447, V492, jfr W277
	Do you have to be able to lift 60 kilos in order to manage your job? If yes: Do you need such physical strength daily in your work, a few times per week or less often?		
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.		
11	Less often	181	5,9
12	A few times per week	222	7,3
13	Daily	215	7,1
20	No	2431	79,7
	Total	3049	100
99	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	
Z668	PHYSICALLY DEMANDING		X654, Y508, U448, V493, W278
	Is your type of work physically demanding in any other way?		
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.		
1	Yes	1320	43,3
2	No	1730	56,7
	Total	3050	100
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	

Z669	DAILY SWEATING			X655, Y509, U449, V494, W279
	Does your work make you sweaty from physical exertion every day?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
	1	Yes	548	18,0
	2	No	2502	82,0
		Total	3050	100
	9	No answer	9	
		Not applicable	1356	
			4415	
Z670	MENTALLY TAXING			X656, Y510, U451, V496, W281
	Är ditt arbete psykiskt ansträngande?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
	1	Yes	1760	57,7
	2	No	1288	42,3
		Total	3048	100
	9	No answer	11	
		Not applicable	1356	
			4415	
Z671	STRESSFUL WORK			X657, Y511, U452, V497, W282
	Is your work stressful?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
	1	Yes	2204	72,3
	2	No	846	27,7
		Total	3050	100
	9	No answer	9	
		Not applicable	1356	
			4415	
Z672	MONOTONOUS WORK			X658, Y512, U453, V498, W283
	Is your work monotonous?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
	1	Yes	560	18,4
	2	No	2490	81,6
		Total	3050	100
	9	No answer	9	
		Not applicable	1356	
			4415	

Z676**MANAGING WORK****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you lead the work of other personnel, i.e. directing, instructing, coordinating etc.?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	1669	54,8
2	A small part of the time	849	27,9
3	Half of the time	215	7,1
4	A large part of the time	144	4,7
5	All of the time	170	5,6
	Total	3047	100
8	Doesn't know	8	
9	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	

Z677**WORK WITH HUMANS, NO MANAGING****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with customers, patients, pupils or other humans besides other personnel?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	758	24,9
2	A small part of the time	701	23,0
3	Half of the time	271	8,9
4	A large part of the time	386	12,7
5	All of the time	934	30,6
	Total	3050	100
8	Doesn't know	5	
9	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	

Z678**WORK WITH TEXT AND/OR NUMBERS****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with text and/or numbers, i.e. writing, counting, reading, editing etc.?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	596	19,6
2	A small part of the time	1068	35,0
3	Half of the time	307	10,1
4	A large part of the time	400	13,1
5	All of the time	677	22,2
	Total	3048	100
8	Doesn't know	7	
9	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	1356	

Z679**WORK WITH TOOLS****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with tools or other equipment, e.g. manufacturing, building, preparing, packing, transporting or similar tasks?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	1637	53,7
2	A small part of the time	492	16,1
3	Half of the time	167	5,5
4	A large part of the time	192	6,3
5	All of the time	559	18,3
	Total	3047	100
8	Doesn't know	8	
9	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	

Z680**WORK WITH HIGH MENTAL EFFORT****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with high mental effort, near your limits?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	761	25,2
2	A small part of the time	1087	35,9
3	Half of the time	380	12,6
4	A large part of the time	467	15,4
5	All of the time	330	10,9
	Total	3025	100
8	Doesn't know	29	
9	No answer	5	
	Not applicable	1356	
		4415	

Z681**WORK WITH LOW MENTAL EFFORT****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with low mental effort, far from your limits?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	1334	44,5
2	A small part of the time	835	27,9
3	Half of the time	369	12,3
4	A large part of the time	305	10,2
5	All of the time	155	5,2
	Total	2998	100
8	Doesn't know	55	
9	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	1356	

4415

Z682**WORK WITH EMOTIONALLY DEMANDING WORK TASKS****NEW**

How large amount of your working time do you work with emotionally demanding tasks?

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

1	Not at all	1681	55,4
2	A small part of the time	771	25,4
3	Half of the time	182	6,0
4	A large part of the time	189	6,2
5	All of the time	210	6,9
	Total	3033	100
8	Doesn't know	19	
9	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	1357	
		4415	

Z683**ABSENCE DUE TO ILLNESS****X669**

During the last 12 months, about how many days have you been absent from work due to own illness? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

0		1391	45,7
1-9		1161	38,2
10-19		267	8,8
20-29		62	2,0
30-39		55	1,8
40-49		17	0,6
50-59		2	0,1
60-69		17	0,6
70-79		5	0,2
80-89		5	0,2
90-99		15	0,5
100-199		23	0,8
200-299		6	0,2
≥300		16	0,5
	Total	3042	100
999	No answer	16	
	Not applicable	1367	
		4415	

Z684	<p data-bbox="354 219 432 241">NOISE</p> <p data-bbox="354 277 1222 300">Is it noisy where you work? If yes: Is it noisy all the time or just sometimes? Is the noise deafening?</p> <p data-bbox="354 336 804 358">The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.</p> <table data-bbox="354 394 1276 712"> <tbody> <tr> <td>111</td> <td>Sometimes deafening</td> <td>280</td> <td>9,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>112</td> <td>Sometimes, not deafening</td> <td>376</td> <td>12,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>121</td> <td>Always deafening</td> <td>230</td> <td>7,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>122</td> <td>Always, not deafening</td> <td>220</td> <td>7,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200</td> <td>No</td> <td>1944</td> <td>63,7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>3050</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>999</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>8</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>1357</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	111	Sometimes deafening	280	9,2	112	Sometimes, not deafening	376	12,3	121	Always deafening	230	7,5	122	Always, not deafening	220	7,2	200	No	1944	63,7		Total	3050	100	999	No answer	8			Not applicable	1357			Total	4415		X663, Y515, U456, V501, W286
111	Sometimes deafening	280	9,2																																			
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	Not applicable	1357																																				
	Total	4415																																				
Z685	<p data-bbox="354 797 671 819">MONOTONOUS MOVEMENTS</p> <p data-bbox="354 855 1085 878">Do you in your work have to perform many repetitive and monotonous movements?</p> <p data-bbox="354 913 804 936">The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.</p> <table data-bbox="354 972 1276 1178"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>1425</td> <td>46,8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>1621</td> <td>53,2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>3046</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>12</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>1357</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Yes	1425	46,8	2	No	1621	53,2		Total	3046	100	9	No answer	12				1357				4415		X664, Y517, U465, V511												
1	Yes	1425	46,8																																			
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	Total	3046	100																																			
9	No answer	12																																				
		1357																																				
		4415																																				
Z686	<p data-bbox="354 1263 703 1285">UNSUITABLE WORK POSITIONS</p> <p data-bbox="354 1321 1145 1344">Does your work force you to take bent, twisted or in other ways unsuitable work positions?</p> <p data-bbox="354 1379 804 1402">The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.</p> <table data-bbox="354 1438 1276 1644"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>1130</td> <td>37,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> <td>1919</td> <td>62,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>3049</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>No answer</td> <td>9</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Not applicable</td> <td>1357</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Yes	1130	37,1	2	No	1919	62,9		Total	3049	100	9	No answer	9			Not applicable	1357				4415		X665, Y518, U466, V512												
1	Yes	1130	37,1																																			
2	No	1919	62,9																																			
	Total	3049	100																																			
9	No answer	9																																				
	Not applicable	1357																																				
		4415																																				
Z687	<p data-bbox="354 1729 568 1751">GAS, DUST, SMOKE</p> <p data-bbox="354 1787 1289 1809">Are you in your work exposed to gas, dust or smoke? If yes: Is this so all the time, often or only sometimes?</p> <p data-bbox="354 1845 804 1868">The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.</p> <table data-bbox="354 1904 1276 2024"> <tbody> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>All the time</td> <td>180</td> <td>5,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>Often</td> <td>199</td> <td>6,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13</td> <td>Sometimes</td> <td>346</td> <td>11,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>No</td> <td>2325</td> <td>76,2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	11	All the time	180	5,9	12	Often	199	6,5	13	Sometimes	346	11,3	20	No	2325	76,2	X666, Y519, U468, V514, jfr W290																				
11	All the time	180	5,9																																			
12	Often	199	6,5																																			
13	Sometimes	346	11,3																																			
20	No	2325	76,2																																			

	Total		3050	100
99	No answer		8	
	Not applicable		1357	
			4415	
Z688	DIRTY WORK			X667, jfr U455, jfr V500, jfr W285
	Do you get dirty in your work? If yes: Do you get just a little dirty or very dirty?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
11	A little dirty		826	27,1
12	Very dirty		232	7,6
13	No		1991	65,3
	Total		3049	100
99	No answer		9	27,1
	Not applicable		1357	
			4415	
Z689	TOXIC SUBSTANCES, ACIDS, EXPLOSIVES			X668, Y521, U470, V516, jfr W291
	Do you come into contact with toxic substances, corroding acids or explosives? If yes: Does this happen all the time, often or only sometimes?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
11	All the time		69	2,3
12	Often		104	3,4
13	Sometimes		355	11,7
20	No		2518	82,7
	Total		3046	100
99	No answer		12	
	Not applicable		1357	
			4415	
Z690	SATISFACTION WITH WAGES			X671, Y523
	How satisfied are you with your current wages (income from work)?			
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.			
1	Very satisfied		417	13,7
2	Rather satisfied		1332	43,8
3	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied		661	21,7
4	Rather dissatisfied		437	14,4
5	Very dissatisfied		194	6,4
	Total		3041	100
9	No answer		17	
	Not applicable		1357	
			4415	

Z691	JOB ATTITUDE		NEW
	If you didn't need the salary, how much would you like to work in your current job?		
	The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.		
	1	Not at all if I didn't need the salary	647 21,4
	2	1-10 hours/week	288 9,5
	3	11-20 hours/week	818 27,1
	4	21-34 hours/week	778 25,7
	5	35-40 hours/week	392 13,0
	6	More than 40 hours/week	99 3,3
		Total	3022 100
	8	Doesn't know	29
	9	No answer	7
		Not applicable	1357 4415
Z694	NYK80 SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER		Y536, jfr U498
	Profession/occupation for self-employed/farmer according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.		
Z695	NYK85 SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER		NEW
	Profession/occupation for self-employed/farmer according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's current job. Not shown.		
Z700	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES IN FIRM/FARM		jfr X684, jfr Y537, jfr U499, jfr V538, jfr W315
	How many employees are there in the company or on the farm? (Assisting family member should not be counted as employee). Here this variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.		
	1		49 29,2
	2		26 15,5
	3		15 8,9
	4		12 7,1
	5		13 7,7
	6		5 3,0
	7		9 5,4
	8		4 2,4
	9		2 1,2
	10-19		16 9,5
	20-29		8 4,8
	30-49		3 1,8
	50-99		3 1,8
	100-200		3 1,8
		Total	168 100
	7777	No employees	288
	9999	No answer	3

	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z701	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS		jfr X685, jfr Y542, jfr U501, jfr V540, jfr W317
	How many hours do you normally work in the company/farm per week seen on average over a whole year? This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.		
	1-9	62	13,7
	10-19	40	8,9
	20-29	51	11,3
	30-39	47	10,4
	40-49	121	26,8
	50-59	78	17,3
	60-69	35	7,8
	70-79	9	2,0
	80-89	7	1,6
	90-99	1	0,2
	Total	451	100
999	No answer	8	
	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z702	HOURS BUSY WEEKS		jfr X686
	How many hours per week do you usually work in the company/farm during busy weeks? This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.		
	1-9	23	5,2
	10-19	30	6,8
	20-29	49	11,1
	30-39	29	6,6
	40-49	71	16,1
	50-59	90	20,5
	60-69	71	16,1
	70-79	40	9,1
	80-89	25	5,7
	90-99	7	1,6
	≥100	5	1,1
	Total	440	100
999	No answer	23	
	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z703**HOURS QUIET WEEKS****jfr X687**

How many hours per week do you usually work in the company/farm during quiet weeks? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.

0		1	0,2
1-9		88	20,0
10-19		40	9,1
20-29		71	16,1
30-39		80	18,1
40-49		108	24,5
50-59		34	7,7
60-69		12	2,7
70-79		4	0,9
80-89		3	0,7
	Total	441	100
999	No answer	18	0,2
	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z704**NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKS****jfr X688**

About how many busy weeks do you have during a one-year period?

The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.

0		49	11,9
1		5	1,2
2		15	3,6
3		19	4,6
4		35	8,5
5		20	4,9
6		24	5,8
7		9	2,2
8		27	6,6
9		2	0,5
10		47	11,4
12		21	5,1
14		4	1,0
15		15	3,6
16		12	2,9
17		1	0,2
18		1	0,2
20		26	6,3
22		2	0,5
23		1	0,2
24		5	1,2
25		8	1,9
26		13	3,2
27		1	0,2

8		21	6,7
9		2	0,6
10		9	2,9
12		4	1,3
16		1	0,3
24		1	0,3
25		1	0,3
51		1	0,3
	Total	312	100
66	Did not work in company / farm 2009	7	
77	Had no vacation	127	
99	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	3960	
		4415	
	Mean value	4,7	
	Standard deviation	3,9	

Z707

VALUE OF COMPANY/FARM

NEW

In your estimation, how much is the company/farm worth if you exclude loans? In 100 SEK.

The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.

<0		2	0,6
0		35	10,6
10-49		91	27,6
50-99		60	18,2
100-149		10	3,0
150-199		23	7,0
200-249		5	1,5
250-259		17	5,2
300-349		4	1,2
350-399		6	1,8
400-449		2	0,6
450-499		12	3,6
500-549		3	0,9
550-599		5	1,5
600-699		6	1,8
700-749		1	0,3
750-799		5	1,5
≥800		43	13,0
	Total	330	100
88888888	Doesn't know	116	
99999999	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z708**RESPONDENT'S SHARE OF OWNING IN COMPANY/FARM****NEW**

Are these assets mostly owned by you, your partner or do you have equal shares? Respondent's share of owning.

The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.

0		37	8,3
2		2	0,4
8		1	0,2
10		1	0,2
11		1	0,2
17		3	0,7
20		3	0,7
23		1	0,2
25		7	1,6
30		1	0,2
33		12	2,7
40		5	1,1
45		1	0,2
49		1	0,2
50		95	21,3
51		2	0,4
52		1	0,2
60		2	0,4
66		1	0,2
70		1	0,2
75		2	0,4
80		3	0,7
90		1	0,2
95		1	0,2
100		262	58,6
	Total	447	100
888	Doesn't know	6	
999	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	3956	
		4415	

Z709**PARTNER'S SHARE OF OWNING IN COMPANY/FARM****NEW**

Are these assets mostly owned by you, your partner or do you have equal shares? Partner's share of owning.

The table is valid for Z601 EQ 1 or Z602 EQ 1.

0		277	75,1
20		2	0,5
25		4	1,1
33		2	0,5
50		62	16,8
60		2	0,5
100		20	5,4
	Total	168	100

	777	Have no partner	82	
	999	No answer	7	
		Not applicable	3957	
			4415	
Z710	SEI FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE			X691, Y545, jfr U508
	What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI).			
	The table is valid for Z603 EQ 1.			
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	9	7,4
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	25	20,5
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	3	2,5
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	7	5,7
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	12	9,8
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	1	0,8
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	22	18
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	1	0,8
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	18	14,8
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	5	4,1
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	6	4,9
	60	Self-employed professionals	5	4,1
	79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	4	3,3
	89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	4	3,3
		Total	122	100
	99	Unclassified	1	
		Not applicable	4292	
			4415	
Z711	NYK80 FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE			X692, Y546, jfr U509
	What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for freelance occupation. Not shown.			
Z712	NYK85 FREELANCE OCCUPATION/SIDE-LINE			X693
	Y What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for freelance occupation. Not shown.			
Z717	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS			X694, Y548, U511, V547, jfr W323
	How many hours a week do you work with your occupation/side-line on average, seen over a year? This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for Z603 EQ 1.			
	1		13	11,1
	2		11	9,4
	3		12	10,3
	4		6	5,1
	5		15	12,8

6		8	6,8
8		6	5,1
10-19		25	21,4
20-29		13	11,1
30-39		5	4,3
40-49		1	0,9
50-59		1	0,9
≥90		1	0,9
	Total	117	100
999	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	4292	
		4415	

Z718 SEI UNEMPLOYED X695, Y549, jfr U516

What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI).

The table is valid for Z604 EQ 1.

11	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	16	7,6
12	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	49	23,3
21	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	30	14,3
22	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	25	11,9
33	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	12	5,7
35	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	18	8,6
45	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	35	16,7
46	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	11	5,2
60	Self-employed professionals	10	4,8
79	Self-employed, unknown size of firm	3	1,4
89	Farmer, unknown size of farm	1	0,5
	Total	210	100
99	Unclassified	22	
	Not applicable	4183	
		4415	

Z719 NYK80 UNEMPLOYED X696, Y550, jfr U517

What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for unemployed. Not shown.

Z720 NYK85 UNEMPLOYED X697

What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.

Z725**WEEKS UNEMPLOYED****X698, Y551,
U525, V559, jfr
W345**

How long have you now been looking/waiting for work/been unemployed/laid off? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for Z604 EQ 1.

1-9		53	23,8
10-19		37	16,6
20-29		28	12,6
30-39		14	6,3
40-49		8	3,6
50-59		14	6,3
60-69		3	1,3
70-79		7	3,1
80-89		5	2,2
90-99		1	0,4
100-109		19	8,5
110-129		4	1,8
120-139		2	0,9
130-149		1	0,4
140-119		1	0,4
150-159		11	4,9
160-169		2	0,9
200-299		6	2,7
300-399		3	1,3
400-499		2	0,9
500-599		1	0,4
≥600		1	0,4
	Total	223	100
999	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	4183	
		4415	

Z726**PREFERED WORKING HOURS****NEW**

How many hours per week would you like to work?

The table is valid for Z604 EQ 1.

0		6	2,6
5		1	0,4
10		2	0,9
15		1	0,4
16		1	0,4
20		18	7,8
24		2	0,9
25		1	0,4
28		1	0,4
30		13	5,7
35		2	0,9
40		180	78,3

45		1	0,4
50		1	0,4
	Total	230	100
999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	4183	
		4415	

Z727

WORK ATTITUDE

NEW

If you didn't need the salary, how much would you like to work?

The table is valid for Z604 EQ 1 AND Z726 GT 0.

1	Not at all if I didn't need the salary	33	15,4
2	1-10 hours/week	14	6,5
3	11-20 hours/week	67	31,3
4	21-34 hours/week	40	18,7
5	35-40 hours/week	50	23,4
6	More than 40 hours/week	10	4,7
	Total	214	100
8	Doesn't know	10	
9	No answer	8	
	Not applicable	4183	
	Total	4415	

Z728

YEAR OF RETIREMENT

**jfr Y552, jfr
U552, jfr V584,
jfr W362**

Number of years between year of retirement and interview date.

The table is valid for Z605 EQ 1

0		41	5,6
1		59	8,0
2		63	8,6
3		58	7,9
4		57	7,8
5		54	7,4
6		41	5,6
7		55	7,5
8		53	7,2
9		33	4,5
10		46	6,3
11		33	4,5
12		26	3,5
13		18	2,5
14		18	2,5
15		15	2,0
16		12	1,6
17		10	1,4
18		8	1,1
19		11	1,5

20		7	1,0
21		1	0,1
22		3	0,4
23		2	0,3
24		1	0,1
25		1	0,1
26		1	0,1
27		1	0,1
29		1	0,1
30		1	0,1
32		1	0,1
38		1	0,1
51		1	0,1
	Total	733	100
88	Doesn't know	5	
96	Not pensioner	3331	
99	No answer	353	
		4415	
	Mean value	7,3	
	Standard deviation	5,8	

Z736

FORMERLY SELF-EMPLOYED/FARMER - EMPLOYEES

**jfr X705, Y557,
U558**

Retired company owners: How many employees did you have?

0	No employees	32	50,8
1		3	4,8
2		5	7,9
3		4	6,3
4		1	1,6
5		3	4,8
7		1	1,6
8		2	3,2
10		1	1,6
11		1	1,6
12		1	1,6
15		4	6,3
17		1	1,6
18		1	1,6
35		1	1,6
70		1	1,6
100		1	1,6
	Total	63	100
	Not applicable	4352	
		4415	

Z737	WANTS TO WORK			X706, Y558, U559, V586, W363
	Would you like to have a job now if you could find something suitable? The table is valid for pensioners not working last week.			
1	Yes		172	20,4
2	No		672	79,6
	Total		844	100
8	No answer		8	
	Not applicable		3563	
			4415	

Z738	WANTED WORKING HOURS PER WEEK			X707, Y559, jfr U560-U562
	How many hours per week would you like to work?			
	The table is valid for Z737 EQ 1.			
3			1	0,6
4			2	1,2
5			3	1,8
7			1	0,6
8			8	4,8
10			34	20,4
12			2	1,2
15			11	6,6
16			4	2,4
18			1	0,6
20			46	27,5
24			2	1,2
25			4	2,4
30			11	6,6
35			1	0,6
40			36	21,6
	Total		167	100
999	No answer		5	
	Not applicable		4243	
			4415	
	Mean value		21,4	
	Standard deviation		11,6	

Z739	DOES NOT MANAGE TO WORK			X708, Y560, U563, V591
	Is that because you feel could not manage work right now?			
	The table is valid for Z737 EQ 2.			
1	Yes (answer is obvious, question not asked)		87	12,9
2	Yes, feel unable to work at present		214	31,8
3	No		371	55,2
	Total		672	100

	Not applicable	3743	
	Total	4415	
Z740	NOT PROFITABLE		X709, Y562, U565, V593
	Financially speaking, do you think it doesn't pay to be gainfully employed?		
1	Yes	77	22,1
2	No	272	77,9
	Total	349	100
9	No answer	22	
	Not applicable	4044	
	Total	4415	
Z748	HOURS – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES		jfr X713, Y567, jfr U542, jfr V576
	Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.		
0		13	0,3
0.5-4		419	9,7
5-9		1174	27,3
10-14		1567	36,4
15-19		598	13,9
20-24		381	8,8
25-30		91	2,1
30-34		35	0,8
35-39		20	0,5
40-44		11	0,3
50-54		1	0,0
	Total	4310	100
88	Doesn't know	85	1,9
99	No answer	20	0,5
		4415	100
	Mean value	11,3	
	Standard deviation	6,4	
Z749	HOURS RESPONDENT – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES		jfr X714, Y568, jfr U543, jfr V577
	Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z748 GT 0.		
0		112	2,9
0.5-4		1433	32,9
5-9		1678	38,9
10-14		750	17,4
15-19		202	4,7
20-24		92	2,1
25-29		33	0,8

30-34		8	0,2
35-39		5	0,1
40-44		1	0,0
	Total	4314	100
88	Doesn't know	67	
99	No answer	19	
	Not applicable	15	
		4415	
	Mean value	6,8	
	Standard deviation	4,9	

Z750 HOURS – CARE OF CLOTHING **jfr X715, Y569,**

jfr U536, U538,

jfr V570, V572

Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on care of clothing (laundry, ironing, etc.) in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.

0		39	0,9
.5		32	0,7
1		479	11,2
1.5		36	0,8
2		948	22,2
2.5		26	0,6
3		786	18,4
3.5		29	0,7
4		598	14,0
4.5		5	0,1
5		524	12,3
5.5		1	0,0
6		178	4,2
6.5		1	0,0
7		219	5,1
8		98	2,3
9		9	0,2
10		188	4,4
11		1	0,0
≥12		78	1,8
	Total	4275	100,0
88	Doesn't know	120	
99	No answer	99	
		4415	
	Mean value	3,9	
	Standard deviation	2,5	

6		149	3,5
7		219	5,1
8		71	1,6
9		12	0,3
10		123	2,9
12		13	0,3
14		37	0,9
15		14	0,3
≥16		22	0,5
	Total	4306	100
88	Doesn't know	89	
99	No answer	20	
		4415	
	Mean value	3,5	
	Standard deviation	2,6	

Z753	HOURS RESPONDENT - CLEANING	jfr X718, Y572, jfr U541, jfr V575	
	Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on cleaning. This variable is divided into categories.		
	The table is valid for Z752 GT 0.		
0		374	8,7
.5		285	6,6
1		1267	29,5
1.5		185	4,3
2		1019	23,7
2.5		59	1,4
3		438	10,2
3.5		40	0,9
4		241	5,6
4.5		3	0,1
5		136	3,2
5.5		1	0,0
6		59	1,4
7		80	1,9
7.5		1	0,0
8		34	0,8
9		7	0,2
10		40	0,9
≥12		25	0,6
0	Total	4294	100
88	Doesn't know	59	
99	No answer	20	
	Not applicable	42	
		4415	
	Mean value	2,0	
	Standard deviation	1,9	

Z754	HOURS – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X719
	Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on repair and maintenance (of residence, motor vehicle and other property) in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.	
	0	1252 29,6
	.5	204 4,8
	1	988 23,3
	1.5	14 0,3
	2	621 14,7
	2.5	4 0,1
	3	278 6,6
	3.5	3 0,1
	4	161 3,8
	4.5	1 0,0
	5	228 5,4
	6	57 1,3
	7	61 1,4
	8	41 1,0
	9	2 0,0
	10	160 3,8
	11	1 0,0
	≥12	158 3,7
		4234 100
	88 Doesn't know	159
	99 No answer	22
		4415
	Mean value	2,2
	Standard deviation	3,0
Z755	HOURS RESPONDENT – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X720
	Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on repair and maintenance (of residence, motor vehicle and other property). This variable is divided into categories.	
	The table is valid for Z754 GT 0.	
	0	746 24,6
	.5	263 8,7
	1	851 28,1
	1.5	40 1,3
	2	392 12,9
	2.5	24 0,8
	3	185 6,1
	3.5	4 0,1
	4	120 4,0
	4.5	4 0,1
	5	122 4,0
	5.5	1 0,0
	6	38 1,3

6.5		3	0,1
7		31	1,0
8		30	1,0
9		13	0,4
9.5		1	0,0
10		73	2,4
11		1	0,0
12		90	3,0
		3032	100
88	Doesn't know	121	
99	No answer	22	
	Not applicable	1240	
		4415	
	Mean value	2,0	
	Standard deviation	2,7	

Z756

HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE

X721

Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent helps a family member or relative outside the household with personal care or housework. This variable is divided into categories.

0		59	5,5
1-4		918	84,8
5-9		67	6,2
10-14		21	1,9
15-19		8	0,7
20-24		7	0,6
30-34		1	0,1
35-39		1	0,1
	Total	1082	100
	No answer	43	
	Doesn't help any family member/relative	3290	
		4415	
	Mean value	1,7	
	Standard deviation	2,8	

Z757

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN

jfr X722

Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's own children (not living in household) do housework in the respondent's home.

0		423	94,2
1		11	2,4
2		9	2,0
3		2	0,4
4		2	0,4
5		2	0,4
	Total	449	100
66	Help from children <1h	3	

77	Help from children, No answer on hours	1
99	No answer	28
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934
		4415

Z758 HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS jfr X723

Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's parents (not living in household) do housework in respondent's home.

0		359	81,0
1		48	10,8
2		21	4,7
3		4	0,9
4		2	0,5
5		3	0,7
6		3	0,7
7		2	0,5
8		1	0,2
	Total	443	100
66	Help from parents<1h	10	
99	No answer	28	
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934	
		4415	

Z759 HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE jfr X724

Approximate number of hours per week that family member/relative of the respondent does housework in respondent's home.

0		383	87,0
1		28	6,4
2		16	3,6
3		4	0,9
4		3	0,7
5		5	1,1
10		1	0,2
	Total	440	100
66	Help from family member/relative<1h	10	
77	Help from family member/relative, No answer on hours	3	
99	No answer	28	
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934	
		4415	

Z760

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE

jfr X725

Approximate number of hours per week that municipal home-help service does housework in respondent's home.

0		425	94,2
1		9	2,0
2		3	0,7
3		1	0,2
4		2	0,4
5		1	0,2
7		2	0,4
10		2	0,4
15		1	0,2
20		3	0,7
35		2	0,4
	Total	451	100
66	Help from municipal home-help service<1h	1	
77	Help from municipal home-help service, No answer on hours	1	
99	No answer	28	
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934	
		4415	

Z761

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE

jfr X726

Approximate number of hours per week that a privately paid home-help service does housework in respondent's home.

0		276	64
1		42	9,7
2		74	17,2
3		20	4,6
4		12	2,8
5		2	0,5
6		2	0,5
7		1	0,2
8		1	0,2
15		1	0,2
	Total	431	100
	Help from privately paid home-help service<1h	15	
77	Help from privately paid home-help service, No answer on hours timmar	7	
99	No answer	28	
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934	
		4415	

Z762**HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER****jfr X727**

Approximate number of hours per week that other than above does housework in respondent's home.

0		378	85,1
1		26	5,9
2		12	2,7
3		4	0,9
4		5	1,1
5		4	0,9
6		1	0,2
7		2	0,5
8		1	0,2
10		1	0,2
12		3	0,7
14		3	0,7
15		1	0,2
20		1	0,2
40		2	0,5
	Total	444	100
66	Help from other<1h	2	
77	Help from others, No answer on hours	5	
99	No answer	30	
	Doesn't receive any help from outside the household	3934	
		4415	

Z763**DISTRIBUTION OF HOUSEHOLD'S MONEY****X728**

How do you and your partner distribute your money?

The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

1	All money is common	1751	58,9
2	We have a common portion and a portion to each of us	895	30,1
3	We have entirely separate economies	322	10,8
4	Other	5	0,2
	Total	2973	100
8	Doesn't know	6	
9	No answer	8	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z764**DIFFERENT OPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK****X729**

How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to division of housework?

The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

1	Often	191	6,4
2	Sometimes	736	24,8
3	Seldom	1193	40,2

4	Never	850	28,6
	Total	2970	100
8	Doesn't know	8	
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z765	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY		X730
How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to use of money?			
The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
1	Often	72	2,4
2	Sometimes	406	13,7
3	Seldom	1270	42,8
4	Never	1222	41,1
	Total	2970	100
8	Doesn't know	8	
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z766	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS		X733
How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much your spouse/partner works?			
The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
1	Often	54	2,3
2	Sometimes	227	9,5
3	Seldom	565	23,6
4	Never	1545	64,6
	Total	2391	100
5	Not applicable	578	
8	Doesn't know	9	
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	1428	
		4415	

Z767	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH RESPONDENT WORKS		X734
How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much you work?			
The table is valid for Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
1	Often	69	2,8
2	Sometimes	339	13,8
3	Seldom	617	25,1
4	Never	1438	58,4
	Total	2463	100

5	Not applicable	506
8	Doesn't know	9
9	No answer	9
	Not applicable	1428
		4415

Z768

NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT DROPS CHILDREN OFF

X735

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, do you drop children off at day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		505	44,0
.5		1	0,1
1		82	7,1
1.5		4	0,3
2		86	7,5
2.5		68	5,9
3		124	10,8
3.5		3	0,3
4		66	5,8
5		204	17,8
7		4	0,3
	Total	1147	100
9	No answer	11	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z769

NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER DROPS CHILDREN OFF

X736

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does your spouse/partner drop children off at day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14 and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

0		456	45,7
1		68	6,8
2		86	8,6
2.5		54	5,4
3		95	9,5
3.5		5	0,5
4		71	7,1
4.5		1	0,1
5		159	15,9
7		2	0,2
	Total	997	100
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	3404	
		4415	

Z770**NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE DROPS CHILDREN OFF****X737**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does someone else drop children off at day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		1049	91,5
.5		2	0,2
1		26	2,3
2		14	1,2
2.5		20	1,7
3		11	1,0
4		4	0,3
5		19	1,7
7		2	0,2
	Total	1147	100
9	No answer	11	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z771**NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PICKS CHILDREN UP****X738**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, do you pick children up from day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		491	42,8
.5		1	0,1
1		84	7,3
1.5		3	0,3
2		152	13,3
2.5		64	5,6
3		132	11,5
3.5		3	0,3
4		67	5,8
4.5		1	0,1
5		145	12,7
6		1	0,1
7		2	0,2
	Total	1146	100
9	No answer	12	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z772**NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PICKS CHILDREN UP****X739**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does your spouse/partner pick children up from day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14 and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

0		423	42,5
.5		2	0,2
1		87	8,7
1.5		1	0,1
2		118	11,9
2.5		50	5,0
3		133	13,4
3.5		5	0,5
4		65	6,5
5		109	11,0
7		2	0,2
	Total	995	100
9	No answer	12	
	Not applicable	3408	
		4415	

Z773**NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PICKS CHILDREN UP****X740**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does someone else pick children up from day-care/recreation centre or school?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		999	87,2
.5		5	0,4
1		61	5,3
2		26	2,3
2.5		18	1,6
3		16	1,4
3.5		1	0,1
4		4	0,3
5		14	1,2
7		1	0,1
	Total	1145	100
9	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z774

NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT COOKS DINNER

X741

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, do you cook dinner?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		100	8,7
.5		2	0,2
1		103	9,0
1.5		3	0,3
2		125	10,9
2.5		3	0,3
3		167	14,5
3.5		47	4,1
4		139	12,1
5		186	16,2
6		90	7,8
6.5		1	0,1
7		182	15,9
	Total	1148	100
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z775

NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER COOKS DINNER

X742

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does your spouse/partner cook dinner?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14 and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

0		122	12,2
.5		2	0,2
1		102	10,2
2		166	16,6
2.5		2	0,2
3		139	13,9
3.5		44	4,4
4		142	14,2
4.5		1	0,1
5		117	11,7
5.5		3	0,3
6		78	7,8
6.5		2	0,2
7		79	7,9
	Total	999	100
9	No answer	8	
	Not applicable	3408	
		4415	

Z776**NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE COOKS DINNER****X743**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does someone else cook dinner?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		1011	87,9
1		52	4,5
2		23	2,0
2.5		1	0,1
3		9	0,8
3.5		6	0,5
4		5	0,4
4.5		1	0,1
5		9	0,8
6		12	1,0
7		21	1,8
	Total	1150	100
9	No answer	8	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z777**NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PUTS CHILDREN TO BED****X744**

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, do you put children to bed?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		259	22,6
.5		1	0,1
1		26	2,3
1.5		55	4,8
2		4	0,3
2.5		143	12,5
3		139	12,1
3.5		131	11,4
4		82	7,1
4.5		43	3,7
5		265	23,1
	Total	1148	100
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z778

NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PUTS CHILDREN TO BED

X745

How many days during a normal week, Monday-Sunday, does your spouse/partner put children to bed?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14 and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.

0		226	22,6
.5		2	0,2
1		34	3,4
2		78	7,8
2.5		1	0,1
3		128	12,8
3.5		129	12,9
4		139	13,9
4.5		1	0,1
5		56	5,6
6		27	2,7
7		177	17,7
	Total	998	100
9	No answer	9	
	Not applicable	3408	
		4415	

Z779

NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PUTS CHILDREN TO BED

X746

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does someone else put children to bed?

The table is valid for respondents with children living in the household below age 14.

0		1079	94,0
.5		7	0,6
1		5	0,4
1.5		3	0,3
2		13	1,1
2.5		15	1,3
3		9	0,8
3.5		2	0,2
4		1	0,1
4.5		14	1,2
	Total	1148	100
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	3257	
		4415	

Z780	CASH MARGIN			X748, Y574, U576, jfr V602, jfr W375
	If a situation suddenly arose where you had to come up with 14 000 kronor in a week, could you manage it?			
	1	Yes	3913	89,3
	2	No	471	10,7
		Total	4384	100
	8	Doesn't know	13	
	9	No answer	18	
			4415	
Z781	ACQUIRING CASH			X749, Y575, U577, jfr V602, jfr W375
	If yes: How would you manage to come up with 14 000 kronor in a week?			
	The table is valid if Z780 EQ 1			
	1	Withdrawal from own bank account	3138	80,3
	2	Sale of stocks, fund shares or the like	156	4,0
	3	Loan from family member	271	6,9
	4	Loan from other relatives or friends	195	5,0
	5	Bank loan or equivalent	123	3,1
	6	Other way	26	0,7
		Total	3909	100
	8	Doesn't know	4	
		Not applicable	502	
			4415	
Z782	ECONOMIC DIFFICULTIES			X754, Y584
	Have you at any time in the last 12 months had difficulty managing your current expenses for food, rent, bills, etc?			
	1	Yes	532	12,1
	2	No	3864	87,9
		Total	4396	100
	8	Doesn't know	2	
	9	No answer	17	
			4415	
Z783	RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH			X755
	Do you receive maintenance for a child born 1982 or later? If yes: What is the total payment per month (SEK per month)? The table is valid for respondent with children under 18 who has separated from the other parent. This variable is divided into categories.			
	1-999		2	2,2
	1000-1499		48	53,9
	1500-1999		1	1,1
	2000-2499		9	10,1
	2500-2999		16	18,0
	3000-3499		5	5,6

	3500-3999		3	3,4
	≥4000		5	5,6
	Total		89	100
88888	Doesn't know		1	
99999	No answer		1	
	Not applicable		4324	
			4415	

Z784

PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH

X756

Do you pay maintenance for a child born 1992 or later? If yes: What is the total payment per month (SEK per month)? The table is valid for respondent with children under 18 who has separated from the other parent. This variable is divided into categories.

	1-999		13	18,3
	1000-1499		28	39,4
	1500-1999		7	9,9
	2000-2499		5	7,0
	2500-2999		7	9,9
	3000-3499		7	9,9
	3500-3999		1	1,4
	≥4000		4	4,2
	Total		72	100
88888	Doesn't know		3	
	Not applicable		4340	
			4415	

Z785

INHERITANCE

NEW

What is the total value of your received inheritance in the last 10 years?

	0	Did not receive inheritance	3563	82,8
	1-49999		113	2,6
	50000-99999		163	3,8
	100000-149999		110	2,6
	150000-199999		45	1,0
	200000-249999		60	1,4
	250000-299999		32	0,7
	300000-349999		41	1,0
	350000-399999		17	0,4
	400000-449999		25	0,6
	450000-499999		8	0,2
	500000-999999		63	1,5
	≥1000000		65	1,5
	Total		4305	100
88888888	Received inheritance, doesn't know the value		68	
99999999	Received inheritance, No answer on value		42	
			4415	
	Mean value (>0)		300045,9	
	Standard deviation (>0)		487240,3	

Z786**TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT GIVEN****X760**

Have you, during the last 12 months, been giving financial support or gifts in a total of 6000 (SEK) or more to a person/persons outside your household? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

6-9		182	22,3
10-19		275	33,7
20-29		113	13,9
30-39		64	7,8
40-49		35	4,3
50-59		35	4,3
60-69		14	1,7
70-79		14	1,7
80-89		6	0,7
90-99		4	0,5
100-199		38	4,7
200-299		17	2,1
300-399		5	0,6
400-499		2	0,2
500-599		1	0,1
600-699		4	0,5
700-799		2	0,2
800-899		1	0,1
1000-1999		1	0,1
2000-2999		2	0,2
≥3000		1	0,1
	Total	816	100
77777777	Been giving, doesn't know how much	66	
88888888	Been giving, No answer on how much	16	
99999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't been giving	3503	
		4415	

Z787**FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK****X761**

Can you approximate the value of your gifts/financial support to your parents during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories

0		821	91,8
1-9		37	4,1
10-19		21	2,3
20-29		5	0,6
30-39		7	0,8
40-49		1	0,1
50-59		1	0,1
≥100		1	0,1
	Total	894	100
77777777	Been giving, doesn't know how much	6	
88888888	Been giving, No answer on how much	2	
99999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't been giving	3499	
		4415	

Z788	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	X762
Can you approximate the value of your gifts/financial support to your grandparents during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.		
0		890 98,7
1-9		7 0,8
10-19		3 0,3
30-39		2 0,2
	Total	902 100
999999999	No answer	14
	Hasn't been giving	3499
		4415
Z789	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X763
Can you approximate the value of your gifts/financial support to the child/children during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.		
0		309 36,7
1-9		99 11,7
10-19		169 20,0
20-29		74 8,8
30-39		45 5,3
40-49		27 3,2
50-59		28 3,3
60-69		12 1,4
70-79		10 1,2
80-89		3 0,4
90-99		3 0,4
100-199		31 3,7
200-299		16 1,9
300-399		6 0,7
400-499		2 0,2
500-599		1 0,1
600-699		3 0,4
700-799		1 0,1
800-899		1 0,1
≥1000		3 0,4
	Total	843 100
777777777	Been giving, doesn't know how much	47
888888888	Been giving, No answer on how much	12
999999999	No answer	14
	Hasn't been giving	3499
		4415
Z790	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	X764
Can you approximate the value of your gifts/financial support to the grandchild/grandchildren during the last 12		

months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		780	87,9
1-9		59	6,7
10-19		28	3,2
20-29		8	0,9
30-39		3	0,3
50-59		2	0,2
60-69		1	0,1
70-79		2	0,2
90-99		1	0,1
300-399		1	0,1
400-499		1	0,1
≥1000		1	0,1
	Total	887	100
77777777	Been giving, doesn't know how much	14	
88888888	Been giving, No answer on how much	1	
99999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't been giving	3499	
		4415	

Z791

FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK

X765

Can you approximate the value of your gifts/financial support to other person (other persons) during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		664	74,9
1-9		89	10,0
10-19		74	8,3
20-29		21	2,4
30-39		13	1,5
40-49		3	0,3
50-59		8	0,9
60-69		2	0,2
70-79		2	0,2
80-89		2	0,2
100-199		7	0,8
200-299		1	0,1
400-499		1	0,1
	Total	887	100
77777777	Been giving, doesn't know how much	12	
88888888	Been giving, No answer on how much	3	
99999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't been giving	3499	
		4415	

Z792**TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT RECEIVED****X766**

Have you, during the last 12 months, been receiving financial support or gifts in a total of 6000 (SEK) or more to a person/persons outside your household? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		1	0,2
1-9		103	25,0
10-19		167	40,5
20-29		55	13,3
30-39		20	4,9
40-49		8	1,9
50-59		16	3,9
60-69		8	1,9
70-79		4	1,0
80-89		1	0,2
90-99		1	0,2
100-199		17	4,1
200-299		5	1,2
300-399		2	0,5
400-499		3	0,7
≥1000		1	0,2
	Total	412	100
77777777	Received gift, doesn't know how much	29	
88888888	Received gift, No answer on how much	5	
99999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't received support/gifts	3955	
		4415	

Z793**FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK****X767**

Can you approximate the value of your received gifts/financial support from your parents during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		129	30,3
1-9		92	21,6
10-19		116	27,2
20-29		30	7,0
30-39		13	3,1
40-49		5	1,2
50-59		13	3,1
60-69		6	1,4
70-79		3	0,7
80-89		1	0,2
100-199		12	2,8
200-299		2	0,5
300-399		1	0,2
400-499		2	0,5
≥1000		1	0,2
	Total	426	100
77777777	Received gift, doesn't know how much		

888888888	Received gift, No answer on how much	22	
999999999	No answer	1	
	Hasn't received support/gifts	14	
		3952	
		4415	

Z794	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK		X768
	your received gifts/financial support from your grandparents during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.		
0		388	87,4
1-9		21	4,7
10-19		22	5,0
20-29		5	1,1
30-39		2	0,5
50-59		3	0,7
100-199		2	0,5
200-299		1	0,2
	Total	444	100
777777777	Received gift, doesn't know how much	3	
888888888	Received gift, No answer on how much	1	
999999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't received support/gifts	3953	
		4415	

Z795	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK		X769
	Can you approximate the value of your received gifts/financial support from the child/children during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)?		
0		441	98,4
1-9		2	0,4
10-19		3	0,7
20-29		1	0,2
40-39		1	0,2
	Total	448	100
999999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't received support/gifts	3953	
		4415	

Z796	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK		X770
	Can you approximate the value of your received gifts/financial support from the grandchild/grandchildren during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)?		
0		448	100
	Total	448	100
999999999	No answer	14	
	Hasn't received support/gifts	3953	
		4415	

Z797	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK		X771	
	Can you approximate the value of your received gifts/financial support from other person (other persons) during the last 12 months (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.			
	0		346	79,0
	1-9		28	6,4
	10-19		30	6,8
	20-29		15	3,4
	30-39		5	1,1
	40-49		2	0,5
	50-59		3	0,7
	60-69		1	0,2
	70-79		1	0,2
	90-99		1	0,2
	100-199		2	0,5
	200-299		2	0,5
	300-399		1	0,2
	400-499		1	0,2
	Total		438	100
	77777777	Received gift, doesn't know how much	7	
	88888888	Received gift, No answer on how much	3	
	99999999	No answer	14	
		Hasn't received support/gifts	3953	
			4415	
Z798	CLOSE FRIEND WHEN ILL		X775, Y614, U699	
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you become ill?			
	1	Yes	4258	97,1
	2	No	125	2,9
		Total	4383	100
	8	Doesn't know	16	
	9	No answer	16	
			4415	
Z799	CLOSE FRIEND AS COMPANY		X776, Y615, U700	
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you want company?			
	1	Yes	4281	97,6
	2	No	106	2,4
		Total	4387	100
	8	Doesn't know	11	
	9	No answer	17	
			4415	

Z800	SOMEONE TO TALK TO	X777, Y616, U701
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you need to talk to someone about personal problems?	
1	Yes	4266 97,2
2	No	122 2,8
	Total	4388 100
8	Doesn't know	9
9	No answer	18
		4415

Z801	VALUE REAL ASSETS	NEW
	What is the APROXIMATE market value of [respondent's or respondent's spouse/partner owned] assets, i.e. house, co-operative apartment, weekend/summer cottage, land or woodland? (Thousands of SEK).	
0		1321 31,1
0,1-99		34 0,8
100-199		50 1,2
200-299		45 1,1
300-399		60 1,4
400-499		73 1,7
500-599		85 2,0
600-699		81 1,9
700-799		81 1,9
800-899		94 2,2
900-999		66 1,6
1000-1099		198 4,7
1100-1199		30 0,7
1200-1299		88 2,1
1300-1399		76 1,8
1400-1499		43 1,0
1500-1599		207 4,9
1600-1699		41 1,0
1700-1799		58 1,4
1800-1899		68 1,6
1900-1999		27 0,6
2000-2099		240 5,7
2100-2199		14 0,3
2200-2299		27 0,6
2300-2399		36 0,9
2400-2499		20 0,5
2500-2599		177 4,2
2600-2699		12 0,3
2700-2799		28 0,7
2800-2899		26 0,6
2900-2999		7 0,2
3000-3999		342 8,1
4000-4999		182 4,3
5000-5999		110 2,6

6000-6999		69	1,6
7000-7999		38	0,9
8000-8999		31	0,7
≥9000		57	1,3
	Total	4242	100
77777777	Has real assets, doesn't know value	137	
88888888	Has real assets, No answer on value	22	
99999999	No answer	14	
		4415	

Z802

DEBTS REAL ASSETS

NEW

Approximately how large are your and your spouse's/partner's debts for all this? [Loans for house, co-operative apartment, weekend/summer cottage, land and woodland?] (Thousands of SEK).

Tabeller för Z801 GT 0.

0	658	22,4
1-99	92	3,1
100-199	156	5,3
200-299	176	6,0
300-399	149	5,1
400-499	154	5,2
500-599	145	4,9
600-699	139	4,7
700-799	129	4,4
800-899	112	3,8
900-999	77	2,6
1000-1099	173	5,9
1100-1199	51	1,7
1200-1299	64	2,2
1300-1399	64	2,2
1400-1499	38	1,3
1500-1599	90	3,1
1600-1699	46	1,6
1700-1799	34	1,2
1800-1899	44	1,5
1900-1999	16	0,5
2000-2099	93	3,2
2100-2199	15	0,5
2200-2299	17	0,6
2300-2399	18	0,6
2400-2499	16	0,5
2500-2599	32	1,1
2600-2699	11	0,4
2700-2799	13	0,4
2800-2899	15	0,5
2900-2999	3	0,1
3000-3999	58	2,0
4000-4999	26	0,9
5000-5999	11	0,4

	6000-6999		2	0,1
	7000-7999		2	0,1
	≥9000		4	0,1
	Total		2943	100
	7777777	Has real assets, doesn't know value	112	
	8888888	Has real assets, No answer on value	21	
	9999999	No answer	14	
		Not applicable	1325	
Z803	REAL ASSETS, OWNING			NEW
	Are these assets mostly owned by you, your partner or do you have approximately equal shares?			
	The table is valid for respondents with real assets and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.			
	1	Mostly by respondent	347	13,9
	2	Mostly by respondent's partner	238	9,6
	3	Equal shares	1907	76,5
		Total	2492	100
	8	Doesn't know	3	
	9	No answer	10	
		Not applicable	1910	
			4415	
Z804	FINANCIAL ASSETS			NEW
	What is the approximate total value of your and your spouse's/partner's financial assets, i.e. account balance, cash, stocks, bonds and other financial instruments? Subtract any other loans, e.g. student loans.			
	1	0-50 000 in assets	1205	29,5
	2	50 000-100 000 in assets	533	13,1
	3	100 000-200 000 in assets	509	12,5
	4	200 000-500 000 in assets	657	16,1
	5	500 000-1 million in assets	354	8,7
	6	1 million-2 millions in assets	232	5,7
	7	2 millions-5 millions in assets	161	3,9
	8	More than 5 millions in assets	58	1,4
	9	0-100 000 in debts	183	4,5
	10	More than 100 000 in debts	189	4,6
		Total	4081	100
	88	Doesn't know	227	
	99	No answer	107	
			4415	

Z805	FINANCIAL ASSETS, OWNING		NEW
	Are these assets mostly owned by you, your partner or do you have approximately equal shares?		
	The table is valid for Z804 GE 1 AND LE 8 and Z154 EQ 4 OR 5.		
	1	Mostly by respondent	423 16,9
	2	Mostly by respondent's partner	229 9,1
	3	Equal shares	1856 74,0
		Total	2508 100
	8	Doesn't know	3
	9	No answer	6
		Not applicable	1898
			4415
Z806	SUFFERED FROM THEFT		X779, Y585, U593, jfr V618
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from any form of theft?		
	1	Yes	442 10,1
	2	No	3956 89,9
		Total	4398 100
	9	No answer	17
			4415
Z807	SUFFERED FROM DAMAGE		X780, Y586, U596, V621
	Has it happened in the last 12 months that someone has damaged or destroyed any property of yours?		
	1	Yes	350 8,0
	2	No	4046 92,0
		Total	4396 100
	9	No answer	19
			4415
Z808	VIOLENCE LEADING TO BODILY HARM		X781, Y587, U601, V626
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of violence leading to visible marks or bodily harm?		
	1	Yes	72 1,6
	2	No	4325 98,4
		Total	4397 100
	9	No answer	18
			4415

Z809	VIOLENCE WITHOUT BODILY HARM			X782, Y588, U602, V627
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of violence which did not lead to visible marks or bodily harm?			
	1	Yes	96	2,2
	2	No	4301	97,8
		Total	4397	100
	9	No answer	18	
			4415	
Z810	SERIOUS THREATS			X783, Y589, U603, V628
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of threat or threats dangerous or serious enough to frighten you?			
	1	Yes	178	4,1
	2	No	4216	95,9
		Total	4394	100
	9	No answer	21	
			4415	
Z811	VACATION TRIP 2009			X784, Y590, U611, V636, jfr W614
	Did you go on a vacation trip (or other leisure trip) in 2009?			
	1	Yes	3159	72,0
	2	No	1231	28,0
		Total	4390	100
	9	No answer	25	
			4415	
Z812	COTTAGE STAY 2009			X785, Y594, U618, V643, W469
	Did you in 2009 spend any time in a summer cottage, allotment-garden cottage or other leisure dwelling?			
	1	Yes	2035	46,3
	2	No	2358	53,7
		Total	4393	100
	9	No answer	22	
			4415	
Z813	FISHING OR HUNTING IN SPARE TIME			X786, jfr Y596- 597, jfr U621- 622, jfr V646- 647, jfr W472- 473
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go fishing or hunting?			
	1	No	3156	71,8
	2	Yes, sometimes	888	20,2
	3	Yes, often	354	8,0
		Total	4398	100
	9	No answer	17	
			4415	

Z814	GARDENING			X787, Y598, U623, V648, W474
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: gardening?			
	1 No	1776	40,4	
	2 Yes, sometimes	999	22,7	
	3 Yes, often	1622	36,9	
	Total	4397	100	
	9 No answer	18		
		4415		
Z815	GO TO THE CINEMA			X788, Y599, U624, V649, W475
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to the cinema?			
	1 No	1653	37,6	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2500	56,8	
	3 Yes, often	245	5,6	
	Total	4398	100	
	9 No answer	17		
		4415		
Z816	GO TO THE THEATRE			X789, Y600, U625, V650, W476
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to the theatre, concerts, museums, exhibitions?			
	1 No	1514	34,4	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2459	55,9	
	3 Yes, often	424	9,6	
	Total	4397	100	
	9 No answer	18		
		4415		
Z817	GO TO A RESTAURANT			X790, Y601, U626, V651, W477
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to a restaurant?			
	1 No	623	14,2	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2726	62,0	
	3 Yes, often	1049	23,9	
	Total	4398	100	
	9 No answer	17		
		4415		

Z818	DANCING			X791, Y602, U627, V652, W478
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go dancing?			
	1 No	3242	73,7	
	2 Yes, sometimes	924	21,0	
	3 Yes, often	231	5,3	
	Total	4397	100	
	9 No answer	18		
		4415		
Z819	VISIT RELATIVES			X792, Y604, U632, V657, W483
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: visit relatives?			
	1 No	403	9,2	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2102	47,8	
	3 Yes, often	1891	43,0	
	Total	4396	100	
	9 No answer	19		
		4415		
Z820	HAVE RELATIVES VISIT			X793, Y605, U633, V658, W485
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: have relatives visit?			
	1 No	611	13,9	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2302	52,4	
	3 Yes, often	1484	33,8	
	Total	4397	100	
	9 No answer	18		
		4415		
Z821	VISIT FRIENDS AND ACQUAINTANCES			X794, Y606, U634, V659, W484
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: visit friends and acquaintances?			
	1 No	212	4,8	
	2 Yes, sometimes	1893	43,0	
	3 Yes, often	2293	52,1	
	Total	4398	100	
	9 No answer	17		
		4415		

Z822	HAVE FRIENDS VISIT			X795, Y607, U635, V660, W486
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: have friends and acquaintances visit?			
	1 No	266	6,0	
	2 Yes, sometimes	2088	47,5	
	3 Yes, often	2044	46,5	
	Total	4398	100	
	9 No answer	17		
		4415		
Z823	READ BOOKS			X796, Y603, U628, V653, W479
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: read books?			
	1 No	1201	27,3	
	2 Yes, sometimes	1195	27,2	
	3 Yes, often	1998	45,5	
	Total	4394	100	
	9 No answer	21		
		4415		
Z824	STUDY CIRCLE			X797, Y608, U636, V661, W487
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: take part in study groups or courses?			
	1 No	3633	82,6	
	2 Yes, sometimes	466	10,6	
	3 Yes, often	298	6,8	
	Total	4397	100	
	9 No answer	18		
		4415		
Z825	PLAY MUSIC OR SING IN A CHOIR			X798, jfr Y610- 611, jfr U638, jfr V663, jfr W488
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: play a musical instrument or sing in a choir?			
	1 No	3717	84,5	
	2 Yes, sometimes	248	5,6	
	3 Yes, often	433	9,8	
	Total	4398	100	
	9 No answer	17		
		4415		

Z826	HOBBY ACTIVITY		X799, Y612, U640, V665, W490
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: pursuit a hobby (knit, sew, do woodwork, paint, collect stamps and the like)?		
1	No	2381	54,2
2	Yes, sometimes	637	14,5
3	Yes, often	1378	31,3
	Total	4396	100
9	No answer	19	
		4415	
Z827	INTERNET		NEW
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: direct contact with others on the internet, such as chatting or playing online computer games?		
1	No	2633	59,9
2	Yes, sometimes	622	14,1
3	Yes, often	1142	26,0
	Total	4397	100
9	No answer	18	
		4415	
Z828	SPORTS ACTIVITY		X800, Y613
	Do you pursue any sports, outdoor or exercise activities, e.g. long walks? If yes: How often?		
1	Yes, several times/week	2454	55,8
2	Yes, about once/week	807	18,3
3	Yes, 1-3 times/month	284	6,5
4	Yes, but less often	398	9,0
5	No	455	10,3
	Total	4398	100
9	No answer	17	
		4415	
Z829	MEMBER OF TRADE UNION		X801, Y617, U648, V666, jfr W491
	Are you a member of a trade union or association?		
1	Yes	2356	53,6
2	No	2037	46,4
	Total	4393	100
9	No answer	22	
		4415	

Z830

UNION

X802, Y618,
U649, V667, jfr
W491

What union (or equivalent) do you belong to?

The table is valid for Z829 EQ 1.

1	Akademikerförbundet (SSR) (The union for professionals)	51	2,2
2	Förbundet Sveriges arbetsterapeuter (FSA) (Occupational therapists' union)	13	0,6
3	Arkitektförbundet (AF) (Swedish association of architects)	5	0,2
5	Byggnadsarbetareförbundet (Building workers' union)	74	3,1
6	Civilekonomerna (Business economists' union)	27	1,1
7	Sveriges ingenjörer (The Swedish association of graduate engineers)	85	3,6
8	Dik-förbundet (university graduates in the fields of culture and communication)	8	0,3
9	Elektrikerförbundet (Electricians' union)	19	0,8
10	Facket för service och kommunikation (SEKO) (Union for Service and Communications Employees)	78	3,3
11	Farmaceutförbundet (Pharmacists' union)	9	0,4
12	Farmaciförbundet (ATF) (Pharmacy union)	2	0,1
13	Fastighetsanställdas förbund (Building Maintenance Workers' Union)	18	0,8
14	Finansförbundet (Financial sector union of Sweden)	24	1,0
15	Facket för försäkring och finans (Union of insurance and finance employees)	7	0,3
16	Försvarsförbundet (Swedish Union of Defence Employees)	4	0,2
17	Försäkringsanställdas förbund (Insurance Employees' Union)	54	2,3
18	GS (The Swedish union of forestry, wood and graphical workers)	37	1,6
19	Handelsanställdas förbund (Union of commercial employees)	87	3,7
20	Unionen (Union of white-collar workers in the private sector)	342	14,5
22	Hotell- och restaurangfacket (Hotel and Restaurant Workers' Union)	29	1,2
23	Industrifacket Metall (Metal Workers' Union)	182	7,7
24	Journalistförbundet (SJF) (Swedish union of journalists)	11	0,5
25	JUSEK (Union of University Graduates of law and social sciences)	58	2,5
26	Kommunalarbetareförbundet (SKAF) (Municipal Workers' Union)	367	15,6
27	Kommunaltjänstemannaförbundet (SKTF) (Union of Local Government Officers)	123	5,2
28	Kyrkans akademikerförbund (KyrkA) (Professional church employees' union)	3	0,1
29	Ledarna (Organization for Managers)	58	2,5
30	Legitimerade sjukgymnasters riksförbund (LSR) (The Swedish Association of Physiotherapists)	9	0,4
31	Livsmedelsarbetareförbundet (Food workers' union)	16	0,7
32	LO (The Swedish trade union confederation), unspec	6	0,3
33	Lärarnas riksförbund (LR) (National Union of Teachers)	59	2,5
34	Läkarförbundet (The Swedish Medical Association)	22	0,9
35	Läraryrket (LF) (Teachers' Union)	157	6,7
36	Musikerförbundet (Musicians' Union)	1	0,0
37	Målarförbundet (Painters' Union)	4	0,2
38	Naturvetareförbundet (Association of Professional Scientists)	19	0,8
39	Officersförbundet (SOF) (Military Officers' Association)	9	0,4
40	Pappersindustriarbetareförbundet (SPIAF) (Paper Workers'	14	0,6

	Union)		
41	Svensk Pilotförening (SPF) (Swedish airline pilot's association)	3	0,1
42	Polisförbundet (The Swedish Police Union)	26	1,1
43	Psykologförbundet (SP) (Swedish Psychological Association)	2	0,1
44	SAC (Central organization of the workers of Sweden)	1	0,0
45	SACO (Professionals' central organization), unspec	20	0,8
46	SACOs allmänna tjänstemannaförbund (SRAT) (Swedish Confederation of Professional Associations)	6	0,3
47	Folkhögskolans lärarförbund (SFHL) (Union for Folk High School Teachers)	3	0,1
48	Vårdförbundet (SHSTF) (The Swedish Association of Health Professionals)	83	3,5
49	Skolledarförbundet (The Swedish Association of School Principals and Directors of Education)	5	0,2
50	Skogs- och lantbrukstjänstemannaförbundet (SLF) (Association of Forestal and Agricultural Employees)	1	0,0
51	Tandläkarförbundet (STF) (The Swedish Dental Association)	5	0,2
52	Sveriges universitetslärarförbund (SULF) (Swedish Association of University Teachers)	9	0,4
53	Transportarbetareförbundet (Transport workers' union)	40	1,7
54	Sveriges fartygsbefälsförening (SFBF) (Union of commanders at sea)	4	0,2
55	Säljarnas riksförbund (National Union of Sales People)	3	0,1
57	TCO (The Swedish Confederation of Professional Employees), unspec	6	0,3
58	Teaterförbundet (TF) (The Swedish Union for Performing Arts and Film)	8	0,3
59	Trafik och järnväg (TJ) (The Saco Transport and Railway Association)	1	0,0
60	Tull – kust (Customs' and coastal guards' union)	1	0,0
61	Veterinärförbundet (SVF) (Veterinary Association)	3	0,1
62	Lantbrukarnas riksförbund (LRF) (The Federation of Swedish Farmers)	7	0,3
63	Svenska tecknare (The association of Swedish illustrators and graphic designers)	1	0,0
65	Konstnärernas riksförbund (KRO) (The Swedish Artists' National Organization)	1	0,0
66	Union outside Sweden	5	0,2
70	Employers' organization	20	0,8
	Total	2355	100
88	Doesn't know	1	
	Not applicable	2059	
		4415	

Z831

VISITED TRADE UNION MEETING

**X803, jfr Y620,
jfr U650, jfr
V668, jfr W492**

Have you been to any trade union meeting during the last year?

1	Yes	573	13,0
2	No	3822	87,0
	Total	4395	100
9	No answer	20	
		4415	

Z832	UNION REPRESENTATIVE			X804, Y621, U652, V670, W493
	Do you now hold or have you at any time held a position of trust in a trade union (committee member and like)?			
	1 Holds position of trust	263	6,0	
	2 Has held position of trust	676	15,4	
	3 No	3455	78,6	
	Total	4394	100	
	9 No answer	21		
		4415		
Z833	UNION ACTIVITY			X805, Y622, U653, V749, W579
	Index of union activity based on the answers from the questions in Z829, Z831 and Z832.			
	Construction of index:			
	1 Not member of trade union			
	2 Member + neither holds nor has held position of trust + not been to trade union meeting last year			
	3 Member + neither holds nor has held position of trust + has been to trade union meeting last year			
	4 Member + holds or has held position of trust			
	1 Not member	2037	46,4	
	2 Passive member	1451	33,0	
	3 Active member	272	6,2	
	4 Representative	632	14,4	
	Total	4392	100	
	9 No answer	23		
		4415		
Z834	PARTY MEMBERSHIP			X806, Y623, U654, V671, W494
	Do you belong to a political party or a political association? If yes: Do you now hold or have you at any time held a position of trust in a political association or organization (committee member and the like)?			
	11 Holds position of trust	63	1,4	
	12 Has held position of trust	39	0,9	
	13 No	148	3,4	
	20 Not member	4145	94,3	
	Total	4395	100	
	99 No answer	20		
		4415		
Z835	VISITED POLITICAL MEETING			X807, jfr Y624, jfr U656, jfr V672, jfr W495
	Have you been to a political meeting or gathering in the last year?			
	1 Yes	283	6,4	
	2 No	4113	93,6	
	Total	4396	100	
	9 No answer	19		
		4415		

Z836	<p>POLITICAL ACTIVITY</p> <p>Index of political activity based on the answers from the questions in Z834 and Z835. Construction of index:</p> <p>1 Not member of political association + not been to political meeting last year 2 Member not position of trust + not been to political meeting last year 3 (Member or not member) + does not hold or has held position of trust + has been to political meeting last year 4 Member + (has held position of trust) or (holds position of trust) + has been to political meeting last year</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Not member</td><td>4125</td><td>93,9</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Passive member</td><td>115</td><td>2,6</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Active member</td><td>55</td><td>1,3</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Representative</td><td>100</td><td>2,3</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Total</td><td>4395</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>No answer</td><td>20</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td>4415</td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Not member	4125	93,9	2	Passive member	115	2,6	3	Active member	55	1,3	4	Representative	100	2,3		Total	4395	100	9	No answer	20				4415		X808, Y625, U658, V750, W578
1	Not member	4125	93,9																											
2	Passive member	115	2,6																											
3	Active member	55	1,3																											
4	Representative	100	2,3																											
	Total	4395	100																											
9	No answer	20																												
		4415																												
Z837	<p>PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 2006</p> <p>Did you vote in the 2006 elections?</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td><td>3633</td><td>91,0</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>No</td><td>361</td><td>9,0</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Total</td><td>3994</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Not eligible to vote</td><td>383</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>No answer</td><td>38</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td>4415</td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	3633	91,0	2	No	361	9,0		Total	3994	100	3	Not eligible to vote	383		9	No answer	38				4415		X809, Y627, U659, V673, jfr W523				
1	Yes	3633	91,0																											
2	No	361	9,0																											
	Total	3994	100																											
3	Not eligible to vote	383																												
9	No answer	38																												
		4415																												
Z838	<p>PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION – 2009 EU-P</p> <p>Did you vote in the European parliament election in 2009?</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td><td>2338</td><td>55,8</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>No</td><td>1849</td><td>44,2</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Total</td><td>4187</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Not eligible to vote</td><td>118</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>No answer</td><td>110</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td>4415</td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	2338	55,8	2	No	1849	44,2		Total	4187	100	3	Not eligible to vote	118		9	No answer	110				4415		NEW				
1	Yes	2338	55,8																											
2	No	1849	44,2																											
	Total	4187	100																											
3	Not eligible to vote	118																												
9	No answer	110																												
		4415																												
Z839	<p>INTENTION TO VOTE IN ELECTION 2010</p> <p>Will you vote in the 2010 elections this autumn?</p> <p>The table is valid for respondents interviewed before Sep 20 2010, i.e. before the elections.</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, for sure</td><td>728</td><td>82,4</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, probably</td><td>79</td><td>8,9</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Maybe</td><td>30</td><td>3,4</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>No, probably not</td><td>10</td><td>1,1</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>No, definitely not</td><td>13</td><td>1,5</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Not eligible to vote</td><td>17</td><td>1,9</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes, for sure	728	82,4	2	Yes, probably	79	8,9	3	Maybe	30	3,4	4	No, probably not	10	1,1	5	No, definitely not	13	1,5	6	Not eligible to vote	17	1,9	NEW				
1	Yes, for sure	728	82,4																											
2	Yes, probably	79	8,9																											
3	Maybe	30	3,4																											
4	No, probably not	10	1,1																											
5	No, definitely not	13	1,5																											
6	Not eligible to vote	17	1,9																											

	7	Has already voted	6	0,7
		Total	883	100
	9	No answer	3	
		Not applicable	3529	
		Total	4415	
Z840		PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 2010		NEW
		Did you vote in the 2010 elections [parliament-, county- or municipal election in Sweden autumn 2010]?		
		The table is valid for respondents interviewed after Sep 19 2010, i.e. after the elections.		
	1	Yes	3147	91,4
	2	No	298	8,6
		Total	3445	100
	3	Not eligible to vote	70	
	9	No answer	15	
		Not applicable	879	
			4415	
Z841		OTHER ASSOCIATIONS		X810, Y629, jfr U670, jfr V683, jfr W500
		Do you belong to any other kind of association or organization than the ones above?		
	1	Yes	2290	52,1
	2	No	2107	47,9
		Total	4397	100
	9	No answer	18	
			4415	
Z842		ASSOCIATION ACTIVITIES		X811, Y630
		How often, roughly, do you take part in organization activities?		
		The table is valid for Z841 EQ 1.		
	2	Never or almost never	540	23,6
	3	Once or twice a year	642	28,1
	4	Once or twice a month	490	21,4
	5	Once or twice a week	353	15,4
	6	Several times a week	263	11,5
		Total	2288	100
	9	No answer	2	
		Not applicable	2125	
			4415	

Z843	RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION		NEW
	What is your religious affiliation?		
	1 Christianity	3078	70,5
	2 Islam	207	4,7
	3 Judaism	3	0,1
	4 Hinduism	4	0,1
	5 Buddhism	27	0,6
	6 Other	16	0,4
	7 No religious affiliation	1029	23,6
	Total	4364	100
	8 Doesn't know	26	
	9 Doesn't want to respond	25	
	Total	4415	
Z844	RELIGION IMPORTANT		NEW
	How important is religion in your life?		
	The table is valid if Z843 GE 1 AND LE 6.		
	1 Very important	364	10,9
	2 Fairly important	739	22,2
	3 Fairly unimportant	1428	42,9
	4 Very unimportant	797	23,9
	Total	3328	100
	9 No answer	13	
	Not applicable	1074	
		4415	
Z845	PUBLIC DEMONSTRATION LAST 10 YEARS		NEW
	Have you participated in a public demonstration in the last 10 years?		
	1 Yes	455	10,4
	2 No	3941	89,6
	Total	4396	100
	9 No answer	19	
		4415	
Z846	PERSONAL CONTACT		X815, Y634, U672, V685, W502
	Have you at any time contacted any person in responsible office in order to influence a decision on a public matter?		
	1 Yes	819	18,7
	2 No	3571	81,3
	Total	4390	100
	9 No answer	25	
		4415	

Z847	SPOKEN IN MEETING			X816, Y635, U673, V686, W503
	Have you ever addressed a meeting of an association or organization?			
	1 Yes, held a speech	1339	30,5	
	2 Yes, took part in a debate	549	12,5	
	3 No, never	2505	57,0	
	Total	4393	100	
	9 No answer	22		
		4415		
Z848	WRITTEN IN NEWSPAPER			X817, Y636, U674, V687, W504
	Have you ever written an article or letter to the editor of a newspaper or magazine?			
	1 Yes, article	472	10,7	
	2 Yes, letter	544	12,4	
	3 No, never	3379	76,9	
	Total	4395	100	
	9 No answer	20		
		4415		
Z849	POLITICAL PARTICIPATION			jfr X818, jfr Y637, jfr U675, jfr V751, jfr W580, W599
	Index of political participation based on the questions in Z845, Z846, Z847 and index Z833 and Z808. Index construction:			
	9 if any of 6 variables has value 9			
	1 if no on all 6 variables			
	2 in other cases			
	1 Outsider	949	21,7	
	2 Not outsider	3429	78,3	
	Total	4379	100	
	9 No answer	37		
		4415		
Z850	CAN COMPLAIN			X819, Y638, U678, V689, W506
	Could you take it upon yourself to write a letter appealing against a decision made by a public authority? If no: Do you know anyone from whom you could get help in such a case?			
	10 Can do it	3202	73,5	
	21 Can get help	909	20,9	
	22 No	244	5,6	
	Total	4355	100	
	99 No answer	60		
		4415		

Z851	HELP WHEN COMPLAINING		X820, Y639
	Do you know where to turn to get help in a situation like this?		
	The table is valid for Z850 NE 10 or 21.		
	1 Yes	57	22,2
	2 No	200	77,8
	Total	257	100
	9 No answer	8	
	Not applicable	4150	
		4415	
Z852	SPEAK ENGLISH		NEW
	Do you speak English?		
	1 Yes, fluent	1005	22,9
	2 Yes, almost fluent	1117	25,4
	3 Yes, good but not fluent	1475	33,5
	4 Yes, but only some words and sentences	562	12,8
	5 No	238	5,4
	Total	4397	100
	9 No answer	18	
		4415	
Z853	READ ENGLISH		NEW
	Can you understand the content in a newspaper in English?		
	1 Yes, everything	1041	23,7
	2 Yes, almost everything	1346	30,7
	3 Yes, a lot	1122	25,6
	4 Yes, but only some words and sentences, e.g. headlines	525	12,0
	5 No	352	8,0
	Total	4386	100
	9 No answer	29	
		4415	
Z854	SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES		X824, jfr Y643
	What do you think of the idea of going for a society with more private alternatives within school, nursing and care?		
	1 Very good idea	417	9,8
	2 Rather good idea	1207	28,2
	3 Neither good nor bad	960	22,5
	4 Rather bad idea	1179	27,6
	5 Very bad idea	513	12,0
	Total	4276	100
	8 Doesn't know	120	

	9	No answer	19	
			4415	
Z855		SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES		X825, Y645
		What do you think of the idea of going for a society where income differences are small?		
	1	Very good idea	780	18,2
	2	Rather good idea	1449	33,9
	3	Neither good nor bad	879	20,6
	4	Rather bad idea	931	21,8
	5	Very bad idea	235	5,5
		Total	4274	100
	8	Doesn't know	121	
	9	No answer	20	
			4415	
Z856		SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY		X826
		What do you think of the idea of going for a society where care for children and the elderly occurs to a greater extent within the family?		
	1	Very good idea	250	5,8
	2	Rather good idea	676	15,8
	3	Neither good nor bad	1032	24,1
	4	Rather bad idea	1694	39,6
	5	Very bad idea	629	14,7
		Total	4281	100
	8	Doesn't know	116	
	9	No answer	18	
			4415	
Z857		SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY		X827
		What do you think of the idea of going for a society where men take as much responsibility for children and the household as women do?		
	1	Very good idea	2261	52,2
	2	Rather good idea	1362	31,5
	3	Neither good nor bad	465	10,7
	4	Rather bad idea	196	4,5
	5	Very bad idea	44	1,0
		Total	4328	100
	8	Doesn't know	70	
	9	No answer	17	
			4415	

Z858	TROUBLESHOOTER		X828, Y649
	Do you usually see a solution to problems and difficulties that other people find hopeless?		
1	Yes, most often	2008	46,2
2	Yes, sometimes	2104	48,4
3	No	233	5,4
	Total	4345	100
9	No answer	70	
		4415	
Z859	LIFE SATISFACTION		X829, Y650
	Do you usually feel that your daily life is a source of personal satisfaction?		
1	Yes, most often	2882	66,0
2	Yes, sometimes	1238	28,4
3	No	245	5,6
	Total	4365	100
9	No answer	50	
		4415	
Z860	HARD TO UNDERSTAND		X830, Y651
	Do you usually feel that things that happen to you in your daily life are hard to understand?		
1	Yes, most often	135	3,1
2	Yes, sometimes	1000	22,9
3	No	3232	74,0
	Total	4367	100
9	No answer	48	
		4415	
Z861	CONTROL OF OWN LIFE		X831, Y652
	Do you usually feel that you are in control of your own life?		
1	Yes, most often	3513	80,2
2	Yes, sometimes	696	15,9
3	No	169	3,9
	Total	4378	100
9	No answer	37	
		4415	

Z862	RESPONDENT'S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION	X832, Y647, U702
	We have now been through a lot of questions about your living conditions in different areas. How do you yourself view your own conditions? By and large, do you think that your situation is very good, rather good, rather bad, or very bad?	
	1 Very good	2300 52,4
	2 Rather good	1909 43,5
	3 Neither good nor bad	99 2,3
	4 Rather bad	66 1,5
	5 Very bad	19 0,4
	Total	4393 100
	9 No answer	22
		4415
Z863	HAS RESPONDENT'S CONDITIONS IMPROVED OR DETERIORATED	X833, Y648, U703
	If you look back over the last ten years, do you think that your living conditions during this time have deteriorated, improved, or remained more or less the same?	
	1 Deteriorated	551 12,6
	2 Improved	2498 57,1
	3 Remained more or less the same	1326 30,3
	Total	4375 100
	9 No answer	40
		4415
Z864	I LIKE ORDERLINESS	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
	1 Disagree	20 0,5
	2 Disagree a little	57 1,5
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	260 6,8
	4 Agree a little	1939 50,4
	5 Totally agree	1572 40,9
	Total	3848 100
	88 Doesn't know	16
	99 No answer	551
		4415
Z865	I DO NOT SHOW FEELINGS TO OTHERS	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
	1 Disagree	643 16,8
	2 Disagree a little	1299 33,9
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	831 21,7
	4 Agree a little	928 24,2
	5 Totally agree	136 3,5
	Total	3837 100

	88	Doesn't know	27	
	99	No answer	551	
			4415	
Z866		SETBACKS DON'T DISCOURAGE ME		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1	Disagree	131	3,5
	2	Disagree a little	251	6,6
	3	Neither agree nor disagree	449	11,8
	4	Agree a little	1924	50,8
	5	Totally agree	1035	27,3
		Total	3790	100
	88	Doesn't know	74	
	99	No answer	551	
			4415	
Z867		I TEND TO BE LAZY		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1	Disagree	1045	27,2
	2	Disagree a little	1341	35,0
	3	Neither agree nor disagree	958	25,0
	4	Agree a little	424	11,1
	5	Totally agree	67	1,7
		Total	3835	100
	88	Doesn't know	29	
	99	No answer	551	
			4415	
Z868		I OFTEN THINK MORE ABOUT HOW OTHERS HAVE IT THAN OF MYSELF		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1	Disagree	179	4,6
	2	Disagree a little	434	11,3
	3	Neither agree nor disagree	1274	33,1
	4	Agree a little	1592	41,3
	5	Totally agree	373	9,7
		Total	3852	100
	88	Doesn't know	12	
	99	No answer	551	
			4415	
Z869		TO SUCCEED IN LIFE YOU HAVE TO TAKE RISKS		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1	Disagree	90	2,3

2	Disagree a little	352	9,2
3	Neither agree nor disagree	866	22,5
4	Agree a little	1927	50,2
5	Totally agree	606	15,8
	Total	3841	100
88	Doesn't know	23	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z870	I GET NERVOUS EASILY		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	677	17,6
2	Disagree a little	1331	34,7
3	Neither agree nor disagree	976	25,4
4	Agree a little	692	18,0
5	Totally agree	162	4,2
	Total	3838	100
88	Doesn't know	26	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z871	I FIND IT EASY TO GET THINGS DONE		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	46	1,2
2	Disagree a little	301	7,9
3	Neither agree nor disagree	808	21,1
4	Agree a little	2059	53,7
5	Totally agree	619	16,1
	Total	3833	100
88	Doesn't know	31	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z872	I LIKE TAKING RESPONSIBILITY		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	32	0,8
2	Disagree a little	184	4,8
3	Neither agree nor disagree	566	14,8
4	Agree a little	1965	51,2
5	Totally agree	1090	28,4
	Total	3837	100
88	Doesn't know	27	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z873	IT DOESN'T PAY TO PLAN FOR THE FUTURE		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	1134	29,6
2	Disagree a little	1440	37,6
3	Neither agree nor disagree	659	17,2
4	Agree a little	432	11,3
5	Totally agree	169	4,4
	Total	3834	100
88	Doesn't know	30	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	
Z874	I HANDLE STRESS WELL		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	114	3,0
2	Disagree a little	402	10,5
3	Neither agree nor disagree	884	23,1
4	Agree a little	1914	50,0
5	Totally agree	511	13,4
	Total	3825	100
88	Doesn't know	39	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	
Z875	I FINISH WHATEVER I BEGIN		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	41	1,1
2	Disagree a little	245	6,4
3	Neither agree nor disagree	587	15,3
4	Agree a little	2018	52,6
5	Totally agree	943	24,6
	Total	3834	100
88	Doesn't know	30	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	
Z876	I'M A RISK TAKER		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	542	14,2
2	Disagree a little	1134	29,7
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1358	35,5
4	Agree a little	638	16,7
5	Totally agree	148	3,9

		Total	3820	100
88		Doesn't know	44	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z877		I DO NOT LIKE CHANGING OLD HABITS		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	326	8,5
2		Disagree a little	997	25,9
3		Neither agree nor disagree	1229	31,9
4		Agree a little	1035	26,9
5		Totally agree	263	6,8
		Total	3850	100
88		Doesn't know	14	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z878		I PUT EFFORT INTO THINGS THAT PAY OFF ONLY IN THE FUTURE		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	189	4,9
2		Disagree a little	602	15,6
3		Neither agree nor disagree	1687	43,8
4		Agree a little	1147	29,8
5		Totally agree	224	5,8
		Total	3849	100
88		Doesn't know	15	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z879		I FIND IT HARD TO RESIST TEMPTATIONS		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	448	11,8
2		Disagree a little	1163	30,6
3		Neither agree nor disagree	1224	32,2
4		Agree a little	855	22,5
5		Totally agree	114	3,0
		Total	3804	100
88		Doesn't know	60	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	

Z880	SUCCESS IS A RESULT OF HARD WORK RATHER THAN LUCK	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
1	Disagree	32 0,8
2	Disagree a little	154 4,1
3	Neither agree nor disagree	679 18,0
4	Agree a little	2199 58,3
5	Totally agree	709 18,8
	Total	3773 100
88	Doesn't know	91
99	No answer	551
		4415
Z881	I HAVE AN ACTIVE IMAGINATION	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
1	Disagree	270 7,2
2	Disagree a little	678 18,0
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1118 29,6
4	Agree a little	1229 32,6
5	Totally agree	477 12,6
	Total	3772 100
88	Doesn't know	92
99	No answer	551
		4415
Z882	I USUALLY PUT OF THINGS THAT FEEL BOTHERSOME	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
1	Disagree	369 9,7
2	Disagree a little	1138 29,9
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1069 28,1
4	Agree a little	1067 28,0
5	Totally agree	164 4,3
	Total	3807 100
88	Doesn't know	57
99	No answer	551
		4415
Z883	WHAT HAPPENS TO ME IS MY OWN DOING	NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?	
1	Disagree	54 1,4
2	Disagree a little	192 5,1
3	Neither agree nor disagree	875 23,0
4	Agree a little	2138 56,3
5	Totally agree	539 14,2

		Total	3798	100
88		Doesn't know	66	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z884		I HAVE A GOOD SELF-CONFIDENCE		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	51	1,3
2		Disagree a little	293	7,7
3		Neither agree nor disagree	714	18,8
4		Agree a little	2128	56,0
5		Totally agree	617	16,2
		Total	3803	100
88		Doesn't know	61	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z885		I HAVE FEW ARTISTIC INTERESTS		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	851	22,4
2		Disagree a little	938	24,7
3		Neither agree nor disagree	647	17,0
4		Agree a little	763	20,1
5		Totally agree	600	15,8
		Total	3799	100
88		Doesn't know	65	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	
Z886		I AM OUTGOING AND SOCIABLE		NEW
		How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1		Disagree	51	1,3
2		Disagree a little	229	6,0
3		Neither agree nor disagree	644	17,0
4		Agree a little	1827	48,2
5		Totally agree	1041	27,5
		Total	3792	100
88		Doesn't know	72	
99		No answer	551	
			4415	

Z887	I HAVE GOOD SELF-DISCIPLINE		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1 Disagree	28	0,7
	2 Disagree a little	236	6,2
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	746	19,6
	4 Agree a little	2105	55,4
	5 Totally agree	687	18,1
	Total	3802	100
	88 Doesn't know	62	
	99 No answer	551	
		4415	
Z888	I DEAL WITH TASKS THOROUGHLY		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1 Disagree	9	0,2
	2 Disagree a little	120	3,2
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	583	15,3
	4 Agree a little	2154	56,6
	5 Totally agree	937	24,6
	Total	3803	100
	88 Doesn't know	61	
	99 No answer	551	
		4415	
Z889	I PREFER TO STAY IN THE BACKGROUND		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1 Disagree	435	11,4
	2 Disagree a little	1091	28,7
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	1248	32,8
	4 Agree a little	857	22,5
	5 Totally agree	172	4,5
	Total	3803	100
	88 Doesn't know	61	
	99 No answer	551	
		4415	
Z890	I TEND TO FIND FAULT WITH OTHERS		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1 Disagree	561	14,7
	2 Disagree a little	1368	36,0
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	1267	33,3
	4 Agree a little	519	13,6
	5 Totally agree	90	2,4

	Total	3805	100
88	Doesn't know	59	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z891	I AM A NATURAL LEADER		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	354	9,3
2	Disagree a little	687	18,1
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1333	35,1
4	Agree a little	1158	30,5
5	Totally agree	267	7,0
	Total	3799	100
88	Doesn't know	65	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z892	AM GENERALLY TRUSTING		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	75	2,0
2	Disagree a little	249	6,5
3	Neither agree nor disagree	653	17,2
4	Agree a little	2331	61,3
5	Totally agree	497	13,1
	Total	3805	100
88	Doesn't know	59	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z893	I AM RESERVED		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
1	Disagree	522	13,7
2	Disagree a little	1097	28,9
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1235	32,5
4	Agree a little	821	21,6
5	Totally agree	125	3,3
	Total	3800	100
88	Doesn't know	64	
99	No answer	551	
		4415	

Z894	IM AM ALMOST ALWAYS IN A GOOD MOOD		NEW
	How well does [above trait] describe your character?		
	1 Disagree	31	0,8
	2 Disagree a little	132	3,5
	3 Neither agree nor disagree	743	19,5
	4 Agree a little	2106	55,3
	5 Totally agree	797	20,9
	Total	3809	100
	88 Doesn't know	55	
	99 No answer	551	
		4415	
Z913	NATIONALITY		X835, Y654, U705
	Citizenship according to the RTB-registry, collected from LISA.		
	0 Sweden	4174	94,5
	1 Nordic countries (except Sweden)	78	1,8
	2 EU15 (except Denmark, Finland and Sweden)	31	0,7
	3 Europe (except EU15 and Nordic countries)	28	0,6
	4 Africa	24	0,5
	5 North america	1	0,0
	6 South america	4	0,1
	7 Asia	68	1,5
	8 Oceania	1	0,0
	11 Unknown	6	0,1
	Total	4415	100
Z914	COUNTY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION		X837, Y656, U707
	County according to current parish registration according to the RTB-registry, collected from LISA.		
	01 Stockholms län	865	19,6
	03 Uppsala län	152	3,4
	04 Södermanlands län	126	2,9
	05 Östergötlands län	219	5,0
	06 Jönköpings län	163	3,7
	07 Kronobergs län	91	2,1
	08 Kalmar län	122	2,8
	09 Gotlands län	29	0,7
	10 Blekinge län	54	1,2
	12 Skåne län	564	12,8
	13 Hallands län	144	3,3
	14 Västra Götalands län	790	17,9
	17 Värmlands län	128	2,9
	18 Örebro län	162	3,7
	19 Västmanlands län	118	2,7
	20 Dalarnas län	130	2,9
	21 Gävleborgs län	134	3,0

	22	Västernorrlands län	113	2,6
	23	Jämtlands län	66	1,5
	24	Västerbottens län	127	2,9
	25	Norrbottnens län	118	2,7
		Total	4415	100
Z915	MUNICIPALITY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION			X838, Y657, U708
	Municipality according to current parish registration according to the RTB-registry, collected from LISA. Not shown.			
Z916	H-REGION			X841, Y660, jfr U728
	H-region, scope according to the RTB-registry, collected from LISA.			
	1	Sthlm/Södertäljes A-region	838	19,0
	3	Medium sized cities	1671	37,8
	4	Southern Sweden	711	16,1
	5	Densely populated northern Sweden	238	5,4
	6	Sparsely populated northern Sweden	223	5,1
	8	Gothenburgs A-region	456	10,3
	9	Malmö/Lund/Trelleborgs A-region	278	6,3
		Total	4415	100
Z917	CIVIL STATUS			X842, Y661, U715, V814, W704
	Civil status according to RTB, collected from LISA.			
	1	G = married	2120	48,0
	2	OG = unmarried	1638	37,1
	3	RP = registered partner	6	0,1
	4	S = divorced	535	12,1
	5	Ä = widower/widow	116	2,6
		Total	4415	100
Z918	SPOUSE'S YEAR OF BIRTH			X843, Y663, U716
	Year of birth for respondent's spouse/partner according to RTB, collected from LISA.			
		1920-1929	10	0,4
		1930-1939	151	6,4
		1940-1949	486	20,7
		1950-1959	489	20,8
		1960-1969	476	20,3
		1970-1979	490	20,9
		1980-1989	231	9,8
		1990-1999	14	0,6
		Total	2347	100
		Not applicable	2068	
			4415	

Z919	INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER ORDINARY DATA COLLECTION AND FOLLOW UP TO COLLECT MISSING DATA	NEW																																													
<p>Applied when analysing the long interviews for all respondents, stratum 1-4. See <i>Teknisk rapport. En beskrivning av genomförande och metoder. Levnadsnivåundersökningen 2010</i> for more a more detailed account. Not shown.</p>																																															
Z920	INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER FOLLOW UP WITH A SHORT VERSION OF THE INTERVIEW	NEW																																													
<p>Applied when analysing the long AND the short interviews for all respondents, stratum 1-4. Se <i>Teknisk rapport. En beskrivning av genomförande och metoder. Levnadsnivåundersökningen 2010</i> för en utförligare beskrivning. Not shown.</p>																																															
Z921	STRATUM 1-3: INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER ORDINARY DATA COLLECTION AND FOLLOW UP TO COLLECT MISSING DATA.	jfr X845, jfr Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942																																													
<p>Applied when analysing the long interviews, the response rate corresponds to stratum 1-3. See <i>Teknisk rapport. En beskrivning av genomförande och metoder. Levnadsnivåundersökningen 2010</i> for more a more detailed account. Not shown.</p>																																															
Z922	STRATUM 1-3: INDIVIDUAL WEIGHT AFTER FOLLOW UP WITH A SHORT VERSION OF THE INTERVIEW	NEW																																													
<p>Applied when analysing the long AND the short interviews, the response rate corresponds to stratum 1-3. See <i>Teknisk rapport. En beskrivning av genomförande och metoder. Levnadsnivåundersökningen 2010</i> for more a more detailed account. Not shown.</p>																																															
Z923	DISPOSABLE HOUSEHOLD INCOME	NEW																																													
<p>Disposable household income in 0000s, collected from LISA. The variable is here categorized</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td><0</td> <td>18</td> <td>0,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-9</td> <td>217</td> <td>4,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10-19</td> <td>675</td> <td>15,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>20-29</td> <td>842</td> <td>19,1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>30-39</td> <td>611</td> <td>13,9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40-49</td> <td>697</td> <td>15,8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>50-59</td> <td>553</td> <td>12,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>60-69</td> <td>321</td> <td>7,3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>70-79</td> <td>178</td> <td>4,0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>80-89</td> <td>109</td> <td>2,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>90-99</td> <td>62</td> <td>1,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>>99</td> <td>130</td> <td>0,4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Totalt</td> <td>4413</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Information saknas</td> <td>2</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>4415</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			<0	18	0,4	0-9	217	4,9	10-19	675	15,3	20-29	842	19,1	30-39	611	13,9	40-49	697	15,8	50-59	553	12,5	60-69	321	7,3	70-79	178	4,0	80-89	109	2,5	90-99	62	1,4	>99	130	0,4	Totalt	4413		Information saknas	2			4415	
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80-89	109	2,5																																													
90-99	62	1,4																																													
>99	130	0,4																																													
Totalt	4413																																														
Information saknas	2																																														
	4415																																														
Z924	R - DISPOSABLE HOUSEHOLD INCOME	NEW																																													
<p>Disposable household income in 0000s – respondent contribution, collected from LISA. The variable is here categorized</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td><0</td> <td>35</td> <td>0,8</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			<0	35	0,8																																										
<0	35	0,8																																													

0-9	601	13,6
10-19	1417	32,1
20-29	1425	32,3
30-39	602	13,6
40-49	176	4,0
50-59	59	1,3
60-69	25	0,6
70-79	22	0,5
80-89	17	0,4
90-99	7	0,2
>99	27	0,6
Total	4413	
Information is missing	2	
	4415	

Z925

EARNINGS

NEW

Yearly earnings in 0000s, collected from LISA. The variable is here categorized

0-9	1800	40,8
10-19	455	10,3
20-29	803	18,2
30-39	763	17,3
40-49	309	7,0
50-59	136	3,1
60-69	61	1,4
70-79	27	0,6
80-89	25	0,6
90-99	7	0,2
>99	27	0,6
Total	4413	
Information is missing	2	
	4415	

**FOLLOWING VARIABLES RELATES TO
PARTNER-LNU (N = 2285).**

PZ1

P – TODAY'S DATE

NEW, jfr Z5

Date – year, month and day – when the interview was carried out. Only min- and max values are shown.

100103	1	
111123	1	
Total	2285	100

PZ2	P – SEX			X1002
	Are you a man or a woman?			
1	Man	1078	47,2	
2	Woman	1207	52,8	
	Total	2285	100	

PZ3	P – YEAR OF BIRTH			X1001
	What year were you born (19XX)?			
27		3	0,1	
28		3	0,1	
29		3	0,1	
30		1	0,0	
31		2	0,1	
32		8	0,4	
33		8	0,4	
34		17	0,7	
35		14	0,6	
36		20	0,9	
37		24	1,1	
38		22	1,0	
39		29	1,3	
40		24	1,1	
41		43	1,9	
42		42	1,8	
43		49	2,1	
44		65	2,8	
45		55	2,4	
46		47	2,1	
47		52	2,3	
48		47	2,1	
49		54	2,4	
50		53	2,3	
51		44	1,9	
52		36	1,6	
53		47	2,1	
54		56	2,5	
55		51	2,2	
56		47	2,1	
57		44	1,9	
58		50	2,2	
59		42	1,8	
60		36	1,6	
61		43	1,9	
62		50	2,2	
63		44	1,9	
64		52	2,3	

	79	Self-employed, number of employees unknown	24	1,4
	89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	2	0,1
		Total	1708	100
	99	Unclassified	282	
		Not applicable	295	
			2285	
PZ5	P – SEI CURRENT EMPLOYMENT STATUS			X1044
	Current occupation according to socio-economic classification (SEI) – occupational status.			
	1	Employed, fulltime	1145	51,3
	2	Employed, part-time	263	11,8
	3	Self-employed	175	7,8
	4	Unemployed	68	3,0
	5	Studying	66	3,0
	6	Working in the home	17	0,8
	7	Pensioner	429	19,2
	8	Other	26	1,2
	9	Two answers	44	2,0
		Total	2233	100
	99	No answer	52	
			2285	
PZ6	P – NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION			NEW
	Current profession/occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ7	P – NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION			NEW
	Current profession/occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ11	P – EGP CURRENT OCCUPATION			NEW
	Current profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).			
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	80	4,8
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	294	17,5
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	475	28,2
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	270	16,0
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	119	7,1
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	47	2,8
	9	IVd Smallholders	9	0,5
	10	Vs Supervisors	48	2,9
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	2	0,1
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	128	7,6
	13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	3	0,2
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	208	12,4
		Total	1683	100

	99	Unclassified	307	
		Not applicable	295	
			2285	
PZ12		P – BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN		X1004
		Were both of your parents born in Sweden?		
	1	No	377	16,6
	2	Yes	1896	83,4
		Total	2273	100
	9	No answer	12	
			2285	
PZ13		P – BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER		X1005
		What is the birth country of your father?		
	1	Sweden	1947	86,3
	2	Denmark, Norway	30	1,3
	3	Finland	76	3,4
	4	Former Yugoslavia	20	0,9
	5	Other Eastern Europe	40	1,8
	6	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	38	1,7
	7	Spain, Italy, Greece	6	0,3
	8	Other nationalities	99	4,4
		Total	2256	100
	9	Okänd	29	
			2285	
PZ14		P – BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER		X1006
		What is the birth country of your mother?		
	1	Sweden	1940	86,2
	2	Denmark, Norway	36	1,4
	3	Finland	87	3,6
	4	Former Yugoslavia	17	1,0
	5	Other Eastern Europe	36	1,4
	6	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	34	1,5
	7	Spain, Italy, Greece	7	0,3
	8	Other nationalities	103	4,5
		Total	2260	100
	9	Okänd	25	
			2285	
PZ15		P – COUNTRY OF ORIGIN		X1008
		Where were you born?		
	1	Sweden	2045	90,3
	2	Denmark, Norway	24	1,1

3	Finland	32	1,4
4	Former Yugoslavia	17	0,8
5	Other Eastern Europe	30	1,3
6	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	18	0,8
7	Spain, Italy, Greece	5	0,2
8	Other nationalities	93	4,1
	Total	2264	100
9	Okänd	21	
		2285	

PZ16

P – AGE AT IMMIGRATION

X1009

How old were you when you came to Sweden? Here this variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for PZ15 NE 1

0		1	0,5
1-4		12	5,5
5-9		13	6,0
10-14		9	4,1
15-19		26	11,9
20-24		51	23,4
25-29		39	17,9
30-34		25	11,5
35-39		22	10,1
40-44		10	4,6
45-49		5	2,3
50-54		1	0,5
55-59		2	0,9
60-64		1	0,5
≥65		1	0,5
	Total	218	100
99	No answer	22	
	Not applicable	2265	
		2285	

PZ17

P – INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY

X1011

Did you live with both your (biological) parents during your whole childhood?

10	Yes	1821	80,3
21	No, divorce/separation	312	13,8
22	No, parents never lived together	44	1,9
23	No, both parents deceased	4	0,2
24	No, father deceased	34	1,5
25	No, mother deceased	17	0,7
26	No, lived with foster parents	10	0,4
27	No, lived with adoptive parents	17	0,7
28	No, no information on reason	8	0,4
	Total	2267	100
99	No answer	18	

PZ18**P – SEI FATHER****X1013**

Father's main profession or occupation. Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	329	15,1
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	277	12,7
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	456	20,9
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	24	1,1
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	28	1,3
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	72	3,3
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	112	5,1
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	29	1,3
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	266	12,2
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	154	7,1
57	Professional, upper-level executive	80	3,7
60	Self-employed professional	79	3,6
79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees	102	4,7
89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	169	7,8
	Total	2177	100
99	Unclassified	108	
		2285	

PZ19**P – NYK80 FATHER****X1014**

Father's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.

PZ20**P – NYK85 FATHER****X1015**

Father's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.

PZ25**P – SEI MOTHER**

Mother's main profession or occupation. Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".

12	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	155	7,0
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	568	25,8
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	23	1,0
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	142	6,4
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	113	5,1
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	18	0,8
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	148	6,7
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	16	0,7
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	316	14,3
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	87	3,9
57	Professional, upper-level executive	13	0,6

	60	Self-employed professional	19	0,9
	79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees	28	1,3
	89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	52	2,4
	92	Homemaker	506	23,0
		Total	2204	100
	99	Unclassified	81	
			2285	
PZ26	P – NYK80 MOTHER			X1018
	Mother's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ27	P – NYK85 MOTHER			X1019
	Mother's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ32	P – FATHER'S EDUCATION			jfr X1024
	Which of the following educational levels is your father's highest education?			
	1	Compulsory school	1080	48,3
	2	Vocational school	342	15,3
	3	Realexamen/2-year theoretical gymnasium	130	5,8
	4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	113	5,1
	5	Higher education	117	5,2
	6	University degree	231	10,3
	7	Father has no education	107	4,8
	8	Doesn't know	115	5,1
		Total	2235	100
	9	No answer	50	
			2285	
PZ33	P – MOTHER'S EDUCATION			jfr X1025
	Which of the following educational levels is your mothers's highest education?			
	1	Compulsory school	1142	51,1
	2	Vocational school	294	13,2
	3	Realexamen/2-year theoretical gymnasium	174	7,8
	4	3-4 -year theoretical gymnasium	105	4,7
	5	Higher education	212	9,5
	6	University degree	111	5,0
	7	Mother has no education	105	4,7
	8	Doesn't know	90	4,0
		Total	1142	51,1
	9	No answer	52	
			2285	

PZ34

P – PARTNER’S EDUCATION IN YEARS

X1023

How many years altogether have you been to school or a vocational training full-time?

0		1	0,0
1		4	0,2
2		1	0,0
3		3	0,1
4		1	0,0
5		7	0,3
6		10	0,4
7		88	3,9
8		79	3,5
9		115	5,1
10		119	5,3
11		268	12,0
12		326	14,5
13		216	9,6
14		191	8,5
15		213	9,5
16		195	8,7
17		167	7,4
18		101	4,5
19		53	2,4
20		30	1,3
21		16	0,7
22		11	0,5
23		5	0,2
24		1	0,0
25		3	0,1
27		2	0,1
30		1	0,0
32		1	0,0
33		1	0,0
35		1	0,0
40		3	0,1
41		1	0,0
43		1	0,0
44		1	0,0
46		1	0,0
47		1	0,0
55		1	0,0
56		1	0,0
58		1	0,0
60		1	0,0
	Total	2242	100
99	No answer	43	
		2285	

PZ35**P – HIGHEST EDUCATION****X1024**

Which of the following educational levels have you passed?

0	No education	13	0,6
1	Elementary school	151	6,6
2	Compulsory school	140	6,1
3	Vocational 3-4-year upper secondary school	767	33,6
4	3- to 4-year academic upper secondary program	180	7,9
5	Post-secondary education	506	22,1
6	University	517	22,6
7	Postgraduate education	11	0,5
	Total	2285	100
		2285	

PZ36**P – NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT****X1025**

About how many years altogether have you spent in gainful employment? This variable is divided into categories.

0		2	0,1
1-4		113	5,1
5-9		202	9,2
10-14		205	9,3
15-19		191	8,7
20-24		265	12,1
25-29		215	9,8
30-34		273	12,4
35-39		267	12,2
40-44		219	10,0
45-49		151	6,9
50-54		83	3,8
55-59		8	0,4
≥60		1	0,0
	Total	2195	100
77	Never been in gainful employment	29	
99	No answer	61	
		2285	

PZ37**P – BEGAN WORKING: YEAR****X1026**

What year and month did you begin the first job you had that lasted at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

1940-49		23	1,1
1950-59		214	9,8
1960-69		393	17,9
1970-79		464	21,2
1980-89		429	19,6
1990-99		366	16,7
2000-09		296	13,5
2010		5	0,2

	Total		2190	100
999999	No answer		50	
777777	Never been in gainful employment/never had a job for at least 6 months.		45	
			2285	
PZ38	P – SEI FIRST JOB			NEW
	First profession/occupation according to Socio-economic group (SEI).			
11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production		289	13,3
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production		623	28,7
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production		252	11,6
22	Skilled manual worker, service production		153	7,0
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks		189	8,7
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers		11	0,5
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates		136	6,3
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors		18	0,8
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates		328	15,1
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker		122	5,6
57	Professional, upper-level executive**		6	0,3
60	Self-employed professionals		36	1,7
79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees		4	0,2
87	Farmer, size of farm unknown		7	0,3
	Total		2174	100
777	Never been in gainful employment/never had a job for at least 6 months.		50	
999	Unclassified		61	
			2285	
PZ39	P – NYK80 FIRST JOB			NEW
	First profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ40	P – NYK85 FIRST JOB			NEW
	First profession/occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ45	P – EGP FIRST JOB			
	First profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe och Portocarero (EGP).			
1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals		36	1,7
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals		128	5,9
3	II Lower-grade professionals		332	15,3
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade		285	13,1
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade		516	23,7
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees		4	0,2
9	IVd Smallholders		7	0,3
10	Vs Supervisors		30	1,4

11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	2	0,1
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	243	11,2
13	Vlj Skilled manual workers in primary production	6	0,3
14	VIIIs Unskilled manual workers	585	26,9
	Total	2174	100
77	Never been in gainful employment/never had a job for at least 6 months.	50	
99	Unclassified	61	
		2285	

PZ46	P – OCCUPATION AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1031	
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner?		
1	Employed, fulltime	1539	70,3
2	Employed, part-time	174	7,9
3	Self-employed	109	5,0
4	Unemployed	48	2,2
5	Studying	257	11,7
6	Working at home	5	0,2
7	Pensioner	12	0,5
8	Other	11	0,5
9	Two answers	35	1,6
	Total	2190	100
99	No answer	95	
		2285	

PZ47	P – SEI AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1032	
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	165	8,4
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	379	19,3
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	230	11,7
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	142	7,2
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	114	5,8
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	25	1,3
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	146	7,4
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	21	1,1
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	400	20,4
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	155	7,9
57	Professional, upper-level executive**	20	1,0
60	Self-employed professionals	47	2,4
79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees	117	6,0
89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	2	0,1
	Total	1963	100
77	No profession/job when present cohab started	63	
99	Unclassified	259	
		2285	

PZ48	P – NYK80 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1033		
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ49	P – NYK85 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1034		
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). Not shown.			
PZ54	P – EGP AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION	X1030		
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Coded according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).			
	1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	49	2,5
	2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	183	9,3
	3	II Lower-grade professionals	420	21,5
	4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	308	15,7
	5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	325	16,6
	6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	18	0,9
	9	IVd Smallholders	7	0,4
	10	Vs Supervisors	41	2,1
	11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	3	0,2
	12	VIs Skilled manual workers	245	12,5
	13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	5	0,3
	14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	354	18,1
		Total	1958	100
	77	No profession/job when present cohab started	63	
	99	Unclassified	264	
			2285	
PZ61	P – IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT LAST WHEN	X1050		
	When did you last engage in gainful employment lasting at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.			
	<1990		16	3,4
	1990		1	0,2
	1991		3	0,6
	1992		5	1,1
	1993		7	1,5
	1994		5	1,1
	1995		7	1,5
	1996		5	1,1
	1997		18	3,8
	1998		12	2,5
	1999		18	3,8
	2000		10	2,1
	2001		19	4,0

2002		22	4,6
2003		26	5,5
2004		21	4,4
2005		29	6,1
2006		37	7,8
2007		36	7,6
2008		45	9,5
2009		69	14,6
2010		58	12,2
2011		5	1,1
		474	100,0
777777	Full- or part-time employed or self-employed	1563	
888888	Never worked more than 6 months	70	
999999	No answer	178	
		2285	

PZ62

P – EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

X1069

Is any schooling or vocational training above elementary schooling necessary for your job?

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7.

1	Yes	1225	75,6
2	No	395	24,4
	Total	1620	100
9	No answer	59	
	Not applicable	606	
		2285	

PZ63

P – SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

X1070

If yes: About how many years of education above elementary school are necessary for your job?

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7 AND PZ62 EQ 1.

0		1	0,1
1		63	5,7
2		128	11,6
3		361	32,6
4		122	11,0
5		89	8,0
6		130	11,8
7		89	8,0
8		61	5,5
9		12	1,1
10		19	1,7
11		5	0,5
12		10	0,9
13		4	0,4
14		2	0,2
15		6	0,5

16		1	0,1
17		1	0,1
19		1	0,1
50		1	0,1
	Total	1106	100
	No answer	178	
	Not applicable	1001	
		2285	

PZ64 **P – SUPERVISORY TASKS** **X1071**

Do you have any supervisory tasks?

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7.

1	Yes	421	26,0
2	No	1200	74,0
	Total	1621	100
9	No answer	58	
	Not applicable	606	
		2285	

PZ65 **P – NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES** **X1072**

If yes: How many persons do you supervise? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7 AND PZ64 EQ 1.

0		15	3,7
1-9		219	54,3
10-19		89	22,1
20-29		30	7,4
30-39		13	3,2
40-49		8	2,0
50-59		2	0,5
60-69		4	1,0
70-79		5	1,2
90-99		1	0,2
100-199		11	2,7
200-299		2	0,5
300-399		2	0,5
400-499		1	0,2
≥500		1	0,2
	Total	403	100,0
999	No answer	76	
	Not applicable	1806	
		2285	

How many hours do you usually work per week?

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 3-7.

0	1	0,1
2	1	0,1
5	1	0,1
7	1	0,1
8	3	0,2
10	4	0,3
14	1	0,1
15	6	0,4
16	4	0,3
17	1	0,1
18	1	0,1
20	56	3,9
22	1	0,1
23	1	0,1
24	9	0,6
25	11	0,8
26	4	0,3
27	6	0,4
28	11	0,8
29	5	0,3
30	85	5,9
31	4	0,3
32	52	3,6
32.5	1	0,1
33	12	0,8
34	14	1,0
35	26	1,8
36	37	2,6
36.7	1	0,1
37	37	2,6
37.5	1	0,1
38	73	5,1
38.5	1	0,1
39	35	2,4
40	823	57,0
41	2	0,1
42	7	0,5
43	1	0,1
44	1	0,1
45	60	4,2
46	2	0,1
47	1	0,1
48	4	0,3
50	16	1,1
55	4	0,3

56		1	0,1
60		7	0,5
65		1	0,1
70		4	0,3
84		1	0,1
90		1	0,1
	Total	1443	100
99	No answer	61	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job currently	781	
		2285	

PZ67

P – HOW OFTEN OVERTIME

X1055

How often do you work overtime in your present job? Is it...

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 3-7.

1	Never	295	20,4
2	A few times a year	294	20,4
3	A few times a month	395	27,4
4	A couple of times a week	260	18,0
5	Several times a week	199	13,8
	Total	1443	100
9	No answer	61	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job currently	781	
		2285	

PZ68

P – NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK: NUMBER OF NIGHTS/YEAR

X1068

Do you ever stay away from home overnight because of your work, e.g., on a business trip? If yes: About how many nights are you away altogether during one year's time? This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7.

0		983	60,7
1-9		292	18,0
10-19		147	9,1
20-29		65	4,0
30-39		35	2,2
40-49		16	1,0
50-59		18	1,1
60-69		7	0,4
70-79		5	0,3
80-89		9	0,6
90-99		7	0,4
100-109		13	0,8
110-119		2	0,1
120-129		3	0,2
130-139		3	0,2
140-149		3	0,2
150-159		4	0,2
160-169		3	0,2

180-189		1	0,1
190-199		1	0,1
≥200		3	0,2
	Total	1620	100
999	No answer	59	
	Doesn't have a job currently	606	
		2285	

PZ69

P – GROSS MONTHLY SALARY

X1073

What is your usual monthly salary from your regular employment? (Gross salary). This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7.

<10		23	1,6
10-14		52	3,7
15-19		153	10,9
20-24		359	25,6
25-29		337	24,0
30-34		181	12,9
35-39		80	5,7
40-44		82	5,8
45-49		48	3,4
50-54		27	1,9
55-59		11	0,8
60-64		16	1,1
65-69		6	0,4
70-74		6	0,4
75-79		4	0,3
80-84		3	0,2
85-89		2	0,1
90-94		2	0,1
≥95		12	0,9
	Total	1404	100
999999	No answer	301	
	Not applicable	580	
		2285	

PZ70

P – NET MONTHLY SALARY

X1074

What is your usual monthly salary from your regular employment? (Net salary). This variable is divided into categories.

The table is valid for PZ5 NE 4-7.

<10		30	17,5
10-14		37	21,6
10-19		51	29,8
20-24		29	17,0
20-29		12	7,0
30-34		7	4,1
30-39		1	0,6
40-44		3	1,8

≥90		1	0,6
	Total	171	100
999999	No answer	1534	
	Not applicable	580	
		2285	

PZ71

P – HOURS P – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES

X1097

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		32	1,5
.5		2	0,1
1		150	7,1
1.5		4	0,2
2		241	11,3
2.5		2	0,1
3		198	9,3
3.5		3	0,1
4		164	7,7
4.5		1	0,0
5		244	11,5
6		118	5,6
7		181	8,5
7.5		3	0,1
8		106	5,0
9		39	1,8
10		274	12,9
11		20	0,9
12		55	2,6
13		8	0,4
14		73	3,4
15		74	3,5
16		13	0,6
17		3	0,1
18		11	0,5
19		1	0,0
20		53	2,5
21		13	0,6
22		1	0,0
23		2	0,1
25		15	0,7
27		1	0,0
28		4	0,2
30		9	0,4
32		1	0,0
35		3	0,1
42		1	0,0
45		1	0,0
	Total	2124	100
99	No answer	161	
		2285	

Mean value for all	7,1
Standard deviation	5,5
Mean value for >0	7,2
Standard deviation for >0	5,5

ZP72

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES

X1098

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0	34	1,7
.5	1	0,0
1	170	8,5
1.5	2	0,1
2	248	12,3
2.5	1	0,0
3	198	9,9
3.5	4	0,2
4	199	9,9
4.5	1	0,0
5	281	14,0
6	137	6,8
6.5	154	7,7
7	2	0,1
7.5	110	5,5
8	32	1,6
9	224	11,1
10	6	0,3
11	40	2,0
12	7	0,3
13	40	2,0
14	53	2,6
15	7	0,3
16	2	0,1
17	6	0,3
18	29	1,4
20	3	0,1
21	2	0,1
24	4	0,2
25	3	0,1
28	6	0,3
30	1	0,0
32	3	0,1
40	34	1,7
	Total	2010 100
99	No answer	275
		2285
	Mean value for all	6,1
	Standard deviation	4,7
	Mean value for >0	6,2

Standard deviation for >0

4,7

PZ73**P - HOURS CHILDREN – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES****X1099**

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		211	40,0
.5		8	1,5
1		188	35,6
2		76	14,4
3		16	3,0
4		7	1,3
5		9	1,7
6		2	0,4
7		6	1,1
8		1	0,2
9		1	0,2
10		1	0,2
15		1	0,2
20		1	0,2
	Total	528	100
99	No answer	581	
	Not applicable	1176	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	1,1	
	Standard deviation	1,7	
	Mean value for >0	1,8	
	Standard deviation for >0	1,9	

PZ74**P – HOURS P – CARE OF CLOTHING****X1100**

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		280	14,0
.5		13	0,6
1		434	21,7
1.5		10	0,5
2		440	22,0
2.5		1	0,0
3		267	13,3
4		178	8,9
5		174	8,7
6		53	2,6
7		55	2,7
8		32	1,6
9		4	0,2
10		40	2,0
11		1	0,0

12		2	0,1
14		8	0,4
15		7	0,3
20		2	0,1
30		2	0,1
	Total	2003	100
99	No answer	282	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	2,7	
	Standard deviation	2,6	
	Mean value for >0	3,2	
	Standard deviation for >0	2,6	

PZ75

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CARE OF CLOTHING

X1101

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		262	14,8
.5		22	1,2
1		371	21,0
1.5		3	0,2
2		321	18,1
2.5		1	0,1
3		240	13,6
4		160	9,0
5		153	8,6
6		47	2,7
7		51	2,9
8		38	2,1
9		5	0,3
10		71	4,0
12		7	0,4
14		6	0,3
15		5	0,3
18		1	0,1
19		1	0,1
20		1	0,1
25		1	0,1
30		1	0,1
40		1	0,1
	Total	1769	100
99	No answer	516	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	3,0	
	Standard deviation	3,0	
	Mean value for >0	3,5	
	Standard deviation for >0	3,0	

PZ76

P – HOURS CHILDREN – CARE OF CLOTHING

X1102

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend?

0		294	66,5
.5		5	1,1
1		97	21,9
2		32	7,2
3		5	1,1
4		3	0,7
5		3	0,7
10		1	0,2
15		1	0,2
20		1	0,2
	Total	442	100
99	No answer	667	
	Not applicable	1176	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	0,6	
	Standard deviation	1,5	
	Mean value for >0	1,7	
	Standard deviation for >0	2,2	

PZ77

P – HOURS P – CLEANING

X1103

About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		109	5,2
.5		13	0,6
1		518	24,9
1.5		4	0,2
2		555	26,7
2.5		3	0,1
3		293	14,1
3.5		1	0,0
4		199	9,6
5		174	8,4
6		43	2,1
7		50	2,4
8		32	1,5
9		3	0,1
10		49	2,4
11		1	0,0
12		6	0,3
13		2	0,1
14		6	0,3
15		9	0,4
16		1	0,0
20		7	0,3
21		1	0,0

22		1	0,0
30		2	0,1
	Total	2082	100
99	No answer	203	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	3,0	
	Standard deviation	2,8	
	Mean value for >0	3,1	
	Standard deviation for >0	2,8	

PZ78

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CLEANING

X1104

About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		121	6,4
.5		13	0,7
1		524	27,7
1.5		4	0,2
2		485	25,6
2.5		4	0,2
3		245	12,9
3.5		1	0,1
4		168	8,9
5		156	8,2
6		49	2,6
7		31	1,6
8		33	1,7
9		2	0,1
10		40	2,1
12		2	0,1
14		4	0,2
15		5	0,3
16		1	0,1
20		1	0,1
30		3	0,2
50		1	0,1
	Total	1893	100
99	No answer	392	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	2,8	
	Standard deviation	2,8	
	Mean value for >0	3,0	
	Standard deviation for >0	2,8	

PZ79

P – HOURS CHILDREN – CLEANING

X1105

About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours possible children spend?

0		173	32,2
.5		15	2,8
1		249	46,4
2		72	13,4
3		14	2,6
4		6	1,1
5		3	0,6
8		1	0,2
9		1	0,2
10		2	0,4
25		1	0,2
	Total	537	100
99	No answer	572	
	Not applicable	1176	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	1	
	Standard deviation	1,5	
	Mean value for >0	1,5	
	Standard deviation for >0	1,7	

PZ80

P – HOURS P – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE

X1106

About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		370	20,8
.1		1	0,1
.15		1	0,1
.5		25	1,4
1		531	29,8
2		284	16,0
3		126	7,1
3.5		1	0,1
4		78	4,4
5		141	7,9
6		25	1,4
7		18	1,0
8		28	1,6
9		2	0,1
10		87	4,9
12		8	0,4
13		1	0,1
14		4	0,2
15		16	0,9
16		5	0,3
17		1	0,1

18		1	0,1
20		14	0,8
21		2	0,1
22		2	0,1
25		2	0,1
30		3	0,2
40		3	0,2
	Total	1780	100
99	No answer	505	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	2,8	
	Standard deviation	4,1	
	Mean value for >0	3,6	
	Standard deviation for >0	4,3	

PZ81

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE

X1107

About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		441	24,2
.5		19	1,0
1		537	29,4
1.5		1	0,1
2		306	16,8
3		140	7,7
4		83	4,5
5		109	6,0
6		19	1,0
7		25	1,4
8		25	1,4
9		2	0,1
10		67	3,7
11		1	0,1
12		4	0,2
13		1	0,1
14		7	0,4
15		10	0,5
19		1	0,1
20		16	0,9
24		1	0,1
25		4	0,2
30		3	0,2
40		2	0,1
45		1	0,1
	Total	1825	100
99	No answer	460	
		2285	
	Mean value for all	2,5	

Standard deviation	3,9
Mean value for >0	3,3
Standard deviation for >0	4,2

PZ82	P – HOURS CHILDREN – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	X1108
About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend?		
0		338 81,3
.5		2 0,5
1		45 10,8
2		23 5,5
3		4 1,0
5		2 0,5
7		1 0,2
10		1 0,2
	Total	416 100
99	No answer	693
	Not applicable	1176
		2285
	Mean value for all	0,3
	Standard deviation	0,9
	Mean value for >0	1,7
	Standard deviation for >0	1,4

PZ83	P – DIFFERENT OPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK	X1116
How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to division of housework?		
1	Often	143 6,4
2	Sometimes	617 27,8
3	Seldom	946 42,6
4	Never	515 23,2
	Total	2221 100
9	No answer	64
		2285

PZ84	P – DIFFERENT OPINIONS USE OF MONEY	X1117
How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to the use of money?		
1	Often	62 2,8
2	Sometimes	389 17,5
3	Seldom	979 44,1
4	Never	788 35,5
	Total	2218 100
9	No answer	67
		2285

PZ85	P – DIFFERENT OPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS			X1120	
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much your spouse/partner works?				
	1	Often	75		3,4
	2	Sometimes	287		13,0
	3	Seldom	716		32,5
	4	Never	970		44,0
	5	Not applicable	158		7,2
		Total	2206		100
	9	No answer	79		
			2285		
PZ86	P – DIFFERENT OPINIONS CHILD RAISING			X1119	
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to child raising?				
	1	Often	79		3,6
	2	Sometimes	299		13,6
	3	Seldom	682		30,9
	4	Never	964		43,7
	5	Not applicable	180		8,2
		Total	2204		100
	9	No answer	81		
			2285		
PZ87	P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 2009: NUMBER OF WEEKS			X1077	
	Were you gainfully employed during calendar year 2009? If yes: How many weeks during 2009?				
	1		1		0,1
	2		6		0,4
	3		2		0,1
	4		6		0,4
	5		9		0,6
	6		3		0,2
	7		1		0,1
	8		11		0,7
	9		4		0,3
	10		18		1,2
	11		1		0,1
	12		15		1,0
	13		1		0,1
	14		2		0,1
	15		4		0,3
	16		8		0,5
	17		6		0,4
	18		2		0,1
	19		3		0,2
	20		33		2,2
21		2	0,1		
22		4	0,3		

24		9	0,6
25		17	1,1
26		3	0,2
27		2	0,1
28		5	0,3
29		1	0,1
30		14	0,9
31		3	0,2
32		10	0,7
33		3	0,2
34		2	0,1
35		10	0,7
36		5	0,3
37		1	0,1
38		14	0,9
39		4	0,3
40		73	4,8
41		5	0,3
42		28	1,9
43		9	0,6
44		31	2,1
45		109	7,2
46		110	7,3
47		169	11,2
48		140	9,3
49		24	1,6
50		43	2,8
51		15	1,0
52		487	32,3
53		21	1,4
55		1	0,1
	Total	1510	100
77	Not in gainful employment 2009	546	
88	Doesn't know	101	
99	No answer	128	
		2285	
	Mean value	43	
	Standard deviation	12,7	

PZ88

P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 2009: HOURS/WEEK

X1078

Were you gainfully employed during calendar year 2009? If yes: Number of hours/week on average? This variable is divided into categories.

1-19	62	4,3
20-29	107	7,3
30-39	352	24,2
40-49	828	56,9
50-59	71	4,9
60-69	27	1,9

	70-79		5	0,3
	80-89		3	0,2
	≥90		1	0,1
	Total		1456	100
	777	Not in gainful employment 2009	546	
	888	Doesn't know	101	
	999	No answer	182	
			2285	
PZ89	P – PREVIOUSLY COHABITING			X1079
	If yes: How many times have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months?			
	1	No	1544	68,8
	2	Yes	701	31,2
		Total	2245	100
	9	No answer	40	
			2285	
PZ90	P – NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS			X1080
	If yes: How many times have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months?			
	The table is valid for PZ89 EQ 2.			
	1		533	76,0
	2		121	17,3
	3		17	2,4
	4		3	0,4
		Total	701	100
	9	No answer	27	
		Not applicable	1584	
			2285	
PZ91	P – YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED			X1081
	If yes: When did your most recent marriage/cohabitation of at least 6 months end, i.e. when did you split up. This variable is divided into categories.			
	The table is valid for PZ89 EQ 2.			
	1950-59		1	0,1
	1960-69		13	1,9
	1970-79		70	10,4
	1980-89		132	19,6
	1990-99		226	33,6
	2000-09		230	34,2
		Total	672	100
	999999	No answer	29	
		Not applicable	1584	
			2285	

PZ92	P – CHILDREN NOT IN HOME	X1082
Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children?		
1		126 36,7
2		150 43,7
3		51 14,9
4		12 3,5
5		4 1,2
	Total	343 100
7	No children with previous partner	1820
8	Doesn't know	122
		2285
PZ93	P – NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1083
Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born 2004 or later?		
The table is valid for PZ92 GE 1.		
0		330 96,2
1		12 3,5
2		1 0,3
	Total	343 100
	Not applicable	1942
		2285
PZ94	P – NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	X1084
Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born between 1992 and 2003?		
The table is valid for PZ92 GE 1.		
0		295 86,0
1		35 10,2
2		10 2,9
3		3 0,9
	Total	343 100
	Not applicable	1942
		2285
PZ95	P – NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born between 1984 and 1991?		
The table is valid for PZ92 GE 1.		
0		48 14,0

1		102	29,7
2		135	39,4
3		44	12,8
4		10	2,9
5		4	1,2
	Total	343	100
	Not applicable	1942	
		2285	

PZ96

P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD

X1086

Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 1 not living in your household born?

The table is valid for PZ92 GE 1.

1940-49		1	0,3
1950-59		15	4,4
1960-69		73	21,4
1970-79		104	30,5
1980-89		86	25,2
1990-99		42	12,3
≥2000		20	5,9
	Total	341	100
9999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	1942	
		2285	

PZ97

P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD

X1087

Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 2 not living in your household born?

The table is valid for PZ92 GE 2.

1950-59		1	0,5
1960-69		46	21,4
1970-79		60	27,9
1980-89		74	34,4
1990-99		24	11,2
≥2000		10	4,7
	Total	215	100
9999	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	2068	
		2285	

PZ98**P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD****X1088**

Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 3 not living in your household born?

The table is valid for PZ92 GE 3.

1960-69		8	12,1
1970-79		19	28,8
1980-89		32	48,5
1990-99		4	6,1
≥2000		3	4,5
	Total	8	12,1
9999	No answer	1	
	Not applicable	2218	
		2285	

PZ99**P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD****X1089**

Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 4 not living in your household born?

The table is valid for PZ92 GE 4.

1950-59		1	6,3
1960-69		1	6,3
1970-79		5	31,3
1980-89		5	31,3
1990-99		3	18,8
≥2000		1	6,3
	Total	16	100
	Not applicable	2269	
		2285	

PZ100**P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD****X1090**

Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 5 not living in your household born?

The table is valid for PZ92 E 5.

1970-79		2	50,0
1980-89		2	50,0
	Total	4	100
	Not applicable	2281	
		2285	

PZ102	P – CASH MARGIN		X1122
		If a situation suddenly arose where you had to come up with 14 000 kronor, could you manage it?	
1	No	131	5,8
2	Yes	2120	94,2
	Total	2251	100
9	No answer	34	
		2285	
PZ103	P – ACQUIRING CASH		X1123
		If a situation suddenly arose where you had to come up with 14 000 kronor, could you manage it? If yes: How would you manage it?	
		The table is valid for PZ102 EQ 2.	
1	Withdrawal from own bank account	1650	78,4
2	Sale of stocks, fund shares or the like	121	5,8
3	Loan from family member	145	6,9
4	Loan from other relatives or friends	81	3,8
5	Bank loan or equivalent	97	4,6
6	Other way	10	0,5
	Total	2104	100
9	No answer	16	
	Not applicable	165	
		2285	
PZ104	P – GENERAL HEALTH		X1124
		How do you judge your general state of health?	
1	Good	1669	73,9
2	Bad	62	2,7
3	Something in-between	527	23,3
	Total	2258	100
9	No answer	27	
		2285	
PZ105	P – SMOKE		NEW
		Do you smoke?	
1	Yes, 10 cigarettes or more a day	108	4,8
2	Yes, less than 10 cigarettes a day	146	6,5
3	No, quited	732	32,5
4	No, never smoked	1269	56,3
	Total	2255	100
9	No answer	30	
		2285	

PZ106	P – DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR, ETC		X1143
	Do you at any time drink wine, strong beer/cider or liquor?		
1	Yes	2044	89,8
2	No	232	10,2
	Total	2276	100
9	No answer	9	
		2285	
PZ107	P – NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC		X1144
	If yes: during the last 12 months, about how often have you consumed wine, strong beer/cider or liquor?		
	The table is valid for PZ106 EQ 1.		
1	Daily	59	2,9
2	2-4 times a week	510	25,1
3	Once a week	524	25,8
4	2-3 times a month	419	20,7
5	Once a month	198	9,8
6	6-11 times a year	135	6,7
7	Less often	166	8,2
8	Never	17	0,8
	Total	2028	100
9	No answer	16	
	Not applicable	253	
		2285	
PZ109	P – P:S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION		X1153
	How do you yourself view your own living conditions? By and large what do you think about your situation?		
1	Very good	1177	51,9
2	Rather good	982	43,3
3	Neither good nor bad	86	3,8
4	Rather bad	19	0,8
5	Very bad	3	0,1
	Total	2267	100
9	No answer	18	
		2285	
PZ110	P – EDUCATIONAL LEVEL – ACCORDING TO REGISTER		NEW
1	Elementary school	163	7,2
2	Compulsory school	146	6,4
3	Vocational gymnasium 2-3 years	806	35,6
4	Theoretical gymnasium 3 years	166	7,3
5	Post-gymnasium	542	23,9
6	University graduation	420	18,5
7	Post-graduate education	24	1,1

	Total	2267	100
9	Information is missing in register	18	
		2285	